

Simulx

Product Documentation

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1 Introduction to Simulx

Simulx is an easy, efficient and flexible application for clinical trial simulations, interconnected with Monolix and flexible in building user-designed scenarios. Simulx combines a user-friendly interface with the highest computational capabilities to help you make faster and more informed decisions.

1.1 Why should I use Simulx?

- To gain new insights from **interactive exploration** of effects of dosing regimens and model parameters with real-time predictions
- To anticipate clinical trials results via **fast simulations of populations** of individuals
- To save time by working in a **simple and efficient environment interconnected with Monolix and PKanalix**.
- To focus on modeling and simulation instead of implementation details thanks to **easy and flexible simulation setup** and integrated **post-processing tools**.

1.2 The Simulx Workflows

1.2.1 Simulx Overview

Simulx has three sections that create an optimal environment to build and analyse simulations:

- Definition – create easily new exploration and simulation elements of different types.
- Exploration – explore different treatments and effects of model parameters on a typical individual.
- Simulation – simulate a clinical trial using a population of individuals in one or several groups with specific treatment or features and use flexible post-processing tools, clear results and interactive plots for analysis.

1.2.2 The exploration workflow

Goals:

- get a better understanding of how parameters impact your simulations
- explore the treatments and prepare your simulation design

Steps:

1. [Import a Monolix project](#) or [Import a PKanalix project](#) or create a [New project from scratch](#)
2. add new elements in the [Definition](#) tab: dosing regimens, parameters, covariates, outputs, etc.
3. [explore](#) effects of model parameters and treatments on a single individual

1.2.3 The simulation workflow

Goals:

- simulate a population in a new situation, such as a clinical trial
- get quantitative answers to your questions

Steps:

1. [Import a Monolix project](#) or [Import a PKanalix project](#) or create a [New project from scratch](#)
2. add new elements in the definition tab: dosing regimens, parameters, covariates, outputs, etc.
3. combine defined elements into a desired simulation with one or several groups for comparison
4. (optional) create outcomes & endpoints to quantify the simulations outputs
5. get your answer with automatically generated results and plots

2 New project

There are three different ways to start working with Simulx:

2.1 Import a Monolix project

There are three methods to start a project in Simulx: **create a new project**, **open an existing project** and **import a project from Monolix or PKanalix**. To import a project from Monolix is as simple as clicking on the button “Import from Monolix” in the Simulx home tab. It is the easiest way to build a simulation scenario, because everything to run a simulation is prepared automatically. As a result, it saves a lot of time. You can always modify current simulation elements, define new ones and change the scenario, so the flexibility of Simulx is not compromised.

2.1.1 Simulx project structure

Importing a project from Monolix creates a Simulx project with predefined elements. You can use them to re-simulate the dataset from the Monolix project or as a base for a new simulation scenario. These elements appear in the Definition tab:

- Model, population parameters and individual parameters estimates and output variables are imported from Monolix.
- Occasions, covariates, treatments and regressors are imported from the dataset (used in the imported Monolix project).

Simulx sets default exploration and simulation scenarios – they are ready to run. They contain one exploration group to simulate a typical individual (in the exploration tab) and one simulation group to re-simulate the Monolix project (in the simulation tab).

2.1.1.1 Default simulation elements

- model: mlxtran model with blocks [INDIVIDUAL], [COVARIATE] and [LONGITUDINAL].
- pop.params.:

- **mlx_PopInit** [*no POP.PARAM task results*]: (vector) initial values of the population parameters from Monolix.
- **mlx_Pop**: (vector) population parameters estimated by Monolix.
- **mlx_PopUncertainSA** (resp. **mlx_PopUncertainLin**): (matrix) an element which enables to sample population parameters using the covariance matrix of the estimates computed by Monolix if the Standard Error task (Estimation of the Fisher Information matrix) was performed by stochastic approximation (resp. by linearization). To sample several population parameter sets, this element needs to be used with replicates.
- indiv.params.:
 - **mlx_IndivInit** [*no POP.PARAM task results*]: (vector) initial values of the population parameters from Monolix.
 - **mlx_PopIndiv**: (vector) population parameters estimated by Monolix.
 - **mlx_PopIndivCov**: (table) population parameters with the impact of the covariates used in the model (but no random effects).
 - **mlx_EBEs**: (table) EBEs (conditional mode) estimated by Monolix.
 - **mlx_CondMean**: (table) conditional mean estimated by Monolix.
 - **mlx_CondDistSample**: (table) one sample of the conditional distribution (first replicate in Monolix).
- covariates [*if used in the model*]:
 - **mlx_Cov**: (table) ids and covariates read from the dataset.
 - **mlx_CovDist**: (distribution) distribution of covariates from the dataset with empirical mean and variance for continuous covariates, set as lognormal for positive continuous covariates, normal for continuous covariate with some negative values, and multinomial low based on frequencies of modalities for categorical covariates.
- treatment:
 - **mlx_AdmiD**: (table) ids, amounts and dosing times (+ tinf/rate or washouts) read from the dataset for each administration type.
- outputs:
 - **mlx_observationName**: (table) ids and measurement times read from the dataset for each output of the observation model
 - **mlx_predictionName**: (vector) uniform time grid with 250 points on the same time interval as the observations for each continuous output of the structural model.
 - **mlx_TableName**: (vector) uniform time grid with 250 points on the same time interval as the observations for each variable of the structural model defined as table in the OUTPUT block.
- occasions:
 - **mlx_Occ** [*if used in the model*]: (table) ids, times and occ(s) read from the dataset.
- regressors:
 - **mlx_Reg** [*if used in the model*]: (table) ids, times and regressor values and names read from the dataset.

2.1.1.2 Default scenarios

Exploration:

- Individ.params: mlx_IndivInit or mlx_PopIndiv.
- Treatment: one exploration group with mlx_AdmlD for all administration IDs.
- Output: mlx_predictionName for all predictions defined in the model.

Simulation:

- Size: number of individuals read from the dataset.
- Parameters: mlx_PopInit or mlx_Pop.
- Treatment: mlx_AdmlD for all administration IDs.
- Output: mlx_observationName for all observations.
- Covariates: mlx_cov if used in the model.
- Regressor: mlx_reg if used in the model.

The screenshot displays the Simulx software interface for configuring a simulation. The top navigation bar includes 'Project', 'Settings', 'Export', and 'Help'. The main interface is divided into sections: 'Tasks' with buttons for 'SIMULATION', 'OUTCOMES & ENDPOINTS', and 'RUN'; 'Simulation' configuration with radio buttons for 'Single simulation' (selected) and 'Replicates', a 'Same individuals among groups' checkbox, and a 'Sampling method' dropdown; a central configuration table; and 'Outcomes & endpoints' at the bottom.

Category	Element	Value/Status
Group size	32	
Parameters	mlx_Pop	
Treatments	mlx_Adm1	Checked
Outputs	mlx_y1	Checked
	mlx_y2	Checked
Covariates	mlx_Cov	Checked

Interface allows to have an overview on all defined elements, modify them and create new ones as well as build simulation scenarios. But, if you modify the imported model, then Simulx will remove all simulation elements. In addition, if you remove occasions, then all occasion-dependent simulation elements will be removed as well.

2.1.2 A typical simulation workflow

The projects shown here are available as demo projects in the interface "1.overview/importFromMonolix_xxx.smlx".

This example is based on a PK-PD model for Warfarin developed and estimated in Monolix. The Warfarin dataset contains concentration and PCA(%) measurements for 32 individuals, who received different oral doses of the drug. Firstly, the goal of the Simulx project is to use the information from the Monolix project to test the efficacy and safety conditions for different treatments. Secondly, to simulate clinical trials and compare various dosing regimens strategies. Simulations should answer the following questions:

- Which “loading dose” strategy assures a rapid steady state without a concentration peak?
- Do multi-dose treatments meet the efficacy and safety criteria?
- What is the uncertainty of the percentage of individuals in a target due to the variability between individuals and due to the size of a trial group?

Model:

The PK model includes an administration with a first order absorption and a lag time. It has one compartment and a linear elimination. The PD model is an indirect turnover model with inhibition of the production. All individual parameters have log-normal distribution besides the I_{max} parameter, which is logitNormally distributed. In addition, the log-transformed scaled weight covariate explains intra-individual variability of the volume, age covariate has an effect on the clearance and sex covariate on the baseline response. Finally, the combined-1 error model is used in the observation model of the concentration, and the constant model of the response.

2.1.2.1 0. Re-simulation of the Monolix project

[Demo project “1.overview – importFromMonolix_resimulateProject.smlx”]

You can download the Monolix project for this example, here. To import it in Simulx, first unzip the folder, then start a Simulx session, click on “Import from: Monolix” and browse the .mlxtran file. After importing a project from Monolix, the task buttons “simulation” and “run” in the Simulation tab re-simulate the project. Plots and results are generated automatically. Results are tables for outputs and individual parameters and plots display model observations as individual outputs and distributions.

2.1.2.2 1. Exploration of the loading dose strategies

[Demo project "1.overview - importFromMonolix_compareTreatments.smlx"]

Exploration tab simulates a typical individual. After importing a project from Monolix (the same as in the previous example), you can choose different types of individual parameters elements, eg. equal to population parameters estimated by Monolix or EBEs. Using several exploration groups allows to compare different treatments in one chart. The goal of this example is to test how many days of a "loading dose" are necessary to reach a steady state without a peak of the concentration. Starting dosing regimens are:

- 1 day with a load dose 12mg OD followed by 13 days with a 6mg single dose OD
- 1 day with a load dose 12mg OD followed by 13 days with a 4mg single dose OD
- 1 day with load doses 4mg twice a day (BID) followed by 26 doses of 2mg every 12 hours.

“Loading dose” treatments elements are of manual type (with time of a dose and amount), while multi-dose elements are of regular type. Regular type includes a specification of a treatment period, inter-dose interval and number of doses. You combine treatments elements directly in the exploration tab (in the left panel).

regDose_BID2mg

regular ▾

Name: regDose_BID2mg Adm: 1

Values

Start time	Interdose interval	Nb doses	Amount
24	12	26	2

Repeat

Scale amount by a covariate

Non-compliance probability

CLOSE

Output is the concentration prediction C_c and the response prediction R on a regular time grid over the whole treatment period ($t = 0:1:336$). The plot displays one subplot per output, and all exploration groups (=dosing regimen) together on each subplot. In the right panel, you can edit treatment elements and parameters interactively – predictions are updated on-the-fly for all groups to help you find which exact regimen is the most promising.

2.1.2.3 2. Treatment comparison: percentage of individuals in the target

[Demo project "1.overview - importFromMonolix_compareTreatments.smlx"]

2.1.2.3.1 Simulation scenario

Exploration tab performed simulation on one individual. In the simulation tab, Simulx simulates a population of individuals. Simulation outputs can be further post-processed to calculate, for example, the percentage of individuals in the target for different treatment arms. This simulation scenario uses the following treatment and output elements.

- BID treatment: One day of a "loading dose" with 4mg or 6mg dose twice a day (BID), followed by 26 doses of 2mg or 3 mg respectively each 12 hours.
- OD treatment: One day of a "loading dose" with 8mg or 12mg dose once a day (OD), followed by 13 doses of 4mg or 6 mg respectively each 24 hours.
- Outputs: manual type using model predictions (Cc and R) at time equal 336h.

In the simulation tab, the button "plus" **adds a new group** and "arrows" (green frames below) move elements from the shared section to the **group specific** section. For treatment, each group has a specific combination of treatments (blue frame). In addition, the option **"same individuals among groups"** removes the effect of intra-individual variability between individuals (red frame). As a consequence, the observed differences between groups are only due to the treatment and simulation can use a smaller number of individuals.

The comparison between groups is in terms of the percentage of individuals in the efficacy and safety target:

- Efficacy: PCA at the end of the treatment should be less than 60%.
- Safety: Ctough on the last treatment day should be less than 2ug/mL.

You can calculate it in the outcomes&endpoints section of the simulation tab. Definition of new outcomes includes selecting an output computed in the simulation scenario and post-processing methods. When you apply threshold condition, then outcome is of a binary (true/false) type.

outcome_efficity

Name

outcome_efficity

Output

Response_day14 ▾

 relative to baseline (first value of output)

Output processing: average value per id ▾

 Apply threshold ≤ 60

CANCEL

OK

In addition, outcomes can be combined together (blue frame below), and an endpoint summarizes “true” outcomes over all individuals in groups.

2.1.2.3.2 Analysis

Similarly to the task button “Simulation”, which runs the simulation, the “Outcomes & endpoint” button performs post-processing, which in this example means calculating the efficacy and safety criteria and the number of individuals in the target. When you run this task, Simulx generates automatically the results in the “endpoint” section and plots for outcomes distributions.

In this example, the outcome distribution compares the number of individuals in the target between groups. The highest number of “true” outcomes is in the group with the low level dose twice a day (gr_BID_lowDose). Failure to satisfy the safety criteria by the two groups with the high dose level causes large numbers of “false” outcomes. In fact, the endpoint results show that for these two groups less than half of the individuals have C_{trough} below the safety threshold (blue frame below).

outcome_safety			
	TRUE	FALSE	
gr_BID_lowDose	42	8	
gr_OD_lowDose	46	4	
gr_BID_highDose	16	34	
gr_OD_highDose	22	28	

2.1.2.4 3. Clinical trial simulation and uncertainty of the results

[Demo project "1.overview - importFromMonolix_clinicalTrial.smlx"]

The previous step shows that the high dose level violates the safety criteria in more than 50% of individuals. Therefore, the simulation of a clinical trial uses only one dose level with the BID and OD administration.

The goal is to analyse the effect of the uncertainty due to the variability between individuals, measurement errors and number of individuals in a trial.

New simulation scenario has four groups which combine different dosing regimens (BID or OD) with different group sizes (30 or 100). Outputs are model observations at the end of the treatment. To simulate the scenario several times (green frames), use the option "replicates". As a result, the endpoints summarize the outcomes not only over the groups but also over the replicates.

[Starting from the demo project "1.overview - compareTreatments.smlx", change number of replicates to 100, and add two groups: one with treatment as for GR_BID, other as GR_OD. Move "number of ids" as group specific, and set N=30 for one BID-OD pair and N=100 for the other. Change names to indicate group sizes.]

The screenshot displays the Simulx software interface for configuring a clinical trial simulation. The main window is titled "importFromMonolix_clinicalTrial.smlx - Simulx - 2020R1". The interface is divided into several sections:

- Tasks:** Includes buttons for "SIMULATION", "OUTCOMES & ENDPOINTS", and "RUN".
- Simulation:**
 - Options for "Single simulation" and "Replicates" (set to 100).
 - Checkboxes for "Same individuals among groups" and "Sampling method".
 - A table defining four groups:

Group Name	Group Size	Parameters	Treatments
gr_BID_N30	30	loadDose_BID4mg, regDose_BID2mg	loadDose_BID4mg, regDose_BID2mg
gr_OD_N30	30	loadDose_OD8mg, regDose_OD4mg	loadDose_OD8mg, regDose_OD4mg
gr_BID_N100	100	loadDose_BID4mg, regDose_BID2mg	loadDose_BID4mg, regDose_BID2mg
gr_OD_N100	100	loadDose_OD8mg, regDose_OD4mg	loadDose_OD8mg, regDose_OD4mg
- Outcomes & endpoints:**
 - Options for "Outcomes" (e.g., outcome_efficacy, outcome_safety).
 - Options for "Combination" (and/or).
 - Options for "Endpoint" (Percent true).
 - Group comparison:**
 - Reference group: gr_BID_N30
 - Comparison type: Statistical test
 - oddsRatio: 1
 - p-value: 0.05

After running both tasks, plots display the endpoint distribution as a box plot with the mean value (dashed line) and standard deviations for each group. As expected, the uncertainty is lower for trial with more individuals. However, the mean values remain at similar levels.

“Group comparison” option in the Outcomes&endpoints section compares the endpoints values across groups (blue frame). Selecting different reference groups and hypothesis (through the odds ratio) allows to change the objectives. Moreover, calculation of new outcomes or endpoints do not require re-running a simulation because the post-processing is a separate task.

The statistical test checks if any of the dosing regimens, BID or OD, is better than the other. Firstly, in the smaller trial so the gr_BID_N30 group is the reference and the hypothesis states that the odds ratio is different from one. For each replicate, if the p-value is lower than selected 0.05, then a test group (GR_OD_N30) is a “success”. Results summary in the “group comparison” section shows that only 5% of the test group replicates are successful (upper image below), which suggests that OD dosing regimen is not significantly better than BID. Larger trial size might give different results. Change reference group to gr_BID_N100 and re-run the outcomes & endpoints task. Percentage of successful replicates for gr_OD_N100 is higher, 8%, (lower image below), but it is comparable to the previous result.

2.1.2.5 4. Propagation of parameter uncertainty to the predictions

[Demo project in 2021 version only "1.overview - importFromMonolix_clinicalTrial_uncertainty.smlx"]

In the previous step, we replicated the study 100 times to check the impact of sampling different individuals on the endpoint, and on the power of the study. For all these replicates, we sampled individuals using the same population parameters (so same typical values and deviations of random effects).

The goal of this final step is to check the impact of the uncertainty of population parameter estimates on the final endpoint and study power. For this, starting from the 2021 version, it is possible to use the population parameter element `mlx_PopUncertainSA` (resp. `mlx_PopUncertainLin`) if standard errors have been computed by stochastic approximation in the original Monolix project (resp. by linearization). Now the 100 replicates will be samples using each time different population parameter values, which are sampled from the variance-covariance matrix of the estimates imported from Monolix.

The screenshot shows the Simulx software interface for configuring a simulation. The 'Simulation' tab is active, and the 'Replicates' option is selected. The 'Group size' is set to 100. A dropdown menu is open for the 'Parameters' section, showing 'mlx_PopUncertainSA' selected. The 'Outcomes & endpoints' section is visible at the bottom.

When running again simulation and outcomes with this population parameter element, we obtain a higher uncertainty on the endpoint than in step 3, since now we observe in addition the uncertainty related to the estimation of parameters in Monolix.

2.2 Import a PKanalix project

There are three methods to start a project in Simulx: **create a new project**, **open an existing project** and **from Monolix to Simulx or import project from PKanalix**. To import a project from PKanalix, simply click the “Import from PKanalix” option of the “Import from” in the Simulx Home tab. It is the most convenient way to create a simulation scenario, as everything is automatically prepared for running a simulation. You can modify current simulation elements, define new ones and change the scenario at any time, such that the flexibility of Simulx is not compromised.

2.2.1 Simulx project structure

Importing a project from PKanalix creates a Simulx project with pre-defined elements. You can use them to re-simulate the dataset from the PKanalix project or as a base for a new simulation scenario. These elements appear in the Definition tab:

- Model, individual parameters estimates and output variables are imported from PKanalix.
- Occasions, treatments and regressors are imported from the dataset.

Moreover, exploration and simulation scenarios are set and ready to run. They contain one exploration group to simulate a typical individual (in the exploration tab) and one simulation group to re-simulate the PKanalix project (in the simulation tab).

2.2.1.1 Default simulation elements

- model: same structural model as in the CA Model tab of PKanalix. Model is written in mlxtran language
- Individ.params.:
 - **pkx_IndivInit** [*no POP.PARAM task results*]: (vector) individual parameters corresponding to the initial values of the parameters in PKanalix
 - **pkx_Indiv**: (table) individual parameters estimated by CA task
 - **pkx_IndivGeoMean**: (vector) geometric mean of individual parameters over all subjects
- treatment:
 - **pkx_AdmiD**: (table) ids, amounts and dosing times (+ tinf/rate or washouts) read from the dataset for each administration type.
- outputs:
 - **pkx_outputName_FineGrid** (vector): for each continuous output of the structural model, a vector with a uniform time grid with 250 points on the same time interval as the observations.
 - **pkx_outputName_OriginalTimes** (table): for each output of the model, a table with values for ids and observation times corresponding to the measurements read from the dataset
 - **pkx_TableName**: (vector) for each variable of the structural model defined as table in the OUTPUT block, a vector with a uniform time grid with 250 points on the same time interval as the observations.
- occasions:
 - **pkx_Occ** [*if used in the model*]: (table) ids, times and occ(s) read from the dataset.
- regressors:
 - **pkx_Reg** [*if used in the model*]: (table) ids, times and regressor values and names read from the dataset.

2.2.1.2 Default scenarios

2.2.1.2.1 Exploration:

- Individ.params: pkx_Indiv or pkx_IndivInit.
- Treatment: one exploration group with pkx_AdmiD for all administration IDs.
- Output: pkx_outputName_FineGrid for all predictions defined in the model on a fine time grid.

2.2.1.2.2 Simulation:

- Size: number of individuals read from the dataset.
- Parameters: `pkx_Indiv` or `pkx_IndivInit`.
- Treatment: `mlx_AdmlId` for all administration IDs.
- Output: `pkx_outputName_OriginalTimes` for all model outputs.
- Regressor: `pkx_reg` if used in the model.

Interface

allows to have an overview on all defined elements, modify them and create new ones as well as build simulation scenarios. But, if you modify the imported model, then Simulx will remove all simulation elements. In addition, if you remove occasions, then all occasion-dependent simulation elements will be removed as well.

importFromPKanalix_resimulateProject.smlx [demo] - Simulx - 2023R1

Project Settings Help

Definition Exploration **Simulation**

Tasks

SIMULATION OUTCOMES & ENDPOINTS RUN

Simulation

Single simulation
 Replicates

Same individuals among groups Sampling method [dropdown]

		Shared	Shared ids
			All None
Group size	32		
Parameters	pkx_Indiv	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Treatments	pkx_Adm1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Outputs	pkx_Cc_OriginalTimes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	pkx_R_OriginalTimes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

New group +

Outcomes & endpoints

2.2.2 A typical simulation workflow

The projects shown here are available as demo projects in the interface "1.overview - importFromPKanalix_xxx.smlx":

This example is based on a PK-PD model for Warfarin developed and estimated in Monolix. The Warfarin dataset contains concentration and PCA(%) measurements for 32 individuals, who received different oral doses of the drug with the amount 1.5mg/kg. Both the PKPD model and the PKPD parameter estimates come from the compartment analysis (CA) performed in PKanalix. The aim of the Simulx project is to use the information from the PKanalix project to test the efficacy and safety conditions for different treatments. Possible questions to answer with simulations:

- Which “loading dose” strategy assures a rapid steady state without a concentration peak?
- Do multi-dose treatments meet the efficacy and safety criteria?

Model:

The PK model includes an administration with a first order absorption and a lag time. It has one compartment and a linear elimination. The PD model is an indirect turnover model with inhibition of the production.

2.2.2.1 0. Re-simulation of the PKanalix project

[Demo project “1.overview - importFromPKanalix_resimulateProject.smlx”]

You can download the PKanalix project for this example, here. To import it in Simulx, first unzip the folder, then start a Simulx session, click on “Import from: PKanalix” and browse the .pkx file. After importing a project from PKanalix, the task buttons “simulation” and “run” in the Simulation tab re-simulate the project. Plots and results are generated automatically. Results are tables for outputs and individual parameters and plots display model observations as individual outputs and distributions.

2.2.2.2 1. Exploration of the loading dose strategies

[Demo project "1.overview - importFromPKanalix_compareTreatments.smlx"]

2.2.2.2.1 Definition

The Exploration tab simulates a typical individual. After importing a project (the same as in the previous example), you can choose different types of individual parameters elements, eg. individual parameters estimated in the CA task or geometric mean estimated over all individual parameters. Using several exploration groups allows to compare different treatments in one chart. The goal of this example is to test how many days of a “loading dose” are necessary to reach a steady state without a peak of the concentration. Starting dosing regimens are:

- 1 day with a load dose 12mg OD followed by 13 days with a 6mg single dose OD
- 1 day with a load dose 12mg OD followed by 13 days with a 4mg single dose OD
- 1 day with load doses 4mg twice a day (BID) followed by 26 doses of 2mg every 12 hours.

“Loading dose” treatments elements are of manual type (with time of a dose and amount), while multi-dose elements are of regular type. Regular type includes a specification of a treatment period, inter-dose interval and number of doses. You combine treatments elements directly in the exploration tab (in the left panel).

New treatment with regular schedule

REGULAR
MANUAL
EXTERNAL

Name
Adm

Values

Start time	Interdose interval	Nb doses	Amount
24	12	26	2

Repeat cycle

Non-compliance probability

CANCEL
OK

2.2.2.2 Exploration

Output is the concentration prediction C_c and the response prediction R on a regular time grid over the whole treatment period ($t = 0:1:336$). The plot displays one subplot per output, and all exploration groups (=dosing regimen) together on each subplot. In the right panel, you can edit treatment elements and parameters interactively – predictions are updated on-the-fly for all groups to help you find which exact regimen is the most promising.

2.2.2.3 2. Treatment comparison: percentage of individuals in the target

[Demo project "1.overview - importFromPKanalix_compareTreatments.smlx"]

2.2.2.3.1 Simulation scenario

Exploration tab performed simulation on one individual. In the simulation tab, Simulx simulates a population of individuals – in this case all individuals from the original dataset used in the imported PKanalix project. Simulation outputs can be further post-processed to calculate, for example, the percentage of individuals in the target for different treatment arms. This simulation scenario uses the following treatment and output elements.

- BID treatment: One day of a "loading dose" with 4mg or 6mg dose twice a day (BID), followed by 26 doses of 2mg or 3 mg respectively each 12 hours.
- OD treatment: One day of a "loading dose" with 8mg or 12mg dose once a day (OD), followed by 13 doses of 4mg or 6 mg respectively each 24 hours.

- Outputs: regular type using model predictions (Cc and R) up to time 336h.

The screenshot shows the 'Simulation' tab in Simulx. At the top, there are three buttons: 'SIMULATION', 'OUTCOMES & ENDPOINTS', and 'RUN'. Below this, the 'Simulation' section is divided into a 'Shared' column and four 'Group specific' columns. The 'Shared' column contains settings for 'Group size' (32), 'Parameters' (pkx_Indiv), 'Treatments', and 'Outputs' (Cc_allTt and Response_allTt). The 'Group specific' columns are labeled 'gr_BID_lowDose', 'gr_OD_lowDose', 'gr_BID_highDose', and 'gr_OD_highDose'. A 'New group' button is visible on the right. An orange box highlights the treatment settings for the groups, and a green box highlights the 'Response_allTt' output setting.

The Simulation tab consists of the same element blocks as the Exploration tab. the button “plus” **adds a new group** and “arrows” (green frames below) move elements from the shared section to the **group specific** section. For treatment, each group has a specific combination of treatments (orange frame). As output a new vector was defined. Click on the “edit” icon to see the time discretization. Both output vectors, for the concentration as well as for the response range from time point 0 to time point 336 with step size 4 (unit is in hours h).

Cc_allTrt

REGULAR

Name
Cc_allTrt

Output variable
Cc Main outputs ▾ Intermediate output ▾

Start time	Interval	Final time
0	4	336

CLOSE

The option **“Same individual among groups”** removes the effect of intra-individual variability between individuals (red frame). As a consequence, the observed differences between groups are only due to the treatment itself. This case

2.2.2.3.2 Outcomes & endpoints

The efficacy and safety criteria correspond to the following conditions:

- Efficacy: at the end of the treatment PCA should not exceed 60%.
- Safety: on the last treatment day concentration should not exceed 1.5µg/mL

You can calculate it in the outcomes&endpoints section of the simulation tab. Definition of new outcomes includes selecting an output computed in the simulation scenario and post-processing methods. When you apply threshold condition, then outcome is of a binary (true/false) type.

outcome_efficacy

Name
outcome_efficacy

Output

Response_allTrt ▼

Relative to none ▼

Output processing: last value per id ▼

Apply threshold ≤ 60

CANCEL
OK

In addition, the defined outcomes can be combined together with a logical operator (green frames below), and an endpoint summarizes “true” outcomes over all individuals in groups.

Outcomes & endpoints ▼

Outcomes	Combination	Endpoint	Group comparison <input type="checkbox"/>	Reference group
<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <p>is_in_target <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <div style="border: 1px solid orange; padding: 2px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> outcome_efficacy ▼ ✎ - </div> <div style="border: 1px solid orange; padding: 2px;"> outcome_safety ▼ ✎ - </div> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: 0.8em;">...</p> </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid green; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;"> <input checked="" type="radio"/> and <input type="radio"/> or </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <p>percent_ids_in_target <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Percent true</p> </div>		<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <p>Reference group</p> <p>gr_BID_lowDose ▼</p> </div>

Outcomes

Endpoints

2.2.2.3.3 Analysis

Analogous to the “Simulation” button that runs the simulation, the “Outcomes & Endpoint” button performs the post-processing – calculates the efficacy and safety criteria and the number of people in the target. In addition, the execution of this task automatically generates the results in the “Endpoint” section and graphs for the outcomes distributions.

In this example, the outcome distribution compares the number of individuals in the target between treatment groups. Stack charts show the highest number of “true” results ($\hat{=}$ at time $t=336h$ $PCA \leq 60\%$ AND $Cc \leq 1.5\mu g/mL$) in the group with the low dose once daily (gr_OD_lowDose).

Large number of “false” in the two groups with the high doses (gr_OD_highDose, gr_BID_highDose) relates to the violation of the safety criteria. The endpoint results show that for these two groups, less than 1/3 of the subjects have concentration below the safety threshold (green frame below).

importFromPKanalix_compareTreatments.smix [demo] * - Simulx - 2023R1

Project Settings Export Help

Definition Exploration Simulation **Results** Plots

OUTCOMES [SUMMARY] OUTCOMES [TABLE] ENDPOINTS [TABLE]

SIMULATION

ENDPOINTS

Summary

is_in_target outcome_efficacy outcome_safety

	TRUE	FALSE		TRUE	FALSE		TRUE	FALSE
gr_BID_lowDose	21	11	gr_BID_lowDose	25	7	gr_BID_lowDose	27	5
gr_OD_lowDose	24	8	gr_OD_lowDose	25	7	gr_OD_lowDose	31	1
gr_BID_highDose	8	24	gr_BID_highDose	31	1	gr_BID_highDose	9	23
gr_OD_highDose	9	23	gr_OD_highDose	31	1	gr_OD_highDose	10	22

DISPLAY

Paginate

COLLAPSE ALL EXPAND ALL

3 items selected

2.2.2.4 Conclusion

In the higher multi-dose regimens, although 31 of 32 subjects reach the efficacy criterion, only 9 to 10 of these subjects meet the safety criterion.

The group with the lower dose administered once per day, gr_OD_lowDose, have the highest success rate: 24 out of 32 subjects, i.e. 75% of the subjects meet both the safety and the efficacy criteria.

Go to typical simulation workflow with a project imported from Monolix, to see how you can extend this analysis to simulations of clinical trials and assessment of the uncertainty.

2.3 New project from scratch

New possibilities, as well as unexpected and unwanted effects, arise during different phases of drugs development. Simulx allows to create a **new project from scratch**, which **gives freedom** in simulating new scenarios. Moreover, it creates easily a space for testing new hypothesis. This **helps to explore the full potential of drugs**, and better prepare for their possible failures.

To create a new project from scratch:

- Select "New project" after opening the Simulx.
- Browse, or write new, mlxtran model (see here for details about the model structure).
- Use Definition tab to specify simulation elements required by the model. Explore in the Exploration tab the effects of treatments and parameters. Build a simulation scenario in the Simulation tab and run the simulation.

Demo project: 1.overview/newProject_TMDDmodel

The following example shows how to build “from scratch” a simulation that aims at comparing different treatments among two populations: healthy volunteers and patients with rheumatoid arthritis. It uses a TMDD model for a ligand and receptor concentrations. In addition, the synthesis of the receptor depends on the population type – lower for healthy subjects. All simulation elements are user-defined. The basic assumption is that a treatment is effective if the free receptor stays below 10% of the baseline. The goal is to test if the dose levels effective on healthy volunteers allow rheumatoid arthritis patients to reach the efficiency target.

2.3.1 Model

When building a project from scratch, loading a model is mandatory and has to be done in the first place. It sets automatically the structure of a simulation based on the model type and its elements.

- Structural model is a TMDD model with the QE approximation, two compartments and oral administration.
- Statistical model defines an effect of the patient state (healthy or with RA) on the synthesis rate of the receptor. It also includes the power law relationship between the weight covariate and the volume of the central compartment.

Covariates and their transformations are described in the [COVARIATE] block, the statistical model of the individual parameters is in the [INDIVIDUAL] block, while the [LONGITUDINAL] block contains the structural model with output definitions.

2.3.2 Definition of the scenario elements:

To guide building a project from scratch, Simulx defines default simulation elements automatically using information from the loaded model. These elements can be removed or modified, as well as new elements can be created. In this example, the definition includes the following new elements used in the exploration and simulation.

- Pop.Param.: Values come from an external table with at least two mandatory rows. The first row contains names of all population parameters as used in the model, while the second has the parameter values.
- Individ.Params.: Individual parameters appear in the exploration tab. In this example, they are equal to population parameters in order to explore the effect of parameters on the model predictions for a typical individual.
- Covariates: The aim of this simulation is to compare two populations (healthy and with rheumatoid arthritis). There are two covariate elements with different values of the “patient” covariate, but the same “weight” covariate.

New covariates from distribution

MANUAL DISTRIBUTION EXTERNAL

Name
cov_healthy

Continuous covariates

Covariate	Distribution	Typical	sd
Weight	LOGNORMAL	70	0.1

Categorical covariates

Covariate	Category	Probability	Auto fill
Patient	HV	1	<input type="checkbox"/>
	RA	0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

CANCEL OK

- Treatment has two cycles (green frame). In each cycle patients receive an oral dose scaled by their weight (blue frame) once per day for 7 days (red frame) followed by 7 days without a treatment. Three different dose levels: 3mg/kg, 6mg/kg and 12mg/kg require three separate treatment elements. An option "duplicate" allows to clone a treatment, and then change only the name and the amount. Note that the "View" option has the scaling formula.

New treatment with regular schedule

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name Adm

trt_amt3 1

Values

Start time	Interdose interval	Nb doses	Amount
0	1	7	3

Repeat

Cycle duration
14

Number of repetitions
1

Scale amount by a covariate

Covariate
Weight

Intercept
0

Non-compliance probability

CANCEL OK

- Outputs elements include the ratio between the free receptor and the baseline. This output on the regular grid is useful in the exploration. Simulation uses only the value at the end of the treatment. The latter choice speeds up the computations in case of many individuals and/or replicates.

2.3.3 Exploration

The model assumes that rheumatoid arthritis disease affects the synthesis of the free receptor (ksyn parameter). It means that for a certain dose level the efficacy target can be reached by healthy individuals (ksyn_pop = 0.789, dashed reference curve in the figure below), but not by patients with rheumatoid arthritis (ksyn_pop = 2.8, solid curve). In this exploration, the scaling of the amount 3mg/kg corresponds to typical individual with a weight 70kg (blue frame).

2.3.4 Simulation

The scenario consists of 6 groups for three dose levels and two populations, see here to learn about creating a simulation scenario.

- Treatment is group specific. Each group uses one of the three covariate dependent doses: 3mg/kg, 6mg/kg or 12mg/kg (green frame).
- Type of a population – healthy or with the rheumatoid arthritis – is in the group specific covariate (blue frame).
- Group size, population parameters and the output are the same for all groups.

The outcomes&endpoints section defines post-processing of the simulation outputs for post-processing, which helps to compare the groups. The main endpoint is the percentage of individuals reaching the efficacy target in each group. It summarizes the “true” outcomes, which correspond to the situation when the ratio between the free receptor and the baseline at the end of the treatment is less than 10% (green frame). In addition, the “group comparison” (blue frame) compares the endpoints of all groups with respect to the reference group (healthy population with 3mg/kg dose level).

Outcomes & endpoints ▾

Outcomes

Target ✗

RR_below10prct ✗

New endpoint...

Endpoint

Percent true

Group comparison

Reference group: healthy_amt3

Direct comparison Statistical test

oddsRatio >> 0.6

Outcomes +

Endpoints f

2.3.5 Results

To run the simulation and the calculation of the endpoints it is enough to select both tasks and click the button “Run”. Generation of the results and plots is automatic in two dedicated tabs. The outcome distribution shows that the efficacy of the treatment in healthy individuals stays above 90% (red line) for all dose levels. On the contrary, a group with rheumatoid arthritis achieves this level only at the highest tested dose.

The response at the lowest dose level by healthy individuals is the reference. Group comparison considers a test group a “success” if the odds ratio of “percentage true” is larger than 0.6. Only the highest dose level satisfies this criterion for unhealthy patients.

newProject_TMDDmodel.smlx* - Simulx - 2020R1

Project Settings Export Help

Definition Exploration Simulation Results Plots

SUMMARY TABLE

Group comparison

Target

REP	HEALTHY_AMT6		HEALTHY_AMT12		RA_AMT3		RA_AMT6		RA_AMT12	
	ODDSRATIO	SUCCESS	ODDSRATIO	SUCCESS	ODDSRATIO	SUCCESS	ODDSRATIO	SUCCESS	ODDSRATIO	SUCCESS
1	1.81	✓	1.81	✓	0.11	✗	0.32	✗	0.76	✓

Display
 Pagination

3 Definition

Exploration or simulation scenarios are built from elements, such as model, parameters, treatments etc. Definition tab, as the name suggests, allows to create these simulation elements through user-friendly and flexible methods. Moreover, it displays them in dedicated sections, which gives a clear overview of the project status. Definition of the following simulation elements is available:

The screenshot shows the Simulx software interface with the 'Definition' tab selected. The sidebar on the left contains navigation icons for various simulation elements: MODEL (highlighted with a blue frame), OCCASIONS, POP.PARAMS, INDIV.PARAMS, COVARIATES, TREATMENTS, OUTPUTS, and REGRESSORS (highlighted with a blue arrow at the bottom). The main workspace displays the 'Model' definition for a file named 'regressor_manual_paramCovRelationship.smlx'. The model code is as follows:

```

1 [INDIVIDUAL]
2 input = {V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl, beta_pop}
3
4 DEFINITION:
5 V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
6 Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_pop, sd=omega_Cl}
7 beta = {distribution=logNormal, typical=beta_pop, no-variability}
8
9 [LONGITUDINAL]
10 input = {V, Cl, PCA, beta, a}
11 PCA = {use=regressor}
12
13 EQUATION:
14
15 ClwithPCA=Cl * PCA^beta / (12^beta+PCA^beta)
16
17 ; PK model definition
18 Cc = pkmodel(V, Cl=ClwithPCA)
19
20 OUTPUT:
21 output = Cc
22
23 DEFINITION:
24 y = {distribution=normal, prediction=Cc, errorModel=constant(a)}
  
```

Below the code, there is a section labeled 'Additional lines in the model' with a text input field.

Each element, imported from Monolix or used-defined, is a table . These icons next to the element name inform about the type when you hover on it with a cursor (green frame). Elements can be displayed, edited, duplicated (besides tables) or deleted (red frame). To create a new element, go to a dedicated section and click the “plus” button (blue frame).

Model is a mandatory element. It has to be loaded as first, because only elements present in the model can be defined. Otherwise, the section is greyed out and unavailable, for instance “regressors” (blue arrow at the bottom). Of course, more than one element of each category is possible.

After importing a project from Monolix, all elements are automatically created using Monolix model, results and dataset, see the list of elements here. In a new project written from scratch, Simulx generates default elements based on the loaded model to guide building new ones.

3.1 Model

The following pages give information on how to write and set up a model for simulations in Simulx:

3.1.1 Setting the model

A single model must be defined in each Simulx project. This model is used both in Exploration and Simulation. Loading or reloading a model deletes all definition elements to avoid incompatibilities between previously defined elements and the new model.

3.1.1.1 Loading or creating a model

In Simulx, structural models are provided as external .txt files, whose path is saved into the Monolix project.

There are three options to load a structural model:

1. Use the option "**Browse**" to load an existing file containing a structural model.
2. Use "**Load from library**" to select a model from the available [model libraries](#). Models from the libraries are not saved as external files but are generated on-the-fly. Once loaded, it is possible to open the content of a library model, edit it and save it as an external file.
3. Use "**New model**" to open the built-in editor, [write your own model](#) using the Mlxtran language, and save it as an external file.

3.1.1.2 Loading another model or modifying a model

Several buttons are available on the top of the page to load or modify a model:

- Browse: to load a new model file by browsing if from the computer.
- Load from library: to load a model from the built-in libraries. Note that all models from the libraries contain only structural models ([LONGITUDINAL] block) with no individual models for the parameters or covariates.
- Reload: to reload the same model after modifying it using the built-in editor or with any text editor.
- Open in editor: to opens the current model in the built-in editor.

Loading or updating a model with the buttons "Browse", "Load from library" or "Reload" deletes all definition elements to avoid incompatibilities with previously defined elements and the new model.

longitudinal_individual.smlx [demo] - Simulx - 2020R1

Project Settings Export Help

Definition Exploration Simulation Results Plots

MODEL

OCCASIONS

POP.PARAMS

INDIV.PARAMS

COVARIATES

TREATMENTS

OUTPUTS

REGRESSORS

Model

Model based on: C:/Users/pauli/fixoft/simulx/simulx2020R1/demos/2.models/longitudinal_individual/ModelFile/model_PK_IV.txt

BROWSE... LOAD FROM LIBRARY RELOAD OPEN IN EDITOR

```

6 [INDIVIDUAL]
7 input = {Tlag_pop, ka_pop, omega_ka, V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl, F_pop, omega_F, corr_V_Cl}
8
9 DEFINITION:
10 Tlag = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Tlag_pop, no-variability}
11 ka = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ka_pop, sd=omega_ka}
12 V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
13 Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_pop, sd=omega_Cl}
14 F = {distribution=logitNormal, typical=F_pop, sd=omega_F}
15 correlation = {level=id, r(V, Cl)=corr_V_Cl}
16
17 [LONGITUDINAL]
18 input = {b, Tlag, ka, V, Cl, F}
19
20 EQUATION:
21
22 ; PK model definition
23 Cc = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, Cl, p=F)
24
25 OUTPUT:
26 output = Cc
27
Additional lines in the model

```

3.1.1.3 Model sections

The model includes different sections:

- **[LONGITUDINAL]** (mandatory)

This section contains the structural model. All variables of the model can be defined as outputs of the simulation.

Details on the syntax to define the structural model is here.

This section can include the definition of random variables in a block DEFINITION:, such as a random event or a variable with residual error.

- **[INDIVIDUAL]** (optional)

If the model considers the inter-individual variability, then definitions of models for individual parameters are in [LONGITUDINAL]. The inputs of [INDIVIDUAL] are population parameters and covariates involved in covariate effects. If the project is imported from Monolix, this section is created automatically. However, when building a project from scratch, the [INDIVIDUAL] section can be generated automatically starting with version 2024 by clicking "+ ADD INDIVIDUAL". This will add an [INDIVIDUAL] section with all parameters in the model with a lognormal distribution and random effects.

Example: Parameters Tlag, ka, V and Cl are described with lognormal distributions, effects of covariates SEX and logtAGE are included on Tlag and Cl, respectively, and there is a correlation between eta_V and eta_Cl:

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {Tlag_pop, ka_pop, omega_ka, V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl, F_pop,
omega_F,
corr_V_Cl, logtAGE, beta_Cl_logtAGE, SEX, beta_Tlag_SEX_M}

SEX = {type=categorical, categories={F, M}}

DEFINITION:
Tlag = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Tlag_pop, covariate=SEX, coefficient={0,
beta_Tlag_SEX_M}, no-variability}
ka = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ka_pop, sd=omega_ka}
V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_pop, covariate=logtAGE,
coefficient=beta_Cl_logtAGE, sd=omega_Cl}
F = {distribution=logitNormal, typical=F_pop, sd=omega_F}
correlation = {level=id, r(V, Cl)=corr_V_Cl}
```

More details on the syntax in this section is here.

- **[COVARIATE]** (optional)

If covariates are used in the model of individual parameters, then they should be defined in a block [COVARIATE]. This block contains the list of inputs (covariates used in the model) and the definition of categories for categorical covariates. It can also include transformations of the covariates, in a section EQUATION: for continuous covariates and in a section DEFINITION: for categorical covariates. All the covariates defined in this block (transformed or not) can be then used in the block [INDIVIDUAL].

Example: There are 3 covariates AGE, RACE and SEX. The covariate AGE is transformed into logtAGE, RACE is transformed into tRACE.

```
[COVARIATE]
input = {AGE, RACE, SEX}

RACE = {type=categorical, categories={Asian, Black, White}}
SEX = {type=categorical, categories={F, M}}

EQUATION:
logtAGE = log(AGE/35)

DEFINITION:
tRACE =
{
transform = RACE,
categories = {
G_Asian = Asian,
```

```
G_Black_White = {Black, White} },  
reference = G_Black_White  
}
```

More details on the syntax in this section is here.

Note that in Simulx it is not possible to define covariates as distributions within the block [COVARIATE] with a section DEFINITION:. However, the covariate distributions can be defined in the tab Definition in the interface of Simulx.

3.1.1.4 Model imported from Monolix

When importing a model from Monolix, the model that appears in the interface of Monolix comes from two sources:

- The structural model ([LONGITUDINAL] block) used in the Monolix project, copied in a new file stored in the result folder of the Simulx project, in a subfolder names ModelFile/.
- The [INDIVIDUAL] and (if there are covariates in the model) [COVARIATE] blocks, derived from the statistical model set up in Monolix, saved directly in the .smlx file.

When opening a model in the editor with “Open in editor”, only the new structural model file is opened for modifications. If this model is changed and reloaded, it will replace the two model sources mentioned above. It means that the [INDIVIDUAL] and [COVARIATE] blocks are removed. To keep these blocks in the modified model, they have to be pasted in the file together with the [LONGITUDINAL] block.

3.1.1.5 Additional lines

Below a model definition, there is a field to write additional lines, which are included “on the fly” in the model. Note that in version 2024 and later, this is accessed by clicking the button “+ ADD LINES”.

This is convenient for example to use variables for simulations that are not defined in the Mlxtran model code, such as the AUC, a change from baseline, or the survival function (see example below). The model file itself is not modified, the additional lines are saved in the .smlx file.

By default, the additional lines are added in a new section EQUATION: below the structural model. In order to add additional lines in the PK block, it is necessary to add “PK:” at the beginning of the additional lines. This is convenient to add a new route of administration, using the iv(), oral() or depot() macro for instance. If this new administration depends on a parameter (e.g the absorption rate ka), the parameter needs to be fixed in the additional lines. It cannot be added to the input parameter list. It is not possible to add additional lines in the [INDIVIDUAL] or [COVARIATE] blocks.

This function is available also with lixoftConnectors functions: setAddLines() and getAddLines(), see here for more details.

i When using “import from Monolix”, “additional lines” fields can (sometimes) be unavailable. In this case, open the Monolix project in Monolix and use “Export to Simulx”. This problem has been fixed in the 2021R1 version.

The screenshot shows the Simulx software interface with the following content:

Model based on: C:/Users/pauli/lixoft/simulx/simulx2020R1/demos/2.models/longitudinal/ModelFile/model_TS_survival.txt

Buttons: BROWSE..., LOAD FROM LIBRARY, RELOAD, OPEN IN EDITOR

```

9 [LONGITUDINAL]
10 input = {a, b}
11
12 input = {TS0, kge, TSmax, Te, beta}
13
14 EQUATION:
15 odeType=stiff
16
17 TS = TS0*TSmax/(TS0+(TSmax-TS0)*exp(-kge*t))
18
19 h = 1/Te * exp(min(19, beta*TS))
20
21 DEFINITION:
22 survival = {type=event, maxEventNumber=1, hazard=h}
23
24 OUTPUT:
25 output = {TS, survival}
26
27
28 DEFINITION:
29 TS_residualerror = {distribution=normal, prediction=TS, errorModel=combined1(a, b)}
30
31 EQUATION:
32 ddt_H = h
33 S = exp(-H)
  
```

Additional lines in the model

```

ddt_H = h
S = exp(-H)
  
```

Buttons: CANCEL, APPLY

In the example below, a oral absorption route is added to the demo TMDD_exploration.smlx, which originally had only iv:

TMDD_exploration.smlx [demo] * - Simulx - 2021R2

Project Settings Help

Definition Exploration Simulation

MODEL

Model based on: C:/Users/celliere/Downloads/bolus_2cpt_full_VkintkonKDksynR0kelk12k21_outputL.txt

BROWSE... LOAD FROM LIBRARY EDIT MODEL

```

8 [LONGITUDINAL]
9 input = {V, kint, kon, KD, ksyn, R0, kel, k12, k21}
10
11 PK:
12 depot(target = L, p = 1/V)
13 ; p = 1/V transforms the dose amount into a concentration added to the concentration L
14
15 EQUATION:
16 odeType = stiff
17 ; Parameter transformation
18 koff = KD*kon
19 kdeg = ksyn/R0
20 ; Initial conditions
21 t_0 = 0
22 L_0 = 0
23 R_0 = R0
24 P_0 = 0
25 A_0 = 0
26 ; Ordinary Differential Equations
27 ddt_R = ksyn - kdeg*R - kon*L*R + koff*P
28 ddt_P = kon*L*R - koff*P - kint*P
29 ddt_L = -kel*L - kon*L*R + koff*P - k12*L + k21*A/V
30 ddt_A = k12*L/V - k21*A
31
32 OUTPUT:
33 output = {L}
34
35 EQUATION:
36 PK:
37 depot(target = L, p = 1/V, ka = 3)
38
39 Additional lines in the model
40 PK:
41 depot(target = L, p = 1/V, ka = 3)

```

3.1.2 Using or editing models from the libraries

Nine different libraries are available in Simulx, detailed in [Libraries of models](#)

- **PK** (pharmacokinetics)
- **PD** (pharmacodynamics)
- **PKPD** (joint PKPD)
- **PK double absorption**
- **Parent metabolite**
- **TMDD** (target-mediated drug disposition)
- **TTE** (time to-event)
- **Count** (for non-continuous count data)
- **TGI** (tumor growth and tumor growth inhibition)

3.1.2.1 Picking a model from a library

To use a model from the libraries, in the Structural model tab, click on “Load from library” and select the desired library. A list of models appears, as well as a menu to filter them. Use the filters and the list of parameters included in the models to select the model you need.

Here is for example how to select a PK model with first-order absorption and linear elimination (parameters k_a , V , Cl):

The model contents correspond to pre-written models in Mlxtran I language. In the case of library models, they are not saved as external text files but are generated on-the-fly inside Simulx. Once selected, the model appears in the Simulx GUI. Below we show the content of the (k_a, V, Cl) model:

Untitled* - Simulx - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Definition Exploration Simulation

MODEL

OCCASIONS

POP.PARAMS

INDIV.PARAMS

COVARIATES

TREATMENTS

OUTPUTS

REGRESSORS

Model

Model based on: lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVCl.txt

BROWSE... LOAD FROM LIBRARY EDIT MODEL

```

1 DESCRIPTION:
2 The administration is extravascular with a first order absorption (rate constant ka).
3 The PK model has one compartment (volume V) and a linear elimination (clearance Cl).
4
5 [LONGITUDINAL]
6 input = {ka, V, Cl}
7
8 PK:
9 ; PK model definition
10 Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)
11
12 OUTPUT:
13 output = {Cc}
14
  
```

+ ADD INDIVIDUAL BLOCK + ADD LINES

3.1.2.1.1 Modifying a model from the libraries

Browse existing models from the libraries using the “Load from library” button, then click the “file” icon next to a model name. This opens a pop-up window where the content of the model file is displayed. Click on “Open in editor” to open the model file in the MlxEditor. There you can adapt the model, for instance to add a PD model. Be careful to save the new model under a new name, to avoid overwriting the library files.

3.1.3 Writing your own model

If the models present in the [libraries](#) do not suit your needs, you can write a model yourself. You can either start completely from scratch or adapt a model existing in the libraries. In both cases, the syntax of the Mlxtran language is detailed on this page. You can also copy-paste models from the typical models section.

In the “Model” tab, you can click on “New model” to open the editor integrated within Simulx, and start writing your own model. The new model contains a convenient template defining the main blocks, input parameters and output variables. When you are done, click on “Create model” button to save your new model as a .txt file. After saving, the model is automatically loaded in the project.

The figure below shows how to use the editor integrated within the interface of Simulx. The model shown as example corresponds to the model included in the Monolix demo 8.case_studies/hcv_project.mlxtran.

i

- A button “Check syntax” is available to check that there is no syntax error in the model. In case of an error, informative messages are displayed to help correct the error. The syntax check is also automatically applied before saving the model so that only a model with a valid syntax can be saved.
- the [INDIVIDUAL] section can be generated automatically starting with version 2024 by clicking “+ ADD INDIVIDUAL”. This will add an [INDIVIDUAL] section with all parameters in the model with a lognormal distribution and random effects.

CHECK SYNTAX
+ ADD INDIVIDUAL BLOCK
🔍
🔍
↶
↷
🗑️
📄

CANCEL
SAVE & APPLY
⋮

3.1.3.1 Understanding the error messages

The error messages generated when syntax errors are present in the model are very informative and quickly help to get the model right. The most common error messages are explained in detail in this video.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HgJ1jBECXPE>

3.1.3.2 Using the external editor

This video shows how to write a new structural model with the mlxEditor application, that could only be used as a separate applications in versions of MonolixSuite prior to 2021R1:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9-q_yuyPAm4

3.1.4 Model syntax: mlxtran language

3.1.4.1 Introduction: model structure for Simulx

The code in the Model tab of Simulx contains the [LONGITUDINAL] section, but can also contain the [COVARIATE] and [INDIVIDUAL] sections to describe the statistical part of the model.

- **[LONGITUDINAL]**: structural model and error model
- **[INDIVIDUAL]**: parameter distributions
- **[COVARIATE]**: covariate declaration and transformations

Depending on the cases, these sections are automatically created or should be provided by the user:

- **When a Monolix project is imported into Simulx**, the model with all sections is created automatically from the .txt Monolix model file and .mlxtran Monolix project file.
- **When a PKanalix project is imported into Simulx**, the [LONGITUDINAL] section is created automatically from the .txt PKanalix model file. It is possible to then manually add [COVARIATE]

and [INDIVIDUAL] sections to consider covariates and inter-individual variability in the simulations.

- **When starting a Simulx project from scratch**, the [LONGITUDINAL] section is mandatory and the [COVARIATE] and [INDIVIDUAL] sections are necessary if covariates and inter-individual variability are present in the model.

More information is given in [Setting the model](#) about how the model is saved in when starting a Simulx project from scratch or after importing a Monolix or PKanalix project.

The sections are themselves divided into blocks, which allow to define different types of variables in different ways:

- **DESCRIPTION:** (optional): block to write comments on the model
- **input** (mandatory): list of input parameters
- **EQUATION:** (optional): block where ODEs can be defined, as well as mathematical expressions (e.g parameter transformations)
- **DEFINITION:** (optional): block to define random variables (discrete or continuous) via their probability distribution
 - within the [LONGITUDINAL] section: error model, probability distribution for count/ categorical output and hazard for time-to-event output
 - within the [INDIVIDUAL] section: distribution of the parameters
- **OUTPUT:** (mandatory): block indicating the output of the model
- **output** (mandatory): list of output parameters included in the OUTPUT block.

Below we show the possible sections and blocks in a Simulx model:

DESCRIPTION:

[COVARIATE]

input = { }

EQUATION:

[INDIVIDUAL]

input = { }

EQUATION:

DEFINITION:

[LONGITUDINAL]

input = { }

PK:

EQUATION:

DEFINITION:

OUTPUT:

output = { }

3.1.4.2 [LONGITUDINAL]: Writing the structural and observation models Smlx

3.1.4.2.1 Description

The [LONGITUDINAL] section is mandatory for all Mlxtran models and is used in Simulx to describe:

- the structural model,
- the observation model for discrete and time-to-event data,
- the error model for continuous observations.

The [LONGITUDINAL] section is itself divided into blocks, which allows to define different types of variables in different ways. Here are the possible blocks and variable lists in that section:

- **DESCRIPTION:** (optional): block to put comments on the model
- **input** (mandatory): list of input parameters
- **PK:** (optional): block where macros can be used and combined to define compartments and transfers between them
- **EQUATION:** (optional): block where ODEs and DDEs can be defined, as well as mathematical expressions (e.g parameter transformations)

- **DEFINITION:** (optional): block to define random variables (discrete or continuous) which represent observations, via their probability distribution: error model, probability distribution for count/categorical output and hazard for time-to-event output
- **OUTPUT:** (mandatory): block indicating the output of the model
- **output** (mandatory): list of output parameters included in the OUTPUT block.

In all blocks, it is possible to use:

- [if/else statements](#) with [logical operators](#)
- [mathematical functions](#)
- [keywords for the time and dose-related events](#)
- [regressors](#)

[Reserved keywords](#) of the Mlxtran language cannot be used as names for other parameters. Mlxtran is a declarative language, not an imperative language. Therefore equations are mathematical definitions rather than a series of instructions.

3.1.4.2.2 Inputs

In Simulx, the `input = { }` list of the [LONGITUDINAL] section declares the individual parameters and the regressors, as well as the error model parameters (while this is done automatically via the GUI in Monolix).

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl, a, b}
```

For regressors, the regressor status must be specified using the following syntax, for instance for two regressors called `regvar1` and `regvar2`. One line per regressor is necessary.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {..., regvar1, regvar2}
regvar1 = {use=regressor}
regvar2 = {use=regressor}
```

In Simulx, the variables appearing in the `input={}` list are recognized differently depending on other blocks. The inputs of [LONGITUDINAL] specified as regressors will be recognized as such and appear in the regressor element in Simulx GUI. Inputs of [LONGITUDINAL] which have been defined in the DEFINITION block of the [INDIVIDUAL] section will be recognized as individual parameters. All others (in particular error model parameters) will be recognized as population parameters in Simulx.

Example:

In this example, in addition to the individual parameters `ka`, `V`, `Cl`, `Emax` and `EC50` and the regressor `E0`, population error model parameters `a` and `b` are also defined.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl, E0, Emax, EC50, a, b}
E0 = {use = regressor}
```

3.1.4.2.3 Outputs

In Simulx, variables listed in `table={}` or `output={}` will have an output element generated automatically. It is also possible to request any model variable as output in Simulx, no matter if it has been declared in the OUTPUT section or not.

Example:

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Conc, Effect}
table = {Ap, T12}
```

3.1.4.2.4 Library of models and examples

The MonolixSuite contains libraries of pre-written structural models which can be directly selected via the GUI in Simulx:

- [PK](#): typical pharmacokinetics models with several types of administrations and 1 to 3 compartments
- [PK/PD](#): joint PK/PD model with direct effect, effect compartment or turnover
- [PK double absorption](#)
- [TMDD](#): target mediated drug disposition models
- [Parent-Metabolite](#) models
- [TTE](#): time-to-event models
- [Count](#): models for count data
- [TGI](#): tumor growth and tumor growth inhibition models

Examples of common models which are not (yet) in the libraries are also given here: [Advanced models](#)

3.1.4.2.5 PK: Using PK macros

On the following pages you can find information about the different types of PK macros:

3.1.4.2.5.1 Introduction PK macros Smlx

Introduction PK macros

A list of PK macros can be used as shortcuts to easily define PK models. All PK macros should be defined in a **PK:** block that must be included into the **[LONGITUDINAL]** section. Macros can be combined with ODE equations defined in an **EQUATION:** block. PK macros cannot be included into an arithmetic expression and cannot be enclosed within a conditional statement

There are three types of macros. We show below as example the same one-compartmental PK model with first-order absorption and linear elimination, using parameters (k_a , V , Cl), defined in three different ways that involve the three types of macros.

You can read more details about each of them here:

Introduction PK macros

The depot macro

This macro is used to provide a link between the administration information in the data set and the model, the rest of the model being defined as equations.

```
PK:
; depot() macro applies doses defined in the dataset to the ODE variable Ad
depot(target = Ac, ka)
EQUATION:
Ac_0 = 0
ddt_Ac = -(Cl/V)*Ac
```

The pkmodel macro

This macro provides a shortcut for standard PK models.

Example:

```
PK:
; pkmodel() macro to define simple PK models in one line
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)
```

Piecewise macros

A list of piecewise macros can be combined together to describe PK models. These macros allow the user to have an intuitive and compact representation of the most common PK models used in pharmacometrics.

Example:

```
PK:
; definition of the central compartment, numbered 1, with volume V and
concentration Cc
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
; definition of an oral absorption with first-order rate ka and bioavailability F
for doses with admid=1
; arriving into the central compartment. Note that the depot compartment is
implicit.
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka)
; definition of an elimination from the central compartment 1 with clearance Cl
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

3.1.4.2.5.2 depot macro

Description

The macro *depot* is a multipurpose macro that can accommodate different types of administrations. It is used together with ODE systems to define how the administrations from the data set are linked with the model variables. It is the only macro that can be used with ODEs for administration without defining a compartment. With the macro *depot*, a bolus, an infusion (with INFUSION RATE or INFUSION duration defined in the data set), a zero order absorption, or a first order absorption (with or without transit process) can be defined.

As for other macros, *depot* must be used in a block PK; while ODEs must be defined in a block EQUATION:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hcgI2NIXcFE>

Arguments

The *depot* macro can be used for bolus doses, infusions (with INFUSION RATE or INFUSION duration defined in the data set), zero-order absorptions, and first-order absorptions. Some arguments are common for the three types of administrations, some are specific.

Arguments common to bolus, zero-order and first-order absorption:

- **adm**: Administration identifier of doses to be read by the depot macro. Its default value is 1. Alias: type.

- **target**: Name of the ODE variable on which the doses will be added. *Mandatory*.
- **Tlag**: Lag time before the absorption. Its default value is 0.
- **p**: Fraction of the absorbed amount. It can affect the effective rate of the absorption, not its duration. p can take any positive value (including > 1). Its default value is 1.

Specific arguments for bolus doses:

For bolus doses, no additional argument is needed.

The following code defines a bolus for doses of type 1 (e.g ADM=1 in the data set), applied to the ODE variable Ad, with a delay Tlag and a fraction absorbed F :

```
PK:  
depot(type=1, target=Ad, Tlag, p=F)
```

Specific arguments for zero-order absorption:

To define a zero-order absorption, the following argument must be added:

- **Tk0**: Duration of the zero order absorption. *Mandatory to define zero-order absorption*.

The following code defines a zero-order absorption process of duration Tk0, for doses of type adm=2, applied to the ODE variable Ac, without lag time (Tlag=0 when not specified) and with the entire dose being absorbed (p=1 when not defined). Note that the “target” is the variable corresponding to the compartment in which the dose arrives (i.e the central compartment). The depot compartment is implicit and does not need to be defined.

```
PK:  
depot(type=2, target=Ac, Tk0)
```

Specific arguments for first-order absorption:

To define a first-order absorption, the following arguments can be added:

- **ka**: Rate of the first order absorption. *Mandatory to define first-order absorption*.
- **Ktr**: Transit rate.
- **Mtt**: Mean transit compartments time for the absorption.

The following code defines a first-order absorption process with rate ka, for doses of type 1 (adm=1 when not specified), applied to the ODE variable Ac, with a lag-time Tlag of 2.1, and only 30% of the dose being absorbed. Note that the “target” is the variable corresponding to the compartment in which the dose arrives (i.e the central compartment). The depot compartment is implicit and does not need to be defined.

```
PK:  
depot(target=Ac, ka, Tlag=2.1, p=0.3)
```

Note: In case of transit compartments and multiple doses, the amounts in the depot, transit and absorption compartments are reset at each new doses. Thus the implementation is valid only if the dose is fully absorbed before the next dose administration. The amount in the central (and possibly other compartments) is not reset and can accumulate.

Rules

- The value after type= must be an integer.
- The value after target= must be a string representing the ODE variable
- The inputs after Tlag=, p=, Tk0=, ka=, Ktr=, Mtt= can be either a
 - Double
 - Input parameter
 - Variable
 - Calculations are not supported
- The associated treatment or administration can be defined with a rate or an infusion timing from the data set (RATE and TINF column-types in the data set). The rules are the same as for the iv macro.

3.1.4.2.5.3 pkmodel macro

Introduction

The function **pkmodel** permits to define common PK models in a very concise way. The purpose of this macro is to simplify the modeling of classical pharmacokinetics. The PK model is inferred from the provided set of named arguments. Most of the arguments are optional, and the **pkmodel** function enables several parametrizations, to select different models of absorption, elimination, etc. With the **pkmodel** function, the most common PK models are available. The concentration within the central compartment is the main output of the function. If an effect compartment is defined, its concentration defines the second output. The pkmodel macro only uses doses with `adm=1`. The **pkmodel** function can be used within the block EQUATION: or the block PK:.

Examples

Example 1: One compartment model with intravenous (bolus or infusion) administration

```
Cc = pkmodel(V, Cl)
```

This simple set of named arguments for `pkmodel` defines a PK model with one central compartment of volume V , with intravenous bolus administration and a linear elimination with clearance Cl . The concentration in the central compartment is the output C_c of the function.

If a column is tagged as infusion duration or as infusion rate in the data, this is recognized by the `pkmodel` macro and the doses with a non-empty infusion rate or duration are administered as an infusion instead of a bolus.

Example 2: Two-compartment model with first order absorption with lag time

- With elimination rates: parameters T_{lag} , k_a , V , k , k_{12} , k_{21}

```
Cc = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, k, k12, k21)
```

- With clearances: parameters T_{lag} , k_a , V , Cl , Q , V_2

```
Cc = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, k=Cl/V, k12=Q/V, k21=Q/V2)
```

Note that it is not possible to give Q and V_2 as direct input parameters. Instead, we give the recognized keywords k_{12} and k_{21} , and defined them using Q , V and V_2 .

Example 3: Three-compartment model with zero-order absorption

```
Cc = pkmodel(Tk0, V, k, k12, k21, k13, k31)
```

Tk_0 represents the duration of the zero-order absorption. k_{12} and k_{21} are the rates to and from the first peripheral compartment and k_{13} and k_{31} are the rates to and from the second peripheral compartment.

Example 4: One compartment model with transit compartments

```
Cc = pkmodel(ka, Mtt, Ktr, V, Cl)
```

In case of transit compartments, the mean transit time is defined as $Mtt = (n+1)/Ktr$ with n the number of transit compartments (excluding the depot compartment and the absorption compartment) and Ktr the transit rate.

The implementation is the same as described in Savic et al, "Implementation of a transit compartment model for describing drug absorption in pharmacokinetic studies" (2007), except that to approximate the factorial $n!$, we use the gamma function, which is more precise, instead of the Stirling formula.

Note that this model has no analytical solution, so the ODE system is used in the background.

Example 5: One compartment model with effect compartment

```
{Cc, Ce} = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl, ke0)
```

The one-compartment model is connected to an effect compartment with a bi-directional rate ke_0 . The concentration in the effect compartment is called C_e in this example and can for instance be used to define a PD model.

Example 6: Model using almost all arguments

```
{Cc, Ce} = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, p, V, Vm, Km, k12, k21, k13, k31, ke0)
```

This more complex set of named arguments for `pkmodel` defines a PK model of a central compartment, with a first order absorption of rate ka , and a Michaelis-Menten elimination of parameters V_m and K_m . The volume of the central compartment is V . The concentration in the central compartment is the first output C_c of the function. An effect compartment is defined with a rate ke_0 and its concentration is the second output C_e . Two peripheral compartments numbered 2 and 3 are linked to the central compartment numbered 1. The respective couples of exchange rates are (k_{12}, k_{21}) and (k_{13}, k_{31}) . The first order absorption has a lag time T_{lag} and the absorbed amount is scaled with a proportion p (bioavailability).

List of arguments

The complete set of named arguments and output for `pkmodel` follows. They correspond to the central compartment, the absorption process, the elimination process, the exchanges with the peripheral compartments, or an effect compartment. Some arguments are mutually exclusive, or require other ones to be also defined. Most of them are optional, so the mandatory arguments are stated.

Arguments for the central compartment

- **Cc** = `pkmodel(...)`: The first output is the concentration within the central compartment. Another name can be used. *Mandatory*.

- **V**: Volume of the central compartment. *Mandatory.*

Arguments for the absorption process of a standard PK model

- **Tk0**: Defines a zero order absorption of duration Tk0. *Excludes ka, Ktr and Mtt.*
- **ka**: Defines a first order absorption of rate ka. *Excludes Tk0.*
- **Ktr**: Along with ka and Mtt, defines an absorption with transit compartments, with transit rate Ktr. *Excludes Tk0.*
- **Mtt**: Along with ka and Ktr, defines an absorption with transit compartments, with mean transit time Mtt. *Excludes Tk0.*
- **Tlag**: Lag time before the absorption.
- **p**: Final proportion of the absorbed amount (bioavailability). Can affect the effective rate of the absorption, not its duration.
- default if no argument supplied for the absorption process: iv bolus

Arguments for the elimination process of a standard PK model

- **k**: Defines a linear elimination of rate k. *Excludes Cl, Vm and Km.*
- **Cl**: Along with V, defines a linear elimination of clearance Cl. *Excludes k, Vm and Km.*
- **Vm**: Along with V and Km, defines a Michaelis-Menten elimination of maximum elimination rate Vm. Units of Vm are amount/time. *Excludes k and Cl.*
- **Km**: Along with V and Vm, defines a Michaelis-Menten elimination of Michaelis-Menten constant Km. Units of Km are concentration so amount/volume. *Excludes k and Cl.*

Arguments for the peripheral compartments of a standard PK model

- **k12**: Along with k21, defines a peripheral compartment 2 of input rate k12.
- **k21**: Along with k12, defines a peripheral compartment 2 of output rate k21.
- **k13**: Along with k31, defines a peripheral compartment 3 of input rate k13.
- **k31**: Along with k13, defines a peripheral compartment 3 of output rate k31.

Arguments for the effect compartment of a standard PK model

- **{Cc, Ce}** = pkmodel(...): The second output is the concentration within the effect compartment. Another name can be used.
- **ke0**: Defines an effect compartment with transfer rate ke0 from the central compartment.

Additional possibilities

Knowing the label of the central compartment (cmt=1) and the administration type supported by the function pkmodel (type=1), one can build up a custom PK model by adding other PK elements to a base standard PK model. Referencing this label and administration type of value 1 allows to connect the additional PK elements.

Overview of arguments

Pkmodel function input	Process	Required parameter	Optional parameter	Excluded parameter
Administration	Bolus		Tlag, p	Tk0, ka, Ktr, Mtt
	Zero order absorption	Tk0	Tlag, p	ka, Ktr, Mtt
	First order absorption	ka	Tlag, p	Tk0
	Absorption with transit compartments of mean transit time Mtt and transit rate Ktr	ka, Ktr, Mtt	Tlag, p	Tk0
	Bioavailability; fraction of the dose absorbed	p	Tlag, Tk0, ka, Ktr, Mtt	
Compartment	Volume	V		
Elimination	Linear, rate	k		Cl, Km, Vm
	Linear, clearance	Cl		k, Km, Vm
	Michaelis Menten	Km, Vm		k, Cl
Transfers	Transfer rates	(k12,k21) (k13, k31)		
	Effect compartment transfer rate constant	ke0		
Output	Concentration in the central compartment	first output name		
	Concentration in the effect compartment	second output name		

Rules

- Only one type of administration is allowed
- Only one **pkmodel** function is allowed in the Mlxtran file
- Arguments must be from the list of defined arguments for **pkmodel**. Arguments with different names are not recognized.

- **pkmodel** can not be used together with any macros for the administration. The administration is defined exclusively with the arguments supplied to `pkmodel()`
- A **pkmodel** output can be used with ODEs or with macros.
- **pkmodel** can also be defined in the PK: block or the EQUATION: block.

3.1.4.2.5.4 piecewise macros

Introduction

The mlxtran language provides a set of macros which allow to define a model piecewise, by defining each compartment and the transfer between compartments. The purpose of these macros is to simplify the modeling of classical pharmacokinetics. The PK model is inferred from the ensemble of used macros and the provided set of named arguments. The piecewise macros must be used within the block PK:

An example is shown below:

```
PK:
; definition of the central compartment, numbered 1, with volume V and concentration Cc
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
; definition of an oral absorption with first-order rate ka and bioavailability F for doses with admid=1
; arriving into the central compartment. Note that the depot compartment is implicit.
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka, p=F)
; definition of an iv administration into central compartment for doses with admid=2
iv(adm=2, cmt=1)
; definition of an elimination from the central compartment 1 with clearance Cl
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

Compartment macro

Purpose

The macro `compartment` defines a PK model compartment. Compartments can be the target of an administration, can be subject to a clearance process or can be linked with other compartments for exchange processes. The compartment amount, concentration and volume are variables.

Arguments

Arguments for the macro `compartment` are:

- **cmt**: Unique identifier of the compartment. Its default value is 1.
- **amount**: Name of variable defined as the amount within the compartment. Its dynamics are defined by dose absorptions, eliminations, and the transfer rates with other compartments.

- **volume**: Name of predefined variable to use as the volume of the compartment. It enables to define concentration. Its default value is 1.
- **concentration**: Name of the variable defined as the concentration within the compartment.

Basic Example

```
PK:
; To define a compartment with number 1, of volume V, an amount called Ac, and a
concentration called Cc
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
```

If no administration is involved for a compartment, and if the amount and all its dynamics are defined as an ODE component with its derivative, then the compartment macro definition is not needed.

Complete Example

In the following example, a compartment is defined in the PK: bloc and the dynamics of the amount is defined with the iv and elimination macro:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac, concentration=Cc, volume=V)
iv(cmt=1, type=1)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
```

Assuming the administration of a dose of amount=1 at time=5, we obtain the following for the concentration Cc:

Rules and Best Practices

- We encourage the user to use all the fields in the macro to guarantee non confusion between concentration, amount, ...
CAUTION: if the volume is not given, it will be assumed to be equal to 1. The volume is in particular needed to calculate k from the clearance when Cl is used as input of the elimination macro.
- The compartment definition has to be done in the first place before additional macros.
- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after `cmt=` is necessarily an integer.
 - The value after `amount=`, `volume=` and `concentration=` are necessarily strings.

Peripheral macro

Purpose

The peripheral macro defines a peripheral compartment. It is equivalent to a compartment with two transfers of drug amount towards and from another base compartment. This base compartment must have been previously defined and referenced by the indexes used in the parameter names: `peripheral(k12, k21)` defines a peripheral compartment numbered 2, which will be connected to the already defined compartment 1. If the amount or concentration of the peripheral compartment are not used afterwards, then they do not need to be defined as part of the macro.

Arguments

Arguments for macro `peripheral` are:

- **`kij` or `ki_j`**: Input rate from the compartment of label i . It also defines a label j for the peripheral compartment. Here, both labels i and j must be integers. If i and/or j are larger than 9, the syntax with the underscore is necessary. *Mandatory.*

- **kji or kj_i**: Output rate to the compartment of label *i*. It also defines a label *j* for the peripheral compartment. Here, both labels *i* and *j* must be integers. If *i* and/or *j* are larger than 9, the syntax with the underscore is necessary. *Mandatory*.
- **amount**: Name of variable defined as the amount within the compartment. Its dynamics are defined by dose absorptions, eliminations, and the transfer rates with other compartments.
- **volume**: Name of predefined variable to use as the volume of the compartment. It enables to define concentration. The default value is 1. If the volume is not defined, the concentration cannot be defined.
- **concentration**: Name of the variable defined as the concentration within the peripheral compartment.

Most of the time it is not necessary to name the amount, volume and concentration.

Example

```
PK:
; definition of a peripheral compartment with cmt=2 with rates k12 and k21
peripheral(k12, k21)

; if the concentration in the peripheral compartment is measured
; a volume V2, and a concentration Cp can also be defined
peripheral(k12, k21, volume=V2, concentration=Cp)

; definition of a peripheral compartment with cmt=3, linked to compartment 1,
peripheral(k13, k31)

; using Q and V2 instead
peripheral(k12=Q/V, k21=Q/V2)
```

```
; with compartments numbers larger than 9
peripheral(k2_13, k13_2)
```

Rules and best practices

- To use inter-compartment clearance *Q* and peripheral volume *V2* as parameters instead of *k12* and *k21*, the syntax is:

```
peripheral(k12=Q/V, k21=Q/V2)
```

- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The values after *k* are necessarily an integer (related to predefined compartment id).
 - The value after *kij=* can be either a double or replaced by an input parameter.
 - The value after *amount=* and *concentration=* are necessarily strings.
 - The value after *volume=* can be either a double or replaced by an input parameter.

Effect macro

Purpose

The macro effect defines an effect compartment. The effect compartment is usually linked to a central compartment. The drug exchange between the effect compartment and the central compartment does not affect the mass balance of the amount in the central compartment (its impact is considered negligible). The central compartment must be defined before the effect compartment is defined.

Arguments

Arguments for the macro effect are:

- **cmt**: Label of the linked base compartment. Its default value is 1.
- **ke0**: Transfer rate from the linked base compartment. *Mandatory*.
- **concentration**: Name of the variable defined as the concentration within the effect compartment. *Mandatory*.

Basic Example

```
PK:
; Define an effect compartment linked to the base compartment 1,
; with a transfer rate ke0 to the effect compartment,
; with Ce as concentration's name
effect(cmt=1, ke0, concentration=Ce)
```

Complete Example:

In the following example, a compartment is defined in the PK: bloc. An iv absorption process along with a linear elimination process is added to the main compartment. An effect compartment is added with a transfer rate ke0.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k, ke0}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac, concentration=Cc, volume=V)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
iv(cmt=1)
effect(cmt=1, ke0, concentration=Ce)
```

Assuming a single infusion at time=5 for a duration of 2hr, the concentration in the central compartment (orange) and in the effect compartment (blue) are:

Rules and Best Practices

- We encourage the user to use all the fields in the macro to guarantee non confusion between fields.
- A base compartment must be defined first.
- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after `cmt=` is necessarily an integer.
 - The value after `ke0=` can be either a double or replaced by an input parameter. Calculations are not supported.
 - The value after `concentration=` is necessarily a string.

Transfer macro

Purpose

The macro transfer defines a uni-directional transfer process from a base compartment to a target compartment. The base compartment and the target compartment must be defined first before the transfer can be defined. For the more common bi-directional transfer process it is better to use the macro peripheral instead of the macro transfer, in particular as it allows to use the analytical solution, which is not the case with the macro transfer.

Arguments

Its named arguments are:

- **from**: Label of the source compartment for the transfer. Its default value is 1.
- **to**: Label of the target compartment for the transfer. Its default value is 1.
- **kt**: Rate of the transfer. *Mandatory*.

Basic Example

```
PK:
; transfer from compartment 1 to compartment 2 with a rate kt
transfer(from=1, to=2, kt)
```

Complete Example

In the following example, a sigmoid absorption model is shown. Two compartments are defined in the PK block to specify a depot and a central compartment. The oral() macro defines a zero-order absorption into the depot compartment (A transfer from compartment 1 to compartment 2 is added, with a transfer rate kt).

```
<MODEL>
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tk0, ka, V, Cl}

PK:
; depot compartment
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ad)
; central compartment
compartment(cmt=2, concentration=Cc, volume=V)
; zero-order absorption into the depot compartment 1
oral(cmt=1, Tk0)
; first-order transfer from depot (1) to central (2)
transfer(from=1, to=2, kt=ka)
; elimination from central compartment (2)
elimination(cmt=2, Cl)
```

Best Practices

- We encourage the user to use all the fields in the macro to guarantee non confusion between the fields.
- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after from= and to= are necessarily integers.
 - The value after kt= can be either a double or replaced by an input parameter. Calculations are not supported.

Absorption/oral macro

Purpose

The macro absorption/oral enables to link the administration and the model, for zero-order and first-order absorption processes (for bolus administrations, use the iv macro instead). For Mlxtran the macro names 'absorption' and 'oral' can be used interchangeably. The administration can either be defined in a data set when Monolix is used, or the administration can be defined via an administration

design definition when Simulx is used. In order to handle models with several administrations each administration has a unique identifier called “adm”. This identifier must be defined in the data set or in the administration design definition, and used in the absorption/oral macro.

Arguments common to zero-order and first-order

The absorption/oral macro can be used for zero-order and first-order absorptions. The arguments common to the two absorptions are:

- **adm**: Administration identifier of doses to be read by this macro. Its default value is 1. Alias: type.
- **Tlag**: Lag time before the absorption. Its default value is 0.
- **p**: Final proportion of the absorbed amount. It can affect the effective rate of the absorption, not its duration. p can take any positive value (including > 1). Its default value is 1.
- **cmt**: Label of the compartment called in by the absorption process. Its default value is 1. The corresponding compartment must be defined before using the absorption/oral macro using a compartment macro.

To define a zero-order or first-order absorption, the additional arguments defined below are needed.

Arguments specific to a zero-order absorption

To define a zero-order absorption, the following argument must be added:

- **Tk0**: Duration of the zero order absorption. *Mandatory to define a zero-order absorption.*

Example:

```
; zero order absorption process for the doses of type 1, in compartment 1 with a  
delay Tlag of 1 and a duration Tk0  
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, Tlag=1, Tk0 = 2, p=1)
```

Arguments specific to a first-order absorption

To define a first-order absorption, the following arguments can be added:

- **ka**: Rate of the first order absorption. *Mandatory to define a first-order absorption.*
- **Ktr**: Transit rate.
- **Mtt**: Mean transit time for the absorption.

Example:

```
PK:  
; first order absorption process for the doses of type 1, in compartment 1 with a  
delay Tlag of 1 and a rate ka  
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, Tlag=1, ka)
```

Note: in case of transit compartments, the mean transit time is defined as $Mtt = (n+1)/Ktr$ with n the number of transit compartments (excluding the depot compartment and the absorption compartment):

The implementation is the same as described in Savic et al, "Implementation of a transit compartment model for describing drug absorption in pharmacokinetic studies" (2007), except that to approximate the factorial $n!$, we use the gamma function, which is more precise, instead of the Stirling formula.

In case of multiple doses, we assume that the previous dose has been completely absorbed (i.e concentration in the Abs compartment is almost zero) when the next dose is administered. If this is not the case, the remaining concentration in the Abs compartment is erased when the next dose is applied, leading to a loss of dose amount entering the system.

Example with mixed absorptions

Some drugs can exhibit atypical absorption profiles with for instance a zero-order absorption followed by a first-order absorption, or first and zero-order simultaneously.

Sequential absorption, zero-order followed by first-order

In the example below, a fraction $F1$ of the drug is absorbed via a zero-order process for a duration $Tk0$. The remaining fraction $1-F1$ is then absorbed via a first-order process, which starts with a lag-time $Tk0$ (i.e at the end of the zero-order absorption phase).

PK:
`absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, Tk0, p=F1)`
`absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka, p=1-F1, Tlag=Tk0)`

Simultaneous first-order and zero-order absorption

In the example below, a fraction $F1$ of the drug is absorbed via a first-order process (with absorption rate ka). Simultaneously the remaining fraction $1-F1$ is absorbed via a zero-order process.

PK:
`absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka, p=F1)`
`absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, Tk0, p=1-F1)`

A lag time for one or the other process can be added if necessary.

Example with different absorption models

In the presented example, we show the difference between the two absorption processes. In addition, the effect of the K_{tr} and M_{tt} parameters is explored in a third model.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, Tlag, ka, Tk0, Ktr, Mtt}

PK:
; model 1 with zero-order absorption
compartment(cmt=1, amount=A1, concentration=Cc_zoa, volume=V)
absorption(cmt=1, adm=1, Tk0)
elimination(cmt=1, k=1)

; model 2 with first-order absorption
compartment(cmt=2, amount=A2, concentration=Cc_foa, volume=V)
absorption(cmt=2, adm=1, Tlag, ka)
elimination(cmt=2, k=1)

; model 3 with transit compartments
compartment(cmt=3, amount=A3, concentration=Cc_foaT, volume=V)
absorption(cmt=3, adm=1, Tlag, ka, Ktr, Mtt)
elimination(cmt=3, k=1)
```

The three concentrations are presented in the following figure:

- zero order absorption (blue): the peak concentration is sharp
- first order absorption (orange): the peak concentration is more smooth. In addition, in this example it is delayed before of the T_{lag}
- transit compartments (purple): the start of the absorption is delayed and progressive

Rules and Best Practices

- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after `cmt=` and `type=` are necessarily integers.
 - The value after `Tlag=`, `p=`, `V=`, `ka=`, `Tk0=`, `Ktr=`, `Mtt=` can be either a double or replace by an input parameter. Calculations are not supported.
 - The associated treatment or administration can not be defined with a rate nor an infusion timing (`RATE` and `TINF` column-types in the data set). If a rate or an infusion timing is present, the user can use the `iv` macro and/or define a compartment to define the dynamics of the absorption.

IV macro

Purpose

The macro `iv` enables to link the administration with the model, for intravenous doses (bolus or infusion). Doses defined in the data set without an administration rate or infusion time are instantaneously absorbed within the associated compartment, as an IV bolus. Doses with an administration rate or infusion time are absorbed according to a zero order process, as an IV infusion.

Arguments

Arguments for macro `iv()` are:

- **cmt**: Label of the compartment called in by the absorption process. Its default value is 1. The corresponding compartment must be defined before using the absorption/oral macro using a compartment macro.
- **adm**: Administration identifier of doses to take in. Its default value is 1. Alias: type.
- **Tlag**: Lag time before the absorption. Its default value is 0.
- **p**: Final proportion of the absorbed amount. It can affect the effective rate of the absorption, not its duration. p can take any positive value (including > 1). Its default value is 1.

Basic Example

```
PK; intravenous bolus for the doses of type 1, in compartment 1 with a delay Tlag at 1
iv(adm=1, cmt=1, Tlag=1, p=1)
```

Complete Example

In the presented example, we show the difference two iv processes with and without a rate in the administration.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, concentration=Cc, volume=V)
iv(cmt=1, adm=1)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
```

The concentration in yellow shows the profile after an iv bolus dose. The concentration in blue shows the profile after an iv infusion of 17 minutes.

Rules and Best Practices

- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after `cmt=` and `adm=` are necessarily integers.
 - The value after `Tlag=`, `p=` can be either a double or replaced by an input parameter. Calculations are not supported.
- With the `iv` macro, it is not possible to give the rate or duration of the infusion as a parameter or fixed value. To do so, use the absorption macro with duration parameter `Tk0` to define a zero-order absorption (i.e infusion).
- When the `iv` macro is used in combination with a data set with a column-type `RATE`:
 - if `RATE >0`: infusion with rate `RATE` and duration `AMT/RATE`
 - if `RATE <=0`: bolus
- When the `iv` macro is used in combination with a data set with a column-type `TINF`:
 - if `TINF >0`: infusion of duration `TINF` at a rate `AMT/TINF`
 - if `TINF <=0`: bolus

Empty and reset macros

Description

The macro *empty* can be used to set any component of the system, defined in an ODE, to 0 at any given time. Similarly, the macro *reset* is used to reset a variable of the system to its initial value. Empty or reset times are indicated via a type of administration (`adm id`). The actions of these macros are thus selective, contrary to the reset applied with an `EVID` column in the dataset with values 3, which resets all compartments.

Arguments

The arguments are the same for both *empty* and *reset* macros:

- **adm**: Administration identifier used to indicate empty or reset times. Its default value is 1. Alias: type. The empty and reset macros only use the administration times, not the amounts.
- **target**: Name of the ODE variable that is set to 0 or reset to its initial value at the specified times, or target=all to reset all system variables. *Mandatory*.

Basic Example

The following code defines an emptying of the ODE variable Ap on administration times of type 1 (e.g ADM=1 in the data set).

```
PK:  
empty(adm=1, target=Ap)
```

This is equivalent to the following code with the depot macro:

```
PK:  
depot(adm=1, target=Ap, p=-Ap/amtDose)
```

The following code defines a reset based on administration times of type 2 (e.g ADM=2 in the data set), applied to the ODE variable Ac.

```
PK:  
reset(adm=2, target=Ac)
```

It is possible to define several *empty* macros with the same adm identifiers to set several targets to 0 at the same times, and the same for *reset* macros. With the example below, dose events with adm=3 will empty both variables Ac and Ap.

```
PK:  
empty(adm=3, target=Ac)  
empty(adm=3, target=Ap)
```

To reset all variables of the system, "target=all" can also be used:

```
PK:  
reset(adm=3, target=all)
```

Complete example: urine compartment

The following script implements a two compartments model with an additional urine compartment. There is a transfer from the central compartment to the urine compartment. A single dose with $adm=1$ is administered to the central compartment at time 0. A selective reset of the urine compartment corresponding to collecting times is defined with an administration with $adm=2$. Each amount for this administration is defined as 1 but is actually not used in the model.

When using this model with a data set, urine would be collected over consecutive periods of 12 hours and the amount of drug measured in the urine volume collected for each period would be recorded.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Cl, V1, Q, V2, p_urine}

PK:
k_urine = p_urine*Cl/V1
k_non_urine = (1-p_urine)*Cl/V1
k12 = Q/V1
k21 = Q/V2

; Dose administration to central compartment (plasma)
depot(adm=1, target=Ac, ka)

; Reset of urine compartment
reset(adm=2, target=Aurine)

EQUATION:
t_0=0
Ac_0=0
Ap_0=0
Aurine_0=0

ddt_Ac = - k_non_urine*Ac - k12*Ac + k21*Ap - k_urine*Ac
ddt_Ap = k12*Ac-k21*Ap
ddt_Aurine = k_urine*Ac

Cc=Ac/V1

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, Aurine}
```

The model gives the following profiles for the drug amount in the urine compartment (blue, left), and the drug concentration in the central compartment (green, right).

Complete example: PD variable

Emptying a compartment or resetting it to its initial state are equivalent actions for compartment which are initially empty. This may be not the case for PD models with non-zero baseline, like in the following example where the PD variable E is reset to its initial value E_0 at time 60 and 108 using a dummy dose with $ADMID=2$.

```

<MODEL>
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, k, E0, IC50, kout}

PK:
depot(target=Ad, type=1)
reset(target=E, type=2)

EQUATION:
E_0 = E0
kin = E0*kout

ddt_Ad = -ka*Ad
ddt_Ac = ka*Ad - k*Ac
ddt_E = kin*(1 - Ac/(Ac+IC50)) - kout*E

OUTPUT:
output = {E}
  
```


Rules

- The value after type= or adm= must be an integer.
- The value after target= must be a string representing the ODE variable.

Elimination macro

Purpose

The elimination macros permits to define different elimination processes (linear or Michaelis-Menten) for compartments. Several eliminations can be defined for the same compartment.

Arguments

Some arguments are common to the two elimination types, while some are specific to a linear or to a Michaelis-Menten type of elimination.

Arguments common to linear and Michaelis-Menten:

- **cmt**: Label of the compartment emptied by the elimination process. Its default value is 1.

Arguments specific to a linear elimination

The use of one of the following additional arguments defines a linear elimination:

- **k**: Rate of the elimination.
- **Cl**: Clearance of the elimination.

Only one of k or Cl must be defined.

Note, that if no volume has been defined for the compartment, then the default volume $V=1$ is assumed.

Example:

```
PK:
elimination(cmt=1,k)
```

Arguments specific to a Michaelis-Menten elimination

The use of both of the following additional arguments defines a Michaelis-Menten elimination:

- **V_m**: Maximum elimination rate. The unit of V_m is amount/time.
- **K_m**: Michaelis-Menten constant. The unit of K_m is a concentration.

Both arguments must be defined.

Example:

```
PK:  
elimination(cmt=1, Vm, Km)
```

Complete Example

The following model implemented with PK macros includes two compartments, an oral absorption and a dual elimination pathway with parallel linear and Michaelis-Menten eliminations. An equivalent model, implemented with ODEs, is defined in the TMDD model library: it corresponds to the Michaelis-Menten approximation of a TMDD model.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]  
input = {ka, V, Vm, Km, Cl, Q, V2}  
  
PK:  
kel = Cl/V  
k12 = Q/V  
k21 = Q/V2  
compartment(cmt=1, concentration=Cc, volume=V)  
absorption(cmt=1, ka)  
peripheral(k12, k21)  
elimination(cmt=1, k=kel)  
elimination(cmt=1, Vm, Km)  
  
OUTPUT:  
output={Cc}
```

Rules and Best Practices

- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after cmt= is necessarily an integer.
 - The value after V=, k=, Cl=, Km=, Vm= can be either a double or be replaced by an input parameter. Calculations are not supported.

3.1.4.2.6 EQUATION: Writing model equations

In the EQUATION: block, ODEs and DDEs can be defined.

3.1.4.2.6.1 Ordinary differential equations (ODEs)

Ordinary differential equations (ODEs)

Introduction

Ordinary differential equations (ODEs) can be implemented in the EQUATION: block of the [LONGITUDINAL] section. The ODEs describe a dynamical system and are defined by a set of equations for the derivative of each variable, the initial conditions, the starting time and the parameters.

Derivatives

The keyword `ddt_` in front of a variable name, as `ddt_x` and `ddt_y`, defines the derivative of the ODE system with respect to time. The variable names denote the components of the solution. These variables are defined at the whole [LONGITUDINAL] section level through their derivatives. The derivatives themselves aren't variables but keywords, and cannot be referenced by other equations nor be defined under a conditional statement (i.e within an if/else block).

Initial conditions

The keyword `t_0` defines the initial time of the differential equation, while the variable names with suffix `_0` define the initial conditions of the system. More precisely, in a differential equation for the variable **x**, **x** is defined at **t = t0** by the initial condition `x_0`, i.e. $x(t_0) = x_0$ and by the differential equation after `t0`.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e8VGTZdbToY>

Linking administration with ODEs

Mlxtran provides the PK macro `depot()` that can be used to link the administration from a data set with the model.

Details and examples how to use `depot()` for the administration are given [here](#).

Ordinary differential equations (ODEs)

Example

We consider in this example a first order differential equation on **x** defined by:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dA_c}{dt} = -k \times A_c \\ A_c(t = 0) = D \end{cases}$$

with **k** the elimination rate and **D** the dose given as a bolus at time 0.

The mlxtran implementation is:

DESCRIPTION: Model description with a simple ODE representing a linear elimination process of a volume

[LONGITUDINAL]

input = {k}

EQUATION:

D = 10

t_0 = 0

Ad_0 = D

ddt_Ad = -k*Ad

Stiff versus non-stiff ODEs

A numerical algorithm providing an efficient and stable way to solve the ODEs and DDEs is used to compute the solution of the dynamical models. Different numerical algorithms can be used to solve the ODE depending on the properties of the ODE system (Adams methods for non stiff ODEs, and Backward Differentiation Formulas methods for stiff ODEs). The right numerical algorithm must be selected in order to get an accurate and stable solution within a reasonable computational time. The stiffness of an ODE systems is one of the main properties that influences the choice of the numerical algorithms. Stiff ODEs can lead to very long computational times if an inappropriate algorithm is used. Stiff ODEs are typical for models that include processes taking place at different time scales. For example models with reaction and diffusion processes are known to be stiff. Reactions can occur at the seconds time scale while diffusion processes can take hours. For such cases a dedicated numerical algorithm for stiff ODEs is available.

A solver for stiff ODEs can be selected in Mlxtran using the keyword `odeType`. There are two possible choices for `odeType`:

```
; ode is considered as stiff
odeType = stiff
; ode is considered as non-stiff (default)
odeType = nonStiff
```

This command has to be defined in the [LONGITUDINAL] section. When `odeType` is not specified then the `nonStiff` ODE solver is used by default.

Note that:

- For the DDEs, the keyword `odeType` is ineffective.
- For many ODEs the stiff solver will provide the best solution.

ODE solver tolerances

The stiff and non-stiff solvers compute the solution of the ODE system up to a certain precision, which is defined through the tolerance. The values by default are the following:

- non-stiff solver: absolute tolerance 1e-6, relative tolerance 1e-3
- stiff solver: absolute tolerance 1e-9, relative tolerance 1e-6

The tolerances can be modified by specifying the desired value in the structural model file using the keywords `odeAbsTol` and `odeRelTol`, for instance:

```
EQUATION:  
odeAbsTol = 1e-12  
odeRelTol = 1e-9
```

The smaller the tolerance, the closer the computed prediction will be from the true solution. The absolute tolerance indicates how much the absolute difference between the computed prediction y_{solver} and the true solution y_{true} can be, i.e. $|y_{solver} - y_{true}| < \text{odeAbsTol}$. The relative tolerance is related to the number of digits which are correct, i.e. $\frac{|y_{solver} - y_{true}|}{|y_{true}|} < \text{odeRelTol}$.

Note that the right hand side needs to be a number (such as `odeAbsTol=1e-12` or `odeAbsTol=0.000001`) and cannot be an expression (`odeAbsTol=10^(-9)` is not accepted).

Rules and Best Practices

- We encourage the users to define the initial conditions explicitly, although the default initial value is $x_0=0$.
- When no starting time t_0 is defined in the Mlxtran model for Monolix then by default t_0 is selected to be equal to the first dose or the first observation, whatever comes first.
- If t_0 is defined, a differential equation needs to be defined.
- Initial conditions can depend on
 - time
 - an input parameter. Therefore, initial condition values can also be estimated in Monolix.
 - a regressor value. In that case, again, *a differential equation needs to be defined*.
- Only first order differential equation can be used with Mlxtran. If you want to use a differential equation of the form $\frac{d^n x}{dt^n} = f(x, \phi)$, you need to transform the higher order differential equation into a first order differential equations by defining n successive differential equations as proposed in the following “Best Practices Ex. 1: Second order differential equation”.
- The derivatives of a ODE system cannot be conditional, i.e. `ddt_` cannot be used within an `if` statement. Instead, conditional intermediate variables for the values of the derivatives should be used as shown in “Best Practices Ex. 2: IF statement”. A conditional statement can be built by combining the keywords `if`, `elseif`, `else` and `end`. Several `elseif` keywords can be chained, and the conditions are exclusive in sequence. A default value can be provided using the keyword `else`, but also as a simple definition preceding the conditional structure. An unspecified conditional value is null. The enclosed variables are not local variables, which means that a variable with remaining conditional definitions is still incomplete and cannot be referenced into another definition, even under the same condition.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H46MeX8kXCs>
Best Practices Ex. 1: Second order differential equation

If you want to use a second order differential equation of the type $\ddot{x} + \dot{x} + x = 0$, with $(x(0), \dot{x}(0)) = (a, b)$, the structural model in Mlxtran writes

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a, b}

EQUATION:
t0 = 0
x_0 = a
dx_0 = b
ddt_x = dx
ddt_dx = -x-dx
```

Best Practices Ex. 2: IF statement

If a parameter value depends on a condition, it can be written with in Mlxtran with the usual if-else-end syntax. For example, if a parameter c should be 1 if $t \leq 10$, 2 if $t < 20$ and 3 otherwise, write

```
if t<=10
  c = 1
elseif t<20
  c = 2
else
  c = 3
end
```

Derivatives cannot be written within an if-else-end structure. Instead, intermediate variables should be used. For example, if a derivative of x over time should be 1 if $t \leq 10$ and 2 otherwise, write

```
if t<=10
  dx = 1
else
  dx = 2
end
ddt_x = dx
```

3.1.4.2.6.2 Delay differential equations (DDEs)

Introduction

Delay differential equations (DDEs) can be implemented in a block EQUATION: of the section [LONGITUDINAL]. For that, the function delay() is proposed. This function allows to delay a dynamical variable by a constant time (which can be estimated). One can also build a model with several delays. Note that delays in the absorption after drug administration represent a different process and must be implemented using the keyword Tlag in the administration macros.

The solver used for delayed differential equations is described in Kuate et al. "A delay differential equation solver for MONOLIX & MLXPLORE".

Since the DDE solver is slower than the ODE solver, we recommend the alternative implementation using ODEs only and presented in the following video, when possible, as it leads to greatly shorter run times.

Example

We consider in this example a first order delay differential equation on x defined by:

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = k_a \times x(t) - k \times x(t - \tau)$$

This DDE is typically an accumulation process with a delayed linear elimination treatment.

```
DESCRIPTION: Model description with a delay
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {x0, ka, k, tau}

EQUATION:
t0 = 0
x_0 = x0
ddt_x = ka*x-k*delay(x,tau)
```

The simulation of this model using ($x_0=10$, $k=0.5$, $k=0.25$, $\tau=2$) is shown on the following figure. The interesting part in this example is that the delay leads to oscillations.

Rules

- The delay function can delay a “pure” component in a dynamical equation. There are three main things to point out and we will discuss the three of them:
 - By pure, we mean that the function can not take state calculations into account. In the previous example, if we had used `delay(k*x,tau)` instead of `k*delay(x,tau)`, this would have generated an error.
 - By component, we mean that the delay function can only delay variable with a dynamic behavior (defined by a derivative equation). In the previous example, using the delay function with anything else than `x` would lead to an error.
 - By dynamical equation, we mean that the delay function should be called directly in a `ddt_` equation. For example, if we have in addition a DDE of the form $\dot{y}(t) = x(t - 1) - y(t)$, one could be tempted to implement it in Mlxtran under the following incorrect form:

```
z = delay(x,1)
ddt_y = z-y
```

It should be defined directly as

```
ddt_y = delay(x,1)-y
```

The first implementation would lead to an error.

- The delay must remain constant over the time.

- It is good practice to define the initial conditions of the DDE system (t_0 and initial values for the variables). If the initial condition is not defined, then it is set to the default value 0. Notice that you can have varying initial conditions. Note also that an initialization can be performed if the values can be analytically computed. For example, we can define $x(t) = V(1 + t) \quad \forall t \in [-1, 0]$, and it would be translated in Mlxtran under the form

```
x_0 = V*(1+t)
```

3.1.4.2.7 DEFINITION: Defining random variables

The DEFINITION: block is used to define models for random variables which represent observations.

The observations can be:

- **Continuous observations** with a residual error. In Simulx, this block is defined in the model file if the Simulx project is based on a model loaded by the user or if it has been imported from PKanalix, but it is automatically included in the .smlx Simulx project if the Simulx project has been imported from Monolix.
- **Non-continuous observations:** count, categorical or time-to-event. In Simulx this block is always defined in the model file.

The following pages detail how to model the different types of random observations:

3.1.4.2.7.1 Continuous observation model

Syntax compatible with Monolix

The DEFINITION: block in the [LONGITUDINAL] section is used to define the observational model:

```
DEFINITION:
observationName = {distribution = distributionType, prediction = predictionName,
errorModel = errorModel(param)}
```

with:

- **observationName:** to be replaced by the name of the observation, e.g. `y1`
- **distributionType:** to be replaced by `logNormal`, `normal` or `logitNormal`
- **predictionName:** to be replaced by a variable defined in the structural model, e.g. `Cc`
- **errorModel(param):** to be replaced by `combined1(a, b)`, `combined2(a, b)`, `proportional(b)` or `constant(a)`. The error model parameters `a` and `b` must also be

listed as input of the [LONGITUDINAL] section. `a` and `b` are commonly used as variable names, but any variable name is accepted (e.g. `a1`, `aEffect`, etc)

For example, if the observation is a concentration with a combined error model ($DV = Cc + (a+b*Cc)*e$), the observational error model is written as

```
DEFINITION:  
DV = {distribution = normal, prediction = Cc, errorModel=combined1(a, b)}
```

When the observational error is defined in the Mlxtran model file, the user must declare the observational model parameters (`a` and `b` in the presented example) as inputs of the [LONGITUDINAL] section.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]  
input = {ka, V, Cl, a, b}
```

When a `logitNormal` distribution is selected, the boundaries (min and max) must also be defined:

```
DEFINITION:  
yE = {distribution = logitNormal, min=0, max=100, prediction = E,  
errorModel=constant(a)}
```

Syntax specific to Simulx (including time-varying error models)

The following is accepted in Simulx. However Simulx projects using this syntax cannot be exported to Monolix.

The DEFINITION: block in the [LONGITUDINAL] section is used to define the observational model:

```
DEFINITION:  
observationName = {distribution = distributionType, prediction = predictionName, sd = sdErr}
```

with:

- **observationName**: to be replaced by the name of the observation, e.g. `y1`
- **distributionType**: to be replaced by `logNormal`, `normal` or `logitNormal`
- **predictionName**: to be replaced by a variable defined in the structural model, e.g. `Cc`
- **sdErr**: to be replaced by a variable defined in the structural model representing the standard deviation of the random observation, e.g. `sd = sdErr` with `sdErr = b*Cc` defined in the

EQUATION: block. Note that the variable representing the sd can vary over time and be defined using if/else statements.

Below we show an example of an error model that varies over time: before time 0.1, the residual error is zero, afterwards a proportional error model is used.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Cc, IC50, E0, kout, b}
Cc = {use = regressor}

EQUATION:
kin = E0*kout

E_0 = E0
ddt_E = kin*(1 - Cc/(Cc + IC50)) - kout*E

if t<0.1
sdErr = 0
else
sdErr = b*E
end

DEFINITION:
yE = {distribution = normal, prediction = E, sd=sdErr}

OUTPUT:
output = {E, yE}
```

Rules and best practices

- The arguments of the `errorModel` can not be calculations (e.g. `errorModel=constant(a)` with `a = 10*Cc` is not accepted), only parameters listed in the input list.
- A parameter can not be shared by two different `errorModel` arguments for two different observations.
- The argument `sd` cannot be directly a formula (e.g. `sd = b*Cc`), an intermediate variable name must be used (e.g. `sd = sdErr` with `sdErr=b*Cc`)

3.1.4.2.7.2 Time-to-event observation model

Related resources on modeling time-to-event data in Simulx:

- [Time-to-event model library](#) : detailed description of the library of time-to-event models integrated within Monolix.
- [Time-to-event data models](#): examples of time-to-event data models from the Simulx demos.

On the current page, we explain the different models for time-to-event data that can be used in Simulx and their syntax.

Time-to-event observation model

Use of time-to-event data

Here, observations are the “times at which events occur”. An event may be one-off (e.g., death, hardware failure) or repeated (e.g., epileptic seizures, mechanical incidents, strikes). Several functions play key roles in time-to-event analysis: the survival, hazard and cumulative hazard functions. We are still working under a population approach here so these functions, detailed below, are thus individual functions, i.e., each subject has its own. As we are using parametric models, this means that these functions depend on individual parameters (ψ_i).

- The **survival function** $S(t, \psi_i)$ gives the probability that the event happens to individual i after time $t > t_{\text{start}}$:

$$S(t, \psi_i) = \mathbb{P}(T_i > t; \psi_i)$$

- The **hazard function** $h(t, \psi_i)$ is defined for individual i as the instantaneous rate of the event at time t , given that the event has not already occurred:

$$h(t, \psi_i) = \lim_{dt \rightarrow 0} \frac{S(t, \psi_i) - S(t + dt, \psi_i)}{S(t, \psi_i) dt}$$

This is equivalent to

$$h(t, \psi_i) = -\frac{d}{dt}(\log S(t, \psi_i))$$

- Another useful quantity is the **cumulative hazard function** $H(a, b; \psi_i)$, defined for individual i as

$$H(a, b; \psi_i) = \int_a^b h(t, \psi_i) dt$$

Note that $S(t, \psi_i) = e^{-H(t_{\text{start}}, t; \psi_i)}$. Then, the hazard function $h(t, \psi_i)$ characterizes the problem, because knowing it is the same as knowing the survival function $S(t, \psi_i)$. The probability distribution of survival data is therefore completely defined by the hazard function.

Repeated events

Sometimes, an event can potentially happen again and again, e.g., epileptic seizures, heart attacks. For any given hazard function h , the survival function S for individual i now represents the survival since the previous event at $t_{i,j-1}$, given here in terms of the cumulative hazard from $t_{i,j-1}$ to $t_{i,j}$:

$$S(t_{i,j}|t_{i,j-1}; \psi_i) = \mathbb{P}(T_{i,j} > t_{i,j} | T_{i,j-1} = t_{i,j-1}; \psi_i) = \exp\left(-\int_{t_{i,j-1}}^{t_{i,j}} h(t, \psi_i) dt\right)$$

Observation model syntax

An observation variable for time-to-event or repeated time to event data is defined using the type `event`. Its additional fields are:

- `eventType`: Type of the events. The exact time of the events can be observed, or censored per interval. The respective keywords are `exact` and `intervalCensored`. By default, an exact time is assumed.
- `maxEventNumber`: Maximum number of events (integer). By default the number of simulated events is unlimited. If the event is one-off (as death for instance), it is important to indicate `maxEventNumber=1` to speed up simulations (including simulations for the prediction interval of the TTE plot in Monolix).
- `rightCensoringTime`: Right censoring time of events (number). It is useful for simulation only, and by default it is the actual time of the last record.
- `intervalLength`: Length of censoring intervals (number). It is useful for simulation only, and by default it is the tenth part of the global length.
- `hazard`: Hazard function.

Example

An example where we define an observation model for this case is proposed here

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={gamma, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(V,Cl)
haz = gamma*Cc

DEFINITION:
Seizure = {type = event, eventType = intervalCensored, maxEventNumber = 1,
rightCensoringTime = 120, intervalLength = 10, hazard = haz}
```

TTE model library

A library of typical parametric models is provided in Simulx: Complete description of the TTE model library.

3.1.4.2.7.3 Count observation model

Related resources on modeling count data in Simulx:

- [Count data model library](#) : detailed description of the library of count models integrated within Monolix.
- [Count data models](#) : examples of count data models from the Simulx demos.

On the current page, we explain the different models for count data that can be used in Simulx and their syntax.

Count observation model

Use of count data

Longitudinal count data is a special type of longitudinal data that can take only nonnegative integer values $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ that come from counting something, e.g., the number of seizures, hemorrhages or lesions in each given time period. In this context, data from individual i is the sequence $y_i = (y_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$ where y_{ij} is the number of events observed in the j th time interval I_{ij} .

Count data models can also be used for modeling other types of data such as the number of trials required for completing a given task or the number of successes (or failures) during some exercise. Here, y_{ij} is either the number of trials or successes (or failures) for subject i at time t_{ij} . For any of these data types we will then model $y_i = (y_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$ as a sequence of random variables that take their values in $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. If we assume that they are independent, then the model is completely defined by the *probability mass functions* $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = k)$ for $k \geq 0$ and $1 \leq j \leq n_i$. Here, we will consider only parametric distributions for count data.

Observation model syntax

Considering the observations as a sequence of conditionally independent random variables, the model is completely defined by the probability mass functions $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = k)$. An observation variable for count data, with name `Y` for instance, is defined using the following syntax:

DEFINITION:

```
Y = {type=count, P(Y=k) = ...}
```

- `type=count`: indicates the data type
- `P(Y=k)`: probability of a given count value `k`, for the observation named `Y`. The observation name is free but must be the same at the beginning of the line and for the probability definition. `k` is a reserved keyword and represents a positive integer. `k` supersedes in this scope any variable `k` defined previously. The probability must be in $[0,1]$.

A transformed probability can also be provided. The transformation can be log, logit, or probit. For instance with a log-transformation:

DEFINITION:

```
Y = {type=count, log(P(Y=k)) = ...}
```

As `k` is only recognized within the probability definition, it is not possible to define the probability using `k` in an EQUATION block above. However, it is possible to use if/else statements within the probability definition:

```

DEFINITION:
Y = {type=count,
if k==0
Pk = ...
else
Pk = ...
end
P(Y=k) = Pk}
  
```

Common mathematical functions to define count distributions are `factorial(a)`, `factln(a)` (logarithm of factorial) and `gammaLn(a)` (logarithm of gamma function). They can be used with `a` any positive numerical value (not only integers). Note that factorials grow very rapidly and can be considered as “+infinity” in a computer, even when the probability is defined as a ratio of two factorials which stays with reasonable values on paper. It is thus convenient to work with logarithms of factorials, which grow much slower (see examples).

Examples

Example 1: Poisson distribution with time evolution

In this example, the Poisson distribution is used for defining the distribution of y_j :

$$y_j \sim \text{Poisson}(\lambda_j) \iff P(Y = k) = \frac{\lambda_j^k e^{-\lambda_j}}{k!}$$

where the Poisson intensity λ_j is function of time $\lambda_j = a + bt_j$. This model is implemented as follows

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a,b}

EQUATION:
lambda = a+b*t

DEFINITION:
y = {type=count, P(y=k) = exp(-lambda)*(lambda^k)/factorial(k)}
  
```

Example 2: Binomial distribution

We consider `n` Bernouilli trials, each having a probability of success `p`. The probability of having `k` successes is:

$$P(Y = k) = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!} p^k (1-p)^{n-k}$$

To avoid that $k!$ be so large that it will be considered as NaN by a computer, it is good practice to define the log of the probability to convert the ratios of large number into a sum of smaller numbers:

$$\log(P(Y = k)) = \log(n!) - \log(k!) - \log((n-k)!) + k \log(p) + (n-k) \log(1-p)$$

The corresponding Mlxtran model is:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {n, p}

DEFINITION:
CountNumber = {type=count, log(P(CountNumber=k)) = gammaln(n+1) - factln(k) -
gammaln(n-k+1) + k*log(p) + (n-k)*log(1-p)}

OUTPUT:
output = Y
```

Example 3: Poisson distribution with zero inflation

Zero-inflations can be encoded using if/else statements:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {lambda, f}

DEFINITION:
CountNumber = {type=count,
if k==0
Pk = exp(-lambda)*(1-f) + f
else
Pk = exp(k*log(lambda) - lambda - factln(k))*(1-f)
end
P(CountNumber=k) = Pk}

OUTPUT:
output = CountNumber
```

Library of count models

The MonolixSuite library of models includes many pre-written count data models: [Count library](#).

3.1.4.2.7.4 Categorical observation model

On the current page, we show details on the different models for categorical data that can be used in Simulx and their syntax.

Here we also give examples of categorical data models from the Simulx demos:

- [Categorical data models](#)
- [Joint models for non-continuous outcomes](#)

Observation model for categorical ordinal data

Use of categorical data

Assume now that the observed data takes its values in a fixed and finite set of nominal categories $\{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_K\}$. Considering the observations $(y_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$ for any individual i as a sequence of conditionally independent random variables, the model is completely defined by the probability mass functions $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = c_k | \psi_i)$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$ and $1 \leq j \leq n_i$. For a given (i, j) , the sum of the K probabilities is 1, so in fact only $K-1$ of them need to be defined. In the most general way possible, any model can be considered so long as it defines a probability distribution, i.e., for each k , $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = c_k | \psi_i) \in [0, 1]$, and $\sum_{k=1}^K \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = c_k | \psi_i) = 1$. Ordinal data further assumed that the categories are ordered, i.e., there exists an order \prec such that

$$c_1 \prec c_2, \prec \dots \prec c_K$$

We can think, for instance, of levels of pain (low \prec moderate \prec severe) or scores on a discrete scale, e.g., from 1 to 10. Instead of defining the probabilities of each category, it may be convenient to define the cumulative probabilities $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \preceq c_k | \psi_i)$ for $k = 1, \dots, K-1$, or in the other direction: $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \succeq c_k | \psi_i)$ for $k = 2, \dots, K$. Any model is possible as long as it defines a probability distribution, i.e., it satisfies

$$0 \leq \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \preceq c_1 | \psi_i) \leq \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \preceq c_2 | \psi_i) \leq \dots \leq \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \preceq c_K | \psi_i) = 1$$

It is possible to introduce dependence between observations from the same individual by assuming that $(y_{ij}, j = 1, 2, \dots, n_i)$ forms a Markov chain. For instance, a Markov chain with memory 1 assumes that all that is required from the past to determine the distribution of y_{ij} is the value of the previous observation $y_{i,j-1}$, i.e., for all $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$,

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = c_k | y_{i,j-1}, y_{i,j-2}, y_{i,j-3}, \dots, \psi_i) = \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = c_k | y_{i,j-1}, \psi_i)$$

Observation model syntax

Considering the observations as a sequence of conditionally independent random variables, the model is

again completely defined by the probability mass functions $P(y_{ij} = c_k)$ for each category. For a given j , the sum of the K probabilities is 1, so in fact only $K-1$ of them need to be defined. The distribution of ordered categorical data can be defined in the block DEFINITION: of the Section [LONGITUDINAL] using either the probability mass functions. Ordinal data further assume that the categories are ordered: $c_1 \leq c_2 \leq \dots \leq c_K$. Instead of defining the probabilities of each category, it may be convenient to define the cumulative probabilities $P(y_j \leq c_k)$ for k from 1 to $K-1$ or the cumulative logits $\text{logit}(P(y_j \leq c_k))$ for k from 1 to $K-1$. An observation variable for ordered categorical data is defined using the type categorical. Its additional fields are:

- categories: List of the available ordered categories. They are represented by increasing successive integers.
- P(Y=i): Probability of a given category integer i , for the observation named Y. A transformed probability can be provided instead of a direct one. The transformation can be log, logit, or probit. The probabilities are defined following the order of their categories. They can be provided for events where the category is a boundary, instead of an exact match. All boundaries must be of the same kind. Such an event is denoted by using a comparison operator. When the value of a probability can be deduced from others, its definition can be spared.

Example

In the proposed example, we use 4 categories and the model is implemented as follows

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {th1, th2, th3}

DEFINITION:
level = {type = categorical, categories = {0, 1, 2, 3},
logit(P(level <=0)) = th1
logit(P(level <=1)) = th1 + th2
logit(P(level <=2)) = th1 + th2 + th3}
```

Using that definition, the distribution associated to the parameters are

- Normal for th1. Elsewise, it implies that $\text{logit}(P(\text{level} \leq 0)) > 0$ and thus that $P(\text{level} \leq 0)$.
- Lognormal for th2 and th3 to make sure that $P(\text{level} \leq 1) > P(\text{level} \leq 0)$ and $P(\text{level} \leq 2) > P(\text{level} \leq 1)$ respectively.

Observation model for categorical data modeled as a discrete Markov chain

Use of categorical data modeled as a Markov chain

In the previous categorical model, the observations were considered as independent for individual i . It is however possible to introduce dependence between observations from the same individual assuming that $(y_{ij})_{j=1,\dots,n_i}$ forms a Markov chain. If observation times are regularly spaced (constant length of time between successive observations), we can consider the observations $(y_{ij}, j = 1, 2, \dots, n_i)$ to be a discrete-time Markov chain.

Observation model syntax

An observation variable for ordered categorical data modeled as a discrete Markov chain is defined using the type `categorical`, along with the dependence definition `Markov`. Its additional fields are:

- `categories`: List of the available ordered categories. They are represented by increasing successive integers. It is defined right after `type`.
- `P(Y_1=i)`: Initial probability of a given category integer i , for the observation named Y . This probability belongs to the first observed value. A transformed probability can be provided instead of a direct one. The transformation can be `log`, `logit`, or `probit`. The probabilities are defined following the order of their categories. They can be provided for events where the category is a boundary, instead of an exact match. All boundaries must be of the same kind. Such an event is denoted by using a comparison operator. When the value of a probability can be deduced from others, its definition can be spared. The initial probabilities are optional as a whole, and the default initial law is uniform.
- `P(Y=j|Y_p=i)`: Probability of transition to a given category integer j from a previous category i , for the observation named Y . A transformed probability can be provided instead of a direct one. The transformation can be `log`, `logit`, or `probit`. The probabilities are grouped by law of transition for each previous category i . Each law of transition provides the various transition probabilities of reaching j . They can be provided for events where the reached category j is a boundary, instead of an exact match. All boundaries must be of the same kind for a given law. Such an event is denoted by using a comparison operator. When the value of a transition probability can be deduced from others within its law, its definition can be spared.

Example

An example where we define an observation model for this case is proposed here

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a1, a2, a11, a12, a21, a22, a31, a32}

DEFINITION:
State = {type = categorical, categories = {1,2,3}, dependence = Markov
P(State_1=1) = a1
P(State_1=2) = a2
logit(P(State <=1|State_p=1)) = a11
logit(P(State <=2|State_p=1)) = a11+a12
```

```

logit(P(State <=1|State_p=2)) = a21
logit(P(State <=2|State_p=2)) = a21+a22
logit(P(State <=1|State_p=3)) = a31
logit(P(State <=2|State_p=3)) = a31+a32}
    
```

Using that definition, the distribution associated to the parameters are

- Logitnormal for a_1 and a_2 to make sure that the initial probability are well defined.
- Normal for a_{11} , a_{21} , and a_{31} to make sure that the probability is in $[0, 1]$.
- Lognormal for a_{12} , a_{22} , and a_{32} to make sure that the cumulative probability is increasing.

Observation model for a categorical data modeled as a continuous Markov chain

Use of categorical data modeled as a continuous Markov chain

The previous situation can be extended to the case where time intervals between observations are irregular by modeling the sequence of states as a *continuous-time Markov process*. The difference is that rather than transitioning to a new (or the same) state at each time step, the system remains in the current state for some random amount of time before transitioning. This process is now characterized by *transition rates* $\rho_{\ell k}(t)$ from the state ℓ to the state k . Given that the system is in state ℓ at time t , the probability to be in state k after a small time h is:

$$\mathbb{P}(y_i(t+h) = k, | y_i(t) = \ell, \psi_i) = h \times \rho_{\ell k}(t, \psi_i) + o(h), \quad k \neq \ell$$

The probability that no transition happens between t and $t+h$ is

$$\mathbb{P}(y_i(s) = \ell, \forall s \in (t, t+h) | y_i(t) = \ell, \psi_i) = e^{h \times \rho_{\ell \ell}(t, \psi_i)}$$

Furthermore, for any individual i and time t , the transition rates $(\rho_{\ell, k}(t, \psi_i))$ satisfy for any $1 \leq \ell \leq K$,

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \rho_{\ell k}(t, \psi_i) = 0$$

Constructing a model therefore means defining parametric functions of time $\rho_{\ell k}$ that satisfy this condition.

Observation model syntax

An observation variable for ordered categorical data modeled as a continuous Markov chain is also defined using the type `categorical`, along with the dependence definition `Markov`. But here transition rates are defined instead of transition probabilities. Its additional fields are:

- `categories`: List of the available ordered categories. They are represented by increasing successive integers. It is defined right after `type`.

- $P(Y_1=i)$: Initial probability of a given category integer i , for the observation named Y . This probability belongs to the first observed value. A transformed probability can be provided instead of a direct one. The transformation can be log, logit, or probit. The probabilities are defined following the order of their categories. They can be provided for events where the category is a boundary, instead of an exact match. All boundaries must be of the same kind. Such an event is denoted by using a comparison operator. When the value of a probability can be deduced from others, its definition can be spared. The initial probabilities are optional as a whole, and the default initial law is uniform.
- $\text{transitionRate}(i,j)$: Transition rate departing from a given category integer i and arriving to a category j . They are grouped by law of transition for each departure category i . One definition of transition rate can be spared by law of transition, as they must sum to zero.

Example

An example where we define an observation model for this case is proposed here

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={p1, q12, q21}

DEFINITION:
State = {type = categorical, categories = {1,2}, dependence = Markov}
P(State_1=1) = p1
transitionRate(1,2) = q12
transitionRate(2,1) = q21}
```

3.1.4.3 [INDIVIDUAL]: Defining parameter distributions

3.1.4.3.1 Description

The [INDIVIDUAL] section is used to define a probability distribution for model parameters, in order to model inter-individual and inter-occasion variability.

3.1.4.3.2 Scope

The [INDIVIDUAL] section is used in mlxtran models for simulation with Simulx. This section is optional and only needed for models that have parameters with inter-individual variability. Mlxtran models for Monolix do not need this section because the parameter distributions are defined via the graphical user interface.

3.1.4.3.3 Inputs

The inputs for the [INDIVIDUAL] section are the parameters that are declared in the `input = { }` list of the [INDIVIDUAL] section. They typically include the population parameters which describe the parameter distributions and the (possibly transformed) covariates. These inputs are obtained from the [COVARIATE] section or considered as global model input defined in the Simulx graphical user interface.

In addition, for categorical covariates, the type and the categories must be listed using the syntax below. The categories can be strings or integers.

```
covName = {type=categorical, categories = {..., ..., ...}}
```


Parameters that appear in the input of the [INDIVIDUAL] section and do not appear as input or output of the [COVARIATE] section will be recognized as population parameters and appear in the population parameter element of Simulx. Parameters that do appear in the [COVARIATE] section will be recognized as covariates.

Example:

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl, WT, SEX}
SEX = {type=categorical, categories = {Male, Female}}
```

3.1.4.3.4 Outputs

All parameters that has been defined in the [INDIVIDUAL] section are considered as an output of this section. There is no explicit OUTPUT block. Outputs from the [INDIVIDUAL] section are used as input for the [LONGITUDINAL] section. [INDIVIDUAL] output to [LONGITUDINAL] input matching is made by matching parameter names in the [INDIVIDUAL] section with parameters in the `inputs = { }` list of the [LONGITUDINAL] section.

3.1.4.3.5 Usage

The definition of probability distribution for a model parameter is done with the **EQUATION:** and **DEFINITION:** blocks. The **EQUATION:** block contains mathematical equations, for instance if parameter transformations are needed. The **DEFINITION:** block is used to define the probability distributions, correlations between random effects, covariate effects and inter-occasion variability. We will define these three aspects one-by-one.

3.1.4.3.5.1 Probability distribution

The main four distributions possible for the parameters are the **normal, lognormal, logitnormal and probitnormal** distributions. Additional distributions available in Simulx are described [here](#). The lognormal, logitnormal and probitnormal distributions are transformations of the normal distribution and therefore convenient to handle:

- If X follows a lognormal distribution with $X \in (0, +\infty)$, then $\log(X)$ follows a normal distribution.
- If X follows a logitnormal distribution with $X \in (0, 1)$, then $\log\left(\frac{X}{1-X}\right)$ follows a normal distribution. The logitnormal distribution can also be defined on an interval $X \in (a, b)$, in this case the transformation is $\log\left(\frac{X-a}{b-X}\right)$.
- If X follows a probitnormal distribution with $X \in (0, 1)$, then $\Phi^{-1}(X)$ follows a normal distribution, with Φ the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution.

These distributions are defined by two parameters, indicating the location and the width of the distribution. It is common to separate this information into two terms, by writing, for a **normal distribution**: $X = X_{pop} + \eta_X$ with X_{pop} the typical value (location) and η_X the random effects following a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_X^2)$, i.e with mean 0 and standard deviation σ_X (width). Note that in this case $X \sim \mathcal{N}(X_{pop}, \sigma_X^2)$ with X_{pop} the mean of the normal distribution and σ_X its standard deviation.

Similarly for **lognormal parameters**, we can write:

$$\log(X) = \log(X_{pop}) + \eta_X \iff X = X_{pop}e^{\eta_X}$$

X_{pop} represent the typical value, $\log(X_{pop})$ the mean of the associated normal distribution and σ_X the standard deviation of both the associated normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(\log(X_{pop}), \sigma_X^2)$ and of the random effects η_X . The logic is the same for logitnormal and probitnormal distributions.

The following syntax applies to define a probability distribution for the random variable X (i.e the individual parameter):

DEFINITION:

`X = {distribution= ..., typical = ..., sd = ..., min= ..., max=...}`

The arguments to the probability distribution definition are:

- **distribution**: indicates the type of the distribution. On the right-hand side, the user must indicate one of the following reserved keywords: `normal`, `lognormal`, `logitnormal`, or `probitnormal`. For use in Simulx, additional distributions are also accepted, but they cannot be combined with covariates and correlations. [The full list of distributions is available here](#).

- **typical:** typical value of the distribution (see above for more). Alternatively, the mean of the corresponding normal distribution can also be indicated, using the argument `mean`. On the right-hand side, the user can give a double value or a parameter given as input or defined in the EQUATION block. When the [INDIVIDUAL] block is generated by Monolix, the typical parameter is noted with `_pop`, but this is not mandatory (parameter names are freely chosen by the user).
- **sd:** standard deviation of the corresponding normal distribution. Alternatively, the variance can also be indicated, using the argument `var`. On the right-hand side, the user can give a double value or a parameter given as input or defined in the EQUATION block. In case of a parameter without variability, `sd=...` can be replaced by `no-variability`. When the [INDIVIDUAL] block is generated by Monolix, the standard deviation parameter is noted with `omega_`, but this is not mandatory (parameter names are freely chosen by the user).
- **min and max:** indicate a lower and upper bound for logitnormal distributions only. On the right-hand side, a double value is indicated. Default values are 0 and 1, if not indicated.

Example:

In this example, F has a logitnormal distribution with bounds]0,1[. As these are the default values, they could also be omitted. ka has no variability. From a mathematical point of view, a parameter without variability does not require a distribution indication, but for consistency with Monolix where this information is used to define the bounds of the possible range of values, it must be indicated. V and Cl have lognormal distributions with variability.

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {F_pop, omega_F, ka_pop, V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl}

DEFINITION:
F = {distribution=logitnormal, typical=F_pop, sd=omega_F, min=0, max=1}
ka = {distribution=lognormal, typical=ka_pop, no-variability}
V = {distribution=lognormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V }
Cl = {distribution=lognormal, typical=Cl_pop, sd=omega_Cl}
```

In the second example, Emax is sampled from a uniform distribution and IC50 from a lognormal distribution.

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {Emax_min, Emax_max, IC50_pop, omega_IC50}

DEFINITION:
Emax = {distribution=uniform, min=Emax_min, max=Emax_max}
IC50 = {distribution=lognormal, typical=IC50_pop, sd=omega_IC50}
```

3.1.4.3.5.2 Correlations between random effects

Correlations between random effects can also be specified. The correlation between one or several pairs of parameters can be indicated. Correlations which are not listed are assumed to be zero. The syntax is the following, with `corr_p1_p2` and `corr_p1_p3` population parameters appearing in the input list and `param1`, `param2` and `param3` individual parameters defined via a distribution with inter-individual variability.

```
correlation = {r(param1, param2)=corr_p1_p2, r(param1,param3)=corr_p1_3}
```

Within a correlation group, all correlations must be defined. For instance if there is correlation (ka, V) and (V, Cl), then ka, V, and Cl form a group and it is also necessary to define the correlation between (V, ka). There can be one or several correlation groups. A parameter can only belong to one group. The corresponding variance-covariance matrix is thus a block diagonal matrix with each block representing one group.

Variance-covariance matrices estimated in another software (omega matrix in Nonmem for instance) can be converted to a correlation matrix using the following equation:

$$\text{corr}(\theta_i, \theta_j) = \frac{\text{covar}(\theta_i, \theta_j)}{\sqrt{\text{var}(\theta_i)}\sqrt{\text{var}(\theta_j)}}$$

Example:

In this example, we have two correlation groups (ka,V,Cl) and (Emax,EC50). The parameter Tlag is not correlated with any other and don't appear in any group.

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {ka_pop, omega_ka, V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl, EC50_pop, omega_EC50,
Emax_pop,
omega_Emax, Tlag_pop, omega_Tlag, corr_ka_V, corr_V_Cl, corr_ka_Cl, corr_Emax_EC50}
DEFINITION:
Tlag = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Tlag_pop, sd=omega_Tlag}
ka = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ka_pop, sd=omega_ka}
V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_pop, sd=omega_Cl}
EC50 = {distribution=logNormal, typical=EC50_pop, sd=omega_EC50}
Emax = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Emax_pop, sd=omega_Emax}
correlation = {r(Emax, EC50)=corr_Emax_EC50, r(V, Cl)=corr_V_Cl, r(ka,
Cl)=corr_ka_Cl, r(ka, V)=corr_ka_V}
```

3.1.4.3.5.3 Covariates

Covariates effects can be defined directly in the distribution definition. In this case the covariates (or their transformations) are added linearly on the transformed normally-distributed parameter, as in Monolix. In Simulx, it is also possible to define the covariate in a more flexible way, by defining the typical value including the covariates in the EQUATION block and then using the typical value in the `typical` argument of the distribution definition. It is possible to use the “Monolix style” for some parameter-covariate relationships and the “flexible style” for others.

In both cases, covariates are considered constant over time for each individual (or each occasion of each individual). For time-varying covariates, see regressors.

Monolix style

When defining a covariate model in Monolix, the covariates are always added linearly on the transformed normally-distributed parameter (e.g $\log(X)$ if X has a lognormal distribution). Using covariate transformations defined in the EQUATION block, different parameter-covariate relationships can be obtained, such as exponential or power law. For instance:

$$\log(V) = \log(V_{pop}) + \beta \times WT + \eta_V \iff V = V_{pop} e^{\beta \times WT} e^{\eta_V}$$

$$\log(V) = \log(V_{pop}) + \beta \times tWT + \eta_V \quad \text{with} \quad tWT = \log\left(\frac{WT}{70}\right) \iff V = V_{pop} \left(\frac{WT}{70}\right)^\beta e^{\eta_V}$$

Categorical covariates have a reference category, which corresponds to the typical value X_{pop} , and the other categories are defined via beta parameters, which indicate the change with respect to the reference category in the linear space. For instance, when adding the covariate RACE with categories “White” (set as reference), “Asian” and “Black” on V which has a lognormal distribution:

$$\log(V) = \log(V_{pop}) + \beta_a [\text{if RACE="Asian"}] + \beta_b [\text{if RACE="Black"}] + \eta_V \iff \begin{cases} V = V_{pop} e^{\eta_V} & \text{if RACE="White"} \\ V = V_{pop} e^{\beta_a} e^{\eta_V} & \text{if RACE="Asian"} \\ V = V_{pop} e^{\beta_b} e^{\eta_V} & \text{if RACE="Black"} \end{cases}$$

To define these relationships in Mlxtran, we add additional arguments `covariate` and `coefficient` in the distribution definition:

DEFINITION:

`X = {distribution= ..., typical = ..., covariate = ..., coefficient=..., sd = ...}`

- **covariate:** indicates the covariates influencing the parameter value. On the right-hand side, the comma-separated list of covariates is indicated, surrounded by curly brackets. Covariates must appear in the input list or be defined in the EQUATION block. For categorical covariates, the categories must be indicated below the input list (see above). All covariates are included linearly on the transformed normally-distributed parameter.

- **coefficient:** indicates the beta coefficients defining the covariate impact. On the right-hand side, the comma-separated list of betas is indicated, surrounded by curly brackets. Betas corresponding to the categories of the same categorical covariate are also surrounded by curly brackets. The betas must be in the same order as the covariates listed in the `covariate` argument and in the same order as the categories listed below the input. For the reference category, a zero is usually indicated. The betas must appear in the input list. The coefficients must be parameters (which can be defined in the EQUATION block or in the input), they cannot be directly numbers.

Example:

In this example, we have two continuous covariates (Age and Weight) and two categorical covariates (Sex and Race). In the [COVARIATE] section, all covariates are listed in the input, categorical covariate categories are listed and continuous covariates are transformed into `logtAge` and `logtWeight`.

In the [INDIVIDUAL] section, the input lists the population parameters (typical values `_pop`, standard deviations `omega_` and all `betas`) and the (possibly transformed) covariates. The order of the categories for categorical covariates is indicated just below. In the DEFINITION bloc, we define the distribution for:

- ka: covariate Race
- V: covariate logtWeight
- Cl: covariates RACE, Sex, logtWeight and logtAge

```

[COVARIATE]
input = {Age, Weight, Race, Sex}
Race = {type=categorical, categories={Caucasian, Black, Latin}}
Sex = {type=categorical, categories={M, F}}

EQUATION:
logtAge = log(Age/65)
logtWeight = log(Weight/70)

[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {V_pop, omega_V, ka_pop, omega_ka, Cl_pop, omega_Cl, logtAge, Race, Sex,
logtWeight,
beta_Cl_Race_Caucasian, beta_Cl_Race_Latin, beta_Cl_Smoke_yes, beta_Cl_logtAge,
beta_V_logtWeight, beta_Cl_logtWeight, beta_ka_Race_Caucasian, beta_ka_Race_Latin}

Race = {type=categorical, categories={Caucasian, Black, Latin}}
Sex = {type=categorical, categories={M, F}}

DEFINITION:
V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, covariate=logtWeight,
coefficient=beta_V_logtWeight, sd=omega_V}
ka = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ka_pop, covariate=Race, coefficient={0,
beta_ka_Race_Black, beta_ka_Race_Latin}, sd=omega_ka}
Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_pop, covariate={Race, Smoke, logtAge,
logtWeight}, coefficient={{0, beta_Cl_Race_Black, beta_Cl_Race_Latin},
{0, beta_Cl_Sex_F}, beta_Cl_logtAge, beta_Cl_logtWeight}, sd=omega_Cl}
  
```

Flexible style

Simulx allows more flexibility in the definition of the covariate model than Monolix. It can for instance be complex non-linear relations between the parameters and the covariates. The most convenient way is to define the typical value including the covariate effects (often prefixed with TV in Nonmem) in the DEFINITION block and then use this variable in the DEFINITION block where the random effects are defined.

In this case, the untransformed covariates are given directly as input to the [INDIVIDUAL] section. To be recognized as covariates and not population parameters, it is important to have a [COVARIATE] section which lists the covariates in the input, and the categorical covariate categories.

The typical value can be defined using mathematical expressions and if/else statements. If/else statements can use conditions based on continuous and categorical covariates. A given if/else statement can combined several continuous covariate or several categorical covariates but not a mix of continuous and categorical covariates in the same if/else statement. When categories contain spaces or symbols (not recommended), they must be surrounded by single quotes. Even when categorical covariates categories are integers, they cannot be used in mathematical expression (e.g (1-SEX) is forbidden).

Example:

In this example, two covariates are used: Age and Race. They are listed in the [INDIVIDUAL] input list, but also the [COVARIATE] section, in order to be recognized as covariates, while the other parameters listed in the [INDIVIDUAL] input are recognized as population parameters. Race has 5 different categories and has an impact on ka. Using if/else statement, Japanese and Chinese are grouped together. All covariate effects are defined in the EQUATION block and the typical value with covariates effects in then used in the definition of the distribution.

```
[COVARIATE]
input = {Age, Race}
Race = {type=categorical, categories={White, Black, Japanese, Chinese, Latin}}

[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {V_pop, omega_V, ka_pop_White, ka_pop_Asian, ka_pop_Other, omega_ka, Cl_pop,
betaAgeCl, betaAgeV, omega_Cl, Age, Race}
Race = {type=categorical, categories={White, Black, Japanese, Chinese, Latin}}

EQUATION:
if Race == White
ka_typ = ka_pop_White
elseif Race == Japanese | Race == Chinese
ka_typ = ka_pop_Asian
else
ka_typ = ka_pop_Other
end

V_typ = V_pop * (Age/45)^betaAgeV

Cl_typ = Cl_pop * (Age/45)^betaAgeCl

DEFINITION:
V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_typ, sd=omega_V}
ka = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ka_typ, sd=omega_ka}
Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_typ, sd=omega_Cl}
```

Categorical covariates categories can also be integers, as in the example below:

```
[COVARIATE]
input = {Sex}
Sex = {type=categorical, categories={0,1}}

[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop0, Cl_pop1, omega_Cl, Sex}
Sex = {type=categorical, categories={0,1}}

EQUATION:
if Sex == 1
Cl_typ = Cl_pop1
else
Cl_typ = Cl_pop0
```

```
end
```

In the third example, we define a parameter-covariate relationship which requires two parameters. Cl depends on the post-conceptual age (PCA) with a Hill-shaped relationship. The duration of the study is short enough to consider PCA constant over time.

```
[COVARIATE]
input = {PCA}

[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl, PCA50, n, PCA}

EQUATION:
TVCL = Cl_pop * PCA^n / (PCA50^n + PCA^n)

DEFINITION:
V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=TVCL, sd=omega_Cl}
```

3.1.4.3.5.4 Inter-occasion variability

In addition to inter-individual variability, it is possible to define one or several additional levels of variability, called occasions. The occasion structure is defined in the Simulx GUI. Although the terms and keyword refer to inter-individual and inter-occasion variability, it is possible to use them with a different meaning, for instance inter-study variability and inter-arm variability.

Importantly, for inter-occasion variability to be taken into account, there must be an occasion element defined in Simulx, and this occasion element must have more than one occasion. If this is not the case, the random effect at IOV level will be skipped and parameters with IOV but no IOV will have no variability.

Inter-occasion variability is taken into account by a separate random effect term η_{ik}^{IOV} , which varies from occasion to occasion (index k), while the inter-individual random effect term η_i^{IIV} varies from individual to individual only (index i). The index i for the IOV random effect indicates that the sampled random effect for id1, occ1 is different than that from id2, occ1. Below we give an example for the definition of the lognormal clearance Cl for individual i and occasion k :

$$\log(Cl_{ik}) = \log(Cl_{pop}) + \eta_i^{IIV} + \eta_{ik}^{IOV}$$

The random effects at the IOV level are characterized by their standard deviation. The syntax is the following:

```
DEFINITION:
X = {distribution = ..., typical = ..., varlevel = {..., ...} sd = {..., ...}}
```

- **varlevel:** indicates the levels at which variability is present. The reserved keywords are `id` (for inter-individual variability), `id*occ` for the first level of inter-occasion variability, `id*occ*occ` for the second level, etc. The syntax `id*occ` stresses that the random effects are IOV level vary from occasion to occasion but also from individual to individual. A parameter can have only IIV, only IOV or both.
- **sd:** the `sd` argument lists as many standard deviations as variability levels defined in `varlevel`.

Of course, `covariates` can also be included as explained above, as well as the `min` and `max` arguments for logitnormal distributions.

Correlations between random effects can be defined at each level, using one line per level and the additional `level` argument with value `id`, `id*occ`, `id*occ*occ`, etc. Correlations can only be defined among parameter which have correlations at this level.

```
correlation = {level = id, r(param1, param2)=corr_p1_p2,
r(param1,param3)=corr_p1_3, ...}
correlation = {level = id*occ, r(param4, param5)=corr_p4_p5, ...}
```

Example:

In this example, `Tlag` has IOV, `ka` and `Cl` have IIV and IOV and `V` has only IIV. The random effects at the IIV level are correlated for `V` and `Cl`. The random effects at IOV level are correlated for `ka` and `Tlag`.

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {ka_pop, omega_ka, Cl_pop, omega_Cl, Tlag_pop, V_pop, omega_V, gamma_Tlag,
gamma_ka, gamma_Cl, corr1_V_Cl, corr2_ka_Tlag}

DEFINITION:
Tlag = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Tlag_pop, varlevel=id*occ, sd=gamma_Tlag}
ka = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ka_pop, varlevel={id, id*occ}, sd={omega_ka,
gamma_ka}}
Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_pop, varlevel={id, id*occ}, sd={omega_Cl,
gamma_Cl}}
V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
correlation = {level=id, r(V, Cl)=corr1_V_Cl}
correlation = {level=id*occ, r(ka, Tlag)=corr2_ka_Tlag}
```

3.1.4.4 [COVARIATE]: describing covariates

3.1.4.4.1 Description

The section [COVARIATE] is used to list the covariates and define transformations. Note that transformations can also be defined [INDIVIDUAL] or in the [LONGITUDINAL] section if this is more

convenient. In both cases, listing the covariates in the [COVARIATE] section is important to make them appear in the [covariate elements of Simulx](#).

i In the mlxR package in combination with MonolixSuite 2019 and before, the covariate block can also be used to define distributions of covariates. This is not possible in the 2020 version and later, where covariates are considered as inputs.

3.1.4.4.2 Scope

The [COVARIATE] section is used in Mlxtran models for simulation with Simulx. It is only needed for models that have parameters that depend on covariates. Mlxtran models for Monolix do not need this section because the covariate model is defined via the graphical user interface.

3.1.4.4.3 Inputs

Inputs to the [COVARIATE] section are provided through the list `input = { }`. The inputs are typically the untransformed covariates. In addition, for categorical covariates, the type and the categories must be listed using the syntax below. The categories can be strings or integers.

```
covName = {type=categorical, categories = {..., ..., ...}}
```

We recommend using only letters, numbers and underscore as covariate name and covariate categories. For covariate categories, it is possible to use spaces and symbols but the string must then be surrounded by single quotes.

The inputs of the [COVARIATE] section will be recognized as covariates and will appear in the [covariate element definition of Simulx](#). Covariates for which no categories are specified will be considered as continuous covariates for which we can give any double value. Covariates with listed categories are considered as categorical covariates and only the categories listed in the model can be provided as value in the GUI.

Example:

The continuous covariate Age is just listed in the input. The categorical covariates DOSE and SEX have their categories defined just below. As the categories for DOSE have a space, they are surrounded by single quotes.

```
[COVARIATE]
input = {AGE, DOSE, SEX}
DOSE = {type=categorical, categories={'50 mg', '100 mg'}}
SEX = {type=categorical, categories={Female, Male}}
```

3.1.4.4.4 Outputs

All variables that have been defined in the [COVARIATE] section are considered as an output of this section. Outputs from the [COVARIATE] section can be an input for the [INDIVIDUAL] section. [COVARIATE] output to [INDIVIDUAL] input matching is made by matching parameter names in the [COVARIATE] section with parameters in the inputs = { } list of the [INDIVIDUAL] section.

3.1.4.4.5 Usage

Transformations of continuous covariates is done in the **EQUATION:** block via mathematical expressions including if/else statements. Transformations of categorical covariates (such as grouping of categories) is done in the **DEFINITION:** block. Transformation of categorical covariates is important in Monolix, but has only little interest in Simulx as the same beta can be reused several times for different categories in the [INDIVIDUAL] section. The syntax is the following to transform a categorical covariates called CovName with categories cat1, cat2 and cat3 into a new covariate called transCovName with a first category newcat12 grouping cat1 and cat2 and a second category newcat3 grouping cat3:

```
transCovName = {transform = CovName, categories = {newcat12={cat,cat2},
newcat3=cat3}, reference = newcat12}
```

3.1.4.4.6 Examples

In this example, three covariates are defined as input and will appear in the Simulx covariate elements: AGE, SEX and RACE. The categories of the categorical covariates SEX and RACE are defined just below the input list, using strings. In the EQUATION: block, a new covariate logtAGE is defined based on AGE, using an if/else statement to introduce a saturation. In the DEFINITION: block, a new categorical covariate tRACE is defined by grouping the categories Black and White together.

```
[COVARIATE]
input = {AGE, RACE, SEX}
RACE = {type=categorical, categories={Asian, Black, White}}
SEX = {type=categorical, categories={F, M}}

EQUATION:
if AGE < 56
logtAGE = log(AGE/35)
else
```

```
logtAGE = log(56/35)
end
```

DEFINITION:

```
tRACE =
{
transform = RACE,
categories = {
G_Asian = Asian,
G_Black_White = {Black, White} },
reference = G_Black_White
}
```

3.1.4.5 Language reference

3.1.4.5.1 Reserved keywords

Reserved keywords

Some keywords are used in Mlxtran for dedicated purposes. Thus these keywords are not available for re-definition or overloading.

Time-related keyword

The reserved keyword for the time is `t`. It corresponds to the time defined in the TIME column in Monolix, and the times defined in the treatment, observation and regressor elements in Simulx.

Example:

The keyword time can be used to define a time-varying clearance for instance:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, CLini, CLss, T12}

EQUATION:
Cl = CLss - (CLss-CLini)*exp(-t/T12)
Cc = pkmodel(V,Cl)
```

Administration-related keywords

Information related to the doses defined in the data set or in the Simulx treatment elements are available in the structural model via several keyword. They are piece-wise constant functions which value is updated each time there is a dose. Before the first dose, their value is zero.

The value of the keyword are directly related to the design, they are unaffected by the absorption/depot macros arguments such as Tlag or p. Note that doses are *not* discriminated according to their administration types.

- **tDose**: holds the time of the last administered dose.
- **amtDose**: holds the amount of the last administered dose.
- **infDose**: holds the infusion duration of the last administered dose.

Example:

The keyword amtDose can be used to define a dose-dependent absorption for instance:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl, D50}

EQUATION:
F = D50/(amtDose+D50)
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl, p=F)
```

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9gy1JLfdssl>

[Full list of keywords](#)

Reserved keywords

Here is the full list of Mlxtran keywords to use in Simulx, except

- the keywords used for distribution definition (that are listed [here](#))
- the keywords used for classical mathematical definition (that are listed [here](#))

Name	Meaning	where can it be used ?	link
absorption	Macro used for defining the absorption process in a longitudinal model	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link

adm	Type of administration (type and adm are equivalent)	In argument of the following macros: absorption, depot, iv and oral	depot macro, other macros
amount	Name of the variable defined as the dose amount within the compartment	In argument of the following macros: compartment and peripheral	link
amtDose	Amount of the last administered dose. This is a step function and is null before the first dose.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	current page
bsmm	Mixture of continuous observations. It is a mixture between subjects model mixtures (BSMM). It assumes no inter individual variabilities for the proportions of each group (i.e. the probabilities to belong to the different groups). It is relevant only for Monolix.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	see Monolix doc
categorical	Type of observation model	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: after a type=	link
categories	List of the available ordered categories for a categorical observation. They are usually represented by increasing successive integers.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is a category	link
cmt	Label of the compartment	In argument of the following macros: absorption, compartment, depot, effect, elimination, iv, oral	link
coefficient	Coefficient under consideration for a distribution definition depending on covariates	In any distribution definition in a block DEFINITION:	link
combined1	Combined error model $y = f + (a + b * f)e$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
combined1c	Corresponds to a combined error model $y = f + (a + b * f^c)e$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link

combined2	Combined error model $y = f + a * e_1 + b * f * e_2$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
combined2c	Combined error model $y = f + a * e_1 + b * f^c * e_2$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
compartment	Macro used for defining a compartment	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
concentration	Name of the variable defined as the concentration within the compartment	In argument of the following macros: compartment, effect, peripheral	link
constant	Constant error model $y = f + a * e$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
continuous	Type of observation model.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: after a type=	link
count	Type of observation model.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: after a type=	link
covariate	Covariate under consideration for a distribution definition	In any distribution definition in a block DEFINITION:	link
delay	It corresponds to delay function to define DDE.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
dependence	It corresponds to the label used to defined that an observation variable for ordered categorical data modelled as a Markov chain.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is categorical	link
depot	It corresponds to an absorption targeting a depot. A component of an ODE system is defined as the target depot for the doses.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link

effect	This macro defines an effect compartment. It is linked to a simple compartment and used through the variable for its effect concentration.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
elimination	This macro defines an elimination process.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
else	It is part of a conditional statement. A conditional statement can be built by combining the keywords if, elseif, else and end.	In a block EQUATION:	link
elseif	It is part of a conditional statement. A conditional statement can be built by combining the keywords if, elseif, else and end.	In a block EQUATION:	link
end	It is part of a conditional statement. A conditional statement can be built by combining the keywords if, elseif, else and end.	In a block EQUATION:	link
errorModel	It corresponds to the label to define an error model for a continuous observation model	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
event	Type of observation model.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: after a type=	link
eventType	Label to define the event type for an event observation model. It allows to define if the exact time of the events or censored per interval is observed.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link
from	Label of the source compartment for the transfer.	In argument of the following macro: transfer	link
hazard	Hazard function	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link

if	It is part of a conditional statement. A conditional statement can be built by combining the keywords if, elseif, else and end.	In a block EQUATION:	link
inftDose	The keyword inftDose defines the infusion time of the last administered dose. This is a step function. The rate of the final absorption can be different from the rate of the administration process. It is null before the first dose.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	current page
input	It corresponds to the definition of the inputs in a subsection	In subsections [LONGITUDINAL], [INDIVIDUAL], and [COVARIATE]	link
intervalCensored	Argument of eventType.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link
intervalLength	Label to length of censoring intervals in an event observation model. It is useful for simulation only,	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link
iv	The macro iv defines an absorption for intravenous doses. Doses without an administration rate or infusion time are instantaneously absorbed within the associated compartment, as an IV bolus.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
linear	It is an argument of odeType= and allows to define the dynamical system as linear	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
Markov	It corresponds to the dependence of a categorical observation model. It allows to define that the observation model is based on a Markov chain	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: after a dependence=	link
maxEventNumber	Maximum number of events in an event observation model. It is useful for simulation only	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link

mean	Mean of the associated normal distribution.	In any distribution definition in a block DEFINITION:	link
nonStiff	It is an argument of odeType= and allows to define the dynamical system is nonStiff and thus yields to an adapted numerical scheme for the resolution	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
odeType	It is the label that allows to define the type of ODE.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
oral	It is a macro used for defining the absorption process in a longitudinal model	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
output	It allows to define the outputs of a structural model	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block OUTPUT:	link
P	The majuscule P corresponds to the definition of a probability	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	link
p	It corresponds to the bio availability in an absorption process	In argument of the following macro: absorption, depot, iv, and oral	link
peripheral	The macro peripheral defines a peripheral compartment. It is equivalent to a simple compartment with two transfers of amount towards and from another compartment.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
PK	It defines where the macros are defined	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL]	link
pkmodel	It defines the macro pkmodel	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block PK: or in a block EQUATION:	link
prediction	It corresponds to the name of the base prediction variable	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link

proportional	Corresponds to proportional error model $y = f + b * fe$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
proportionalc	Corresponds to proportional error model $y = f + b * f^c e$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
regressor	It declares the input regression values.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], after the input definition	link
rightCensoringTime	Right censoring time of events. It is useful for simulation only	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link
sd	Standard deviation of the associated normal distribution (standardDeviation and sd are synonymous keywords)	In any distribution definition in a block DEFINITION:	link
standardDeviation	Standard deviation of the associated normal distribution (standardDeviation and sd are synonymous keywords)	In any distribution definition in a block DEFINITION:	link
stiff	It is an argument of odeType= and allows to define the dynamical system is nonStiff and thus yields to an adapted numerical scheme for the resolution	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
t	time	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	Current page
t_0	Initialization time for the equations	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	link
t0	Initialization time for the equations	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	link

table	This keywords declares the variables to record in tables.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block OUTPUT:	link
target	Name of the component of an ODE system that is shifted by the absorption.	In argument of the following macro: depot	link
tDose	The keyword tDose defines the time of the last administered dose. This is a step function. Its value is unaffected by any lag time Tlag. Indeed, a lag time targets the dose absorption. It is null before the first dose.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	Current page
to	Label of the target compartment for the transfer	In argument of the following macro: transfer	link
transfer	The macro transfer defines a transfer of amount from a first compartment to a second one.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
transitionRate	Transition rate departing from a given category to another one. It is used in the definition of a categorical observation model.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	link
type	It allows the type of observation model. It can be continuous, count, categorical, or event.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	link
typical	It corresponds to the typical value during a distribution definition	In any distribution definition in a block DEFINITION:	link
use	It allows to define the regressor in the longitudinal subsection. Regressors are defined as inputs at the beginning and thus are specified as regressors using use=	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], after the input definition	link
var	Variance of the associated normal distribution (variance and var are synonymous keywords)	In any distribution definition in a block DEFINITION:	link

variance	Variance of the associated normal distribution (variance and var are synonymous keywords)	In any distribution definition in a block DEFINITION:	link
volume	It corresponds to the name of predefined variable to use as the volume of the compartment	In argument of the following macros: compartment, effect, peripheral	link
wsmm	Mixture of continuous observations. It is a mixture within subjects.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	see Monolix doc

3.1.4.5.2 If/else statements

If a parameter value depends on a condition, it can be written with in `Mlxtran` with the usual if-else-end syntax. For example, if a parameter `c` should be 1 if `t<=10`, 2 if `t<20` and 3 otherwise, write

```

if t<=10
  c = 1
elseif t<20
  c = 2
else
  c = 3
end

```

3.1.4.5.2.1 Conditional derivatives

Derivatives cannot be written within an if-else-end structure. Instead, intermediate variables should be used. For example, if a derivative of `x` over time should be 1 if `t<=10` and 2 otherwise, write

```

if t<=10
  dx = 1
else
  dx = 2
end
ddt_x = dx

```

3.1.4.5.2.2 Example: count model

Some models from the Count model library are defined with if/else statements, such as the zero-inflated Poisson model:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input= {lambda0, nu, f}

EQUATION:
lambda = lambda0*exp(-t/nu)

DEFINITION:
CountNumber= {type=count,
  if k==0
    Pk = exp(-lambda)*(1-f) + f
  else
    Pk = exp(k*log(lambda) -lambda -factln(k))*(1-f)
  end
P(CountNumber=k) = Pk}

OUTPUT:
output= CountNumber
```

3.1.4.5.3 Mathematical functions

The following usual mathematical functions are available. They perform scalar operations, either on integers or real numbers. These operations are performed using a double precision for their floating-point implementation.

Function	Syntax	Remarks
Smallest value	min(a,b)	
Largest value	max(a,b)	
Absolute value	abs(a)	
Square root	sqrt(a)	
Exponential	exp(a)	
Natural logarithm	log(a)	
Common logarithm	log10(a)	

Function	Syntax	Remarks
Logistic function	logit(a)	
Inverse of the logistic function	invlogit(a)	
Probit function	probit(a)	Aliases: norminv, qnorm.
Normal CDF	normcdf(a)	Alias: pnorm.
Sine	sin(a)	
Cosine	cos(a)	
Tangent	tan(a)	
Inverse Sine	asin(a)	
Inverse Cosine	acos(a)	
Inverse Tangent	atan(a)	
Hyperbolic Sine	sinh(a)	
Hyperbolic Cosine	cosh(a)	
Hyperbolic Tangent	tanh(a)	
Four quadrant inverse tangent	atan2(a,b)	
Logarithm of gamma function	gammaln(a)	Alias: lgamma
Downward rounding	floor(a)	
Upward rounding	ceil(a)	
Factorial	factorial(a)	
Logarithm of factorial	factln(a)	
Remainder after division	rem(a, b)	

3.1.4.5.4 Probability distributions

This page summarizes the distributions available in Mlxtran. In Simulx, they can be used to define random variables in the [\[INDIVIDUAL\]](#) section (individual parameters) or in the [\[LONGITUDINAL\]](#) section (observations).

3.1.4.5.4.1 Normal distribution and the associated transformed

To define the normal distribution and its transformations, the user can either define the `mean` of the associated normal distribution or the `typical` value of the distribution; as well as the standard deviation `sd` or variance `var` of the associated normal distribution. For the logitnormal distribution, the `min` and `max` can also be specified (optional). Covariates and correlations between random effects can also be added, see the [\[INDIVIDUAL\]](#) section.

- Normal distribution, used with keyword `normal` : $h(X) = X$

```
y_norm = {distribution=normal, typical=0, sd=1}
y_norm = {distribution=normal, mean=0, sd=1}
```

- Log-normal distribution, used with keyword `lognormal` : $h(X) = \log(X)$

```
y_ln = {distribution=lognormal, typical=1, sd=0.3}
y_ln = {distribution=lognormal, mean=0, sd=0.3}
```

- Logit-normal distribution, used with keyword `logitnormal` : $h(X) = \log\left(\frac{X-a}{b-X}\right)$ with a and b the bounds of the logit-normal distribution indicated in the optional arguments `min` and `max`. By default, $a=0$ and $b=1$.

```
y_lgn = {distribution=logitnormal, typical=0.5, sd=0.6, min=0, max=1}
y_lgn = {distribution=logitnormal, mean=0, sd=0.6, min=0, max=1}
```

- Probit-normal distribution, used with keyword `probitnormal` : $h(X) = \Phi^{-1}(X)$, where Φ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution

```
y_pbn = {distribution=probitnormal, typical=0.5, sd=0.6}
y_pbn = {distribution=probitnormal, mean=0, sd=0.6}
```

3.1.4.5.4.2 Other distributions

Additional distributions are available for simulation purpose in Simulx. They include continuous and discrete distributions. These distributions can neither be combined with the argument `covariate`, nor with the definition of correlations of random effects.

Continuous distributions

- Uniform distribution, used with keyword `uniform`,

```
y_uni = {distribution=uniform, min=0, max=100}
```

- Exponential distribution, used with keyword `exponential`,

```
y_exp = {distribution=exponential, rate=0.7}
```

- Gamma distribution, used with keyword `gamma`,

```
y_gamma = {distribution=gamma, shape=2, scale=0.5}
```

- Weibull distribution, used with keyword `weibull`,

```
y_weibull = {distribution=weibull, shape=0.75, scale=1.2}
```

- ExtremeValue distribution, used with keyword `extremeValue`,

```
y_ev = {distribution=extremeValue, location=-10, scale=1.8}
```

- ChiSquared distribution, used with keyword `chiSquared`,

```
y_cs = {distribution=chiSquared, df=2}
```

- Cauchy distribution, used with keyword `cauchy`,

```
y_cauchy = {distribution=cauchy, location=-5.2, scale=2.7}
```

- FisherF distribution, used with keyword `fisherF`,

```
y_fisherF = {distribution=fisherF, df1=10, df2=9}
```

- StudentT distribution, used with keyword studentT,

```
y_studentT = {distribution=studentT, df=2}
```

Discrete distributions

- Bernoulli distribution, used with keyword bernoulli,

```
y_ber = {distribution=bernoulli, prob=0.3}
```

- Discrete uniform distribution, used with keyword discreteUniform,

```
y_du = {distribution=discreteUniform, min=-4, max=2}
```

- Binomial distribution, used with keyword binomial,

```
y_bi = {distribution=binomial, size=30, prob=0.7}
```

- Geometric distribution, used with keyword geometric,

```
y_ber = {distribution=geometric, prob=0.2}
```

- Negative binomial distribution, used with keyword negativeBinomial,

```
y_nb = {distribution=negativeBinomial, size=3, prob=0.1}
```

- Poisson distribution, used with keyword poisson.

```
y_nb = {distribution=poisson, lambda=0.1}
```

3.1.4.5.5 Operators

The following operators are available, under their mathematical acceptance.

3.1.4.5.5.1 Arithmetic operators

The arithmetic operators perform operations on real numbers. These operations are performed using a double precision for their floating-point implementation. The specific operations on integers have a function call syntax, e.g. factorial.

Operator	Syntax	Remarks
Equal	$a=b$	Defines variables
Addition	$a+b$	
Subtraction	$a-b$	
Multiplication	$a*b$	
Division	a/b	
Power	a^b	Right associative
Unitary plus	$+a$	
Unitary minus	$-a$	

3.1.4.5.5.2 Logical operators

The logical operators perform operations on boolean values. They appear as conditions within conditional statements.

Operator	Syntax	Other possible syntax
Negation	$\sim a$	$!a$
Or	$a b$	$a b$
And	$a\&b$	$a\&\&b$

3.1.4.5.5.3 Relational operators

The relational operators perform operations on real numbers. These operations are performed using a double precision for their floating-point implementation.

Operator	Syntax	Other possible syntax
Equal to	$a==b$	
Not equal to	$a\neq b$	$a!=b$
Greater than	$a>b$	
Less than	$a<b$	
Greater or equal to	$a\geq b$	
Less or equal to	$a\leq b$	2

3.1.5 Libraries of models

On the following pages you can find details about the models contained in each library of Simulx:

3.1.5.1 PK model library

The PK library is a library of standard PK models. Instead of writing the structural model yourself, you can select among simple PK models already written and verified for you. When you select the PK library, a full list of all available models appear. You can filter a specific model by selecting options for administration, distribution and elimination.

The screenshot shows the 'Structural model' tab in Monolix. It displays a table of PK models with columns for Administration, Delay, Absorption, Distribution, and Elimination. Below the table, there is a search bar and a list of model configurations with their corresponding names and icons for deletion.

PK	Administration	Delay	Absorption	Distribution	Elimination
PD	bolus	no delay	zero order	1 compartment	linear
PKPD	infusion	lag time	first order	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
PK Double Absorption	oral/extravascular	transit compartments		3 compartments	
TMDD	oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion				

Below the table, there is a search bar and a list of model configurations:

- TTE**: bolus_1cpt_VCl
- Count**: bolus_1cpt_VVmKm
- TGI**: bolus_1cpt_Vk
- Count**: bolus_2cpt_CIV1QV2
- TGI**: bolus_2cpt_V1QV2VmKm
- Count**: bolus_2cpt_Vk12k21VmKm
- TGI**: bolus_2cpt_Vkk12k21
- Count**: bolus_2cpt_alphabetaAB
- TGI**: bolus_3cpt_CIV1Q2V2Q3V3
- Count**: bolus_3cpt_V1Q2V2Q3V3VmKm
- TGI**: bolus_3cpt_Vk12k21k13k31VmKm
- Count**: bolus_3cpt_Vkk12k21k13k31
- TGI**: bolus_3cpt_alphabetaGammaABC

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 157
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 Showing 1 to 25 of 157 entries

Here we provide general guidelines to select a standard PK model that is the most suited to your dataset.

If you open any of the .txt files in this library, corresponding to the model written in mlxtran-formatted code, you see that the pkmodel macro is always used. This macro enables to define all standard PK models in a compact manner (except for <https://monolixsuite.slp-software.com/monolix/?contextKey=multiple-administration-routes>). It uses the analytical solution of the ODE system to simulate it, if it is available (which is the case for all models with linear elimination and without transit compartments), and otherwise the ODE system itself. A complete list of the analytical solutions for standard PK and PKPD models is available in this document: PKPDlibrary.pdf

If none of the standard PK models seems to fit your needs, consider using a model from our other PK libraries (PK double absorption, TMDD). To define your own custom PK model, jump directly to data and models.

All PK models in the library correspond to a system of equations with the following structure:

- an input rate which depends on the type of administration
- an ODE system based on a number of compartments
- an elimination rate which depends on the type of elimination selected.

The equations express the concentration $C(t)$ in the central compartment at a time t after the last drug administration:

- *Single dose:* at time t after dose D given at time t_D
- *Multiples doses:* at time t after n doses D_i for i from 1 to n given at time t_{D_i}
- *Steady state:* at a time t after dose D given at time t_D after repeated administration of dose D given at interval τ (only for linear elimination)

3.1.5.1.1 Routes of administration

You should know the type of administration to use based on the study that generated the dataset. The route of administration will determine the dynamics of the input rate $In(t)$ for the system described in the Distribution section.

To explore the differences in administration routes, we will see how they impact the input rate of a model with 1 compartment and linear elimination, parametrized with the clearance.

The ODE system for this model is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA_C}{dt} &= In(t) - \frac{Cl}{V} A_C \\ C_C &= \frac{A_C}{V} \end{aligned}$$

3.1.5.1.1.1 Intravenous bolus

The intravenous bolus is an injection which quickly raises the concentration of the substance in the blood to an effective level. When bolus is selected, if D is the dose administered at time t_D , we set the amount in the central compartment to $A_C(t_D) = D$. This is equivalent to modeling the input rate as a Dirac delta $In(t) = \delta_{t_D} D$.

The response in the central compartment to a bolus in case of a model with 1 compartment with linear elimination is a decreasing exponential:

3.1.5.1.2 Infusion

This section focuses on intravenous infusion. For subcutaneous infusions, check the dedicated subsection in the oral/extravascular section.

To have the input modeled as an infusion instead of a bolus, you need to have a column tagged as 'infusion rate' or 'infusion duration' in your dataset in Monolix (the duration will be deduced from the amount and rate columns if rate is specified, and vice versa). In Simulx, you need to create a treatment element that is an infusion.

The intravenous infusion of duration T_{inf} sets the input rate to a constant value during the infusion, and then to zero: $In(t) = \frac{D}{T_{inf}} \mathbf{1}_{[t_D, t_D+T_{inf}]}$.

The response in the central compartment in case of a model with 1 compartment with linear elimination is increasing as soon as the infusion starts, and decreasing as soon as it stops.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination
bolus	1 compartment	linear
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
oral/extravascular	3 compartments	
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion		

Note that bolus and infusion models are encoded exactly the same way with the `pkmodel` macro. It is the `pkmodel` macro that will check if a column tagged as `INFUSION RATE` or `INFUSION DURATION` appears in the dataset, and if this is the case, use the analytical solution of the infusion equations instead of the bolus equations.

3.1.5.1.2.1 Oral/extravascular administration

In the case of an oral or extravascular administration, you have additional options for delay and for the type of absorption.

Administration	Delay	Absorption	Distribution	Elimination
bolus	no delay	zero order	1 compartment	linear
infusion	lag time	first order	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
oral/extravascular	transit compartments		3 compartments	
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion				

Absorption: 0 or 1st order?

The type of absorption will determine if the peak in the response is sharp or smooth.

A zero-order absorption is modeled with the same input rate as for an infusion, i.e. with a square pulse input, with 2 differences:

- the duration of the input T_{k0} is not known, it is thus part of the parameters to optimize, and it will influence the height and the duration of the response,
- a delay can be added between the dosing time and the start of the pulse, and this delay can also be optimized.

$$In^{0-order-lag}(t) = \frac{D}{T_{k0}} \mathbf{1}_{[t_D+T_{lag}, t_D+T_{lag}+T_{k0}]}$$

A first-order absorption will instead correspond to a sharper input pulse with a slow exponential decay which depends on the absorption rate. Because of this, the response peak is smoother. This input rate is the analytical solution of a system with a depot compartment where the dose would be added at time $t_D + T_{lag}$, and which would be transferred to the central compartment with an absorption rate k_a :

	$In^{1st-order-lag}(t) = Dk_a e^{-k_a(t-t_D-T_{lag})} \mathbf{1}_{[t_D+T_{lag}, \infty[}$
---	---

We compare here zero and 1st order absorption in the case of a lag time, but if there is no lag in the response, the no delay option can be selected and the parameter T_{lag} will disappear.

Delay: lag time or transit compartments?

In the case of a 1st order absorption, it is possible to select between two types of delay: a lag time or transit compartments. The type of delay selected will change the rising phase of the pulse input. A lag time corresponds to an instantaneous increase of the input rate at time $t_D + T_{lag}$ whereas transit compartments will lead to a more gradual increase of the input rate right after t_D . The rationale for transit compartments and alternative phenomenological models for delayed absorption are described here. Transit compartments are sometimes more accurate than a lag time but the models take longer to simulate because there is no analytical solution available.

Instead of adding the dose to a depot compartment which would be also the absorption compartment at $t_D + T_{lag}$, the dose is added at t_D but a number of transit compartments with transit rate kt_r between the depot and the absorption compartment.

The input rate is the solution of the following system:

$$A_n = D \frac{(k_{tr}t)^n e^{-k_{tr}t}}{n!}$$

$$\frac{dA_a}{dt} = k_{tr}A_n - k_a A_a$$

$$In = k_a A_a$$

This absorption model gives more flexibility to fit the absorption phase with the 3 following parameters: transit rate k_{tr} , the absorption rate k_a and the mean transit time $M_{tt} = \frac{n+1}{k_{tr}}$.

Subcutaneous infusion

To have the input modeled as a subcutaneous infusion, you need to

- select a model with an oral/extravascular administration
- have a column tagged as 'infusion rate' or 'infusion duration' in your dataset in Monolix (the duration will be deduced from the amount and rate columns if rate is specified, and vice versa), or create a treatment element that is an infusion in Simulx.

Only 1st-order absorption is available in this case, and the input rate in case of Tlag (or no delay, i.e. Tlag = 0) is the solution of the following subsystem, combining the equations described above for infusion and for first-order absorption:

$$A_d(0) = 0$$

$$\frac{dA_d}{dt} = \frac{D}{T_{inf}} - k_a A_d$$

$$In(t) = k_a A_d(t - T_{lag})$$

3.1.5.1.2.2 Multiple administration routes

It is possible to use a combination of an oral or extravascular administration, and a bolus or an infusion. For this, a column should be tagged as administration ID in the dataset with 1 for all doses administered intravenously and 2 for orally or extravascularly administered doses. In this case, the input rate is the sum of:

- an infusion rate if columns tagged as INFUSION RATE or INFUSION DURATION appear in the data, or a bolus rate otherwise,
- a rate for oral administration defined above.

In practice, most of the time the two administrations are not simultaneous and the rate takes in turn the value of a rate for an infusion/bolus and for an oral administration, according to the dosing times in the data set.

For each of the combined models, there is a possibility to incorporate the bioavailability by selecting the model with parameter F . This will multiply the oral/extravascular administration input rate by the number F . We give this possibility only in case of multiple administration routes because in a single route setting, F and V would only appear in the ratio V/F which makes them non-identifiable.

3.1.5.1.3 Distribution

The input rate defined by the administration route impacts the amount of drug in the central compartment. You can select to have additional peripheral compartments leading to a system with 1, 2 or 3 compartments in total:

The ODE system for standard PK models involves one species per compartment. The amount of drug in the central compartment is called A_c , and for the 2nd and 3rd compartment it is called A_2 and A_3 . The output of the model is the concentration in the central compartment C_c .

The ODE system for each case is given here, parametrized by the volumes in each compartment V_1, V_2, V_3 and the inter-compartmental clearance Q .

Instead of using the inter-compartmental clearance Q_i between the central compartment and a peripheral compartment i , and a volume V_i for each compartment, it is also possible to use the volume V in the central compartment only and transfer rates for each peripheral compartmental compartment i :

$$i: k_{1i} = \frac{Q_i}{V_1}, k_{i1} = \frac{Q_i}{V_i}.$$

In and El rates are defined by the selected administration route and the elimination rate.

To show the impact of the number of compartments, we will see how they impact the response of a model with a bolus and linear elimination, parametrized with the clearance.

3.1.5.1.3.1 Impact of parameters in the case of 1 compartment

In the case of 1 compartment, the ODE system for a bolus with linear elimination parametrized with the clearance for $t \geq t_D$ is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_C(t_D) &= D \\
 \frac{dA_C}{dt} &= -\frac{Cl}{V} A_C \\
 C_C &= \frac{A_C}{V}
 \end{aligned}$$

The response is given by a decreasing exponential $\log(Cc) = \log\left(\frac{D}{V}\right) - \frac{Cl}{V}(t - t_D)$. If the elimination rate Cl/V is kept constant (to focus on the effect of the distribution parameters), increasing the volume V will translate the whole response down:

3.1.5.1.3.2 Impact of parameters in the case of 2 compartments

In the case of 2 compartments, the ODE system for a bolus with linear elimination leads to a response involving a sum of decreasing exponentials such that $\log(Cc)$ shows 2 different slopes. Increasing V_1 makes the response start lower, increasing V_2 decreases the value at which the slope changes, and increasing Q moves this point earlier, making the slope change also sharper.

3.1.5.1.3.3 Impact of parameters in the case of 3 compartments

The case of 3 compartments is similar to the case of 2 compartments. $\log(Cc)$ shows 3 different slopes. V_1 , V_2 and Q_2 influence the early dynamics by playing on the initial value, and on the time and height of the first point of slope change. Q_3 and V_3 influence the later dynamics by playing on the second point of slope change.

3.1.5.1.4 Elimination

The elimination rate denoted in the previous section as El can be either a linear rate involving the clearance Cl , or a Michaelis Menten rate involving the constants K_m and V_m . Another possible parametrization for the linear rate is using the elimination rate $k=Cl/V$. To visualize the difference in the response, we show below the response of a 1-compartment model to a bolus in the two cases.

3.1.5.2 PK/PD model library

The PK/PD model library is combining our library of standard pharmacokinetic models described on the PK model library page, with a library of standard pharmacodynamic models.

Most PD models included in the PK/PD library can also be used alone (without a PK model) in the PD library, and some models from the PD library are only available alone.

Here we provide general guidelines to guide you towards the standard PD model that is the most suited to your dataset. The guidelines are also summarized in this guidelines pdf: [summary_pkpd_library_v2.pdf](#)

The complete list and full equations for PD models in the PD library is available in this document: [PKPDlibrary.pdf](#) Here we focus on the PD models of the PK/PD library because they are the most widely used.

PD models can be categorized by:

- the type of response linking the concentration of the drug in the central compartment CC
- to the effect E or to the response R . The effect can be either direct, or with an effect compartment, or an action on a turnover rate;
- the type of drug action on the response or on the rate. It can be a stimulation action or an inhibition;
- the presence or absence of sigmoidicity in this drug action.

3.1.5.2.1 Type of response

The response links the drug concentration C_C to the effect E or the response R via a function A modeling the action of the drug. The type of response specifies whether this action impacts directly the effect, or via an effect compartment or turnover rates. The content of the action function will be specified in the next section: type of drug action. To explore the differences in the types of response, we will see how they impact the PD output for a 1 compartment PK linear infusion model, with a stimulation action of the drug and without sigmoidicity.

3.1.5.2.1.1 Direct

In case of a direct response, the effect E directly relates to the concentration in the central compartment C_C via

$$E = A(C_C)$$

Therefore the dynamics of the effect follow the dynamics of C_C without any delay, meaning that as soon as C_C starts decreasing, E decreases as well, and the trajectory in the phase plane C_C vs E is a single line because it follows the same route during the increase and the decrease of the signals. Below is an example simulation of a direct model with a stimulation action of the drug on the PD.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination	
bolus	1 compartment	linear	
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	
oral/extravascular	3 compartments		
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion			
Response	Drug Action	Baseline	Sigmoidicity
direct	Emax	with baseline	without sigmoidicity
effect compartment	Imax	baseline = 0	with sigmoidicity
turnover			

3.1.5.2.1.2 Effect compartment

The site of action of the drug is often not be the same as the central compartment, and therefore a delay often appears between the PK and the PD measurements. To account for this delay it may be enough to add a single theoretical effect compartment with a drug concentration C_e equal to the concentration at the site of action. This theoretical compartment is assumed not to impact the

concentration in the central compartment C_C , therefore we write the transfer arrows between the central compartment and the effect compartment with dashed lines. A single transfer rate k_{e0} is used and the effect now directly relates to C_e :

$$\frac{dC_e}{dt} = k_{e0} C_C - k_{e0} C_e$$

$$E = A(C_e)$$

Below is an example simulation of a model with an effect compartment and with a stimulation action of the drug on the PD. The higher the transfer parameter k_{e0} , the higher the response and shorter the delay in the response.

Administration		Distribution		Elimination	
bolus		1 compartment		linear	
infusion		2 compartments		Michaelis-Menten	
oral/extravascular		3 compartments			
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion					
Response		Drug Action		Baseline	
direct		Emax		with baseline	
effect compartment		Imax		baseline = 0	
turnover				with sigmoidicity	

3.1.5.2.1.3 Turnover

To model a PD response showing delay compared to the PK, it is also possible to consider that the PK concentration has an impact on the production or the degradation rate of a response variable R , as described by Sharma et al (1998). The response is then modeled with the following ODE:

- if action on the production rate: $\frac{dR}{dt} = k_{in} A(C_C) - k_{out} R$
- if action on the degradation rate: $\frac{dR}{dt} = k_{in} - k_{out} A(C_C) R$

In both cases, the model can be parametrized with the initial value of R R_0 and the parameter k_{out} , and k_{in} is derived as $k_{in} = R_0 k_{out}$.

We compare below the response in the case of production stimulation and degradation inhibition. k_{out} plays a similar role as ke_0 in the case of an effect compartment: the higher k_{out} , the shorter the delay.

The difference between a turnover effect on the production or on the degradation is not obvious when checking the response to a single dose amount. A clear difference can be seen if two different dose amounts are given to the same individual. In the case of a turnover on production, the responses will show exactly the same delay, whereas in the case of a turnover on degradation, the delay in the response will be different for different dose amounts.

3.1.5.2.2 Type of drug action

The type of drug action will determine the function A relating the PK concentration to the PD effect. It can be a stimulation or an inhibition, and it is written differently depending on the type of response.

3.1.5.2.2.1 Stimulation

- In the case of a **direct model** or an **effect compartment**, the action of stimulation is parametrized with E_{max} , EC_{50} , γ if sigmoidicity is selected (otherwise $\gamma=1$), and E_0 if baseline is selected (otherwise $E_0=0$). The equation for A in the most general case is:

$$A(C) = E_0 + \frac{E_{max} C^\gamma}{C^\gamma + EC_{50}^\gamma}$$

where C is the concentration in the central compartment C_C if the model is direct, and the concentration in the effect compartment C_E if the model includes an effect compartment.

- In the case of a **turnover model**, the action of stimulation can happen on the production or on the degradation rate. In any case, it is parametrized with E_{max} , EC_{50} , and γ if sigmoidicity is selected, and the function always takes as an input the concentration in the central compartment CC . E_0 does not appear because turnover models already include a parameter R_0 to model the initial value of the response R .

$$A(C_C) = 1 + \frac{E_{max} C_C^\gamma}{C_C^\gamma + EC_{50}^\gamma}$$

Below is the example response of a direct model with a stimulation action (called E_{max} in the drug action section of the library) and without sigmoidicity ($\gamma=1$). We show the influence of increasing E_0 , E_{max} , or the EC_{50} . The influence of the sigmoidicity parameter γ is shown in the next section.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination	
bolus	1 compartment	linear	
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	
oral/extravascular	3 compartments		
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion			
Response	Drug Action	Baseline	Sigmoidicity
direct	E_{max}	with baseline	without sigmoidicity
effect compartment	I_{max}	baseline = 0	with sigmoidicity
turnover			

3.1.5.2.2.2 Inhibition

- In the case of a **direct model** or an **effect compartment**, the action of inhibition is parametrized with E_0 , IC_{50} , I_{max} if partial inhibition is selected (otherwise $I_{max}=1$), γ if sigmoidicity is selected (otherwise $\gamma=1$). The equation for A in the most general case is:

$$A(C) = E_0 \left(1 - \frac{I_{max} C^\gamma}{C^\gamma + EC_{50}^\gamma} \right)$$

where C is the concentration in the central compartment C_C if the model is direct, and the concentration in the effect compartment C_E if the model includes an effect compartment.

- In the case of a **turnover model**, the action of inhibition can happen on the production or on the degradation rate. In any case, it is parametrized with IC_{50} , I_{max} if partial inhibition is selected (otherwise $I_{max}=1$), and γ if sigmoidicity is selected, and the function always takes as an input the concentration in the central compartment CC . E_0 does not appear because turnover models already include a parameter R_0 to model the initial value of the response R.

$$A(C_C) = 1 - \frac{I_{max} C_C^\gamma}{C_C^\gamma + IC_{50}^\gamma}$$

Below is the example response of a direct model with an inhibition type of action (called I_{max} in the drug action section of the library) and without sigmoidicity ($\gamma=1$). We show the influence of increasing I_{max} , or the IC_{50} . The influence of the sigmoidicity parameter γ is shown in the next section.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination	
bolus	1 compartment	linear	
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	
oral/extravascular	3 compartments		
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion			
Response	Drug Action	Inhibition	Sigmoidicity
direct	E_{max}	full inhibition	without sigmoidicity
effect compartment turnover	I_{max}	partial inhibition	with sigmoidicity

3.1.5.2.3 Sigmoidicity

Whether it is a stimulation or an inhibition type of action, the drug action function can always involve an exponent parameter γ . If this parameter is higher than 1, the response curve in the phase plane (C_c vs E) looks more like a sigmoid. Sigmoidicity can impact the dynamics in the PD response, making the response more switch-like due to threshold effects. If sigmoidicity is selected, the parameter γ will be estimated.

Below is the example response of a direct model with a stimulation type of action, and with sigmoidicity. The higher the gamma, the steeper the dose response, and the more square-like the time response.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination	
bolus	1 compartment	linear	
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	
oral/extravascular	3 compartments		
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion			
Response	Drug Action	Baseline	Sigmoidicity
direct	E _{max}	with baseline	without sigmoidicity
effect compartment	I _{max}	baseline = 0	with sigmoidicity
turnover			

3.1.5.3 TMDD model library

3.1.5.3.1 Introduction to TMDD concepts

The concept of TMDD has been proposed as an explanation to the non-linear behavior (violation of the superposition principle and dose-dependent volume of distribution) displayed by some drugs such as bosentan. The concept was first formulated by Gerhard Levy in

Levy, G. (1994). *Pharmacologic target-mediated drug disposition. Clinical Pharmacology Therapeutics*, 56(3), 248–252.

Levy describes the TMDD in the following way: "a considerably larger fraction of the dose of these high-affinity compounds is bound to target sites, enough so that this interaction is reflected in the pharmacokinetic characteristics of the drug."

Target-mediated drug disposition happens when the binding of the drug to the target influences the drugs distribution and elimination. This is in particular often the case for **biologics** (see section Examples of molecules), such as monoclonal antibodies for instance (for a review, see for instance Dostalek et al. (2013)), because they are designed to be highly specific and strongly bind to their target. In this case, the drug is eliminated both via usual linear clearance mechanisms, that dominate at high concentrations when the target is saturated, and non-linear target-mediated clearance (via binding and internalization of the drug-target complex), that is mainly visible at low concentrations.

The interplay of these mechanisms results in **complex concentration-time curves**. To describe the observed data, Mager and Jusko ((2001) JPP 28(6)) have introduced a set of equations that includes:

- the linear elimination of the ligand (elimination rate kel)
- the turnover of the receptor (synthesis rate $ksyn$, degradation rate $kdeg$, initial receptor concentration $R0=ksyn/kdeg$)

- the binding of the ligand to the receptor to form the complex (binding rate k_{on} , dissociation rate k_{off} , dissociation constant $KD=k_{off}/k_{on}$)
- the internalization of the complex (rate k_{int})
- (optional) the distribution of the ligand to a peripheral compartment (rates k_{12} and k_{21})

A key characteristic of TMDD systems is that the pharmacokinetic behavior depends on the dose. Let us focus on the free ligand concentration-time course with several doses of different magnitudes. In the figure below, we look at the concentration (on **log-scale**) with respect to time. In addition, we use a **bolus administration** and a **single compartment** for the ligand (the two compartment case will be studied later on).

As can be seen on the green curve, when **the initial concentration of ligand is larger than the initial receptor concentration (here $R_0=100$)**, the ligand concentration-time curve displays a complex shape (see also Peletier et al. (2012)) with:

- **Phase 1:** steep initial decrease, corresponding to the rapid binding of the ligand to the receptor.
- **Phase 2:** linear elimination phase, where the receptor is saturated with ligands (almost no more binding of ligand to receptor happens), and the ligand is eliminated via usual elimination processes (renal filtration, etc).
- **Phase 3:** transition phase, where the ligand binds to the no-longer saturated receptor.
- **Phase 4:** terminal elimination phase, where elimination of the free ligand happens mainly due to internalization (or degradation) of the target/receptor, which shifts the binding equilibrium out of balance leading to new binding of ligand.

Note that we focus on the concentration of the *free* ligand, such that binding of the ligand to the receptor constitutes an “elimination” mechanism in that it reduces the concentration of free ligand.

On the opposite, as can be seen on the red curve, if **the initial ligand concentration is of the same order of magnitude or lower than the receptor concentration (here $R_0=100$)**, the free ligand concentration time-curve displays two phases:

- **Phase 1:** steep initial decrease, corresponding to the rapid binding of the ligand to the receptor
- **Phase 4:** terminal elimination phase, where elimination of the free ligand happens mainly due to internalization (or degradation) of the target/receptor, which shifts the binding equilibrium out of balance leading to new binding of ligand

Note that in this case, the receptor is never saturated with ligand and target-mediated elimination usually dominates over the linear elimination. Thus, the curve goes directly from phase 1 to phase 4.

Below we show the **typical concentration-time curves for the other entities** in linear scale and log scale. The total ligand L_{tot} is the sum of free ligand L and bound ligand P (complex). The total receptor R_{tot} is the sum of free receptor R and bound receptor P (complex).

The original TMDD model and its approximations are useful to capture concentration data that display this kind of shapes, or part of them.

on linear y-scale:

on log y-scale:

3.1.5.3.2 TMDD library overview

The library contains a **large number of TMDD models corresponding to different approximations, different administration routes, different parameterizations, and different outputs**. In total 608 model files are available. The ordering and naming convention permits to easily browse through the list. The file names follow the pattern below:

3.1.5.3.2.1 Administration

Five different types of administrations are possible:

- **bolus**: iv bolus
- **infusion**: infusion with rate or infusion duration given in the data set (column RATE or TINF)
- **oral0**: zero-order absorption, with parameter Tk0 for the duration
- **oral1**: first-order absorption, with parameter ka
- **oral1+bolus**: first-order absorption or bolus depending on the dose. Bolus doses must be tagged with ADM=1 in the data set and first-order doses (oral or subcutaneous for instance) with ADM=2.

Note that repeated administrations are also allowed. If combinations other than oral1+bolus are necessary, the model file can be duplicated and modified to include a second administration type. In the model, the administration types are distinguished using the type or adm keyword. In the data set, an ADM column must be present.

3.1.5.3.2.2 Number of compartments

All models are available either with **1 compartment or with 2 compartments** (central and peripheral). The impact on the model behavior will be detailed in the next section.

3.1.5.3.2.3 Models (approximations)

Beside the original full TMDD system of equations, **several approximations have been derived, corresponding to different limit cases**. The hierarchy of these approximations and their impact on the model behavior will be detailed in the next section.

3.1.5.3.2.4 Parameters

The list of parameters is mentioned in each file name. The naming convention follows Gibiansky et al. (2008), JPP 35(5). We use the parameters (ksyn, R0) instead of (ksyn, kdeg), and (kon, KD) instead of (kon, koff) because they allow an easier initialization of the parameters. For the elimination and peripheral compartment, two parametrizations are possible, either **using clearances or using rates**. In addition, a parameter Tlag is available to introduce a time lag for the administration.

3.1.5.3.2.5 Outputs

The model outputs will be matched to the observed data. If only **the free ligand L**, or **the total ligand Ltot** have been measured, the files ending with 'outputL' and 'outputLtot' can be used respectively. If one or several other entities have been measured, the model files must be adapted to output one or several variables in the `OUTPUT` section.

If several outputs are present, the outputs will be matched by order with the YTYPEs defined in the data set (first model output matched to observations with YTYPE=1, second model output matched to

observations with YTYPE=2, etc). For all models except the Michaelis-Menten TMDD model, **the available outputs are the following:**

- **L:** free ligand
- **R:** free target/receptor
- **P:** free complex
- **Ltot:** total (free + bound) ligand
- **Rtot:** total (free + bound) target/receptor
- **TO:** receptor occupancy ($TO=R/R_{tot}$)
- **RR:** ratio of free receptor to baseline value ($RR=R/R_0$)

For the Michaelis-Menten TMDD model, only the free ligand L is available as output.

3.1.5.3.2.6 Adapting the models for multiple administration types

Except the oral1+bolus, the models from the library are written for only one administration type per data set. However, they can easily be modified to handle several types of administrations.

In the data set, the doses must be associated to an administration identifier in the ADM column. In the example below, the first dose is assigned to ADM=1 and the second to ADM=2. Often the CMT column of NONMEM data sets can simply be tagged as ADM column in Monolix.

ID	TIME	Y	AMT	ADM
1	0	.	500	1
1	7	55.2	.	.
1	14	44.3	.	.
1	28	35.5	.	.
1	32	23.9	.	.
1	60	.	100	2
1	67	61.1	.	.
1	74	47.3	.	.

Using the library model files as a template, the user can then create a new model file adapting the depot statements in the PK: block to its need. In the case of iv and sub-cutaneous administrations, one would write:

```
PK:
depot(adm=1, target=L, p=1/V) ; doses with ADM=1 in the data set, iv bolus
depot(adm=2, target=L, p=1/V, ka) ; doses with ADM=2 in the data set, first-order
absorption with rate ka
```

For each dose, the depot macro will apply a bolus or first-order input rate to the target L, depending on the ADM identifier of the data set.

Do not forget to include the additional parameters into the `input` statement.

3.1.5.3.2.7 Overview of the model hierarchy

The figure below gives an overview of the different models, their parameter and the resulting typical concentration-time curve for the free ligand. The assumptions leading from one approximation to another one are also depicted.

The plots represent typical concentration-time curves in log-scale for the free ligand L. The arrows depict the degrees of flexibility: curved arrows denote that the angle can be changed, while straight arrows denote that the curve can be shifted.

A few comments to better understand the scheme:

- The QE and QSS models are shown together because their system of equations is the same. However the QSS model is derived from the full model using a quasi steady-state assumption. In this case, the name of the new parameter is $K_{SS} = \frac{k_{int} + k_{off}}{k_{on}}$.

- The parameters for the **second compartment** (k_{12} and k_{21}) influence the non-linear concentration decrease in phase 2, but also the slopes of phase 3 and 4 (which is not depicted for clarity). In the models that lack flexibility in phase 4 (IB, Wagner, MM and const Rtot+IB), some flexibility is present due to k_{12} and k_{21} but it is tightly related to the shape of the non-linearity in phase 2.
- In the first and second rows of models, k_{int} influences the slope of phase 4. On the opposite, in the third and fourth rows, k_{int} influences the start time of phase 3, which was previously influenced by k_{syn} . Note that because $k_{int} = k_{deg}$ and $R_0 = \frac{k_{syn}}{k_{deg}}$, k_{syn} and k_{int} are related via $k_{syn} = R_0 k_{int}$.
- The circled numbers represent the **number of parameters** for a two compartment model. In case of a one compartment model, the number of parameters would be reduced by two. With a single compartment, the phase 2 would be linear. In addition, phase 4 would be completely missing for the IB, MM and const. Rtot+IB models. These curves can be seen in the detailed description section.
- In the **IB model**, the k_{int} parameter has no influence on the free ligand concentration L , but it has on the total ligand concentration L_{tot} . If only the free ligand concentration L is measured, the IB and the const. Rtot+IB models are equivalent.

3.1.5.3.2.8 Detailed description of the models

For clarity reasons, each model has its own dedicated page. All the links are below.

3.1.5.3.2.9 Typical parameters for TMDD

Following the PAGE talk by Leonid Gibiansky, the table below summarizes the typical TMDD parameters, their distribution, their usual range of values, their units, as well as possible covariates:

Parameter	Distribution	Typical value	Typical covariates
Dose	-	10-3000 nmol	-
Cl, Q	log-normal	0.24-1.4 L/day	weight, disease state, liver and kidney function, sex, anti-drug antibodies
V, V2	log-normal	3-6 L	weight
ka	log-normal	0.2-1.5 /day	age, formulation
kon	log-normal	1-100 /nM/day	-
koff	log-normal	0.1-100 /day	-
K _D	log-normal	1-100 nM	-
kint (soluble target)	log-normal	0.01-0.2 /day	-
kint (membrane target)	log-normal	5-100 /day	-
ksyn	log-normal	1-2 nM/day	-
kdeg	log-normal	1-150 /day	-
R ₀	log-normal	0.001-10 nM	-

Note that parameters related to the binding (such as Km, KD, kon, koff) depends on the molecule's chemical properties and are less likely to vary from individual to individual, compared to volumes or parameters that depend on enzyme levels such as kel for instance.

An extensive literature review of parameter values for monoclonal antibodies is also presented in Le Dirks (2010).

3.1.5.3.2.10 Examples of molecules

The table below presents a few examples of molecules displaying TMDD. Biologics are typical candidates for TMDD but small molecules can also display TMDD kinetics. The models used to describe the kinetics of these molecules range from simple MM TMDD models with one compartment to the full TMDD model with 2 compartments.

Drug	Type	Disease	Model	Ref
Tocilizumab	anti-IL6 mAB	rheumatoid arthritis	MM – 2cpt	Frey 2010
Omalizumab	anti-IgE mAB	asthma	QE – 1cpt	Hayashi 2006
HSP90 inhibitors	small molecule	cancer	QE – 1 and 2cpt	Yamazaki 2013
ABT-384	small molecule	diabetes	Const.Rtot – 2cpt	An 2014
recombinant VEGF	growth factor	cardiovascular	MM – 2 cpt	Eppler 2002
Thrombopoietin	cytokine	platelet	full – 2 cpt	Jin 2004

3.1.5.3.2.11 Extensions to more complex TMDD models

In this section, we propose links to resources to extend the proposed library of models to more complex TMDD models. The user who wishes to incorporate these extensions can use the library model files as a starting point.

PK/PD modeling

The mechanistic approach used in TMDD models makes it easy to extend the PK model to a PK/PD model and assume that the pharmacological effect is proportional to the concentration of the drug-receptor complex or to the target occupancy. PK/PD models for molecules displaying TMDD kinetics are for instance presented in Bauer et al. (1999), JPB 27(4), or in Mager et al. (2003), JPET 307(3).

Prediction of human PK from animal data

The prediction of the human PK of drugs is a key step for the accurate estimation of doses for first in human clinical trials. Two approaches are often used: allometric scaling and physiologically-based PK models.

Inter-species allometric scaling

To predict human pharmacokinetic parameters values from animal data, inter-species scaling is often used for small molecules. In the most common approach, the PK parameters are related to the body-weight using a power law. This approach is also often used for biologics, although possible species difference in the target must be kept in mind (Glassmann et al. (2016), JPP 43(4)). Successes and limitations are for instance presented in Kagan et al. (2010, Pharm Res 27), and Dong et al. (2011, Clin Pharm 50(2)).

Physiologically-based TMDD models

Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models extend typical PK models to more compartments that represent the different organs or tissues of the body, with interconnections corresponding to

blood flows. The incorporation of the body's anatomy and physiology in a more detailed way makes it possible to predict human PK by adapting the volumes and flows of the animal body to those of the human body. A quite generic PBPK model for molecules displaying TMDD kinetics is presented in Glassman et al. (2016), JPP 43(3), and applied to four monoclonal antibodies. For three of them, the model could well predict the human PK.

Ligand facilitated target removal

To use ligand facilitated target removal (LFTR) model, presented in Peletier et al. (2021), a small change needs to be made to the full TMDD model available in the TMDD library. ODE line describing ligand behavior needs to be changed to $ddt_L = -k_{el} * L - k_{on} * L * R + (k_{off} + k_{int}) * P$.

More complex PK TMDD models

The full TMDD model presented here contains a number of implicit assumptions such as no binding in peripheral tissues, only one target, only one ligand, and no presence of endogenous drug amounts. Models have been proposed that alleviate these hypotheses. They are reviewed in Dua et al. (2015), CPT:PSP 4(6) and we here propose a short list of possible extensions:

- binding in the tissue compartment: Lowe et al. (2010), BCPT 106(3).
- multiple targets: Gibiansky et al. (2010), JPP 37(4).
- receptor recycling: Krippendorff et al. (2009), JPP 36.
- immune response: Perez-Ruixo et al. (2013), AAPS journal 15(1).
- drug-drug interactions: Yan et al. (2012), JPP 39(5), and Koch et al. (2017), JPP 44(1).
- endogenous drug present: Koch et al. (2017), JPP.

3.1.5.3.3 Detailed TMDD models

3.1.5.3.3.1 Full model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the original (full) TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

Equations

The first TMDD model has been proposed in Mager & Jusko (2001), JPP 28(6). The equations read:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{el} L - k_{on} L R + k_{off} P \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= k_{syn} - k_{deg} R - k_{on} L R + k_{off} P \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on} L R - k_{off} P - k_{int} P \end{aligned}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma, R the *concentration* of the target/receptor, and P the *concentration* of the complex. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear

elimination rate for the ligand, k_{on} the binding rate, k_{off} the dissociation rate, k_{syn} the synthesis rate for the target/receptor, k_{deg} its degradation rate, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $In(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

In the library model file, a slightly different parameterization is used using $R_0 = \frac{k_{syn}}{k_{deg}}$ the steady-state initial receptor concentration (which replaces k_{deg} in the list of parameters), and $K_D = \frac{k_{off}}{k_{on}}$ the dissociation constant (which replaces k_{off} in the list of parameters). This permits to better separate the effect of each parameter.

If in addition the ligand can distribute to peripheral tissues, a **second compartment** can be added, leading to:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{el} L - k_{on} L R + k_{off} P - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= k_{syn} - k_{deg} R - k_{on} L R + k_{off} P \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on} L R - k_{off} P - k_{int} P \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

The main assumptions of this model are the following (Gibiensky et al. PAGE 2011 talk):

- the binding of the ligand to the target is simple, not cooperative
- binding occurs only in the central compartment
- target and complex do not diffuse to peripheral compartments
- internalized ligand-receptor complexes are not recycled

Model properties

To better understand the properties of such a model, we propose to **explore the typical concentration-time curves of this model and the influence of the parameter values**. We will focus on the concentration-time curve of the **free ligand after a bolus dose**. The vignettes below explicit the impact of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time curve:

The effects are summarized below:

For every phase of the concentration-time curve, there exists a parameter to modify it. This is in contrast with the various approximations that lack flexibility for one or several phases of the curve.

Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way. Note that kon has been chosen large (very steep phase 1), to better focus on phase 2, where k_{12} and k_{21} have their main effect.

Full TMDD model with 2 compartments

3.1.5.3.3.2 Rapid binding (QE) and quasi steady-state (QSS) models

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the QE and QSS TMDD models, as well as the model behavior.

Rapid binding equations

The steep initial decrease (Phase 1) of the free ligand concentration in the full model usually occurs on a very short time-scale (minutes to hours) compared to the other phases (elimination over days or weeks). If the acquired data starts only after this initial phase, **the parameters associated with the binding (especially k_{on}) may not be identifiable**. This is why the rapid-binding (also called quasi-equilibrium) **approximation has been proposed**.

The first derivation has been detailed in Mager & Krzyzanski (2005), Pharm Res 22(10), while a more mathematically rigorous derivation can be found in Koch et al. (2016). JPP. In brief, **it is assumed that binding and dissociation of the ligand and target is much more rapid than the other processes**, such that the free ligand, free receptor and the complex are at quasi-equilibrium: $\frac{L \times R}{P} = K_D$ with $K_D = \frac{k_{off}}{k_{on}}$ the dissociation constant. To derive a new set of equations, it is convenient to introduce the total ligand concentration $L_{tot} = L + P$ and the total receptor concentration $R_{tot} = R + P$. Below we present the equations using these quantities, which are the most common ones, but other equivalent formulations are also possible (see Koch et al. (2016). JPP).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_{tot}}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{int} L_{tot} - (k_{el} - k_{int})L \\ \frac{dR_{tot}}{dt} &= k_{syn} - k_{deg} R_{tot} - (k_{int} - k_{deg})(L_{tot} - L) \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{tot} - R_{tot} - K_D) + \sqrt{(L_{tot} - R_{tot} - K_D)^2 + 4K_D L_{tot}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

As before, V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, K_D the dissociation rate, k_{syn} the synthesis rate for the target/receptor, k_{deg} its degradation rate, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $In(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to

the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

In the library model file, a slightly different parameterization is used using $R_0 = \frac{k_{syn}}{k_{deg}}$ the steady-state initial receptor concentration (which replaces k_{deg} in the list of parameters). This permits to better separate the effect of each parameter.

The complex concentration can be calculated via $P = L_{tot} - L$ and the free receptor concentration can be calculated via $R = R_{tot} - (L_{tot} - L)$.

As for the full model, the system can be extended with a peripheral compartment, leading to:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_{tot}}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{int} L_{tot} - (k_{el} - k_{int})L - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dR_{tot}}{dt} &= k_{syn} - k_{deg} R_{tot} - (k_{int} - k_{deg})(L_{tot} - L) \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{tot} - R_{tot} - K_D) + \sqrt{(L_{tot} - R_{tot} - K_D)^2 + 4K_D L_{tot}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

Note that the number of parameters has been reduced by one, as k_{on} and k_{off} have been replaced by K_D . The behavior of the rapid-binding approximation will be close to the full model behavior if indeed the binding and dissociation reactions are fast compared to the other reactions.

Quasi steady-state equations

The quasi steady-state approximation has been proposed by Gibiansky et al. (2008, JPP 35(5)) for the same reasons as the rapid-binding approximation: lack of identifiability of the full model for typical data sets.

In the QSS approximation, one assumes that the binding rate is balanced by the sum of the dissociation and internalization rates leading to $k_{on} L R - (k_{int} + k_{off})P = 0$, i.e. $K_{SS} = \frac{k_{int} + k_{off}}{k_{on}} = \frac{L R}{P}$.

The behavior of the QSS approximation is close to that of the full model if the binding, the dissociation and the elimination of the complex are fast compared to the other processes.

Again, it is more convenient to work with the total ligand concentration and the total receptor concentration, and the equations read:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_{tot}}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{int} L_{tot} - (k_{el} - k_{int})L \\ \frac{dR_{tot}}{dt} &= k_{syn} - k_{deg} R_{tot} - (k_{int} - k_{deg})(L_{tot} - L) \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{tot} - R_{tot} - K_{SS}) + \sqrt{(L_{tot} - R_{tot} - K_{SS})^2 + 4K_{SS} L_{tot}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

The complex concentration can be calculated via $P = L_{tot} - L$ and the free receptor concentration can be calculated via $R = R_{tot} - (L_{tot} - L)$.

And with a peripheral compartment, they read:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_{tot}}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{int} L_{tot} - (k_{el} - k_{int})L - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dR_{tot}}{dt} &= k_{syn} - k_{deg} R_{tot} - (k_{int} - k_{deg})(L_{tot} - L) \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{tot} - R_{tot} - K_{SS}) + \sqrt{(L_{tot} - R_{tot} - K_{SS})^2 + 4K_{SS}L_{tot}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Notice that this system of equation is exactly the same as for the rapid binding approximation. The only difference is that the QSS approximation uses $K = K_{SS} = \frac{k_{int} + k_{off}}{k_{on}}$, while the rapid binding approximation uses $K = K_D = \frac{k_{off}}{k_{on}}$. The interpretation of the meaning of the parameter K differs, but the behavior of the QSS and rapid binding models are exactly the same.

Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts (bolus administration).

Here is the summary figure:

The phase 1 is completely missing. Indeed, as the binding is assumed infinitely fast, part of the ligand binds immediately to the receptor. In addition, the slope of phase 3 is now fixed with none of the parameters having an influence on it.

Note also that both V and R_0 impact the initial concentration. However, whereas a change in V leads to the same shift of the initial concentration for all doses (on a linear scale), a change in R_0 shifts the initial concentration of low doses more. If the tested doses do not range over enough orders of magnitude, R_0 may be unidentifiable.

Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way.

QE and QSS TMDD models with 2 compartments

3.1.5.3.3 Constant Rtot TMDD model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the constant Rtot TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

Equations

If the degradation rates of the free receptor and the complex are similar (i.e. the binding of the ligand to the receptor does not modify the receptor internalization rate), it may not be possible to identify both of them. If both rates are equal ($k_{int} = k_{deg}$), the total receptor concentration stays constant over time ($R_{tot}(t) = R_0 = \frac{k_{syn}}{k_{deg}}$) and the ODE system below can be derived, using the full model as starting point. This approximation is for instance analyzed in Peletier & Gabrielsson (2009). EJPS, 38(5). The equations read:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - (k_{el} + k_{on}R_0) L + (k_{off} + k_{on}L) P \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on} R_0 L - (k_{off} + k_{int} + k_{on}L) P \end{aligned}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma and P the *concentration* of the complex. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, k_{on} the binding rate, k_{off} the dissociation rate, R_0 the initial receptor concentration, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $In(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

In the library model file, a slightly different parameterization is used using $K_D = \frac{k_{off}}{k_{on}}$ the dissociation constant (which replaces k_{off} in the list of parameters). This permits to better separate the effect of each parameter.

The free receptor concentration can be calculated via $R = R_0 - P$. Compared to the full model, the number of parameters is reduced by one, as k_{syn} and k_{deg} are replaced by R_0 .

With 2 compartments for the free ligand, one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - (k_{el} + k_{on}R_0) L + (k_{off} + k_{on}L) P - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on} R_0 L - (k_{off} + k_{int} + k_{on}L) P \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts (bolus administration).

The summary figure is the following:

On opposite to the QE/QSS models, the constant R_{tot} model still captures all four phases of the free ligand concentration-time curve. However, note that because $k_{syn} = k_{int} \times R_0$, k_{int} now influences both the start time of phase 3 (as k_{syn} was doing in the full model), and height of phase 4 (and very slightly its slope at low doses). The flexibility on the slope of phase 4 is mostly missing.

Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way. Note that k_{on} has been chosen large (very steep phase 1), to better focus on phase 2, where k_{12} and k_{21} have their main effect.

Constant R_{tot} TMDD model with 2 compartments

3.1.5.3.3.4 Irreversible binding TMDD model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the irreversible binding TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

Equations

If the binding of the ligand to the receptor is so strong that the dissociation of the ligand from the receptor is negligible, one can consider the binding reaction as irreversible, i.e. $k_{off} = 0$. This approximation has been proposed in Gibiansky et al. PAGE 2010 poster, as a simplification of the full model. In this case, the system of ODEs reduces to:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{\text{el}} L - k_{\text{on}} L R \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= k_{\text{syn}} - k_{\text{deg}} R - k_{\text{on}} L R \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{\text{on}} L R - k_{\text{int}} P\end{aligned}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma, R the *concentration* of the target/receptor, and P the *concentration* of the complex. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, k_{on} the binding rate, k_{syn} the synthesis rate for the target/receptor, k_{deg} its degradation rate, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $\text{In}(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

In the library model file, a slightly different parameterization is used using $R_0 = \frac{k_{\text{syn}}}{k_{\text{deg}}}$ the steady-state initial receptor concentration (which replaces k_{deg} in the list of parameters). This permits to better separate the effect of each parameter.

With a **second compartment**, one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{\text{el}} L - k_{\text{on}} L R - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= k_{\text{syn}} - k_{\text{deg}} R - k_{\text{on}} L R \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{\text{on}} L R - k_{\text{int}} P \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A\end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

This approximation has **one parameter less compared to the full model (koff is fixed to zero)**. In addition, if only the free ligand L and/or the free receptor R are observed, the equation for P can be removed, leading to:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{\text{el}} L - k_{\text{on}} L R \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= k_{\text{syn}} - k_{\text{deg}} R - k_{\text{on}} L R\end{aligned}$$

In this case, the system has two parameters less than the full system: k_{off} is fixed to zero and k_{int} doesn't influence the observed species L and R .

Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts.

V (volume):
initial concentration

ksyn (target synthesis rate):
start time of phase 3

kel (elimination rate):
slope of phase 2

kon (binding rate):
slope of phase 1 and 3

R0 (initial target concentration):
depth of initial steep decrease

The summary picture is:

We observe that **the phase 4 is completely missing**. This approximation can make sense when the phase 4 is **below the lower limit of quantification** and no data point can be recorded in this zone. If this is the case, KD (or k_{off}) and k_{int} cannot be estimated. Note that if measurements about L_{tot} , R_{tot} or P would be available, then the k_{int} parameter might be identifiable.

Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way. Note that k_{on} has been chosen large (very steep phase 1), to better focus on phase 2, where k_{12} and k_{21} have their main effect.

Irreversible binding TMDD model with 2 compartments

The introduction of a second compartment permits to recover a phase 4. Its flexibility is limited and linked to the effect of parameters k_{12} and k_{21} on phase 2.

3.1.5.3.3.5 Wagner model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the Wagner TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

Equations

The constant R_{tot} , QSS/QE and irreversible binding approximations may still be overparametrized. A further simplification can be made and is called the Wagner model. It has initially been described in Biopharmaceutics and relevant pharmacokinetics by Wagner. The Wagner model can be derived from the QE/QSS approximation assuming in addition that the total receptor pool is constant (i.e.

$k_{int} = k_{deg}$ and $R_{tot} = R_0 = \frac{k_{syn}}{k_{deg}}$), as shown in Mager et al. (2005). It can also be derived from the

constant R_{tot} model by assuming in addition rapid binding (i.e. $\frac{L R}{P} = K_D = \frac{k_{off}}{k_{on}}$) or from the irreversible binding model by assuming in addition quasi-steady state of the free receptor ($k_{syn} - k_{deg}R - k_{on}L R = 0$, see Gibiansky et al. (2010) PAGE poster).

Adding these simplifications reduces the number of parameters by one more compared to the first level of approximations, leading to 5 parameters for a 1 compartment model (or 7 for 2 compartments).

Two formulations are possible, either using the free ligand concentration L or using the total ligand concentration L_{tot} . To our knowledge, the formulation using L is always presented:

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{\frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{el} L - \frac{R_0 k_{int} L}{K_D + L}}{1 + \frac{R_0 K_D}{(K_D + L)^2}}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, K_D the dissociation constant, R_0 the initial receptor concentration, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $In(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

If the system is derived from the QSS approximation, then K_D is replaced by K_{SS} . If it is derived from the irreversible model, then K_D is replaced by $K_W = \frac{k_{deg}}{k_{on}}$.

This formulation presents a disadvantage: in case of a bolus administration, the initial free ligand concentration cannot be assumed to be $L_0 = \frac{D}{V}$ with D the dose (amount of drug), because the dose will immediately split between the free and bound form L due to the assumed infinitely fast binding. Thus a so-called dose correction is needed. For the first dose, the corrected initial concentration is relatively simple to calculate:

$$L(t=0) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{D}{V} - R_0 - K_D \right) + \sqrt{\left(\frac{D}{V} - R_0 - K_D \right)^2 + 4K_D \frac{D}{V}} \right]$$

however, the situation becomes more complicated for subsequent doses, where $R_{tot}(t)$ must be used instead of $R_{tot}(t=0)=R_0$.

We thus propose to use instead the formulation in L_{tot} (total ligand concentration):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_{tot}}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{int} L_{tot} - (k_{el} - k_{int})L \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{tot} - R_0 - K_D) + \sqrt{(L_{tot} - R_0 - K_D)^2 + 4K_D L_{tot}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

The number of parameters is the same, and the system complexity also. P , R and R_{tot} can easily be calculated using $P = L_{tot} - L$, $R_{tot} = R_0$ and $R = R_0 - (L_{tot} - L)$. Because the dose is applied to L_{tot} , no dose correction is needed: $L_{tot}(t=0) = \frac{D}{V} = P(t=0) + L(t=0)$, irrespective of the splitting of the dose between the free form L and the bound form P .

With a **second compartment**, the system becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_{tot}}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{int} L_{tot} - (k_{el} - k_{int})L - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{tot} - R_0 - K_D) + \sqrt{(L_{tot} - R_0 - K_D)^2 + 4K_D L_{tot}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts (bolus administration).

The summary picture is:

The Wagner model combines the assumptions of the QE (or QSS) model and those of the constant R_{tot} model. **As for QE, the phase 1 is missing:** the free concentration of ligand directly starts at the equilibrium concentration. In addition, the lack of k_{on} passes on the lack of flexibility in the slope of phase 3. **As for the constant R_{tot} model, we also have a lack of flexibility on the slope of phase 4.**

Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way.

Wagner TMDD model with 2 compartments

3.1.5.3.3.6 Irreversible binding and constant R_{tot} model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the constant R_{tot} + irreversible binding TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

Equations

In the same way as the rapid binding + constant R_{tot} assumptions lead to the Wagner model, we can combine the irreversible binding and constant R_{tot} approximations to obtain a **new model**. To our knowledge, this approximation has not yet been presented in the literature. The equations read:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{el}L - k_{on}L(R_0 - P) \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on}R_0L - (k_{int} + k_{on}L)P \end{aligned}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma and P the *concentration* of the complex. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, k_{on} the binding rate, R_0 the initial receptor concentration, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $In(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

With **two compartments**, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{el}L - k_{on}L(R_0 - P) - k_{12}L + k_{21}A/V \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on}R_0L - (k_{int} + k_{on}L)P \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12}LV - k_{21}A \end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

The system has 5 parameters: same number of parameters as in the Wagner model, and one less compared to QE/QSS, irreversible binding and constant R_{tot} .

Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts (bolus administration).

Here is the summary picture:

If one looks only at the free ligand concentration, **this model is similar to the irreversible binding model. However it has one parameter less.** Note that the phase 4 is missing.

Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way. Note that k_{on} has been chosen large (very steep phase 1), to better focus on phase 2, where k_{12} and k_{21} have their main effect.

Const. Rtot + Irr. Bind. TMDD model with 2 compartments

The introduction of a second compartment permits to recover a phase 4. Its flexibility is limited and linked to the effect of parameters k_{12} and k_{21} on phase 2.

3.1.5.3.3.7 Michaelis-Menten model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the Michaelis-Menten (MM) TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

Equations

The MM TMDD model has been proposed in Gibiansky et al. (2008), JPP 35(5). It is a further simplification of the Wagner model, assuming that $\frac{R_0 K_D}{(L+K_D)^2} \ll 1$. Introducing $K_m = K_D$ and $V_m = k_{int} R_0$ (which reduces by one the number of parameters), the equation for the free ligand reads:

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{el} L - \frac{V_m L}{K_D + L}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, V_m the maximal velocity of the non-linear elimination and K_m the Michaelis-Menten constant of the non-linear elimination. $\text{In}(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

With a **second compartment**, the model becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{el} L - \frac{V_m L}{K_D + L} - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

The MM model can also be derived from the “irreversible + constant R_{tot} ” model, assuming a quasi state-steady on P (i.e. $k_{on} L(R_0 - P) - k_{int} P = 0$) and $\frac{R_0 K_I}{(L+K_I)^2} \ll 1$ with $K_I = \frac{k_{int}}{k_{on}}$.

In principle, a **dose correction must also be applied in case of bolus administration**, to split the incoming drug amount into free and bound ligand. However, the dose correction requires the use of one additional parameter, which would cancel out the advantages of the MM model compared to the Wagner or “constant R_{tot} + irreversible binding” models. Similarly, **the concentrations of P, R, R_{tot} and L_{tot} could be calculated from the concentration of L, but this would require to use of R_0 as additional parameter**. The MM model with 4 parameters (6 if 2 compartments) is thus applicable only if the only measured species is the free ligand.

Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts (bolus administration).

V (volume):
initial concentration

Km (MM constant):
slope of 3

kel (elimination rate):
slope of phase 2

Vm (MM reaction velocity):
start time of phase 3

The summary picture is:

The MM model with one compartment does not capture phase 1 and phase 4. In addition, the dose-dependent shift of the initial concentration is missing: the free ligand concentration starts at the concentration obtained by dividing the dose amount by the volume, as if the ligand would not bind to

the receptor. If the amount of administrated ligand is large compared to the amount of free receptor, this assumption is reasonable.

Model with 2 compartments

The MM model is often used with a second compartment. In this case the shape is modified in the following way:

Michaelis-Menten (MM) TMDD model with 2 compartments

The introduction of a second compartment permits to recover a phase 4. Its flexibility is limited and linked to the effect of parameters k_{12} and k_{21} on phase 2.

3.1.5.3.4 Guidelines to choose a TMDD model

The choice of a model is often not trivial. Because the data may not be sufficient to identify all the parameters of the full model, the parameter estimation process using the full model may not only lead to parameter estimates with large uncertainty but also fail to converge. This page gives guidelines to help the modeler to choose an appropriate TMDD model for his data set.

The necessity of using simplified TMDD models is commonly the consequence of a limited data set and should not hide the fact that the reality may be more complex than the model.

In addition to using the TMDD approximation models (which are derived using assumptions on the parameter values), it is also possible to fix the unidentifiable parameter values, for instance using prior knowledge and typical values, while keeping the full TMDD model structure.

These guidelines are also conveniently summarized on this attached cheat sheet:

3.1.5.3.4.1 When to use a TMDD model

Several aspects can guide the choice of using a TMDD model.

First the **type of molecule**: biologics such as monoclonal anti-bodies, cytokines, growth factors, fusion proteins, antibody-small molecule drug conjugates or hormones are likely to display TMDD kinetics, at least in a certain concentration range. *Notice that even if the biologic is eliminated via a TMDD mechanism, the typical TMDD behavior may not be observable due to too high or too low doses.* In this case, a TMDD model will probably be over-parameterized. On the opposite, TMDD models should not be restricted to biologics as small molecules can also display TMDD kinetics (Guohua An (2017) J Clin Pharm 57(2)).

Second, the results of a **non-compartmental analysis (NCA)** can hint at TMDD kinetics if **the apparent volume of distribution or the total clearance vary between the first dose and subsequent doses or for different dose amounts** (Levy (1994), Clin Pharm Ther 56(3)).

Third, the **shapes of the concentration-time curves** is a key aspect. It will help to detect a TMDD behavior but also to choose the appropriate TMDD model among the several approximations possible.

3.1.5.3.4.2 How to choose a first model

Using prior information

The order of magnitude for some parameters might have been measured directly, for instance with in vitro experiments (e.g Biacore experiments, which usually provide k_{on} and k_{off}). This information can be used to choose an appropriate approximation:

- **evidence of fast binding to receptor** (high k_{on} and k_{off}) => QE, Wagner, MM
The influence of the k_{on} parameter on the concentration-time curve is depicted below using MlXplore, for typical parameter values. When k_{on} is large, the initial drop of concentration due to the binding of the drug to the target is so fast that no data has been recorded in this part of the curve, therefore preventing a reliable estimation of k_{on} . In this case, as can be seen on the right, the QE

approximation gives the same concentration-time curve as the full model, except for the initial drop (phase 1).

- evidence of irreversible binding to receptor** (very low dissociation constant K_D) => IB, "const. $R_{tot} + IB$ ", MMThe dissociation constant K_D controls the height of the last phase (phase 4). When the binding affinity is very strong and thus the K_D low, the last phase of the concentration-time curve is often below the LOQ and cannot be measured. In that case it is not possible to estimate K_D and one can assume that the binding is irreversible. As can be seen on the left panel, the full model and the IB approximation model will differ in a part of the curve in which anyway no data had been recorded.

- evidence of similar rates for the elimination of free and bound receptor** (k_{deg} and k_{int}) => constant R_{tot} , Wagner, "const. $R_{tot} + IB$ ", MMIn the plot below (left), we show the total concentration of receptor. When k_{int} is larger than k_{deg} , the total receptor concentration will decrease after the ligand administration. Indeed, part of the receptor is then bound to the ligand and the complex is eliminated faster than the free receptor ($k_{int} > k_{deg}$). It is often the case in practice, as the binding of the ligand promotes the internalization of the receptor. On the opposite, when $k_{int} < k_{deg}$, the total receptor concentration increases. Finally, when the complex internalization rate k_{int} and the receptor degradation rate k_{deg} are very similar, the total receptor concentration is constant. The equation for the total receptor can then be dropped

leading to a system with less parameters to estimate. When truly $k_{int}=k_{deg}$, the constant R_{tot} model perfectly superimpose with the full model (right panel).

Entities measured

Usually, in the case of a soluble target, the total ligand concentration (L_{tot}) is available, and sometimes the free ligand concentration (L) and/or the total target concentration (R_{tot}). For membrane-bound targets, usually the free ligand concentration (L) is available, and sometimes the target occupancy (TO) (see Gibiansky et al. PAGE 2011 Talk).

The following outputs are available for all models except the MM model: free ligand L , total ligand L_{tot} , free receptor R , total receptor R_{tot} , complex P , target occupancy TO and ratio of free receptor to baseline RR . Here are the restrictions in the model choice depending on the measured entities:

- **only free ligand L measured** => all models
- **any other combination of measured entities** => all models except MM

Shape of measured concentrations

As can be seen in the overview figure, the different approximations lead to different typical concentration shapes. As a consequence, the shape of the measured concentrations is a key element to choose an appropriate model. Two situations are particularly common: first, if the binding of the drug to the target is fast, phase 1 will be very short (in time) and measurements may only start after phase 1. In this case, the parameters related to the binding (especially k_{on}) will not be identifiable and one can assume rapid-binding. Second, it may be that phase 4 appears at very low concentrations that are below the limit of quantification (LOQ). This may happen if the dissociation constant K_D is small, i.e if the binding is almost irreversible.

- **phase 1 not observable due to too rapid binding** => QE, Wagner, MM
- **phase 4 not observable because below LOQ** => IB, "const. R_{tot} + IB", MM

Range of doses

The initial receptor concentration R_0 and the volume of the central compartment V have a similar influence on the ligand concentration-time curve, except that the shift induced by a volume change is dose-independent (same shift for all doses), while that induced by a change in R_0 is dose-dependent (larger shift for small doses). **If the tested doses do not range over a sufficient range, R_0 may be difficult to identify.** In this case the MM model may be a good approximation. If the MM model is not possible or insufficient, it is also possible to fix the value of R_0 .

The plots below show the concentration-time profile for different initial receptor concentrations (related to the receptor production and degradation rates via \square).

- **$C_0 \gg R_0$:** When the initial drug concentration (calculated as Dose/V) is small compared to the initial receptor concentration, we recover the low dose case presented above, where only phase 1 and phase 4 can be seen.
- **$C_0 \approx R_0$:** When the initial ligand and receptor concentrations are of the same order of magnitude, the typical TMDD concentration-time curve shape is observed. The initial drop appears clearly and is dose-dependent. **If several doses are tested, R_0 (i.e. k_{deg}) is likely to be identifiable.**
- **$C_0 \ll R_0$:** When the initial drug concentration is much larger than the initial receptor concentration (which is often the case), the initial drop due to binding to the receptor is small on the scale of the ligand concentration and probably hard to quantify in the presence of measurement noise. In this case, **the parameter R_0 (or k_{deg} using the usual**

parameterization) which influences the height of the initial drop is usually not identifiable.

3.1.5.3.4.3 Improving the model

Bottom-up versus top-down approaches

A top-down approach to find an appropriate TMDD model has been proposed in Gibiansky et al. (2008), JPP 35(5). The procedure is the following: (i) fit the data with the full TMDD model, (ii) use the estimated parameters to simulate typical concentration-time curves with the full model and the approximations, (iii) if the simulations using a approximation are equivalent to the simulations with the full model, the approximation should be used. The strong disadvantage of this method is that the fitting of the full model may not converge, or give very uncertain estimates that are not informative and not reliable for simulations.

On the opposite, **in a bottom-up approach, simpler models are tested first and progressively complexified if mis-specifications are detected in the diagnostic plots.** Depending on the prior information, the first tested model can be any typical PK or TMDD model, and the diagnostic plots can help improving the model by removing one or several assumptions, in one or several steps. We recommend to use the bottom-up approach.

Examples of diagnostics

- **Residuals** (population weighted residuals, individual weighted residuals or normalized prediction distribution errors versus time or predictions): residuals plots help to detect if the model performs poorly for some specific times ranges or concentration ranges. Stratifying by dose group also permits to detect dose-dependent trends. An example is given below. **The trend in the residuals indicates a model mis-specification. In this case a more complex model (with more parameters and thus more flexibility) can be tried.**

- **Covariates:** plotting the distribution of parameter values (or of random effects) for the different dose groups (which needs to be considered as a categorical covariate) allows to detect dose-dependent trends that indicate a model mis-specification. In the figure below (left), the individual parameters distribution of V_m is stratified by dose and **shows a significant trend with increasing doses. This indicates that a more complex model is needed.**

- **Non-convergence of SAEM:** if the fixed effect estimates is unstable and/or the omega value representing the standard deviation of the random effects converges to a very high value (see example below), the model is probably over-parameterized. Several options are possible to reduce the model complexity: (i) remove the inter-individual variability on this parameter, (ii) fix the value of the parameter, (iii) choose a model with less parameters.

SAEM convergence

- **High condition number:** the condition number is the ratio of the largest eigenvalue of the correlation matrix over the smallest value. High condition numbers hint at high correlations between parameters and thus model over-parameterizations. As a rule of thumb, condition numbers below 10 are ok, between 10 and 100 the model can be questionable, and above 100 the model is likely to be over-parameterized. In the example below, the high condition number probably reflects the high correlation between kdeg (kout) and KD. When the Monolix project is exported to Mlxplore using the last estimated parameters, one indeed clearly see that the influence of kdeg and KD on the concentration-time curve is the same. It will therefore not be possible to identify both. In this case, options are: (i) fix the value of one of the two parameters, or (ii) choose a model with less parameters.

```

correlation matrix of the estimates(linearization)
V_pop      1
kep_pop    0.07      1
KD_pop     -0.31    -0.17      1
kin_pop    -0.29     0.02     0.12      1
kout_pop   0.31     0.29    -0.97     -0.09      1
C11_pop    0.05     0.03    -0.15    -0.56     0.15      1
Q_pop      -0.29     0.05     0.01     0.37     0.03     0.02      1
V2_pop     -0.14     0.06    -0.29     0.48     0.28    -0.18     0.34

Eigenvalues (min, max, max/min): 0.019  2.4  1.3e+002
  
```

- **High r.s.e values:** the r.s.e values indicate how uncertain the parameter estimate is. A high uncertainty may be the result of the parameter being unidentifiable because of lacking data. If a fixed parameter has a high r.s.e, one can try to either remove the IIV on this parameter, or fix this parameter value or try a model with less parameters. When an omega has a high r.s.e, one can try to remove the IIV on this parameter.

	parameter	s.e. (lin)	r.s.e. (%)
V_pop	: 2.51	0.093	4
kep_pop	: 2.8	27	958
kon_pop	: 17.1	12	73
koff_pop	: 0.00547	0.27	4.88e+003
kin_pop	: 1.6	0.089	6
kout_pop	: 0.672	0.52	78
C11_pop	: 0.126	0.0088	7
Q_pop	: 0.672	0.1	15
V2_pop	: 1.79	0.12	6

3.1.5.3.4.4 Conclusion

1. **Visualize and explore the data before starting the modeling.**

2. **Have in mind how the parameters influence the curves. It is possible to check the influence for specific parameter sets with Mlxplore.**
3. **Use the graphics to diagnose the model.**
4. **Try several models, the librairie makes it easy.**
5. **Consider several levels of flexibility:**
 - different model approximations, and 1 or 2 compartments
 - parameters estimated or fixed
 - parameters with or without inter-individual variability
6. **Keep in mind the ultimate modeling goal.**

3.1.5.4 Library of PK models with double absorption

Some drugs can display complex absorption kinetics. Common examples are mixed first-order and zero-order absorptions, either sequentially or simultaneously, and fast and slow parallel first-order absorptions. Multiple peaks in concentration-time curves can also be described with mixed absorptions, and can be explained by different physiological processes, such as enterohepatic recycling, delayed gastric emptying, or variability of absorption.

In most cases, a two mixed absorptions are sufficient to capture the main features of the absorption.

We have developed a library of double absorption models implemented in Monolix to take into account all the combinations of absorption types and delays. The absorptions can be specified as simultaneous or sequential, and with a pre-defined or independent order. This library simplifies the selection and testing of different types of absorptions and delays.

3.1.5.4.1 Modeling choices

In this documentation we detail the filtering options in the interface of Monolix, shown on the figure below, and the corresponding parameters and modelling choices.

First absorption		Second absorption				Global	
Type	Delay	Type	Delay	Order of absorption	Force longer delay	Distribution	Elimination
ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL
zero order	no delay	zero order	no delay	simultaneous	false	1 compartment	linear
first order	lag time	first order	lag time	sequential	true	2 compartments	Michaellis-Menten
	transit compartments		transit compartments			3 compartments	

In all cases, a fraction F1 of the dose is absorbed via the first absorption and the remaining 1-F1 fraction of the dose is absorbed via the second absorption. As the parameter F1 must stay within [0,1], a logit distribution is automatically chosen, and the default initial value is 0.5.

The choices for the **first absorption** are:

- **Type of absorption:**
 - zero order, modelled with the parameter Tk01
 - first order, modelled with the parameter ka1
- **Delay:**
 - no delay,
 - a lag time, modelled with the parameter Tlag1
 - transit compartments, modelled with the parameters Mtt1 (mean transit time) and Ktr1 (transfer rate)

The choices for the **second absorption** are:

- **Type of absorption:**
 - zero order, modelled with the parameter Tk02
 - first order, modelled with the parameter ka2
- **Delay:**
 - no delay,
 - a lag time, modelled with the parameter Tlag2
 - transit compartments, modelled with the parameters Mtt2 (mean transit time) and Ktr2 (transfer rate)
- **Order of absorption:** this option is available if the first absorption is a zero-order type, otherwise absorptions are always simultaneous.
 - Simultaneous: both absorptions are modelled with independent parameters. Depending on the values estimated for the parameters, the absorptions will be simultaneous or not.
 - Sequential: the second absorption starts at the end of or after the zero-order process corresponding to the first absorption. So the second absorption is necessarily modelled with a delay, with two possible parametrizations:
 - $Tlag2 = Tk01$ if “no delay” was chosen for both absorptions: the delay of the second absorption is equal to the duration of the first absorption.
 - $Tlag2 = Tlag1 + Tk01$, if “lag time” was chosen for the first absorption and “no delay” was chosen for the second absorption.
 - $Tlag2 = Tk01 + diffTlag2$, if “no delay” was chosen for the first absorption and “lag time” was chosen for the second absorption. In that case $diffTlag2$ is estimated instead of $Tlag2$, but the value of $Tlag2$ will be available in the outputs of Monolix thanks to the table statement. This parametrization ensures that the delay for the second absorption is greater than the duration of the first absorption.
 - $Tlag2 = Tlag1 + Tk01 + diffTlag2$, if “lag time” was chosen for both absorptions. Similarly as before, $diffTlag2$ is estimated instead of $Tlag2$.
 - $Mtt2 = Tk01 + diffMtt2$, if “no delay” was chosen for the first absorption and “transit compartments” was chosen for the second absorption. Similarly as before, $diffMtt2$ is estimated instead of $Mtt2$.

- $Mtt2 = Tlag1 + Tk01 + diffMtt2$, if “lag time” was chosen for the first absorption and “transit compartments” was chosen for the second absorption. Similarly as before, $diffMtt2$ is estimated instead of $Mtt2$.
- **Force longer delay:** this option is available if both absorptions were selected with a delay (lag time or transit compartments), and if the absorptions are not sequential.
 - False: the parameters used to describe both delays are independent, so for the second absorption $Tlag2$ is estimated if “lag time” was chosen, and $Mtt2$ is estimated if “transit compartments” was chosen.
 - True: similarly as above, the parameter for the delay of the second absorption is forced to be larger than the delay of the first absorption. For example, if “lag time” was chosen for both absorptions, $Tlag2$ is written as $Tlag2 = Tlag1 + diffTlag2$, and $diffTlag2$ is estimated instead of $Tlag2$.

Finally, just like for the PK library, the remaining choices are:

- **Distribution:**
 - 1 compartment: the volume of the central compartment is V
 - 2 compartments: the two compartments are modelled with the parameters $V1$ (volume of central compartment), Q (inter-compartment clearance) and $V2$ (volume of peripheral compartment), or with V (volume of central compartment), $k12$ and $k21$ (transfer rates between the central and peripheral compartments).
 - 3 compartments: in the same way, the three compartments are modelled with $V1$, $Q2$, $V2$, $Q3$ and $V3$, or with V , $k12$, $k21$, $k13$ and $k31$.
- **Elimination:**
 - Linear: modelled with Cl (clearance) or k (elimination rate)
 - Michaelis-Menten: modelled with Vm and Km .

3.1.5.4.1.1 File names

The PK double absorption library contains many models, because of the many combinations of absorption types and delays for both absorptions, constraint on the time of the second absorption, distribution and parametrizations. In total 418 model files are available. The file names follow the pattern below:

In this pattern, *oral0* means zero-order absorption, *oral1* means first-order absorption, *seqAbs* corresponds to the filtering option "Order of absorptions = sequential" (the second absorptions starts at the end of the first absorption), and *seqDelay* corresponds to the filtering option "Force longer delay = true" (the delay for the second absorption is necessarily longer than the delay for the first absorption). If no keyword "seqDelay" or "seqAbs" are present in the file name, this is equivalent to the filtering option "Order of absorptions = sequential" and it means that the parameters for both absorptions are independent.

3.1.5.4.2 Examples

The models are written with PK macros.

For example, the model corresponding to a *zero-order* process with a *lag time* for the first absorption and a *simultaneous* (independent) *first-order* process with *transit compartments* for the second absorption, with a *longer delay* than the delay of the first absorption, a single compartment and parametrized with the clearance, is named *oral0_oral1_seqDelay_1cpt_Tk01ka2F1Tlag1diffMtt2Ktr2VCl.txt* and reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tk01, ka2, F1, Tlag1, diffMtt2, Ktr2, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
odeType=stiff

; Parameter transformations
k = Cl/V
Mtt2 = Tlag1 + diffMtt2

PK:
;PK model definition
compartment(cmt = 1, volume = V, concentration = Cc)
absorption(cmt = 1, Tk0 = Tk01, Tlag = Tlag1, p = F1)
```

```
absorption(cmt = 1, ka = ka2, Mtt = Mtt2, Ktr = Ktr2, p = 1-F1)
elimination(cmt = 1, k)
```

OUTPUT:

```
output = Cc
table = Mtt2
```

3.1.5.4.3 Case study

A case study presenting a step-by-step modeling workflow for the PK of veralipride, using models from the double absorption library is available.

Veralipride plasma concentrations exhibit double peaks after oral absorption, due to site-specific absorption.

3.1.5.5 Library of parent-metabolite models

Drugs can undergo a transformation into metabolites – pharmacologically active and/or producing adverse effects. They can impact the pharmacokinetics of the parent and drive the efficacy. But, at the same time, can rise safety concerns. Joint parent – metabolite models account for the impact of the parent-metabolite interactions on the estimation.

Library of Parent – Metabolite models includes many characteristic mechanisms, such as first pass effect, uni and bidirectional transformation and up to three compartments for parent and metabolite, which makes it an excellent tool for exploration and modeling. Implementation with mlxtran macros uses analytical solutions for faster parameter estimation and makes a great basis for the development of more complex models.

Administration Select administration route, delay, absorption mechanism and first pass effect to correctly model drug input.	Transformation Check non-reversible and reversible metabolic systems to predict the impact of parent-metabolite interactions.
Distribution Explore different number of peripheral compartments independently for parent and metabolite.	Elimination Try linear or non-linear Michaelis-Menten elimination mechanism to get a better fit.

3.1.5.5.1 Parent-metabolite model filters

3.1.5.5.1.1 Administration

Parent-metabolite models can be combined with standard administration routes: bolus, infusion, oral/extravascular and oral with bolus. Intravenous doses are always administered to the central parent compartment. Oral doses can be in addition split between parent and metabolite – the first pass effect.

Intravenous doses (bolus, infusion) are always administered to the central parent compartment, can be with or without a time delay and does not include the first pass effect.

Oral doses can be with the following options:

- with or without the first pass effect
- zero ($Tk0$) or first order absorption process (ka for parent, kam for metabolite in case of the first pass effect)
- without or with a time delay ($Tlag$) or with the transit compartments (Mtt , Ktr)
- oral + bolus: bioavailability F (estimated as a separated parameter)

First pass effect

The first pass effect is a phenomenon in which a drug undergoes any biotransformation at a specific location in the body – for example transformation of parent to metabolite before reaching its site of action or the systemic circulation. The first-pass effect can be clinically relevant when the metabolized fraction is high or when it varies significantly from individual to individual or within the same individual over time, resulting in variable or erratic absorption. It also has an impact on peak drug concentrations, which may result in parent concentration peaks occurring much earlier.

In the Monolix library, models with the first pass effect include splitting a dose – with or without dose apportionment – and absorbing one fraction in the central parent compartment ($Tk0$ or ka) and the other fraction in the central metabolite compartment ($Tk0m$ or kam). The absorption process, zero or first order, is the same for parent and metabolite.

- **Dose apportionment** means that the splitting is independent of the absorption constants (Tk_0 , Tk_{0m} or ka , kam), with a fraction F_D of the dose leading to the parent and a fraction $1 - F_D$ leading to the metabolite prior to reach the plasma.
- In models **without dose apportionment**, dose splitting is implicit and results from different absorption rates ka , kam (or absorption times Tk_0 , Tk_{0m}).

3.1.5.5.1.2 Distribution

Parent		Metabolite	
Distribution	Elimination	Distribution	Elimination
1 compartment	Linear	1 compartment	Linear
2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
3 compartments		3 compartments	

In the library it is possible to select different number of compartments for parent and for metabolite. The central compartments have the same volume V – identifiability issue when only parent drug is administered.

Parametrization

Parent and metabolite have the same parametrization. As for the PK and PKPD libraries, there are two parametrizations available:

- **with exchange rates:** k_{12} , k_{21} for parent and k_{12m} , k_{21m} for metabolite for the second compartments, and k_{13} , k_{31} and k_{13m} , k_{31m} for the third compartments. Peripheral compartments are defined implicitly through the exchange rates, so volumes V_2 , V_3 , V_{2m} and V_{3m} are not estimated. The volume of central compartments is V (for both parent and metabolite)

- **with inter - compartment clearance:** Q_2, V_2, Q_3, V_3 for parent and $Q_{2m}, V_{2m}, Q_{3m}, V_{3m}$ for metabolite. The volume of central compartments is V_1 (for both parent and metabolite), to be compatible with the PK models in case of the sequential model development.

3.1.5.5.1.3 Transformation and elimination

Drug, after administration is eliminated from the system or transformed into metabolite, which subsequently is also eliminated. In addition, metabolite can be back-transformed into a parent – it is a common process for example for amines. Both, unidirectional and reversible, transformations can be selected from the “global” section of filters in the Monolix parent-metabolite library. Elimination, linear or non-linear (Michaelis-Menten), is specific for parent and for metabolite.

- Transformation:
 - K_{pm} – transformation rate from parent to metabolite
 - K_{mp} – transformation rate from metabolite to parent

Global				
Administration	First Pass Effect	Delay	Absorption	Transformation
Bolus	No first pass effect	No delay	Zero order	Uni-directional
Infusion	With dose apportionment	Lag time	First order	Bi-directional
Oral	Without dose apportionment	Transit compartments		
Oral + Bolus				

- Elimination: parent and metabolite can be eliminated with different process (linear or non-linear)
 - Cl, k, V_m, K_m – elimination parameters for parent
 - $Cl_m, k_m, V_{mm}, K_{mm}$ – elimination parameters for metabolite

Global			Parent		Metabolite	
Administration	Delay	Transformation	Distribution	Elimination	Distribution	Elimination
Bolus	No delay	Uni-directional	1 compartment	Linear	1 compartment	Linear
Infusion	Lag time	Bi-directional	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
Oral			3 compartments		3 compartments	
Oral + Bolus						

Filter	Model
V Cl Cl_m K_{pm}	bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VClClmKpm
V Cl V_{mm} K_{mm} K_{pm}	bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VClVmmKmmKpm
V V_m K_m Cl_m K_{pm}	bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VVmKmClmKpm
V V_m K_m V_{mm} K_{mm} K_{pm}	bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VVmKmVmmKmmKpm
V V_m K_m k_m K_{pm}	bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VVmKmkpm
V k V_{mm} K_{mm} K_{pm}	bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VkVmmKmmKpm
V k k_m K_{pm}	bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VkkmKpm

Examples:

3.1.5.5.2 Analytical solutions

Implementation in the Mlxtran

Example: a model with oral absorption (rate ka) of a dose D , one central compartment for parent (cmt = 1) and one for metabolite (cmt = 2), linear elimination (rates: k , km) and uni-directional transformation (rate K_{pm}), is the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dC_p}{dt} &= \frac{ka \cdot D}{V} \cdot e^{-ka \cdot t} - k \cdot C_p - K_{pm} \cdot C_p \\ \frac{dC_m}{dt} &= K_{pm} \cdot C_p - k_m \cdot C_m \\ C_p(0) &= 0, C_m(0) = 0, \end{aligned}$$

where C_p and C_m are the concentrations in the central compartments of parent and metabolite respectively.

Models in the parent-metabolite Monolix library are build using mlxtran macros. For the above model:

```

;PK model definition for parent
compartment(cmt = 1, volume = V, concentration = Cp)
oral(cmt = 1, ka)
elimination(cmt = 1, k)

;PK model definition for metabolite
compartment(cmt = 2, volume = V, concentration = Cm)
elimination(cmt = 2, k = km)
transfer(from = 1, to = 2, kt = Kpm)
    
```

Analytical solutions

Analytical solutions, which are more accurate than numerical solutions and are faster than ODE solvers, are implemented for parent – metabolite models satisfying the following conditions:

- administration (bolus, IV, oral 0 or 1st order) is to the central parent compartment only => *models from the library with first pass effect ("with dose apportionment" and "without dose apportionment") do not use analytical solutions*
- parameters are not time dependent (exception: dose coefficients such as Tlag, which are evaluated only once),
- elimination is linear and only from the central parent and/or metabolite compartments, => *models from the library with elimination = "Michaelis-Menten" do not use the analytical solutions*
- there are no transit compartments, => *models from the library with delay = "transit compartments" do not use the analytical solution*
- transfer between parent and metabolite is only between their central compartments,
- there are maximally two peripheral compartments for parent and maximally two for metabolite.

Comparison of the performance between analytical and numerical solutions

The following example compares the computational time (in seconds) of the parameter estimation task (SAEM) using analytical solutions (AS) and numerical solutions (ODE) for models with different number of compartments.

Dataset: simulated in Simulx N = 100 individuals, who received a single or multi oral doses. 5 or 20 measurements of both, parent and metabolite concentrations registered for each individual.

SAEM: (fixed number of iterations) 500 iterations for the exploratory phase, 200 iterations for the smoothing phase.

Number of cmt: Parent + metabolite	Single dose			Multidose		
	AS	ODE		AS	ODE	
1 + 1 (2dim)	27	100	3.7	27	130	4.8
2 + 1 (3dim)	48	150	3.1	44	180	4
2 + 2 (4dim)	71	210	3.0	66	230	3.5
3 + 2 (5dim)	96	260	2.7	91	290	3.2
3 + 3 (6dim)	140	310	2.2	130	340	2.6

Times are given in seconds, and values in bold give the speed up ratio when using an analytical solution.

3.1.5.6 Tumor growth inhibition (TGI) library

A wide range of ODEs models for tumour growth (TG) and tumour growth inhibition (TGI) is available in the literature and correspond to different hypotheses on the tumor or treatment dynamics. In the absence of detailed biological knowledge, selecting the most appropriate model is a challenge. In MonolixSuite2020, we provide a modular TG/TGI model library that combines sets of frequently used basic models and possible additional features. This library permits to easily test and combine different hypotheses for the tumor growth kinetics and effect of a treatment, allowing to fit a large variety of

tumor size data.

When available, analytical solutions are used.

3.1.5.6.1 Tumor growth models

3.1.5.6.1.1 Initial tumor size

The initial tumour size TS_0 can be either be:

- a parameter to estimate,
- a regressor to read from the dataset.

It has to be noted that the time corresponding to the initial tumour size is not necessarily 0. It is the case for models implemented with an analytical solution, but for models implemented with an ODE system it corresponds to the initial integration time. This time is not fixed for most models from this library, which means that it is by default the first dose or observation time in the data set, and can vary between individuals. If one wishes to fix the initial integration time for all individuals, one can uncomment the line "`t_0=0`" in the model to fix the initial integration time at 0, and modify the line to choose another initial time, which must necessarily be before any dose or observation in the data set. Thus only models implemented with an analytical solution can capture observations at prior times than the time for TS_0 .

3.1.5.6.1.2 Kinetics of tumor growth

After a growing phase, tumors experience a saturation due to limits of nutrient supply. However, this saturation property is often never measured in patients in practice because the host dies in the majority of cases before this saturation phase begins. Also in preclinics, the experiments have to be canceled if a specific tumor size is reached due to ethical reasons. Thus, tumor growth models may be divided into two broad categories: those which are able to capture the saturation as the tumor grows (achieved by the introduction a carrying capacity or a spontaneous decay component) and those which do not.

No saturation

- Linear
- Quadratic
- Exponential
- Power law
- Simeoni / Exponential-linear
- Koch

Saturation

- Gompertz
- Gompertz-exponential
- Logistic
- Generalized logistic
- Simeoni-logistic
- Von Bertalanffy
- Generalized Von Bertalanffy

- **Models without saturation**

- **Linear**

The linear tumor growth assumes a constant zero-order growth rate.

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dTS}{dt} = kgl$ $TS(t_0) = TS_0$	$TS = kgl \times t + TS_0$	

- **Quadratic**

The quadratic tumor growth combines linear and quadratic growth rates. Because time is involved in this model, the initial time is fixed to 0 in corresponding library models.

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{gl} + 2 \times k_{g2} \times t$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = k_{gl} \times t + k_{g2} \times t^2 + T_{S0}$	

- **Exponential**

The exponential growth assumes the growth rate of a tumor is proportional to tumor burden (first-order growth).

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{ge} \times T_S$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = T_{S0} \times e^{k_{ge} \times t}$	

- **Power law**

If $0 < \gamma < 1$, the power law model (also named generalized exponential) provides a description in terms of a geometrical feature of the proliferative tissue: the growth rate is proportional to the number of proliferative cells as a fraction of the full tumor volume. The case $\gamma=1$ corresponds to proliferative cells uniformly distributed within the tumor and leads to exponential growth. The case $\gamma=2/3$ represents a proliferative rim limited to the surface of the tumor, where the tumor radius grows linearly in time.

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{ge} \times T_S^\gamma$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = (k_{ge} \times (1 - \gamma) \times t + T_{S0}^{1-\gamma})^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}}$	

- **Exponential-linear**

Experimental data of tumor growth in untreated xenograft mice suggest that tumor growth dynamics follow two distinctively different phases of growth: an initial exponential growth, followed by a linear growth phase. Biologically, this is due to the fact that the growth of the tumor is almost unlimited at first, but that as the nutrients go scarce, its growth is then necessarily restricted.

The simple exponential-linear model captures this with a transition between an exponential (first-order) growth to a linear (zero-order) growth. The transition time is computed to ensure that the solution is continuously differentiable, but this is possible only if the model is not combined with any treatment effect or additional features. In that case, the transition time corresponds to $TS = k_{gl}/k_{ge}$.

In the library, the exponential-linear model is provided with its analytical solution and can not be combined to any treatment effect or additional features.

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{ge} \times T_S, t \leq \tau$ $\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{gl}, t \geq \tau$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$ $\tau = \frac{1}{k_{ge}} \ln\left(\frac{k_{gl}}{k_{ge} \times T_{S0}}\right)$	$T_S = T_{S0} \times e^{k_{ge} \times t}, t \leq \tau$ $T_S = k_{gl} \times (t - \tau) + T_{S0} * e^{k_{ge} \times \tau}, t \geq \tau$ $\tau = \frac{1}{k_{ge}} \ln\left(\frac{k_{gl}}{k_{ge} \times T_{S0}}\right)$	

- **Simeoni**

The Simeoni model approximates the exponential-linear model with a single differential equation. The power term is fixed to 20 to allow the system to pass from the first-order to the zero-order growth sharply enough, as in the original system. With this value, the growth rate is approximated by $k_{ge} \times T_S$ when T_S is smaller than k_{gl}/k_{ge} , and by k_{gl} when T_S is larger than k_{gl}/k_{ge} . The advantage of the Simeoni model over the exponential-linear model is that it is differentiable even when combined with any type of treatment effect.

When used in combination with the description of non-proliferating subpopulations of cells (transit compartments with cell distribution, or two populations model), with TS the size of the proliferating subpopulation, the growth function is slowed down by the factor $TS/TotalTS$ only when the tumor is in its linear growth phase, but not in the exponential growth phase.

ODE system	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = \frac{k_{ge} * T_S}{(1 + (\frac{k_{ge}}{k_{gl}} * T_S)^\psi)^{\frac{1}{\psi}}}$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	Simeoni et al. (2004).	

- **Koch**

Similarly to the exponential-linear and Simeoni models, the Koch tumor growth model is a nonlinear growth function that follows an initial exponential growth followed by a linear growth phase. Its particularity is a smooth transition between exponential and linear growth phase, rather than a rapid switch after a threshold reached for the time (exponential-linear) or tumor size (Simeoni).

When used in combination with the description of non-proliferating subpopulations of cells (transit compartments with cell distribution, or two populations model), with TS the size of the proliferating subpopulation, the growth function is slowed down by the factor $TS/TotalTS$.

ODE system	Analytical solution	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = \frac{2k_{ge} * k_{gl} * T_S}{k_{gl} + 2k_{ge} * T_S}$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = T_{S0} e^{2k_{ge}(t + \frac{1}{k_{gl}}(T_{S0} - T_S))}$	Koch et al. (2009)	

- **Models with saturation**

- **Logistic**

This model assumes an exponential growth rate which decelerates linearly with respect to the tumor size. This results in sigmoidal dynamics - with an initial exponential growth phase followed by a growth-saturated phase as the tumor reaches its carrying capacity (TS_{max}).

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{ge} * T_S(1 - \frac{T_S}{T_{Smax}})$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = \frac{T_{Smax} * T_{S0}}{T_{S0} + (T_{Smax} - T_{S0}) * e^{-k_{ge} * t}}$	

- **Generalized logistic**

In this model, tumor growth depends on tumor size with a generalized logistic function. It reduces to the logistic model if $\gamma = 1$, or to the Gompertz model when γ is close to 0.

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{ge} * T_S \left(1 - \left(\frac{T_S}{T_{Smax}}\right)^\gamma\right)$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = \frac{T_{Smax} * T_{S0}}{(T_{S0}^\gamma + (T_{Smax}^\gamma - T_{S0}^\gamma) * e^{-k_{ge} * \gamma * t})^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}}$	

- **Simeoni-logistic**

In [Haddish-Berhane et al., 2013], a hybrid model derived from the Simeoni model is proposed, that combines exponential, linear and logistic growth.

ODE system	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = \frac{k_{ge} * T_S * \left(1 - \frac{T_S}{T_{Smax}}\right)}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{k_{ge}}{k_{gl}} * T_S\right)^\psi\right)^{\frac{1}{\psi}}}$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	Haddish-Berhane et al., 2013	

- **Gompertz**

The Gompertz model follows the observation of a deceleration of the growth rate over time, without any phase at which the growth rate remains constant. The volume converges asymptotically to

$$T_{Smax} = T_{S0} \cdot \exp(\alpha/\beta)$$

Several parametrizations can be used, and two are displayed on the table below. The first parametrization is the one implemented in the library, and the one for which the impacts of the parameters are the most separate and easiest to control. However, the carrying capacity T_{Smax} can be difficult to estimate and can lack biological meaning if no clear tumor size saturation is seen. With the second parametrization, alpha and beta have an impact on the carrying capacity and on the growth rate, while T_{S0} also has an impact on the carrying capacity.

ODE system	Analytical solution	

$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = T_S * \beta * \ln\left(\frac{T_Smax}{T_S}\right)$ $T_S(t_0) = T_S0$	$T_S = T_Smax * e^{-\beta * t * \ln\left(\frac{T_S0}{T_Smax}\right)}$	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = \alpha * e^{-\beta * t} * T_S$ <p>or, equivalently,</p> $\frac{dT_S}{dt} = (\alpha - \beta * \ln(T_S))T_S$ $T_S(t_0) = T_S0$	$T_S = T_Smax * e^{-\beta * t * \ln\left(\frac{T_S0}{T_Smax}\right)}$	

• **Exponential-Gompertz**

An exponential-Gompertz model can also be considered, built upon the assumption that the tumor follows at first an exponential growth, and is then akin to a Gompertz model once the nutrients start to go scarce.

ODE system	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = \min(k_{ge} * T_S, T_S * \beta * \ln\left(\frac{T_Smax}{T_S}\right))$ $T_S(t_0) = T_S0$	Wheldon (1988)	

• **Von Bertalanffy**

This model is based on balance equations of metabolic processes. The growth is limited with a loss term.

ODE system	Analytical solution	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_g \cdot T_S^{2/3} - k_d \cdot T_S$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = \left[\frac{k_g}{k_d} + \left(T_{S0}^{1/3} - \frac{k_g}{k_d} \right) \cdot e^{-1/3 \cdot k_d \cdot t} \right]^3$		

- **Generalized Von Bertalanffy**

This is the generalized version of the Von Bertalanffy model. The von Bertalanffy model corresponds to the case $\gamma = 2/3$, where the growth is proportional to the surface of the tumor.

The loss term induces for some parameter values a saturation of the tumor, with . When the loss term is neglected, the generalized von Bertalanffy model reduces to a power law

$$T_{S_{max}} = \left(\frac{k_g e}{k_d} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}}$$

When the Von Bertalanffy model (or generalized Von Bertalanffy model) is used in combination with a tumor inhibition model which makes use of the Norton Simon killing hypothesis, the treatment effect is only applied to the growth term of the model (and not to its decay term).

ODE system	Analytical solution	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_g \cdot T_S^\gamma - k_d \cdot T_S$ $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = \left[\frac{k_g}{k_d} + \left(T_{S0}^{1-\gamma} - \frac{k_g}{k_d} \right) \cdot e^{-(1-\gamma) \cdot k_d \cdot t} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}}$	Von Bertalanffy, 1957	

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3.1.5.6.1.3 Additional features

Additional features can be included to consider more complex tumor growth models:

- Dynamic carrying capacity due to *angiogenesis*

The library includes, as an example, a module taken from Hahnfeldt et al,1999 that models the effect of angiogenesis as a dynamic carrying-capacity. When selecting the dynamic carrying-capacity module, T_{Smax} is defined as an ODE variable instead of a constant parameter, with the following ODE:

ODE	Reference	
$\frac{dT_{S_{max}}}{dt} = kp_v \cdot TS - \kappa \cdot TS_{max} - kd_v \cdot TS \cdot TS^{2/3}$	Hahnfeldt et al,1999	

- *Immune dynamics* causing shrinkage or oscillations of tumor size

The library includes, as an example, a model of tumor-immune interactions with chemotherapy proposed by De Pillis et al. (2007), taking into account the control of the tumor growth by the immune system, and the weakening of the immune system as a side effect of chemotherapy. The model includes an additional ODE defining effector-immune cells:

ODE system	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = growth - k_i \cdot I \cdot T_S$ $\frac{dI}{dt} = kp_i - kd_i \cdot I + g \cdot \frac{T_S}{h + T_S} \cdot I - p \cdot I \cdot T_S$	De Pillis et al. (2007)	

More details on these additional features.

3.1.5.6.2 Treatment effect

3.1.5.6.2.1 Type of treatment

Flexible treatment definition is provided thanks to several possibilities:

- **No treatment**

This option corresponds to simple tumor growth models.

- **PK model**

Dosing information is encoded in the dataset, and the effect of the treatment is modeled via a simple PK model (one compartment, bolus administration, linear elimination) which can be easily adapted to a more complex model or to fix some parameters. The predicted concentration inhibits tumor size.

Note that in case of a high number of doses, it is preferable to approximate the exposure by a piecewise regressor or by a constant treatment, to reduce computation cost. Particularly when the dosing is daily and the disease lasts several years, modeling of the PK is not useful and very costly.

- **Exposure as regressor**

Values which describe the evolution of the treatment's exposure/concentration with respect to time are already stored within the data set and are used within the TGI model under the variable EXPOSURE.

DATA FORMAT RESTRICTIONS: The values describing the treatment's exposure with respect to time must be stored in a separate column of the data set labelled 'REGRESSOR'.

- **Treatment start at $t=0$**

The tumour growth inhibition component is applied with a constant effect after $t=0$.

DATA FORMAT RESTRICTIONS: The data must be formatted as to have the treatment being added at time $t=0$ for all individuals. Measurements before that can make use of negative values for time. Note that in that case, the initial integration time (corresponding to the initial tumour size TS_0) is the first measurement time and can vary between individuals.

- **Treatment start time as regressor**

The time at which the treatment is added is a variable named T in the model, which may vary between individual, and whose value is read from a regressor column in the data set. When time $t < T$, a simple tumour growth model is being implemented. After, a tumour growth inhibition component to the model is added.

DATA FORMAT RESTRICTIONS: The values for T must be stored within the data set in a separate column tagged as 'REGRESSOR'.

- **No treatment (0) vs treatment (1) regressor**

A simple tumour growth model is being implemented if the variable $Trt = 0$. If $Trt = 1$, a tumour growth inhibition component to the model is added. Trt is read from a regressor column in the dataset.

DATA FORMAT RESTRICTIONS: A 0 – if the measurement was taken before or after treatment – or 1 – if it was taken during treatment – must be matched and stored within a separate column under the header 'REGRESSOR' for each of the measurements of the data set.

3.1.5.6.2.2 Killing hypothesis

There are two different most commonly used hypothesis relevant to the method of killing of any given treatment within the literature:

- **Skipper-Schabel-Wilcox log-kill hypothesis**

$$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = growth - K \cdot T_S$$

This hypothesis states that exposure to a given amount of treatment kills a constant fraction of the total tumour cell population by increasing apoptosis. Consequently, the proportion of tumour cells removed every time a dose of treatment is administered remains constant regardless of the size of the tumor at the start of therapy. Tumor cell log-kill is typically induced by a standard cytotoxic or a targeted therapy. With this hypothesis, the Tumor Static Concentration (TSC) corresponds to $K \cdot T_S = growth$.

- **Norton-Simon killing hypothesis:**

$$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = growth \cdot (1 - K)$$

This hypothesis was based on the observation that faster-growing tumors respond better to chemotherapy than do slower-growing tumors, and states that the killing term is proportional to growth rate (tumor growth modulation). [R. Simon and R. Norton: The Norton-Simon hypothesis: designing more effective and less toxic chemotherapeutic regimens, Nature Clinical Practice Oncology 3(8) (2006), 406-407.] In the case of an anti-angiogenic drug for example, the cytostatic effect is assumed to be due to a direct inhibitory action on the unperturbed tumor growth rates. With this hypothesis, and if no decay or apoptosis term is considered, the Tumor Static Concentration (TSC) corresponds to $K=1$.

If the growth is exponential (λ), the log-kill and Norton-Simon hypotheses result in inhibition dynamics with equivalent shapes, but the inhibition from the Norton-Simon model depends on the growth rate while the log-kill inhibition does not: they are equivalent if K from the log-kill model is equal to K/k_{ge} in the Norton-Simon model.

On the figure below, the tumor size follows an exponential-linear growth, a constant treatment effect is applied either in the exponential phase (at $t=20$) or in the linear phase (at $t=60$). The treatment kinetics is linear. The parameters are adapted such that, thus the treatment effect is the same in the exponential phase. However, if the same treatment is applied later in the linear phase, a smaller proportion of tumor is removed with the Norton-Simon hypothesis, following a linear killing while the tumor remains in the linear phase. It enfolds that under the Norton-Simon hypothesis the optimal treatment should deliver the most effective dose level of drug over as short a time as possible (high dose density), since tumors given less time to grow between treatments are more likely to be eradicated.

$$growth = k_{ge} \cdot T_S$$

3.1.5.6.2.3 Dynamics of treatment effect

Five different exposure-dependent treatment kinetics which we found to be most common within the literature can be combined with both of these killing hypotheses. Below are plots showing the curves resulting from the addition of these TGI models to an exponential TG model, with a punctual drug exposure resulting from a single dose which is absorbed at time 0 and then eliminated. On the first figure, a linear range of different dose amounts has been applied in order to exhibit the linear and non-linear relationships between exposure and treatment effect.

When the treatment exposure is not given, the treatment effect is constant.

3.1.5.6.2.4 Delay of treatment effect

Chemotherapeutic effects often appear days or weeks following drug exposure. To account for a more progressive tumour regression, a delay in either the treatment effect (i.e. signal distribution model) or cell death (i.e. cell distribution model) may be added via transit compartments.

- **Signal distribution model**

Lobo and Balthasar (2002) applied to tumor growth the transit compartment model proposed by Sun & Jusko (1998) to characterize delayed drug effects that occur via a cascade or signal transduction. The operative rate function of tumor cells killing, K_3 , is related to K via a series of transit compartments (K_1 - K_3). τ refers to the mean transit time in each transit compartment. Although 4 transit compartments were used in Lobo and Balthasar (2002), the model implemented in our library has only 3 compartments for an easier comparison to the cell distribution model. It can be easily edited by the user to add more compartments if needed.

- **Cell distribution model**

The cell distribution model proposed in Simeoni et al., 2004 assumes that the anticancer treatment makes some cells non-proliferating. These cells pass through different stages (also called transit compartments), characterized by progressive degrees of damage, and, eventually, they die. Hence, the attacked tumor cells have a lifespan.

The number of stages of damage and the value of τ affect the shape of the distribution of the time-to-death of damaged tumor cells. The lifespan, or time-to-death, of the attacked tumor cells, is the mean transit time that it takes for the tumor cells, affected by the action of a drug, to go through the

cascade of damaging events to cell death. For n transit compartments, the average lifespan is computed by $Mtt = n \cdot \tau$. This library includes an implementation of the model with three transit compartments, as in Simeoni et al., 2004.

When the model considers two populations of cancer cells in the tumor (sensitive/resistant), the treatment induces the transfer or both types of cells into the first transit compartment, with different rates.

Below are plots showing the curves resulting from the addition of both of these delays to a model making use of exponential TG component and a log-kill constant TGI component depending on constant treatment starting at time 30.

3.1.5.6.2.5 Emergence of resistance

A common feature of tumours is the emergence of treatment-resistance. This phenomena can be modelled in a variety of ways. Decrease in treatment efficacy can be simply added in a phenomenological approach. More mechanistic models try to represent the cell population in its heterogeneity, splitting it into at least two subpopulations: the proliferating and the quiescent cells.

In this library, we included two common methods used within the literature to achieve this:

- **Claret exponential**

This simple phenomenological model accounts for the loss of drug-induced decay over time due to declining

efficacy of the drug, which can be due to the emergence of resistance. It uses a single resistance parameter, and it can be combined with any treatment effect.

Equation	Reference	
$K = K_0 \cdot e^{-\lambda \cdot t}$	Claret et al. (2009)	<p data-bbox="790 728 1412 795">Figure for an exponential growth function and constant treatment effect starting at time t=0.</p>

- **Resistant population**

There are many models in the literature that apply variations of the same approach based on two tumor cell populations with different sensitivities, for example Hahnfeldt et al., 2003, Desmée et al., 2017, Lobo & Balthasar, 2002, Jusko, (1973). We have integrated in the library simple versions inspired by this principle, combined with different treatment effects: these models assume that a fraction of the tumor is resistant to the treatment, thus being killed with a smaller rate than the sensitive part of the tumor. They use a parameter f as initial fraction of resistant tumour cells, and the number of parameters characterizing the treatment effect doubles to have population-specific effects.

Equation	
<p data-bbox="167 1288 375 1321"><i>Log-kill hypothesis:</i></p> $\frac{dT_{S_s}}{dt} = growth - T_{S_s} \cdot K_{T_{S_s}}$ $\frac{dT_{S_r}}{dt} = growth - T_{S_r} \cdot K_{T_{S_r}}$ <p data-bbox="167 1433 446 1467"><i>Norton-Simon hypothesis:</i></p> $\frac{dT_{S_s}}{dt} = growth \cdot (1 - K_{T_{S_s}})$ $\frac{dT_{S_r}}{dt} = growth \cdot (1 - K_{T_{S_r}})$ <p data-bbox="167 1579 351 1612"><i>Initial conditions:</i></p> $T_{S_s}(t_0) = T_{S0} \cdot (1 - f)$ $T_{S_r}(t_0) = T_{S0} \cdot f$	<p data-bbox="566 1713 1380 1780">Figure for an exponential growth function and constant treatment effect starting at time t=0.</p>

Below is a figure showing the curves resulting from the addition of these two resistance components to a model making use of exponential TG component and a log-kill linear TGI component, with a constant treatment effect starting at time 0.

3.1.5.6.2.6 Effect of treatment on angiogenesis or immune dynamics

If more complexity was added to the TG model by means of modelling immune dynamics or a dynamic carrying capacity, it can be decided that these should also be influenced by the addition of a treatment.

- **Combination therapy with active inhibition of angiogenesis**

Combination therapy is often used to maximise chances of tumour regression and minimise chances of treatment-resistant clones from emerging. As such, it may be wished to model the effect of an angiogenesis inhibitor, on top of the tumour inhibitor. This corresponds to an additional option named "Additional treatment effect" available in the library when both angiogenesis and a treatment effect are selected. In that case the ODE for TS_{max} becomes:

$$\frac{dTS_{max}}{dt} = kp_v \cdot TS - \kappa \cdot TS_{max} - kd_v \cdot TS \cdot TS^{2/3} - e \cdot TS_{max}$$

The treatment on angiogenesis is added as a second constant treatment (on top of the one selected earlier on). By choosing this additional option, it is assumed that no PK data is available for this second treatment and consequently, first-order kinetics are used to model the effect. Furthermore, the effect of the second treatment is assumed to follow a log-cell kill killing hypothesis.

- **Combination therapy with decay of immune cells**

If the treatment added does not only target tumour cells but a more general cell population (such as chemotherapy), it may be relevant to include a killing term on the immune cell dynamics as well. This feature is available in the library if modelling of immune dynamics was selected during selection of tumour growth model. It consists in adding an extra decay constant to take into consideration the effect chemotherapy will have on immune cells. The equations then become:

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = kp_i - kd_i \cdot I + g \cdot \frac{TS}{h+TS} \cdot I - p \cdot I \cdot TS - K_i \cdot I$$

where the killing term $-K_i \cdot I$ actually follows the same pattern as the killing term on TS selected in the library.

3.1.5.6.3 Shortcut models

Lastly, we found that some typical models within the literature. In order to ease access to these models, we created a shortcut tab which automatically leads one to the appropriate selections when applicable, or loads the dedicated model otherwise. In each case, the initial tumor size TS_0 can be set as a parameter or as a regressor.

- **Claret exponential model**

This model from Claret et al., 2009 corresponds to the following choices in the library:

The treatment “PK model” is selected by default, but the Claret model is actually compatible with any type of treatment effect. The version with a constant treatment effect starting at $t=0$ (choice “Treatment start at $t=0$ ”), has an analytical solution implemented in the mode, and is therefore much faster to compute than other models implemented as ODEs

$$TS = TS_0 \cdot \exp\left(k_{ge} \cdot t - \frac{k_{kill}}{\lambda} \cdot (1 - \exp(-\lambda \cdot t))\right)$$

- **Simeoni model**

This model from Simeoni et al., 2004 corresponds to the following choices in the library:

Here again, the treatment “PK model” is selected by default, but the Simeoni model is actually compatible with any type of treatment effect.

The equations are:

$$TS(t_0) = TS_0$$

$$TS_1(t_0) = 0$$

$$TS_2(t_0) = 0$$

$$TS_3(t_0) = 0$$

$$\frac{dTS}{dt} = \frac{k_{ge} \cdot TS}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{k_{ge}}{k_{gl}} \cdot TS\right)^\psi\right)^\psi} - K \cdot TS$$

$$\frac{dTS_1}{dt} = \frac{k_{ge} \cdot TS}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{k_{ge}}{k_{gl}} \cdot TS\right)^\psi\right)^\psi} - \frac{TS_1}{\tau}$$

$$\frac{dTS_2}{dt} = \frac{TS_1 - TS_2}{\tau}$$

$$\frac{dTS_3}{dt} = \frac{TS_2 - TS_3}{\tau}$$

$$TS_{total} = TS + TS_1 + TS_2 + TS_3$$

- **Two-population model**

Also called evolutionary model, this simple model corresponds to an exponential growth, and a treatment effect based on log-cell kill hypothesis with first-order kinetics and no delay. The treatment can be set by the user as constant or exposure-dependent.

Shortcuts To Commonly Used Models					
Claret exponential	Simeoni	Stein	Wang	Bonate	Ribba
Initial Tumor Size			Treatment		
As parameter			PK model		
As regressor			Exposure as regressor		
			Treatment start at t0		
			Treatment start time as regressor		

The equations are:

$$TS_0 = TS_0 \cdot (1 - f)$$

$$TSr_0 = TS_0 \cdot f$$

$$\frac{dTS}{dt} = -k_{kill} \cdot EXPOSURE \cdot TS$$

$$\frac{dTS_r}{dt} = k_{ge} \cdot TS_r$$

$$TS_{total} = TS + TS_r$$

TS represents the sensitive part of the tumor, and TSr the resistant part. TotalTS is the total tumor size. If the treatment is constant and starts at time 0, the model is encoded with its analytical solution:

$$TS = TS_0 \cdot \left(f \cdot \exp(k_{ge} \cdot t) + (1 - f) \cdot \exp(-k_{kill} \cdot t) \right)$$

with kkill=0 before t=0.

- **Stein regression-growth model**

This model from Stein et al., 2011 is a simple phenomenological equation based on the assumption that the change of tumor size during therapy results from two independent component processes: an exponential decrease/regression and an exponential regrowth of the tumor:

$$TS = TS0 \cdot (\exp(-kkill \cdot t) + \exp(kge \cdot t) - 1)$$

with $kkill=0$ before $t=0$.

This model is only available with the treatment option "Treatment start at $t=0$ ".

In responding tumors, regression dominates from start of therapy until nadir, growth dominating after nadir. Theoretical curves depicting the separate components of the model and how these combine together to give the time dependence of the tumor size appear in the figure below.

• Wang model

This model from Wang et al., 2009 combines an exponential-decay (shrinkage) and a linear-growth (progression). In the original model, the linear growth component is considered as an approximation of tumor growth under a specific treatment, with a treatment-dependent slope. In the present library, the model is implemented with the same linear growth rate before and during treatment. It goes as follows:

$$TS = TS0 \cdot \exp(-kkill \cdot t) + kgl \cdot t$$

This model can only be used with the option "Treatment starting at time 0". The following figure shows a typical prediction:

• Bonate model

This model is based on Bonate & Suttle, 2013. It is a modification of the Wang model in which a quadratic growth term has been added to account for curvature of tumor growth following nadir.

The equation is:

$$TS = TS0 \cdot \exp(-kkill \cdot t) + kgl \cdot t + kg2 \cdot t^2$$

• Ribba model

This model has been proposed by Ribba et al., 2012. It is able to capture the growth kinetics of low-grade glioma after termination of chemotherapy, characterized by a frequent decrease in volume despite chemotherapy no longer being administered, by considering delayed action of chemotherapy on quiescent tumor cells. The tumor is represented as proliferative and quiescent tumor tissues that respond differently to treatment. The treatment concentration affects both proliferative and quiescent tissue. The tissue composed of cells in proliferation is directly eliminated because of lethal DNA damages induced by the treatment. Nonproliferative tissue is also subject to DNA damages due to the treatment. When re-entering the cell cycle, the DNA-damaged quiescent cells can either repair their DNA damages and return to a proliferative state or die because of unrepaired damages.

It is represented on this figure adapted from [Ribba et al., 2012]:

The following curves show the prediction of each variable of the model before and after a treatment dose at time 0, on the left, and the impact of the parameters on the prediction for TotalTS on the right. The treatment concentration causes an initial sharp drop in P and thus in TotalTS, as well as the transfer of cells from Q to Qp. While the treatment concentration decreases then rapidly to 0, TotalTS continues decreasing slowly, driven by the elimination of Qp. TotalTS increases again only once enough cells have been transferred from Qp to P. The growth function chosen in this model includes a saturation with a carrying capacity TSmax.

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3.1.5.7 Time-to-event model library

This page presents the **TTE model library** included in Monolix. It includes an introduction on time-to-event data, the different ways to model this kind of data, and typical parametric models.

3.1.5.7.1 What is time-to-event data

In case of time-to-event data the recorded observations are the times at which events occur. We can for instance record the time (duration) from diagnosis of a disease until death, or the time between administration of a drug and the next epileptic seizures. In the first case, the event is one-off, while in the second it can be repeated.

In addition, the event can be:

- **exactly observed:** we know the event has happen exactly at time t_i ($T_i = t_i$)
- **interval censored:** we know the event has happen during a time interval, but not exactly when ($a_i \leq T_i \leq b_i$)
- **right censored:** the observation period ends before the event can be observed ($T_i > t_{end}$)

3.1.5.7.2 Formatting of time-to-event data in the MonolixSuite

In the data set, exactly observed events, interval censored events and right censoring are recorded for each individual. Contrary to other softwares for survival analysis, the MonolixSuite requires to specify the time at which the observation period starts. This allow to define the data set using absolute times, in addition to durations (if the start time is zero, the records represent durations between the start time and the event).

For instance for single events, exactly observed (with or without right censoring), **one must indicate the start time of the observation period (Y=0), and the time of event (Y=1) or the time of the end of the observation period if no event has occurred (Y=0)**. In the following example:

ID	TIME	Y
1	0	0
1	34	1
2	0	0
2	80	0

the observation period last from starting time $t=0$ to the final time $t=80$. For individual 1, the event is observed at $t=34$, and for individual 2, no event is observed during the period. Thus it is indicated that at the final time ($t=80$), no event had occurred. Using absolute times instead of durations, we could equivalently write:

ID	TIME	Y
1	20	0
1	54	1
2	33	0
2	113	0

The durations between start time and event (or end of the observation period) are the same as before, but this time we record the day at which the patients enter the study and the days at which they have events or leave the study. Different patients may enter the study at different times.

Examples for repeated events, and interval censored events are available here.

3.1.5.7.3 Important concepts: hazard and survival

Two functions have a key role in time-to-event analysis: the survival function and the hazard function. **The survival function $S(t)$ is the probability that the event happens after time t .** A common way to estimate it non-parametrically is to calculate the Kaplan-Meier estimate. **The hazard function $h(t)$ is the instantaneous rate of an event, given that it has not already occurred.** Both are linked by the following equation:

$$S(t) = e^{-\int_0^t h(x)dx}$$

3.1.5.7.4 Different types of approaches

Depending on the goal of the time-to-event analysis, different modeling approaches can be used: non-parametric, semi-parametric (Cox models) and parametric.

- **Non-parametric models** do not require assumptions on the shape of the hazard or survival. Using the Kaplan-Meier estimate, statistical tests can be performed to check if the survival differs between sub-populations. The main limitations of this approach are that (i) only categorical covariates can be tested and (ii) the way the survival is affected by the covariate cannot be assessed.
- **Semi-parametric models (Cox models)** assume that the hazard can be written as a baseline hazard (that depends only on time), multiplied by a term that depends only on the covariates (and not time). Under this hypothesis of proportional covariate effect, one can analyze the effect of covariates (categorical and continuous) in a parametric way, leaving the baseline hazard undefined.
- **Parametric models** require to fully specify the hazard function. If a good model can be found, statistical tests are more powerful than for semi-parametric models. In addition, there is no restrictions on how the covariates affects the hazard. Parametric models can also be easily used for predictions.

The table below synthesizes the possibilities for the 3 approaches.

	Non-parametric approach	Semi-parametric approach (Cox models)	Parametric approach
Requires assumptions on baseline hazard	no	no	Yes, must be fully specified
Requires assumptions on covariates effect	no	Yes, effect of covariates must be proportional	Yes, no restrictions (accelerated failure time models possible)
Takes into account censoring	Partly, only right censoring	Partly, only right censoring	Yes, all types of censoring are easily taken into account
Uses all the available data	No, only the ranking of events	No, only the ranking of events	Yes
Statistical test for difference between subpopulations	Yes	Yes	Yes
Quantification of the effect of covariates	No	Yes	Yes
Power of statistical tests	Low to intermediate	Intermediate	Strong (if model is correct)
Can handle categorical covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes
Can handle continuous covariates	Only if transformed into categories	Yes	Yes
Can handle frailty models (to capture inhomogeneities between individuals, that are not recorded in covariates)	No	Feasible	Yes
Extrapolations/predictions possible	No	No	Yes

3.1.5.7.5 Focus on parametric modeling with the MonolixSuite

In the MonolixSuite, the only possible approach is the parametric approach. The model is defined via the hazard function, which in a population approach typically depends on individual parameters: $h(t, \psi_i)$. With the hazard function, the survival function can easily be computed, as well as the conditional distribution $p_{y_i|\psi_i}$ for various censoring situations (which is required for parameter estimation via SAEM, log-likelihood calculation, etc).

The typical syntax to define the output is the following:

DEFINITION:

```
Event = {type=event, maxEventNumber=1, hazard=h}
```

The output `Event` will be matched to the time-to-event data of the data set. The `hazard` function h is usually defined via an expression including the input individual parameters. For one-off events, the maximal number of events per individual is 1. It is important to indicate it in the `maxEventNumber` argument to speed up calculations. To use the model for simulations with Simulx, `rightCensoringTime` must be given as additional argument. Check here for details.

Note that the hazard can be a function of other variables such as drug concentration or tumor burden for instance (joint PK-TTE or PD-TTE models). An example of the syntax is given here.

3.1.5.7.6 Library of parametric models for time-to-event data

To describe the various shapes that the survival Kaplan-Meier estimate can take, several hazard functions have been proposed. Below we display the *survival curves*, for the most typical hazard functions:

A few comments:

- We have reparametrized T'_e as a function of T_e to better separate the effects of the scale parameter (characteristic time) and the shape parameter (shape of the curve).
- All parameters are positive. If we assume inter-individual variability, a log-normal distribution is usually appropriate.

The table below summarizes the number of parameters and typical parameter values:

Model	Number of parameters	Typical parameter values	Comments
Exponential	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.4$ 	
Uniform	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S=0$ 	
Weibull	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.4$ • <u>shape</u> $p = 1 - 4$ 	If $p = 1$, simplifies to exponential
Log-logistic	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.5$ • <u>shape</u> $s = 1 - 4$ 	
Gompertz	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.5$ • <u>shape</u> $k = 0.01 - 1$ 	
Gamma	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.4$ • <u>shape</u> $\alpha = 1 - 10$ 	
Generalized gamma	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.4$ • <u>shape</u> $\alpha = 1 - 10$ • <u>shape</u> $p = 1 - 4$ 	If $p = 1$, simplifies to gamma If $p = \alpha$, simplifies to Weibull

For each model, we can in addition consider a delay `del` as additional parameter. The delay will simply shift the survival curve to the right (later times). For $t < del$, the survival is $S(t < del) = 1$.

3.1.5.7.6.1 Lognormal TTE model

The lognormal TTE model is quite standard but not yet included in the library. The mlxtran model for it is shown below:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={mu, sigma}

EQUATION:
if t<0.001
h = 0
else
a = (log(t)-mu)/sigma
```

```
h = (sigma*t*sqrt(3.14*2))(-1) * exp(-1/2 * a2) / (1 - normcdf(a))
end
```

DEFINITION:

```
Event = {type=event, maxEventNumber=1, hazard=h}
```

OUTPUT:

```
output = {Event}
```

All models are available as Mlxtran model file in the TTE library. Each model can be with/without delay and for single/repeated events. For performance reasons, it is important to choose the file ending with '_singleEvent.txt' if you want to model one-off events (death, drop-out, etc).

3.1.5.8 Count data model library

3.1.5.8.1 What is count data

Count data come from counting something, e.g., the number of trials required for completing a given task. The task can for instance be repeated several times (longitudinal count data) and the individuals performance followed.

Count data can also represent the number of events happening in regularly spaced intervals, e.g the number of seizures every week. If the time intervals are not regular, the data may be considered as repeated time-to-event interval censored, see this example. Alternatively the interval length can be given as regressor or covariate to be used to define the probability distribution in the model, see this example.

3.1.5.8.2 Formatting of count data in the MonolixSuite

Count data can take only non-negative integer values. The counts for each individual are recorded in the OBSERVATION column-type. If the data is longitudinal (over time), the times at which the counts have been recorded are indicated in the TIME column-type. If the data is not longitudinal, the TIME column is still necessary and a time of 0 can be used for instance.

ID	TIME	Y
1	0	8
1	4	9
1	8	11
2	0	6
2	4	6
2	8	7

In the example above, the values in the time column can either indicate the time at which the counts have been counted, or the start or end time of the period over which the number of events are recorded.

In the Monolix GUI, the user must indicate that the data is of type Count/Categorical:

3.1.5.8.3 Important concept: the probability mass function

Count data are described by their probability mass function, which gives the probability that the discrete random variable is exactly equal to some value: $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = k)$ with y_{ij} the observed count number for individual i at time j and $k > 0$.

For instance the probability mass function for a Poisson distribution is:

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = k) = \frac{\lambda^k e^{-\lambda}}{k!}$$

If $\lambda=3$, then the probability of having a count of 0 is 4.9%, a count of 1 is 14.9%, a count of 2 is 22.4%, a count of 3 is 22.4%, etc.

3.1.5.8.4 Encoding of count models with the MonolixSuite

In Monolix, a model for count data is defined via the probability mass function, which in a population approach typically depends on individual parameters: $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = k) = f(t_j, \psi_i)$.

The typical syntax to define the random variable representing the count number is the following:

DEFINITION:

```
CountNumber = {type=count, P(CountNumber=k) = ...}
```

`CountNumber` is the name of the random variable and can be replaced by another name. On the opposite, `k` is a mandatory name for the values. The random variable `CountNumber` is then listed in the outputs, to be matched to the observed data.

The probability mass functions often involve ratios of factorials. While the ratio is often a reasonable value, the numerator and denominator can be huge values that are difficult to handle numerically. **It is therefore better to work with the log of the factorials.** The function for log factorial in Mlxtran language is `factln()` (for integers). To extend the factorials to the continuous domain, the gamma function can be useful: $\Gamma(n) = (n - 1)!$. The log of the gamma function corresponds to the `gammaLn()` function in Mlxtran. It is possible to define directly the log of the probability mass function with:

DEFINITION:

```
CountNumber = {type=count, log(P(CountNumber=k)) = ...}
```

For instance to define a binomial distribution, we can write:

DEFINITION:

```
Y = {type=count, log(P(Y=k)) = gammaLn(n+1) - factln(k) - gammaLn(n-k+1) + k*log(p) + (n-k)*log(1-p)}
```

where `gammaLn()` is used for terms that can be non-integers and `factln()` for terms that are integers.

It is possible to use "if" statements related to `k` in the definition of the probability mass function by using the syntax below. This can be useful to define zero-inflated models for instance. The "if" statements relating to time, regressors, or parameters values can be put in a **EQUATION:** section before the **DEFINITION:** block.

DEFINITION:

```
CountNumber = {type=count,
  if k==0
  Pk = ...
  else
  Pk = ...
  end
  P(CountNumber=k) = Pk}
```

The parameters involved in the definition of the probability mass function (for instance λ for a Poisson distribution) can be identical for all individuals, or vary from individual to individual. This is defined in the section “Individual model” of the graphical interface as usual. These parameters can also evolve over time or be a function of other variables such as drug concentration or tumor burden for instance. See the demo “PKcount_project.mlxtran” for instance in the Monolix demo folder, section 4.2.

3.1.5.8.5 Library of models for count data

To describe the various shapes that a count distribution can take, we have developed a library of models. The library includes the most typical distributions, their zero-inflated counterpart, and several options for the evolution of time of the main parameter:

Distribution:

Poisson
Binomial
Negative binomial
Beta binomial
Generalized Poisson
Geometric
Hypergeometric
Logarithmic
Bernoulli
Uniform

Zero-inflation:

not zero-inflated
zero-inflated

Time evolution:

Constant
Linear
Exponential
Emax
Hill (sigmoidal)

The probability mass functions and a description of the parameters is given below:

Model name	Probability mass function	Support	Parameters
Bernoulli	$P(Y = k) = p^k(1 - p)^k$	{0, 1}	$p =$ probability of success, $\in [0,1]$
Poisson	$P(Y = k) = \frac{\lambda^k e^{-\lambda}}{k!}$	{0, 1, ..., inf}	$\lambda =$ average number of events (i.e event rate), > 0
Binomial	$P(Y = k) = \frac{n!}{k!(n - k)!} p^k(1 - p)^{n-k}$	{0, 1, ..., n}	$n =$ maximum count number (i.e number of trials), > 0 $p =$ probability of success, $\in [0,1]$
Negative Binomial	$P(Y = k) = \frac{(k + r - 1)!}{k!(r - 1)!} p^k(1 - p)^r$ or $P(Y = k) = \frac{\Gamma(k + \frac{1}{o})}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{o})} \frac{\lambda}{k!} \left(\frac{\lambda}{\frac{1}{o} + \lambda}\right)^k \left(\frac{1}{1 + o\lambda}\right)^{\frac{1}{o}}$	{0, 1, ..., inf}	$r =$ number of failures, > 0 $p =$ probability of success, $\in [0,1]$ or $\lambda =$ average number of events (i.e event rate), > 0 $o =$ overdispersion, > 0
Generalized Poisson	$P(Y = k) = \frac{\lambda(1 - \delta)(\lambda(1 - \delta) + k\delta)^{k-1}}{k!} e^{-(\lambda(1 - \delta) + k\delta)}$	{0, 1, ..., inf}	$\lambda =$ average number of events (i.e event rate), > 0 $\delta =$ overdispersion, > 0
Beta Binomial	$P(Y = k) = \frac{\Gamma(n + 1)}{\Gamma(k + 1)\Gamma(n - k + 1)} \frac{\Gamma(k + \alpha)\Gamma(n - k + \beta)}{\Gamma(n + \alpha + \beta)} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)}$	{0, 1, ..., n}	$n =$ maximum count number (i.e number of trials), > 0 $\alpha =$ first shape parameter, > 0 $\beta =$ second shape parameter, > 0 or $n =$ maximum count number (i.e number of trials), > 0 $p = \frac{\alpha - 1}{\alpha + \beta - 2} =$ most probable value for the probability, $\in [0,1]$ $\kappa = \alpha + \beta =$ concentration of the beta distribution, > 0
Geometric	$P(Y = k) = p(1 - p)^{k-1}$	{0, 1, ..., inf}	$p =$ probability of success, $\in [0,1]$
Hypergeometric	$P(Y = k) = \frac{K!}{k!(K - k)!} \frac{(N - K)!}{(n - k)!(N - K - n + k)!} \frac{n!(N - n)!}{N!}$	{max(0, n+K-N), ..., min(n, K)}	$N =$ size of the population > 0 $np = n/N$, number of draws divided by the population size, $\in [0,1]$ $p = K/N$, number of elements considered as success divided by the population size, $\in [0,1]$
Logarithmic	$P(Y = k) = \frac{-1}{\ln(1 - p)} \frac{p^k}{k}$	{1, 2, ..., inf}	$p =$ probability, $\in [0,1]$
Uniform	$P(Y = k) = \frac{1}{N}$	{0, 1, ..., n-1}	$n =$ maximum count number, > 0

3.1.6 Typical models

The following pages show how to write typical models for continuous or non-continuous outcomes.

3.1.6.1 Typical PK models

Various absorption models

- Mixed first-order and zero-order absorption, or parallel first-order
- Saturation of the absorption rate
- Sigmoid absorption, transit compartments and Weibull absorption

3.1.6.2 Models for non-continuous data

- [Time-to-event data models](#)
- [Count data models](#)
- [Categorical data models](#)
- [Joint models for non-continuous outcomes](#)

3.1.6.3 Typical extensions of structural models

- **Time varying parameters**
 - Time-varying clearance

- Auto-induction model
- Enterohepatic circulation model
- **Additional model outputs**
 - Computing additional model outputs such as C_{max} or AUC
 - Calculating the half-life

3.1.6.4 Advanced models

- Lifespan models
- K-PD models
- Friberg model for myelosuppression
- ADC model
- Beta regression models

3.1.6.5 Typical PK models

The following pages describe writing of typical PK models:

3.1.6.5.1 Mixed first-order and zero-order absorption, or parallel first-order

Some drugs can display complex absorption kinetics. Common examples are mixed first-order and zero-order absorptions, where one fraction of the dose is absorbed via one route and the other fraction via another route, either simultaneously or with one of the route showing a delay. Another example is fast and slow first-order absorptions in parallel. Finally, sequential absorption with a zero-order process into a transit compartment followed by a first-order absorption in the central compartment is also possible.

A few examples of those kinds of absorption kinetics are listed below:

- **parallel first-order:** oral sustained-release Diltiazem (Murata et al. 1989) and sublingual doses with a rapid absorption from the bucal cavity followed by a delayed absorption from the gastrointestinal tract (“Pharmacokinetic and Pharmacodynamic Data Analysis: Concepts and Applications” by Gabrielsson and Weiner)
- **first-order followed by zero-order:** oral sumatriptan (Cosson et al. 1999)
- **zero-order followed by first-order:** oral cefadroxil (Guarrigues et al. 1991)

More examples of complex absorptions are given in:

Zhou, H. (2003). *Pharmacokinetic Strategies in Deciphering Atypical Drug Absorption Profiles*. *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 43(3), 211–227.

3.1.6.5.1.1 Mlxtran models

For the examples below, we consider a single compartment and a linear elimination. The model is described using macros. When two absorption routes are considered, a fraction F of the dose is

absorbed via the one process and the remaining $1-F$ fraction of the dose is absorbed via another process. **In the data set, the dose lines must *not* be duplicated.** A single dose line can be split into two processes using the keyword `p` in the absorption macros.

As the parameter F must stay within $[0,1]$, a logit distribution must be chosen in the Monolix GUI.

Sequential absorption

In this model, the drug is first absorbed via a zero-order process into a transit compartment and then transferred from the transit compartment into the central compartment using a first-order process. This model allows to capture a progressively faster increase of the concentration during the absorption phase with a simpler model than when taking into account an estimated number of transit compartments (absorption macro with M_{tt} and K_{tr} parameters). In addition, this model has the advantage of using an analytical solution, so it is faster to run than a model with estimated transit compartments that require the solve an ODE system. For the analytical solution to be used, a dummy elimination (equal to zero) from the transit compartment is necessary.


```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tk0, ka, V, Cl}

PK:
compartment(cmt = 1, amount = Ad)
oral(cmt = 1, Tk0)
elimination(cmt = 1, Cl=0) ; dummy elimination term
compartment(cmt = 2, volume = V, concentration = Cc)
transfer(from = 1, to = 2, kt = ka)
elimination(cmt = 2, Cl)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

This model is not yet available in the Monolix libraries.

Parallel first-order

Parallel first-order absorptions can have various causes, among other: absorption via water and lipid routes for dermal administrations, absorption in the bucal cavity and GI tract for sublingual

administrations, progressive solubilisation along the GI tract and subsequent intestinal absorption for oral administrations or simply two different absorption sites.


```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka1, ka2, Tlag, F, V, Cl}
```

```
PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
absorption(cmt=1, ka=ka1, p=F)
absorption(cmt=1, ka=ka2, Tlag, p=1-F)
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

This model is available in the PK double absorption library, with the name *oral1_oral1_1cpt_ka1ka2F1Tlag2VCl.txt*, with Tlag named Tlag2 and F named F1.

Simultaneous zero-order and first-order

The drug is simultaneously absorbed via a first-order and a zero-order process, which both start at the administration time (no lag time).


```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Tk0, F, V, Cl}
```

```
PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
absorption(cmt=1, Tk0, p=F)
absorption(cmt=1, ka, p=1-F)
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}

This model is available in the PK double absorption library, with the name *oral0_oral1_1cpt_Tk01ka2F1VCl.txt*, with Tk0 named Tk01, ka named ka2, and F named F1.

Sequential zero-order followed by first order

The drug is first absorbed via a zero-order process during a time Tk0. Once this is finished, the remaining fraction is absorbed via a first-order process, which starts with a lag time Tk0.

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Tk0, F, V, Cl}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
absorption(cmt=1, Tk0, p=F)
absorption(cmt=1, Tlag=Tk0, ka, p=1-F)
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}

This model is available in the PK double absorption library, with the name *oral0_oral1_seqAbs_1cpt_Tk01ka2F1VCl.txt*, with Tk0 named Tk01, ka named ka2, and F named F1.

Sequential first-order followed by zero-order

Because a first-order absorption never ends (there is always a little bit of drug remaining in the depot compartment and being absorbed into the central compartment), the two absorption processes will not be truly sequential. Yet **we can introduce a lag time for the zero-order process**, such that the zero-order process starts when the first-order process becomes negligible.


```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Tk0, F, Tlag, V, Cl}
```

```
PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
absorption(cmt=1, Tk0, p=F, Tlag)
absorption(cmt=1, ka, p=1-F)
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

This model is available in the PK double absorption library, with the name *oral1_oral0_1cpt_ka1Tk02F1Tlag2VCl.txt*, with *ka* named *ka1*, *Tk0* named *Tk02*, *Tlag* named *Tlag2*, and *F* named *F1*.

Two administration routes and mixed absorption

Below we present a model for an administration scheme with two different routes: some doses are administrated via iv and some orally. **The two routes are distinguished using an identifier:** in the data set the doses are tagged using the ADM column with either ADM=1 (iv for instance) or ADM=2 (oral). In the model, the adm keyword is used to associate a route to specific doses.

In addition, we introduce the total bioavailability for the oral route *Foral*.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Tk0, F, Foral, Tlag, V, Cl}
```

```
PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
iv(adm=1, cmt=1)
absorption(adm=2, cmt=1, Tk0, p=F*Foral, Tlag)
absorption(adm=2, cmt=1, ka, p=(1-F)*Foral)
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

3.1.6.5.2 Saturation of the absorption rate

In some cases, for instance in case of transporter-mediated uptake, the absorption from the depot compartment into the central compartment can saturate. To model this phenomenon, one can replace the first-order rate of absorption by a Michaelis-Menten term.

Examples of drugs displaying a saturating absorption include Phenylbutazone, Naproxen, Chlorothiazide, beta-lactam antibiotics and are reviewed in:

Wood, J. H., & Thakker, K. M. (1982). Michaelis-menten absorption kinetics in drugs: Examples and implications. *European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 23(2), 183–188.

3.1.6.5.2.1 Mlxtran model

To describe a saturable absorption, the depot compartment must be explicitly described and the model must be written as an ODE system. Below we present a one-compartment model with linear elimination and saturable absorption.

The depot macro permits to add the doses defined in the data set to the amount in the depot compartment. The Michaelis-Menten term is written using the amount of the depot compartment instead of the concentration as the volume needed to calculate the concentration is unidentifiable.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={Vm, Km, V, Cl}

PK:
depot(target=Ad)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ad_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

ddt_Ad = -Vm*Ad/(Ad+Km)
ddt_Ac = Vm*Ad/(Ad+Km) - Cl/V*Ac

Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

3.1.6.5.3 Absorption delays via sigmoid absorption, transit compartments or Weibull absorption

Absorption delays are common after oral administrations. They reflect the time needed for drug dissolution and/or for transit to the absorption site (Savic et al., 2007). A simple option is to model this

delay via a lag time (i.e the absorption starts after a delay). However, this may not properly capture the concentration-time profile and the progressive appearance of the drug to the absorption site. Several approaches have been used to model a progressive delay:

1. **sigmoid absorptions**, which assume a zero-order input into the depot compartment followed by a first-order absorption from the depot to the central compartment.
2. **transit compartment models**, which describes the absorption as a multiple step process with a chain of pre-systemic compartments
3. **Weibull absorptions**, which describe the change in the absorption rate k_a in a phenomenological way via a Weibull function.

3.1.6.5.3.1 Sigmoid absorption

The sigmoid model is also called “sequential zero order + first order absorption” where sequential is meant in terms of order of compartments. The absorption from the depot to the central compartment occurs via a usual first-order process with parameter k_a . To introduce the delay, the dose is put into the depot compartment progressively, via a zero-order process of duration Tk_0 (instead of a bolus). The model scheme is the following:

The sigmoid absorption model presents the advantage of introducing a **single additional delay parameter** and having an **analytical solution**. For the analytical solution to be used, it is necessary to add a dummy elimination with clearance equal zero from the depot macro.

Note that in comparison to Nonmem, it is **not necessary to add a RATE=-1 or RATE=-2 column** in the dataset.

The mlxtran code reads:

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tk0, ka, V, Cl, Q, Vp}

PK:
; depot compartment
compartment(cmt = 1, amount = Ad)
  
```

```

; zero order input in depot (cmt=1)
absorption(cmt = 1, Tk0)
; elimination from depot is required for analytical solution but can be set to zero
elimination(cmt = 1, Cl=0)
; central compartment
compartment(cmt = 2, volume = V, concentration = Cc)
; first order absorption from depot to central
transfer(from = 1, to = 2, kt = ka)
; elimination from central compartment
elimination(cmt = 2, Cl)
; optional peripheral compartments (one or two peripheral compartments)
peripheral(k23=Q/V, k32=Q/Vp)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
  
```

If a bioavailability F needs to be considered, it can be added in the absorption() macro as:

```
absorption(cmt = 1, Tk0, p=F)
```

3.1.6.5.3.2 Transit compartments

Transit compartment can easily be implemented using the oral macro (when describing the model using macros) or the depot macro (when describing the model using ODEs), by adding the parameters M_{tt} and K_{tr} in addition to the usual absorption rate k_a . M_{tt} represents the mean transit time and K_{tr} the transit rate between compartments. These two parameters are related via the number of compartments n :

i In case of multiple doses, the amounts in the depot, transit and absorption compartments are reset at each new doses. Thus the implementation is valid only if the dose is fully absorbed before the next dose administration. The amount in the central (and possibly other compartments) is not reset and can accumulate.

Example with model based on macros

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={ka, Mtt, Ktr, V, k}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
oral(cmt=1, Mtt, Ktr, ka)
elimination(cmt=1,k)

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

Example with model based on ODEs

The entire absorption process is handled by the depot macro, which reads the dose information in the data set and applies an input rate to the target A_c corresponding to an oral administration with transit compartments.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={ka, Mtt, Ktr, V, k}

PK:
depot(target=Ac, ka, Mtt, Ktr)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

ddt_Ac = - k * Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

3.1.6.5.3.3 Weibull absorptions

Despite the lack of physiological basis, the Weibull model is appreciated for its flexibility (Zhou et al, 2003). In practice, it is rarely used. We here demonstrate the implementation of one Weibull function models. The extension to two Weibull functions is straightforward. The time-varying absorption rate is:

$$k_a(t) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{t}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1}$$

The model requires to be written as an ODE system with a depot compartment and at least a central compartment. The transfer of matter from the depot compartment to the central compartment is described using a time-varying rate constant. To allow for multiple doses, the time is calculated with respect to the time of the last dose, using the tDose keyword. Note that only one type of administration (only oral or only iv for instance) is allowed per individual, as the tDose keyword doesn't distinguish between different administration types ADM.

The alpha parameter describes the delay, while the beta parameter influences the steepness of the absorption phase.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={beta, alpha, V, k}

PK:
depot(target=Ad)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ad_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

ddt_Ad = -Ad * (beta/alpha)*(max(0,t-tDose)/alpha)^(beta-1)
ddt_Ac = Ad * (beta/alpha)*(max(0,t-tDose)/alpha)^(beta-1) - k*Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

3.1.6.6 Models for non-continuous data

The following pages describe examples of models for non-continuous outcomes in Simulx:

3.1.6.6.1 Time-to-event data models

Related resources on modeling time-to-event data in Simulx:

- [Time-to-event observation model](#): details on the different models for time-to-event data that can be used in Simulx and their syntax.
- [Time-to-event model library](#): detailed description of the library of time-to-event models integrated within Simulx.

On the current page, we show examples of time-to-event data models from the Simulx demos, discuss the possibility to consider repeated interval-censored events as count data, and explain the format of simulated time-to-event data.

3.1.6.6.1.1 Single event

To begin with, we will consider a one-off event. Depending on the application, the length of time to this event may be called the *survival time* (until death, for instance), *failure time* (until hardware fails), and so on. In general, we simply say “time-to-event”. The random variable representing the time-to-event for subject i is typically written T_i .

Single event exactly observed or right censored

- **7.1.tte/tte_single_event.smlx** (model=lib:weibull_model_singleEvent.txt)

In this Simulx demo, a Weibull TTE model for single events, taken from the TTE library, is used:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Te, p}

EQUATION:
h = p/Te * (t/Te)^(p-1)

DEFINITION:
Event = {type=event, maxEventNumber=1, hazard=h}

OUTPUT:
output = {Event}
```

Here, T_e is the expected time to event and p is the shape parameter. Specification of the maximum number of events is required for the simulations.

The model is simulated with replicates over 500 subjects until time=250, without inter-individual variability.

Time limits (start time and final time) of the output element define the observation period during which the survival curve is computed. The final time 250 thus defines the censoring time. In the plot Individual output plot, this censoring times is shown as a red dot for some replicates (for example replicate 9 on the figure below) for which some individuals had no event until that time.

The variability across replicates is visible as a prediction interval on the Output distribution plot:

Single event interval censored or right censored

- **7.1.tte/tte_interval_censored.smlx**

(model=weibull_model_singleEvent_intCensored_length10.txt)

We may know the event has happened in an interval I_i but not know the exact time t_i . This is *interval censoring*.

We use the same basic model, but we now need to specify that the events are interval censored with an interval of length 10:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Te, p}

EQUATION:
h = p/Te * (t/Te)^(p-1)

DEFINITION:
Event = {type=event, maxEventNumber=1, hazard=h, eventType=intervalCensored,
intervalLength=10}

OUTPUT:
output = {Event}
```

3.1.6.6.1.2 Repeated events

Sometimes, an event can potentially happen again and again, e.g., epileptic seizures, heart attacks. For any given hazard function h , the survival function S for individual i now represents the survival since the previous event at $t_{i,j-1}$, given here in terms of the cumulative hazard from $t_{i,j-1}$ to $t_{i,j}$:

$$S(t_{i,j}|t_{i,j-1}; \psi_i) = \mathbb{P}(T_{i,j} > t_{i,j} | T_{i,j-1} = t_{i,j-1}; \psi_i) = \exp\left(-\int_{t_{i,j-1}}^{t_{i,j}} h(t, \psi_i) dt\right)$$

Repeated events exactly observed or right censored

- **7.1.tte/tte_repeated_event.smlx** (model=lib:loglogistic_model_repeatedEvents_IIV.txt)

In this demo, a loglogistic TTE model for repeated events, taken from the TTE library and then modified to add IIV on the Te parameter, is simulated over 200 subjects with 50 replicates.

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {Te_pop, omega_Te}

DEFINITION:
Te = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Te_pop, sd=omega_Te}

[LONGITUDINAL]
```

```
input = {Te, s}
```

EQUATION:

$$h = s/Te * (t/Te)^{(s-1)} / (1+(t/Te)^s)$$

DEFINITION:

```
Event = {type=event, hazard=h}
```

OUTPUT:

```
output = {Event}
```

For each simulated individual, a sequence of n_i event times is precisely observed before $t_{stop} = 250$. The Individual output plots for the first event and the mean number of events per individual is shown for each replicate:

Prediction intervals over all replicates for these two curves are displayed on the Output distribution plot:

3.1.6.6.1.3 Considering the data as count or TTE data

Interval-censored repeated time-to-event data can also be considered as count data: we count the number of events during an interval.

As in [Time-to-event observation model](#), we note the hazard h and the cumulative hazard H .

Time-to-event data models

The probability density function (pdf) for a single exactly observed event at time t_i is $p(y_i) = h(t_i) \times e^{-H_{t_0}^{t_i}}$. The pdf for a single event interval-censored between t_1 and t_2 , is $p(y_i) = e^{-H_{t_0}^{t_1}} \times (1 - e^{-H_{t_1}^{t_2}})$. The pdf for repeated interval censored events is slightly more complicated.

The probability density function (pdf) to observe k events within a time interval from t_1 to t_2 , given the hazard h , can be calculated as:

$$p(y_i) = \exp\left(-H_{t_1}^{t_2}\right) \frac{\left(H_{t_1}^{t_2}\right)^k}{k!} = \exp\left(-\int_{t_1}^{t_2} h\right) \frac{\left(\int_{t_1}^{t_2} h\right)^k}{k!}$$

with $\int_{t_1}^{t_2} h$ being the cumulative hazard between t_1 and t_2 .

If we have a model with a constant hazard $h = \alpha$, the cumulative hazard is equal to $H_{t_1}^{t_2} = \alpha \times (t_2 - t_1)$ and the probability density function is:

$$p(y_i) = \exp(-\alpha \times (t_2 - t_1)) \frac{(\alpha \times (t_2 - t_1))^k}{k!}$$

If, in addition, the intervals over which the events are counted are all of equal length, then we can define $\mu = \alpha \times (t_2 - t_1)$ and obtain:

$$p(y_i) = P(y = k) = \exp(-\mu) \frac{\mu^k}{k!}$$

We recognize the usual Poisson model for count data, which assume independent events and equal interval durations.

If we want to write a count model for data with non-equal interval durations, we can still use the Poisson model but make sure that the parameter μ takes into account the interval duration. This can be done by passing the *interval duration* as REGRESSOR, or by passing t_1 as REGRESSOR and obtaining the time t_2 , which is the current time, using the mlxtran keyword `t`.

The models for the data considered as TTE and the model for the data considered as count are equivalent. Note that when defining a TTE model, it is the hazard that must be defined. When defining the count model, we define the pdf. Thus, **considering the data as count can also be used to model TTE data but provide a custom likelihood (pdf) instead of providing the hazard function.**

Model parameters should be consistent whether the data is considered as count or as TTE. However **the plots provided by Smulx will be different:** survival curve in case of TTE and probability over time to observed k events in case of count data.

A detailed example of a dataset modeled either with a TTE model or a count model is shown on the Monolix documentation page, these projects can be easily exported to Simulx and simulated to see the difference there.

3.1.6.6.1.4 Formatting of time-to-event data in the MonolixSuite

Exporting simulated events in Simulx will generate a time-to-event dataset. This section explains how such data is formatted in the MonolixSuite.

In the data set, exactly observed events, interval censored events and right censoring are recorded for each individual. **Contrary to other softwares for survival analysis, the MonolixSuite requires to specify the time at which the observation period starts.** This allows to define the data set using absolute times, in addition to durations (if the start time is zero, the records represent durations between the start time and the event).

The column TIME also contains the end of the observation period or the time intervals for interval-censoring. The column OBSERVATION contains an integer that indicates how to interpret the associated time. The different values for each type of event and observation are summarized in the table below:

TIME	OBSERVATION (EVENT)	Exactly observed		Interval-censored	
		Single	Repeated	Single	Repeated
Start time of the observation period	0	✓	✓	✓	✓
Time of event	1	✓	✓		
Start of an interval where one or several event have occurred	0			✓	✓
End of an interval where an event has occurred	1			✓	
End of an interval where N events have occurred	N				✓
End of the observation period, with a possible event later on (right-censoring)	0	✓	✓	✓	✓

The figure below summarizes the different situations with examples:

For instance for single events, exactly observed (with or without right censoring), **one must indicate the start time of the observation period (Y=0), and the time of event (Y=1) or the time of the end of the observation period if no event has occurred (Y=0)**. In the following example:

ID	TIME	Y
1	0	0
1	34	1
2	0	0
2	80	0

the observation period lasts from starting time $t=0$ to the final time $t=80$. For individual 1, the event is observed at $t=34$, and for individual 2, no event is observed during the period. Thus it is noticed that at the final time ($t=80$), no event had occurred. Using absolute times instead of duration, we could equivalently write:

ID	TIME	Y
1	20	0
1	54	1
2	33	0
2	113	0

The duration between start time and event (or end of the observation period) are the same as before, but this time we record the day at which the patients enter the study and the days at which they have events or leave the study. Different patients may enter the study at different times.

Examples for repeated events, and interval censored events are available on the Monolix data set documentation page.

3.1.6.6.2 Count data models

Details on the different types of models for count data that can be used in Simulx and their syntax are given here: [Count observation model](#) and a detailed description of the library of count models integrated within Simulx is given here: [Count data model library](#).

On the current page, we show an example from the Simulx demos and explain the format of simulated count data.

3.1.6.6.2.1 Count data with time-varying distribution

- **7.3.count/count.smlx** (model = 'Verhulst_model.txt')

In this demo, we observe the number of correct answers to a questionnaire of 30 questions. The probability of giving a correct answer is decreasing over time, due to the disease progression. No random effect is considered on the parameters of the model.

[LONGITUDINAL]

input={p0, alpha}

EQUATION:

; maximum value of correct answers = number of questions = number of experiments

n = 30

; probability of success => decreases over time

$p = p_0 / ((p_0 + (1-p_0) \cdot \exp(\alpha \cdot t)))$

DEFINITION:

; binomial distribution of n trials and probability of succes p

nbCorrectAnswers = {type=count, $\log(P(\text{nbCorrectAnswers}=k)) = \text{factln}(n) - \text{factln}(k) - \text{factln}(n-k) + k \cdot \log(p) + (n-k) \cdot \log(1-p)$ }

OUTPUT:

output = nbCorrectAnswers

The output element "NbCorrectAnswers" records the value of nbCorrectAnswers every 4 weeks:

NbCorrectAnswers

REGULAR

Name
NbCorrectAnswers

Output variable
nbCorrectAnswers

Main output ▼
Intermediate outputs ▼

Start time	Interval	Final time
0	4	48

CLOSE

This output element can be used in [Simulation](#) but not in [Exploration](#), because the model variable nbCorrectAnswers is a random variable.

The model is simulated over 1000 individuals. The resulting simulations can be visualized as continuous curves in the Individual output plot (left) and as probabilities for the different values in the Output distribution plot (right):

3.1.6.6.2.2 Formatting of count data in the MonolixSuite

After simulating a count model, it is possible to export the simulated data from Simulx. This section describes the standard format for count data in the MonolixSuite.

Column-types used to define responses

Count data can take only non-negative integer values that come from counting something, e.g., the number of trials required for completing a given task. The task can for instance be repeated several times and the individuals performance followed.

Count data can also represent the number of events happening in regularly spaced intervals, e.g the number of seizures every week. If the time intervals are not regular, the data may be considered as repeated time-to-event interval censored, or the interval length can be given as regressor to be used to define the probability distribution in the model.

Examples

- **Basic example:** in the data set below, 10 trials are necessary the first day (t=0), 6 the second day (t=24), etc.

ID	TIME	Y
1	0	10
1	24	6
1	48	5

1 72 2

One can see the epilepsy attacks data set from the Monolix documentation for a more practical example.

3.1.6.6.3 Categorical data models

Details on the different types of models for categorical data that can be used in Simulx and their syntax are given here: [Categorical observation model](#)

On the current page, we show an example from the Simulx demos and explains the format of simulated categorical data.

3.1.6.6.3.1 Ordered categorical data with covariate effect

- **7.2.categorical/categorical.smlx** (model = 'categorical_model.txt')

In this demo, we model categorical observations, which can take seven different values. The categories are ordered and we use cumulative odds ratio to define the probability of each category in the model. The dose level of the treatment is encoded as a continuous covariate which impacts the slope parameter. Random effects are considered on the cumulative odds ratios.

```
[COVARIATE]
input = Dose

EQUATION:
logtDose = log(Dose/15)

[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {th0_pop, th1_pop, th2_pop, th3_pop, th4_pop, th5_pop, slope_pop,
omega_slope, omega_th0, omega_th1, omega_th2, omega_th3, omega_th4, omega_th5,
logtDose, beta_slope_logtDose}

DEFINITION:
th0 = {distribution=normal, typical=th0_pop, sd=omega_th0}
th1 = {distribution=logNormal, typical=th1_pop, sd=omega_th1}
th2 = {distribution=logNormal, typical=th2_pop, sd=omega_th2}
th3 = {distribution=logNormal, typical=th3_pop, sd=omega_th3}
th4 = {distribution=logNormal, typical=th4_pop, sd=omega_th4}
th5 = {distribution=logNormal, typical=th5_pop, sd=omega_th5}
slope = {distribution=logNormal, typical=slope_pop, covariate=logtDose,
coefficient=beta_slope_logtDose, sd=omega_slope}

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {th0, th1, th2, th3, th4, th5, slope}

EQUATION:
lgp0 = slope*t + th0
```

```

lgp1 = slope*t + th0 + th1
lgp2 = slope*t + th0 + th1 + th2
lgp3 = slope*t + th0 + th1 + th2 + th3
lgp4 = slope*t + th0 + th1 + th2 + th3 + th4
lgp5 = slope*t + th0 + th1 + th2 + th3 + th4 + th5
    
```

DEFINITION:

```

level = {type = categorical, categories = {0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6}}
  logit(P(level<=0)) = lgp0
  logit(P(level<=1)) = lgp1
  logit(P(level<=2)) = lgp2
  logit(P(level<=3)) = lgp3
  logit(P(level<=4)) = lgp4
  logit(P(level<=5)) = lgp5
}
    
```

OUTPUT:

```
output = level
```

The model is simulated with 3 groups of 50 subjects with different dose levels. The simulations are displayed as individual evolution of categories over time in the Individual output plot:

and as the time evolution of probabilities of different categories in the Output distribution plot:

3.1.6.6.3.2 Formatting of categorical data in the MonolixSuite

After simulating a categorical model in Simulx, the simulated dataset can be exported. This section describes the standard format for categorical data used in the MonolixSuite.

Column-types used to define responses

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZG7LhmApb_s

In case of categorical data, the observations at each time point can only take values in a fixed and finite set of nominal categories. In the data set, the **output categories must be coded as consecutive integers**.

Examples

- **Basic example:**

```

ID TIME Y
1 0.5 3
1 1 0
1 1.5 2
1 2 2
1 2.5 3
    
```

One can see the respiratory status data set and the warfarin data set in the Monolix documentation for example for more practical examples on a categorical and a joint continuous and categorical data set respectively.

3.1.6.6.4 Joint models for non-continuous outcomes

Details on the different types of models for non-continuous data in Simulx and their syntax are given on these pages:

- [Time-to-event observation model](#)
- [Count observation model](#)
- [Categorical observation model](#)

Detailed descriptions of the library of non-continuous data models integrated within Simulx are given here:

- [Time-to-event model library](#)
- [Count data model library](#)

On the current page, we show examples of joint models combining continuous and non-continuous outcomes from the Simulx demos.

3.1.6.6.4.1 Joint model for continuous PK and categorical PD data

- **7.2.categorical/PKcategorical.smlx**

In this PK/PD demo, the PD is represented by three severity levels: 1 (Low), 2 (Medium) and 3 (High). The severity levels are modeled via a probability distribution for each category. As the categories are ordered, cumulative odds ratios are used in the model definition. The concentration of the PK model is affecting the probabilities via an effect compartment to mimic an effect delay.

Let $y_{ij}^{(2)}$ be the PD level for patient i at time $t_{ij}^{(2)}$. We can then use a proportional odds model for modeling this categorical data:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{logit} \left(\mathbb{P}(y_{ij}^{(2)} \leq 1 | \psi_i) \right) &= \alpha_i + \beta_i Ce(t_{ij}^{(2)}, \phi_i^{(1)}) \\ \text{logit} \left(\mathbb{P}(y_{ij}^{(2)} \leq 2 | \psi_i) \right) &= \alpha_i + \gamma_i + \beta_i Ce(t_{ij}^{(2)}, \phi_i^{(1)}) \\ \text{logit} \left(\mathbb{P}(y_{ij}^{(2)} \leq 3 | \psi_i) \right) &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

where $C_e(t, \phi_i^{(1)})$ is the predicted concentration of warfarin in the effect compartment at time t for patient i with PK parameters $\phi_i^{(1)}$. This model defines a probability distribution for y_{ij} if $\gamma_i \geq 0$.

If $\beta_i > 0$, the probability of low PCA at time $t_{ij}^{(2)}$ ($y_{ij}^{(2)} = 1$) increases along with the predicted concentration $Ce(t_{ij}^{(2)}, \phi_i^{(1)})$.

The full model implemented in the model includes the joint structural model and a statistical model with random effects on the PK parameters and α , and an effect of the wt covariate (weight) on V and Cl:

[COVARIATE]

```

input = wt

EQUATION:
lw70 = log(wt/70)

[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {Tlag_pop, omega_Tlag, ka_pop, omega_ka, V_pop, beta_V_lw70, lw70, omega_V,
Cl_pop, beta_Cl_lw70, omega_Cl, ke0_pop, omega_ke0, alpha_pop, omega_alpha, beta_pop,
gamma_pop}

DEFINITION:
Tlag = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Tlag_pop, sd=omega_Tlag}
ka = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ka_pop, sd=omega_ka}
V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, covariate=lw70, coefficient=beta_V_lw70,
sd=omega_V}
Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_pop, covariate=lw70,
coefficient=beta_Cl_lw70, sd=omega_Cl}
ke0 = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ke0_pop, sd=omega_ke0}
alpha = {distribution=normal, typical=alpha_pop, sd=omega_alpha}
beta = {distribution=normal, typical=beta_pop, no-variability}
gamma = {distribution=logNormal, typical=gamma_pop, no-variability}

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tlag, ka, V, Cl, ke0, alpha, beta, gamma, a, b}

EQUATION:
{Cc,Ce} = pkmodel(Tlag,ka,V,Cl,ke0)
lp1 = alpha + beta*Ce
lp2 = lp1+ gamma          ; gamma >= 0

DEFINITION:
Level = {type = categorical, categories={1,2,3}, logit(P(Level<=1)) = lp1,
logit(P(Level<=2)) = lp2}
Conc = {distribution=normal, prediction=Cc, errorModel=combined1(a, b)}

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, Conc, Level}

```

Two simulation groups are defined: multiple and single dose.

See [Categorical data models](#) for more details about categorical data models.

3.1.6.6.4.2 Joint model for continuous PK and count PD data

- **7.3.count/PKcount.smlx**

In this demo, we observe how the number of seizures per week decreases when two different dosing regimens of a drug are given. The number of seizures per week is described using a Poisson distribution, assuming that the Poisson parameter is function of the predicted concentration. For any individual i , we have

$$\lambda_i(t) = \lambda_{0,i} \left(1 - \frac{C c_i(t)}{C c_i(t) + IC50_i} \right)$$

where $C c_i(t)$ is the predicted concentration for individual i at time t and

$$\log(P(y_{ij}^{(2)} = k)) = -\lambda_i(t_{ij}) + k \log(\lambda_i(t_{ij})) - \log(k!)$$

The joint model is implemented in the model file, along with a statistical model with random effect on the PK parameters and λ_0 :

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {V_pop, omega_V, k_pop, omega_k, ke0_pop, lambda0_pop, omega_lambda0,
IC50_pop}

DEFINITION:
V= {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
k = {distribution=logNormal, typical=k_pop, sd=omega_k}
ke0 = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ke0_pop, no-variability}
lambda0 = {distribution=logNormal, typical=lambda0_pop, sd=omega_lambda0}
IC50 = {distribution=logNormal, typical=IC50_pop, no-variability}

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k, ke0, lambda0, IC50}

PK:
{Cc,Ce} = pkmodel(V, k, ke0)

EQUATION:
; time evolution
lambda = lambda0 * (1 - Ce/(Ce+IC50))

DEFINITION:
CountNumber = {type=count, log(P(CountNumber=k)) = k*log(lambda) - lambda -
factln(k)}

OUTPUT:
output = CountNumber
```

See [Count data models](#) for more details about count data models.

3.1.6.6.4.3 Joint model for continuous PK and time-to-event data

- **7.1.tte/PKrtte.smlx**

In this demo, a joint PK-TTE model is used to capture Hemorrhaging adverse events induced by drug concentration following multiple doses.

We use a Weibull model for the events count data, assuming that the baseline is function of the predicted concentration. For any individual i , we define the hazard function as

$$h_i(t) = \gamma_i Cc_i(t) t^{\beta-1}$$

where $Cc_i(t)$ is the predicted concentration for individual i at time t . The joint model is implemented in the model file, that includes also a statistical model with [random effects](#) on the PK parameters and a [proportional error model](#) for the simulated PK:

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {ka_pop, omega_ka, V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl, gamma_pop, beta_pop}

DEFINITION:
ka = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ka_pop, sd=omega_ka}
V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_pop, sd=omega_Cl}
gamma = {distribution=logNormal, typical=gamma_pop, no-variability}
beta = {distribution=logNormal, typical=beta_pop, no-variability}

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {b}

DESCRIPTION: PK + repeated event
input = {ka, V, Cl, gamma, beta}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)
if t<0.1
  h = 0
else
  h = gamma*Cc*(t^(beta-1))
end

DEFINITION:
Hemorrhaging = {type=event, hazard=h}

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, Hemorrhaging}

DEFINITION:
y = {distribution=normal, prediction=Cc, errorModel=proportional(b)}
```

See [Time-to-event data models](#) for more details about time-to-event data models.

3.1.6.7 Typical extensions of structural models

The following pages describe typical extensions of structural model:

- **Time varying parameters**
 - [Time-varying clearance](#)
 - [Auto-induction model](#)
 - [Enterohepatic circulation model](#)
- **Additional model outputs**
 - [Computing additional model outputs such as Cmax or AUC](#)
 - [Calculating the half-life](#)

3.1.6.7.1 Time-varying clearance

When treatments span over a long time with numerous repeated doses, the clearance can be observed to change over time, for instance due to a change in the disease status. One possible approach to handle this case is to define in a parametric way how the clearance changes over time. A common assumption is to use an I_{max} or E_{max} model. Below, we show how to implement such a model in the Mlxtran language.

Examples of time-varying clearances are for instance presented for PEGylated Asparaginase, and for mycophenolic acid here

Würthwein et al. Population Pharmacokinetics to Model the Time-Varying Clearance of the PEGylated Asparaginase Oncaspar® in Children with Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia. Eur J Drug Metab Pharmacokinet (2017). doi:10.1007/s13318-017-0410-5 .

van Hest et al. (2007). Time-dependent clearance of mycophenolic acid in renal transplant recipients. British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology. Volume 63, Issue 6, June 2007.

3.1.6.7.1.1 Mlxtran structural model

In the example below, we assume that the clearance is decreasing over time, with a sigmoidal shape. We consider a one-compartment model with first-order absorption. The Mlxtran code for the structural model reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Clini, Imax, gamma, T50}

PK:
depot(target=Ac, ka)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

Clapp = Clini * (1 - Imax * t^gamma/(t^gamma + T50^gamma))
ddt_Ac = - Clapp/V * Ac
```

$$C_c = A_c/V$$

OUTPUT:

$$\text{output} = \{C_c\}$$

The Cl_{ini} parameter described the initial clearance, $Imax$ the maximal reduction of clearance, $T50$ the time at which the clearance is reduced by half of the maximal reduction, and γ characterizes the sigmoidal shape.

The apparent clearance Cl_{app} is defined via an analytical formula depending on the time t and is then used in the ODE system. The first-order absorption is directly defined using the depot macro, which here indicates that the doses of the data set must be applied to the target Ac via a first-order absorption with rate ka (ka is a reserved keyword).

3.1.6.7.2 Auto-induction model

Auto-induction models have been proposed when **the drug stimulates its own metabolism, usually via induction of the metabolic enzyme expression**. Auto-induction models have for instance been used to describe the pharmacokinetics of Rifampin in Smythe et al. (2012), and of cyclophosphamide in Hassan et al. (1999).

The typical auto-induction model explicitly describes the enzyme level which is modeled using an turnover model with the drug inhibiting the enzyme degradation rate or increasing the enzyme production rate. The enzyme level is then taken into account in the apparent clearance for the drug.

The typical equations read:

$$\frac{dAc}{dt} = In(t) - Cl/V \times Enz \times Ac$$

$$\frac{dEnz}{dt} = K_{enz,in} - K_{enz,out} \left(1 - \frac{C_c}{C_c + IC50}\right) \times Enz$$

With $In(t)$ the drug input rate. To avoid unidentifiability issues (i.e the product $Cl \cdot Enz_0$ is identifiable, but not Cl and Enz_0 separately), the steady-state enzyme level is enforced to 1 which leads to $K_{enz,in} = K_{enz,out}$. It is usually not necessary to introduce an I_{max} parameter.

3.1.6.7.2.1 Mlxtran code

For a zero-order absorption, the model reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={Tk0, V, Cl, Kenz, IC50}

PK:
depot(target=Ac, Tk0)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0
Enz_0 = 1

Cc = Ac/V

ddt_Ac = - Cl/V*Ac*Enz
ddt_Enz = Kenz - Kenz * (1- Cc/(Cc+IC50)) * Enz

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

3.1.6.7.3 Enterohepatic circulation model

Enterohepatic circulation (EHC) occurs when drugs circulate from the liver to the bile in the gallbladder, followed by entry into the gut when the bile is released from the gallbladder, and reabsorption from the gut back to the systemic circulation. The presence of EHC results in longer apparent drug half-lives and the appearance of multiple secondary peaks. Various pharmacokinetic models have been used in the literature to describe EHC concentration-time data.

The reference below provides a basic review of the EHC process and modeling strategies implemented to represent EHC.

Okour, M., & Brundage, R. C. (2017). *Modeling Enterohepatic Circulation. Current Pharmacology Reports*, 3(5), 301–313. doi: 10.1007/s40495-017-0096-z/

3.1.6.7.3.1 Mlxtran structural model

We present two examples of EHC models, based on a two-compartments model with iv bolus administration. Both models have been implemented with PK macros.

Example with switch function

In the first example, the gallbladder emptying is modeled with a switch function: the emptying rate constant follows a simple piece-wise function, implemented with if/else statements. Hence, gallbladder emptying occurs within time windows, where the rate constant outside these windows is assumed to be zero.

The Mlxtran code for the structural model reads:

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, Cl, Q, V2, kbile, kempt, ka_gut, Tfirst, Tsecond}

PK:
k=Cl/V
k12=Q/V
k21=Q/V2
duration=1
if t>Tfirst & t<Tfirst+duration
kemptying = kempt
elseif t>Tsecond & t<Tsecond+duration
kemptying = kempt
else
kemptying = 0
end

compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
iv(adm=1, cmt=1)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
peripheral(k12, k21)
compartment(cmt=3)
compartment(cmt=4)
transfer(from=1, to=3, kt=kbile)
transfer(from=3, to=4, kt=kemptying)
  
```

```
transfer(from=4, to=1, kt=ka_gut)
```

OUTPUT:

```
output = {Cc}
```

The parameters `kbile`, `kempt` and `ka_gut` describe respectively the transfer rate between the central compartment and the bile, between the bile and the gut, and between the gut and the central compartment.

The parameter `kemptying` is the rate constant controlling the gallbladder emptying process, and its value changes with time as displayed below:

Here two windows of duration `duration=1` have been defined starting at times `Tfirst` and `Tsecond`. It is of course possible to extend this model with additional emptying windows, if more than two secondary peaks are noticeable in the data, and to change the value of the parameter `duration`.

Example with sine function

In the second example, gallbladder emptying is modeled with a sine function, assumed to equal zero outside the gallbladder emptying times. This model accounts for multiple cycles of gallbladder emptying.

The Mlxtran code for the structural model reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
```

```

input = {V, Cl, Q, V2, kbile, kempt, ka_gut, phase, period}

PK:
k=Cl/V
k12=Q/V
k21=Q/V2

kemptying = max(0, kempt * (cos(2*3.14*(t+phase)/period)))

compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
iv(adm=1, cmt=1)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
peripheral(k12, k21)
compartment(cmt=3)
compartment(cmt=4)
transfer(from=1, to=3, kt=kbile)
transfer(from=3, to=1, kt=kemptying)
transfer(from=4, to=1, kt=ka_gut)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
  
```

This model assumes fixed intervals between gallbladder release times, with the parameter `period` defining their frequency. The parameter `phase` represents the time of the beginning of the first gallbladder release. The value of the parameter `kemptying` over time is then:

Variation with oral administration

If the drug administration is oral instead of a bolus, the model can be adapted by replacing the macro `iv(adm=1, cmt=1)` with `absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka)`, which defines a first-order absorption with a rate `ka`. While `ka` represents the absorption of the drug, `ka_gut` represents its reabsorption after storage in the gallbladder. These two physiological processes are not strictly equivalent, as the bile

stored in the gallbladder is released into the duodenum. Depending on the drug, `ka` and `ka_gut` can be set as separate or identical rate constants.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, ka, Cl, Q, V2, kbile, kempt, ka_gut, phase, period}

PK:
k=Cl/V
k12=Q/V
k21=Q/V2

kemptying = max(0, kempt * (cos(2*3.14*(t+phase)/period)))

compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
peripheral(k12, k21)
compartment(cmt=3)
compartment(cmt=4)
transfer(from=1, to=3, kt=kbile)
transfer(from=3, to=1, kt=kemptying)
transfer(from=4, to=1, kt=ka_gut)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

3.1.6.7.4 Computing additional model outputs such as Cmax or AUC

Computing additional outputs such as AUC and Cmax in the structural model is possible but requires a particular syntax, because it is not possible to redefine a variable in Mlxtran. For example, it would not be possible to directly update the variable $C_{max} = C_c$ when $C_c > C_{max}$. But it is possible to compute Cmax via an ODE, where Cmax increases like Cc at each time where $C_c > C_{max}$. This page gives detailed examples for the AUC on full time interval or specific interval, Cmax, nadir, and other derived variables such as duration above a threshold.

Often the Area under the PK curve (AUC) is needed as an important PK metric to link with the pharmacodynamic effect. We show here how to:

- compute the AUC within the mlxtran model file
- output the AUC calculations for later analysis.

Calculation of the AUC can be done in the EQUATION section of the Mlxtran model. If a dataset contains the AUC observations, then the calculation in the EQUATION section can be used as an output in the `output={}` definition (matched to observations of the data set). Or it can be saved for post-treatment using `table={}`.

3.1.6.7.4.1 AUClast from t=0 to t=tlast

The following code is the basic implementation of the AUC for a 1-compartmental model with the absorption rate k_a . It integrates the concentration profile from the start to the end of the observation period.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}

PK:
Cc=pkmodel(ka,V,Cl)

EQUATION:
odeType=stiff
ddt_AUC = Cc

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {AUC}
```

3.1.6.7.4.2 AUC in a time interval

The following code computes the AUC between two time points t_1 and t_2 . The idea is to compute the AUC_{0,t_1} and AUC_{0,t_2} using if/else statements and then do the difference between the two.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}
PK:
depot(ka, target=Ac)

EQUATION:
odeType = stiff
useAnalyticalSolution=no

Cc = pkmodel(ka,V,Cl)

t1=24
t2=48
AUCt1_0 = 0
if(t < t1)
    dAUCt1 = Cc
else
    dAUCt1 = 0
end
ddt_AUCt1 = dAUCt1
```

```

AUCt2_0 = 0
if(t < t2)
  dAUCt2 = Cc
else
  dAUCt2 = 0
end
ddt_AUCt2 = dAUCt2

AUC_t1_t2 = AUCt2 - AUCt1

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {AUC_t1_t2}

```

i Note that the $t=tDose$ would not work because the integrator does not necessarily evaluate the time exactly at the times of doses. Thus the test $t=tDose$ might not be tested at all during the computation.

i Also note that, although partial AUC can be calculated by comparing time with the both boundaries in the if statement (e.g. if $(t>20 \text{ and } t<40)$), this might not be the best practice when concentration is calculated using an analytical solution, because ODE solver used for calculating AUC could be deceived by AUC remaining 0 for a period of time and might increase the integration time step to a value larger than the difference between time boundaries.

3.1.6.7.4.3 Dose-interval AUC (AUCtau)

The following code compute the AUCtau for each dose interval. At each dose the AUC is reset to zero and the concentration is integrated until the next administration.

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}

PK:
Cc = pkmodel(ka,V,Cl)

; Reset the ODE variable AUCtau to zero each time there is a dose
empty(target=AUCtau)

```

```

EQUATION:
odeType=stiff
ddt_AUCtau = Cc

```

```
OUTPUT:  
output = {Cc}  
table = {AUCtau}
```

Since AUCtau is equal to 0 at each dosing time as it has just been reset, the AUC in the last interdose interval should actually be read just before that time.

Here we provide a Simulx project with an example of a PK model where AUCtau is calculated as additional lines in the model and defined as an output of the simulations.

3.1.6.7.4.4 Computing the Cmax or nadir in the structural model

Cmax

Cmax can be calculated directly in the structural model by integrating the increase of the concentration. Alternatively, the Cmax can also be calculated in Simulx using the Outcomes and Endpoints tab.

Cmax for models with first-order absorption

The following example shows how to do it in case of a one-compartment model with first-order absorption and linear elimination. Absorption processes defined via the depot macro must be replaced by explicit ODEs, while the depot macro is used to add the dose as a bolus into the depot compartment.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]  
input = {Cl, ka, V}  
  
PK:  
depot(target=Ad)  
  
EQUATION:  
  
; initial conditions  
t_0 = 0  
Ad_0 = 0  
Ac_0 = 0  
  
ddt_Ad = -ka*Ad  
ddt_Ac = ka*Ad - k*Ac  
Cc = Ac/V  
  
; Calculation of Cmax  
slope = ka*Ad - k*Ac  
Cmax_0 = 0  
if slope > 0 && Cc > Cmax
```

```

    x = slope/V
else
    x = 0
end

ddt_Cmax = x

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {Cmax}

```

Cmax for model with bolus administration or infusion

If the dose is administered as bolus, it is necessary to add in the model a very short infusion. This prevents from the instantaneous increase of the concentration. The following example shows this situations in case of a three-compartments model with linear elimination. The duration of the “short infusion” can be adapted with respect to the time scale by modifying $dT=0.1$.

If the doses are administered via iv infusion, then $dT=0.1$ can be replaced by $dT = \text{inftDose}$, which reads the infusion duration from the data.

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Cl, V1, Q2, V2, Q3, V3}

EQUATION:

; Parameter transformations
V   = V1
k    = Cl/V1
k12 = Q2/V1
k21 = Q2/V2
k13 = Q3/V1
k31 = Q3/V3

; initial conditions
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0
A2_0 = 0
A3_0 = 0

;short pseudo-infusion duration
dT = 0.1 ; use dT=inftDose if the administration is infusion: inftDose is the
infusion duration from the last dose read from the data

; infusion input to Ac
if t < tDose+dT
    input = amtDose/dT ;amtDose is the last dose amount read from the data
else
    input = 0
end

```

```

dAc = input -k*Ac - k12*Ac - k13*Ac + k21*A2 + k31*A3
ddt_Ac = dAc
ddt_A2 = k12*Ac - k21*A2
ddt_A3 = k13*Ac - k31*A3
Cc = Ac/V

; Calculation of AUC
AUC_0 = 0
ddt_AUC = Cc

; Calculation of Cmax
Cmax_0 = 0
if dAc > 0 && Cc > Cmax
  x = dAc/V
else
  x = 0
end

ddt_Cmax = x

OUTPUT:
output = {Ac, Cc}
table = {Cmax, AUC}

```

Cmax for models with transit compartments

The transit compartments defined via the depot() macro must be replaced by explicit ODEs. The amount in the last (nth) transit compartment is described via an analytical solution using the keyword amtDose to get the dose amount and (t-tDose) to get the time elapsed since the last dose. The calculation of Cmax then follows the same logic as for a first-order absorption.

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input={F, Ktr, Mtt, ka, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
k = Cl/V
odeType=stiff

; transit model with explicit ODEs
n = max(0, Mtt*Ktr - 1)
An = F * amtDose * exp( n * log(Ktr*(t-tDose)) - factln(n) - Ktr * (t-tDose))

t_0 = 0
Aa_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

ddt_Aa = Ktr*An - ka*Aa
ddt_Ac = ka*Aa - k*Ac

```

```

Cc = Ac/V

; Calculation of Cmax
slope = ka*Aa - k*Ac
Cmax_0 = 0
if slope > 0 && Cc > Cmax
  x = slope/V
else
  x = 0
end

ddt_Cmax = x

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {Cmax}

```

Nadir

This example shows how to compute tumor size (variable TS) at time of nadir:

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Vl, Cl, TS0, kge, kkill, lambda}
EQUATION:

odeType=stiff
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)

; ODE system for tumor growth dynamics
t_0 = 0
TS_0 = TS0
TSDynamics = (kge*TS)-kkill*TS*Cc*exp(-lambda*t)
ddt_TS = TSDynamics

; ===== computing TS at nadir
if TSDynamics < 0 && TS < TS_atNadir
  x = TSDynamics
else
  x = 0
end
TS_atNadir_0 = TS0
ddt_TS_atNadir = x

OUTPUT:
output = {TS}
table = {TS_atNadir}

```

Here is an example of simulation for TS and TS_atNadir with a multiple dose schedule:

3.1.6.7.4.5 Time above a threshold

Here we compute the time that a variable C spends above some threshold, which could be a toxicity threshold for example. This piece of code comes in the structural model, after the dynamics of the variable C has already been defined.

```

TimeAboveThreshold_0 = 0
if C > Cthreshold
  xTime = 1
else
  xTime = 0
end
ddt_TimeAboveThreshold = xTime
  
```

3.1.6.7.4.6 Time since disease progression

In this full structural model example, tumor size TS is described with an exponential growth, and a constant treatment effect since time=0 with a log-kill killing hypothesis and a Claret exponential resistance term. Several additional variables are computed:

- $TS_{atNadir}$: the tumor size at the time of nadir,
- PC_{from_Nadir} : the percent change of TS between the time of nadir and the current time,
- DP : predicted disease progression status (1 if TS has increased more than >20% and >5-mm from last nadir, 0 otherwise),
- TDP : time since disease progression (duration since last time when DP is switched from 0 to 1)

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {TS0, kge, kkill, lambda}

EQUATION:
odeType=stiff

;initial conditions:
;t_0 = 0 ;this should be uncommented if the initial time is 0 for all subjects
TS_0 = TS0

K = kkill*exp(-lambda*t)

;Saturation for TS at 1e12 to avoid infinite values
if TS>1e12
  TSDynamics = 0
else
  if t<0 ; before treatment
    TSDynamics = (kge*TS)
  else ; after treatment
    TSDynamics = (kge*TS)-K*TS
  end
end

ddt_TS = TSDynamics

; Computing time to nadir (TS decreases after treatment start at time=0, then
increases again because of resistance)
if TSDynamics<0
  x1=1
else
  x1=0
end
TimeToNadir_0=t0
ddt_TimeToNadir = x1 ; x1 is used as intermediate variable because it is not possible
to define an ODE inside an if/else statement

; Computing TS at time of nadir
if TSDynamics < 0 & TS < TS_atNadir
  x2 = TSDynamics
else
  x2 = 0
end
TS_atNadir_0 = TS0
ddt_TS_atNadir = x2 ;

; Computing DP: predicted disease progression status at the previous visit (1 if TS
has increased more than >20% and >5-mm from last nadir, 0 otherwise)
PC_from_Nadir = (TS/TS_atNadir-1)*100
if t>TimeToNadir & PC_from_Nadir > 20 & (TS-TS_atNadir) > 5
  DP = 1
else
  DP = 0

```

```

end

; Computing TDP = time since disease progression: duration since last time DP was
switched from 0 to 1
if DP==1
    x3 = 1
else
    x3 = 0
end
TDP_0 = 0
ddt_TDP = x3

OUTPUT:
output = {TS}
table = {TS_atNadir, PC_from_Nadir, DP, TDP}
    
```

Simulx can be conveniently used to simulate each intermediate variable with typical parameters (the example model and Simulx project can be downloaded here):

3.1.6.7.5 Calculating the half-life

Calculating the half-life

The half-life is usually not part of the estimated parameters but it often needs to be reported. It presents the advantage of having units of time and being easy to understand. The terminal plasma half-life is the time required to divide the plasma concentration by two after reaching pseudo-equilibrium. It is especially relevant to multiple dosing regimens, because it controls the degree of drug accumulation and the time taken to reach equilibrium. For a more detailed overview, please refer to:

Toutain P.L, Bousquet-Melou A. Plasma terminal half-life, J. vet. Pharmacol. Therap. 27, 427-439, 2004

This documentation page explains the half-life formulas and how to modify the Monolix or Simulx models to calculate it.

Half-life formulas

One-compartmental model

For a drug captured by a model with one compartment and linear elimination, and without flip-flop kinetics, the half-life is calculated as:

$$T_{1/2} = \frac{\log(2)}{k} = \frac{\log(2) \times V}{Cl}$$

with k the elimination rate, Cl the clearance and V the volume of distribution. Note that $\log(2) \approx 0.632$ so you might also find the formula written with this value.

Two-compartmental model

For a drug captured by a model with one compartment and linear elimination, the half-life correspond to the slope of the second part of the curve on a log-concentration over time plot, once pseudo-equilibrium is achieved. The slope of the terminal (second) phase is usually called β , the first slope α and the intercepts A and B.

The parametrization of the 2-compartment model with (A, B, α, β) is an alternative parametrization compared to the parametrization with (k, V, k_{12}, k_{21}) or (Cl, V, Q, V_2) .

It is possible to convert between these different parametrizations using the following formulas:

$$\alpha = \frac{k_{21}k}{\beta} = \frac{\frac{Q}{V_2} \frac{Cl}{V_1}}{\beta}$$

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \left(k_{12} + k_{21} + k - \sqrt{(k_{12} + k_{21} + k)^2 - 4k_{21}k} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{Q}{V_1} + \frac{Q}{V_2} + \frac{Cl}{V_1} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{Q}{V_1} + \frac{Q}{V_2} + \frac{Cl}{V_1} \right)^2 - 4 \frac{Q}{V_2} \frac{Cl}{V_1}} \right)$$

The half-life corresponds to the terminal phase and is defined as:

$$T_{1/2} = \frac{\log(2)}{\beta} = \frac{\log(2)}{0.5 \left(k_{12} + k_{21} + k - \sqrt{(k_{12} + k_{21} + k)^2 - 4k_{21}k} \right)}$$

3.1.6.8 Advanced models

The following pages show how to write advanced models:

3.1.6.8.1 Lifespan models

Lifespan based indirect response (LIDR) models have originally been proposed in the field of hematology. The population of cells are described by cell production and cell degradation. **The main**

assumption of LIDR models is that a cell dies when its lifespan expires. This implies that the cell degradation rate is equal to the cell production rate delayed by the lifespan. This assumption differs from classical indirect response model where the cell (or response) degradation is proportional to the cell number (first-order process), independently of the production rate or the lifespan.

LIDR models have been reviewed in detail in:

Krzyzanski, W., & Perez Ruixo, J. J. (2012). Lifespan based indirect response models. Journal of Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics, 39(1), 109–123.

The implementation of LIDR model makes use of delayed differential equations, which can easily be solved in the MonolixSuite using the delay differential equation solver. In the following, we will consider a drug with simple exponential decay after a bolus administration and a response R, which can for instance be the number of blood cells.

3.1.6.8.1.1 Mlxtran code for LIDR models

LIDR model for drugs affecting the production rate of the response

In this model, **the drug affects the response via an I_{max} model on the production rate.** The equation for the response is:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = k_{in} \left(1 \pm I_{max} \frac{C(t)}{IC_{50} + C(t)} \right) - k_{in} \left(1 \pm I_{max} \frac{C(t - T_R)}{IC_{50} + C(t - T_R)} \right)$$

where + would be used if the drug increases the production rate and - if it decreases it. Notice that the degradation rate is simply the production rate delayed by the lifespan T_R . If necessary, a sigmoidicity parameter gamma can be added to the formula. When implemented in mlxtran, $C(t - T_R)$ translates into delay(C,TR) which means that we use the value of the concentration C delayed by time T_R .

Note that the delay function makes use of the DDE solver, which is slower than the ODE solver. This video presents an alternative implementation using ODEs only, which leads to greatly shorter run times.

The mlxtran code reads (for the inhibition case):

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={V, k, kin, Imax, IC50, TR}

PK:
depot(target=Ac)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0
R_0 = kin * TR

Cc = Ac/V
ddt_Ac = -k*Ac
```

```

ddt_R = kin*(1 - Imax *Cc/(Cc+IC50)) - kin*(1 - Imax *delay(Ac,TR)/(delay(Ac,TR)
+IC50*V))
    
```

OUTPUT:

```
output = {Cc, R}
```

As usual, the depot macro permits to link the doses defined in the data set to the DDEs system. In the model formulation above, it is assumed that both the drug concentration C_c and the response R are recorded in the data set. If only R is observed, the output line should be changed to `output= {R}`. Note that if the concentration C_c is not observed, it is not possible to identify both V and IC_{50} . The value of V can then be fixed. Alternatively, the K-PD model can be reformulated as in Jacqmin et al. (2007). In the delay macro, it is mandatory to use an ODE variable. We thus use A_c rather than C_c and divide by the volume V outside of the delay macro.

For a drug inhibiting the production rate, the typical response shape is the following (darker colors indicate larger drug amounts). The response start to change from baseline at time 0 and is maximal at time T_R :

If the drug would increase the production rate instead of decreasing it, the response would increase over time before recovering its basal level:

LIDR model for drugs affecting the cell lifespan distribution

This model assumes that initially the lifespan is T_R and that the drugs modifies the cell lifespan to a new value T_D . The drug effect is described by an I_{max} term, which represents the fraction of cells with lifespan T_D . The higher the drug concentration is, the more cells will switch from the baseline lifespan T_R to the new lifetime T_D .

The equation for the response is:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = k_{in} - k_{in} \left(1 - I_{max} \frac{C(t-T_R)}{IC50+C(t-T_R)} \right) - k_{in} \left(I_{max} \frac{C(t-T_D)}{IC50+C(t-T_D)} \right)$$

The mlxtran code reads:

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input={V, k, kin, Imax, IC50, TR, TD}

PK:
depot(target=Ac)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0
R_0 = kin * TR

Cc = Ac/V
ddt_Ac = -k*Ac
ddt_R = kin - kin*(1 - Imax *delay(Ac,TR)/(delay(Ac,TR)+IC50*V)) - kin*(Imax
*delay(Ac,TD)/(delay(Ac,TD)+IC50*V))

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, R}
  
```

For a drug reducing the lifespan from $T_R = 30$ to $T_D = 10$ days, the typical response shape is the following (darker colors indicate larger drug amounts). The response is maximal at time $\max(T_R, T_D)$. Note that there is a delay before the response starts to change, which corresponds to $\min(T_R, T_D)$.

The possibility to have this delay requires one more parameter compared to the lifespan model for drugs affecting the production rate.

If the drug would increase the lifespan (i.e. $T_D > T_R$), the curves would be flipped over (increasing response):

LIDR model with a precursor pool

In this model we assume that **the drug effects a precursor pool, which matures into the main pool represented by the response R**. Interestingly, it is not necessary to solve the equation for the precursor, only the equation for the response R is needed:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = k_{in} \left(1 \pm I_{max} \frac{C(t-T_P)}{IC50+C(t-T_P)} \right) - k_{in} \left(1 \pm I_{max} \frac{C(t-T_P-T_R)}{IC50+C(t-T_P-T_R)} \right)$$

where + is used if the drug increases the precursor production rate and - if it decreases it. T_R represents the lifespan of the main cells (response) and T_P the lifespan of the precursor.

The mlxtran code reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={V, k, kin, Imax, IC50, TR, TP}
```

```
PK:
depot(target=Ac)
```

```
EQUATION:
```

```
t_0 = 0
```

```
Ac_0 = 0
```

```
R_0 = kin * TR
```

```
Cc = Ac/V
```

```
ddt_Ac = -k*Ac
```

```
ddt_R = kin*(1 - Imax *delay(Ac,TP)/(delay(Ac,TP)+IC50*V)) - kin*(1 - Imax
*delay(Ac,TP+TR)/(delay(Ac,TP+TR)+IC50*V))
```

```
OUTPUT:
```

```
output= {Cc, R}
```

The typical response-time curve is displayed below for the case where the drug inhibits the precursor production. The response start to change at time T_P and the change is maximal at time $T_P + T_R$.

If the drug increases the precursor production, we obtain:

Exploration of indirect model and LIDR model differences with Mlxplore

We explore the differences between:

- the LIDR model
- the indirect response model

In both models, we assume that the drug inhibits the response production rate. Yet, in the LIDR model, the response degradation rate is equal to the production rate delayed by the lifespan. On the opposite, in the indirect response model, the response degradation rate is proportional to the response magnitude.

3.1.6.8.2 K-PD models

Usual PK-PD models describe the relationships between dose regimens, drug concentration and effect (or response). They are applied when both the drug concentration and the effect can be measured. However situations exist where the concentration PK data is not available. This may for instance be the case for phase III clinical trials or pediatric studies. **In this case K-PD models can be used: the drug concentration-effect relationship model is kept, but the (unobserved) PK profile is assumed to have a simple shape.** In comparison to dose-response studies which directly link the (constant) dose to the PD response, K-PD models permit to capture PD profile that varies over time as a consequence of the underlying time-varying PK profile.

Although not being the first published example of K-PD model, the usual reference is:

Jacqmin, P., Snoeck, E., Schaick, E. A. Van, Gieschke, R., Pillai, P., Steimer, J., & Girard, P. (2007). Modelling Response Time Profiles in the Absence of Drug Concentrations : Definition and Performance Evaluation of the K-PD Model. *Journal of Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics*, 34(1).

3.1.6.8.2.1 Mlxtran code for K-PD models

The effect of the drug on the response can be as diverse as presented in the indirect response models and direct response models examples. **We here focus on the case of an indirect response where the drug decreases the response production rate.**

Formulation by Jacqmin et al.

The authors in Jacqmin et al. describe the model in the following way: "A virtual compartment representing the biophase in which the concentration is in equilibrium with the observed effect is used to extract the (pharmaco)kinetic component from the pharmacodynamic data alone. Parameters of this model are the elimination rate constant from the virtual compartment (KDE), which describes the equilibrium between the rate of dose administration and the observed effect, and the second parameter, named EDK50 which is the apparent in vivo potency of the drug at steady state.

The equations read:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA}{dt} &= -KDE \times A \\ IR &= KDE \times A \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= K_s \left(1 - \frac{IR}{EDK_{50} + IR} \right) - K_D R \end{aligned}$$

with A the drug amount, R the response, KDE the drug elimination rate, Ks the response synthesis rate, Kd the response disappearance rate constant. EDK50 represents the potency of the drug and also corresponds to EDK50 constant corresponds to the product of the EC50 and the clearance.

The corresponding Mlxtran code is:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={Ks,Kd,KDE,EDK50}

PK:
depot(target=A)

EQUATION:
; initialization
t_0 = 0
A_0 = 0
R_0 = Ks/Kd

; ODEs
ddt_A = - KDE*A
ddt_R = Ks * (1 - (KDE*A)/(EDK50 + (KDE*A))) - Kd*R

OUTPUT:
output = {R}
```

Note that the only output is the response R, as only the response has been measured and recorded in the data set.

Alternative formulation

For some applications, the interpretation of the parameters of the Jacqmin model may be difficult. It is also unusual to consider that it is the rate at which the drug disappears (IR) that drives the effect on the response. **We thus propose an alternative formulation of the same model.**

We start by writing the model using the usual (and physiologically relevant) effect of the drug concentration on the response:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA}{dt} &= -KDE \times A \\ C_A &= \frac{A}{V_A} \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= K_s \left(1 - \frac{C_A}{IC_{50} + C_A} \right) - K_D R \end{aligned}$$

This set of equations can be rewritten into:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA}{dt} &= -KDE \times A \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= K_s \left(1 - \frac{A}{IC_{50} \times V_A + A} \right) - K_D R \end{aligned}$$

using the fact that $C_A = \frac{A}{V_A}$. When the drug concentration is observed, it is possible to identify both V_A and IC_{50} separately because V_A influences the observed drug concentration. However when the drug concentration is not measured, it is not possible to identify both V_A and IC_{50} , but only the product of the two. The unidentifiability of the volume of distribution is explored visually and interactively in the next section.

We thus introduce $A_{50} = IC_{50} \times V_A$ and write our final model as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA}{dt} &= -KDE \times A \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= K_s \left(1 - \frac{A}{A_{50} + A} \right) - K_D R \end{aligned}$$

The parameter A_{50} can simply be interpreted as the product of the usual IC_{50} and the volume of distribution V_A of the drug.

The mxtran model reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={Ks,Kd,KDE,A50}

PK:
depot(target=A)

EQUATION:
; initialization
t_0 = 0
```

```
A_0 = 0
R_0 = Ks/Kd

; ODEs
ddt_A = - KDE*A
ddt_R = Ks * (1 - A/(A50 + A) ) - Kd*R

OUTPUT:
output = {R}
```

The model can also be written using macros for the (P)K part. When macros are used, the PK part of the model will be calculated using the analytical solution while the PD part will be solved using the ODE solver.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={Ks,Kd,KDE,A50}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=A)
iv(cmt=1)
elimination(cmt=1, k=KDE)

EQUATION:
; initialization
t_0 = 0
R_0 = Ks/Kd

; ODEs
ddt_R = Ks * (1 - A/(A50 + A) ) - Kd*R

OUTPUT:
output = {R}
```

Extensions

If data is sufficient to allow for the estimation of the additional parameters, the model can be extended, for instance in the following directions:

- more complex profile for the drug concentration, for example with a first-order input rate. In this case, the additional input arguments can be directly given in the depot macro;
- sigmoidal E_{max} or I_{max} model with a hill exponent;
- E_{max} or I_{max} value different from one.

The model can also be adapted to consider **K-PK models, where two drugs interact** and only one of the two is measured.

Simplifications

The use of an Emax or I_{max} model is only suited if the dose range is sufficiently large to cover both the linear and saturating part of the Michaelis-Menten curve. If concentrations are always smaller than the EC₅₀, the model simplifies to:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = -KDE \times A$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = K_s (1 - K_e \times A) - K_D R$$

3.1.6.8.3 Friberg model for myelosuppression

The Friberg model is a semi-mechanistic pharmacodynamic model describing chemotherapy-induced myelosuppression. It has been originally developed to describe leukocyte and neutrophil data after administration of docetaxel, paclitaxel, etoposide, DMDC and irinotecan and vinflunine in Friberg et al. (2002), and has been reused in many other publications since.

Friberg et al. (2002). Model of chemotherapy-induced myelosuppression with parameter consistency across drugs. Journal of Clinical Oncology, 20(24), 4713–4721.

3.1.6.8.3.1 Model description

The model consists of a proliferating compartment that is sensitive to drugs, three transit compartments that represent maturation, and a compartment of circulating blood cells. The parameterization is parsimonious (initial circulating concentration, mean transit time and a feedback parameter), well suited for sparse data. The drug effect can be implemented as a linear function or with an Emax model, as shown below.

The PK part of the model is in this example a (ka,V,Cl) model but can be replaced by any other PK model. PK parameters can either be estimated (as below) or read from the data set (uncomment the three lines below the input line to consider the PK parameters as regressors).

3.1.6.8.3.2 Mlxtran model code

```
DESCRIPTION:
PD = Friberg et al (2002) 'Model of Chemotherapy-Induced Myelosuppression with
Parameter Consistency Across Drugs', Journal of Clinical Oncology 20:4713-4721

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl, Circ0, MTT, gam, Emax, EC50}
; ka = {use=regressor}
; V = {use=regressor}
; Cl = {use=regressor}

EQUATION:
odeType=stiff
; PK model
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)

; parameter transformations
n = 3
ktr = (n+1)/MTT
kprol = ktr
kcirc = ktr

; drug effect
Edrug = Emax * Cc/(EC50 + Cc)

; initial values
t_0 = 0
Prol_0 = Circ0
T1_0 = Circ0
T2_0 = Circ0
T3_0 = Circ0
Circ_0 = Circ0

;ODEs for the response
ddt_Prol = kprol*Prol*(1-Edrug)*(Circ0/Circ)^gam - ktr*Prol
ddt_T1 = ktr*Prol - ktr*T1
ddt_T2= ktr*T1 - ktr*T2
ddt_T3 = ktr*T2 - ktr*T3
ddt_Circ = ktr*T3 - kcirc*Circ

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, Circ}
```

In the Monolix GUI, a lognormal distribution can be chosen for Circ0, MTT, gam and EC50, and a **logit distribution for Emax** to ensure that (1-Edrug) stays always positive. It is common to remove the random effects on gam.

3.1.6.8.4 ADC model

Antibody-drug conjugates or **ADCs** are a class of drugs designed as a targeted therapy for treating cancer. They are complex molecules composed of an antibody that targets a specific tumor antigen, linked to a biologically active cytotoxic payload or drug.

On this page we show an example of population PK model for an ADC drug published in:

Li, H., Han, T.H., Hunder, N.N., Jang, G. and Zhao, B. (2017), *Population Pharmacokinetics of Brentuximab Vedotin in Patients With CD30-Expressing Hematologic Malignancies*. *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 57: 1148-1158. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcph.920>

In the publication the model is written for NONMEN, here we have translated it in Mlxtran for use with the MonolixSuite.

The model describes the PK of **brentuximab vedotin**, a CD30-directed antibody-drug conjugate (**ADC**), which is approved for treating certain patients with CD30-expressing hematologic malignancies. Its primary mechanism of action is the targeted delivery of a microtubule-disrupting agent, monomethyl auristatin E (**MMAE**), to CD30-expressing cells. In the model considers intravenous administration of **brentuximab vedotin** and characterizes also the PK of **unconjugated MMAE**.

The following figure from the publication describes the model:

Figure 1. ADC and MMAE PK model schema after an intravenous infusion of brentuximab vedotin. ADC, antibody-drug conjugate; DAR, drug-antibody ratio; CL, clearance of ADC by proteolytic degradation; Q_2 and Q_3 , ADC intercompartmental clearance; CL_M , MMAE apparent clearance; MMAE, monomethyl auristatin E; Q_5 , MMAE apparent intercompartmental clearance.

3.1.6.8.4.1 Mlxtran code for the ADC and MMAE population PK model

The full Mlxtran code is given below:

DESCRIPTION:

ADC-MMAE model describing ADC and MMAE concentrations following intravenous administration of brentuximab vedotin.

Published in:

Li, H., Han, T.H., Hunder, N.N., Jang, G. and Zhao, B. (2017), Population Pharmacokinetics of Brentuximab Vedotin in Patients With CD30-Expressing Hematologic Malignancies. *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 57: 1148-1158. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcph.920>

[LONGITUDINAL]

input={CL, V1, Q2, V2, Q3, V3, CLM, V4, Q5, V5, CYCLE, FM, DAR0, ALPHA, BETA}
 CYCLE = {use = regressor}

PK:

MW_ADC = 153000 ; molecular weight of ADC [g/mol]
 MW_MMAE = 718 ; molecular weight of MMAE [g/mol]

depot(target=A1, p=1e3/MW_ADC) ; from mg to nmol

EQUATION:

odeType=stiff

K10=CL/V1

K12=Q2/V1

K21=Q2/V2

K13=Q3/V1

K31=Q3/V3

K40=CLM/V4

K45=Q5/V4

K54=Q5/V5

FMC = CYCLE^FM ; FRACTION OF ADC CONVERTS TO MMAE BY CYCLE

DAR=DAR0*(ALPHA + (1-ALPHA)*exp(-BETA*(t-tDose)))

ddt_A1 = - (K10 + K12 + K13)*A1 + K21*A2+ K31*A3 ; ADC CENTRAL COMPT

ddt_A2 = K12*A1 - K21*A2 ; ADC PERI COMPT -1

ddt_A3 = K13*A1 - K31*A3 ; ADC PERI COMPT -2

ddt_A4 = K10*A1*DAR*FMC + A1*(DAR-DAR0*ALPHA)*BETA-K40*A4-K45*A4 + K54*A5 ; MMAE CENTRAL COMPT

ddt_A5 = K45*A4 - K54*A5 ; MMAE PERI COMPT

; Proteolytic pathway

ddt_A6 = K10*A1*DAR

; deconjugation pathway

ddt_A7 = A1*(DAR-DAR0*ALPHA)*BETA

ADCc_pmol_mL = A1/V1 ; in nmol/L

MMAEc_pmol_mL = A4/V4 ; in nmol/L

ADCc = ADCc_pmol_mL*(MW_ADC/1e3) ; from nmol/L to ug/mL

MMAEc = MMAEc_pmol_mL*(MW_MMAE/1) ; from nmol/L to ng/mL

OUTPUT:

```
output = {ADCc, MMAEc}
```

The model has two outputs for ADC concentration and MMAE concentration.

The average drug load (or drug-antibody ratio DAR) was not measured but was assumed to decrease exponentially after each dose. In Mlxtran, the equation for DAR uses the keyword tDose that corresponds to the time of the last dose.

CYCLE is a time-varying regressor indicating the number of the last dose cycle. The fraction of ADC converted to MMAE by cycle varies with $FMC = \text{CYCLE}^{\text{FM}}$.

The model uses the molecular weights of ADC and MMAE to convert the dose amount from mg to nmol and the output concentrations from nmol/L to $\mu\text{g/mL}$ or ng/mL .

3.1.6.8.4.2 Typical simulations of the model in Simulx

This Simulx project (Brentuximab Vedotin Simulation.zip) uses the brentuximal model and the population estimates from the paper to simulate a typical prediction:

(note that the link points to a zip file, so the download might be blocked by your browser, in that case you need to right-click > Save link as > Keep)

3.1.7 External model editor

mlxEditor is an application to write, edit and organise models written in the mlxtran language. It has mlxtran dedicated features, such as syntax coloring, autocompletion and verification, and is integrated with Monolix, Simulx and PKanalix for easier model development.

The screenshot shows the MlxEditor - 2021R1 application window. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Edit, Session, Settings, Help), a tab bar with three open files (Untitled*, model_PD.txt, run15_dup_TK0_CIAIag_3comp_rev15_comb2_remocov_built_simulxModel.txt), and a toolbar with buttons for MONOLIX, CHECK SYNTAX, search, undo, redo, and save/export. The main editor area contains the following mlxtran code:

```

1 DESCRIPTION:
2
3 [LONGITUDINAL]
4 input={alpha_S, RF, RE, epsilon, PSAb, Nmax}
5
6 EQUATION:
7 odeType=stiff
8   stiff
9 p=20
10 delta=0.23
11 g=0.0000001
12
13 alpha_R=RF*alpha_S
14 d=RE*RF*alpha_S
15
16
17 PSA_0=PSAb
18 S_0=delta*PSAb/p
19 R_0=g/max(d-RF*(g+d),1e-9)*delta*PSAb/p
20
21
22 if t>0
23 alpha_S_=alpha_S*(1-epsilon)
24 else
25 alpha_S_=alpha_S
26 end
  
```

Main functions:

- Writing models in the mlxtran language.
- Editing user custom models and models from the Monolix library, which is integrated with the application.
- Editing models directly in the GUI: Monolix (tab: Structural model), Simulx (Tab: Definition/Model) and PKanalix (tab: Model, CA).
- Managing models in work sessions.

Main features:

- Mlxtran syntax coloring for different model elements, such as block definition, parameters, macros.

- Autocompletion for variables, mlxtran keywords, functions (tab-key accepts a selected item).
- Find and Find&Replace.
- Zoom in/out to increase/decrease the font size.
- Syntax check to verify if the mlxtran code is correct and a model can be loaded in Monolix or Simulx.

In the mlxEditor application:

- Access to the Monolix libraries,
 - Monolix and Simulx syntax check,
 - Save and export to Simulx,
 - Sessions: collections of models that can be reloaded automatically.

In the GUI edit mode:

- Several saving options: Save & apply – saves the model under the same name (overwrites the previous model) and applies it to the current project, Save as & apply – saves the model under a different name and applies it to the current project, Save as – saves the model under a different name without applying to the current project.
 - Zoom applied in the edition model remains in the “Tab: Structural model” after closing the edition mode.

3.2 Occasions

Occasions definition. When the model to simulate contains inter-occasion variability (ie variability between different periods of measurements within the same individual), you should define a single element Occasions. Like for the model, and contrary to the other simulation elements, it is not possible to define several occasion elements to choose from for the simulation.

Demo projects: 3.7. occasions

All other defined elements must be compatible with the structure of occasions.

3.2.1 Common occasions for all subjects

In the interface, it is possible to define a common structure of occasions applied to all simulated subjects. This structure can contain one or several levels of occasions, and one or several occasions per subject.

After defining such common occasion structure, other common elements (parameters, covariates, treatments, outputs and regressors of type "manual" or "regular") can be defined occasion-wise thanks to a dedicated toggle "occasion-wise values", as on this example screenshot for covariates:

New manual covariates

MANUAL
DISTRIBUTION
EXTERNAL

Name
covManual1

Occasion-wise values

1#1

Covariate	Value
AGE	45
FOOD	Fed
SEX	F

2#1

Covariate	Value
AGE	45
FOOD	Fasted
SEX	F

2#2

Covariate	Value
AGE	45

CANCEL
OK

Moreover, elements defined as external tables may contain one or several columns to assign different values to different subject-occasions.

3.2.2 Subject-specific occasions

To define subject-specific occasions use an external file containing a table with columns ID, time and one or several columns for the occasions. The header names for these columns are free and are used by Simulx. The external file separator can be tab, comma or semicolon. The possible file extensions are .csv or .txt.

Below is an example of the occasions element defined after loading the external table (on the left).

ID	OCC	TIME
1	1	0
1	2	24
1	3	48
2	1	0
2	2	48
3	1	0
3	2	24
4	1	0
4	2	24
4	3	48
4	4	72
5	1	0
6	1	0
6	2	48
6	3	72

 Load external occasions

The screenshot shows the Simulx software interface with the 'Definition' tab selected. The 'Occasions' table is displayed with the following data:

ID	time	OCC
1	0	1
1	24	2
1	48	3
2	0	1
2	48	2
3	0	1
3	24	2
4	0	1
4	24	2
4	48	3
4	72	4
5	0	1
6	0	1
6	48	2
6	72	3

After defining such subject-specific occasion structure, other elements (parameters, covariates, treatments, outputs and regressors) must be common over subjects (type “manual”, “regular” or “distribution”), or can be defined with occasion-wise values as external tables only, with the same occasion structure.

3.2.3 Occasions imported from Monolix

Upon import of a Monolix run, Simulx creates an occasion element with the individual structure of occasions from the Monolix data set.

- **mlx_subjects**: a table containing the occasions and their starting times for each individual. The table has at least 3 columns: id, time, occ. Additional columns may be present in case of several levels of occasions.

3.2.4 Rules for simulating occasions

- Occasions are not simulated in Exploration: only the first occasion from the selected subject is simulated.
- If occasions are not defined, inter-occasion variability is not taken into account for the simulation of individual parameters.
- From the 2023 version on, the sampling of individual parameters takes into account the inter-occasion variability if one or several occasions are defined. In previous versions (2020 and 2021), if the structure of occasions contains a single occasion for some subject, then the simulation of individual parameters for this subject does not take into account inter-occasion variability.
- When an occasion element has been defined, in case of several replicates, the sampling method has to be ‘Keep Order’.

3.2.5 Occasions in outcomes, results and plots

Occasions are indicated as additional columns in the table of individual parameters. In the plots of individual outputs, occasions are highlighted as dashed yellow lines on hover of one the occasions from the same subject. Furthermore, all plots of results can be stratified by occasions.

Individual parameters

Sampled individual parameters and covariates

simulationGroup1

id ↕	OCC1 ↕	ka ↕	V ↕	Cl ↕
1	1	2.45	0.47	0.038
2	1	1.45	0.43	0.037
2	2	1.31	0.43	0.037
2	3	0.77	0.43	0.037
2	4	0.78	0.43	0.037
3	1	1.1	0.4	0.034
3	2	2.25	0.4	0.034
3	3	1.08	0.4	0.034
4	1	1.21	0.44	0.039
4	2	2.38	0.44	0.039

When occasions are defined, the definition of outcomes can be made by post-processing the simulation outputs by subject (one outcome value per individual) or by subject-occasion (one outcome value for each occasion of each individual). When the post-processing by subject-occasion is selected, the occasion column(s) appear(s) also in the corresponding outcome table.

outcome1

Name

outcome1

- calculate for each individual
 calculate for each occasion of each individual

Output

outputExternal1 ▾

relative to baseline (first value of output)

Output processing: average value per id ▾

Apply threshold

CANCEL

OK

3.3 Population parameters

Definition of population parameters as simulation elements allows to simulate individual parameters from probability distributions. In the mlxtran model they are:

- [INDIVIDUAL] block input parameters that are neither inputs nor outputs of the block [COVARIATE].
- [LONGITUDINAL] block input parameters that are neither individual parameters nor regressors.

POP.PARAM section in the “Definition” tab is available only if the list of population parameters from the model is not empty.

Demo projects: 3.3. population parameters

3.3.1 Overview

In the “Population parameters” tab, elements created automatically after a “new project” or an “import from Monolix/PKanalix” and elements created by the user are shown.

The buttons on the right allow to do the following actions:

- VIEW: display the content of the element (the value of the population parameters)
- EDIT: modify the content of the element. *Note:* the elements “mlx_PopUncertainSA”, “mlx_PopUncertainLin”, “mlx_TypicalUncertainSA”, and “mlx_TypicalUncertainLin” represent multidimensional distributions and cannot be edited.
- DUPLICATE: open a pop-up window for a new element with the same content as the previous element. *Note:* the elements “mlx_PopUncertainSA”, “mlx_PopUncertainLin”,

“mlx_TypicalUncertainSA”, and “mlx_TypicalUncertainLin” cannot be duplicated. Elements based on external files can also not be duplicated.

- **DELETE:** delete the element. When the deleted element is based on an external file located in <result folder>/ExternalFiles, the file itself is also deleted upon save.
- **CREATE NEW INDIV:** creates a new element “individual parameters” from the population parameters fixed effects (e.g $V = V_{pop}$). This option is available for population elements of type “manual” only.

3.3.2 New population parameters element

After loading a model, Simulx generates automatically a default population parameter element. It is a table with parameters names from the model and all entries equal to one. It helps to create a new element by just modifying the values. Clicking the button “plus” adds a new population parameter, which may be one of the three types.

- **Manual:** It is a vector and has one value for each parameter.
- **Distribution:** Parameters are a distribution law – normal, lognormal (default), logitnormal, uniform – with a typical value and a standard deviation. If the distribution is lognormal or logitnormal, sd is the standard deviation of the distribution in the Gaussian space. The typical value is the median of the population parameter distribution.

•

In the case of a lognormal distribution, in order to get the sd s_G of the distribution in the Gaussian space given a typical value of the lognormally distributed covariate μ , or given its mean m , and given its sd s , you can use the following formulae:

$$s_G = \sqrt{\ln\left(1 + \left(\frac{s}{m}\right)^2\right)} = \sqrt{\ln\left(1 + \sqrt{1 + 4\left(\frac{s}{\mu}\right)^2}\right) - \ln(2)}$$

Both formulae are equivalent if $\frac{s}{\mu} \ll 1$ (in that case $\mu \approx m$).

New population parameters from distribution

MANUAL DISTRIBUTION EXTERNAL

Name
distribution_parameter

Parameter	Distribution	Typical	sd
Tlag _{pop}	LOGNORMAL	0.8	0.1
ka _{pop}	LOGNORMAL	1	0.2
ω _{ka}	LOGNORMAL	0.1	0.1
V _{pop}	LOGNORMAL	8	0.1
ω _V	LOGNORMAL	0.3	0.1
Cl _{pop}	LOGNORMAL	2.5	0.01

CANCEL OK

- **External:** It is a file with a table that has each population parameter in a separate column.

New population parameters from external file

MANUAL DISTRIBUTION EXTERNAL

Name
external_parameter

File
ExternalFiles/simulated_popParam.csv SELECT

CANCEL OK

'simulated_popParam.csv'

pop	Tlag _{pop}	ka _{pop}	V _{pop}	beta_V_logtWt	Cl _{pop}	a	b
1	0.51	0.84	8.50	0.26	0.13	0.00	0.31
2	0.85	1.77	8.97	0.44	0.12	0.00	0.31
3	0.63	1.31	8.65	0.52	0.12	0.00	0.33

The external file can have only one column header different from the population parameters names. It indicates replicates (eg. from bootstrap or simpopmlx). All individual parameters of the same replicate come from the same population distribution.

3.3.3 Population parameters imported from Monolix

Demo projects: 1.overview/importFromMonolixsmlx

Importing a Monolix project generates automatically a population parameter element with values from the Monolix result folder.

- **mlx_Pop** contains population parameters estimated by Monolix if the POP.PARAM task results are available.

- **mlx_PopInit** contains initial estimates of the population parameters if the `mlx_pop` does not exist.
- **mlx_Typical** (NEW since 2023 version) is the same as `mlx_Pop` but with all standard deviations of random effects (omega parameters) set to 0. It enables to simulate a typical individual in terms of parameters (no unexplained variability), and still include non-typical covariates in the simulation. The variability in the sampled individual parameters will come only from sampling different covariate values. To see how this element can be used in practice, check the demo project `1.overview/importFromMonolix_CovEffectOnTypical.smlx`.

`mlx_Pop`, `mlx_PopInit` and `mlx_Typical` are vectors (single set of population parameters). If replicates are used in the Simulation tab, with these elements, the same set of population parameters will be used for all replicates.

- **mlx_PopUncertainSA** (resp. **mlx_PopUncertainLin**) enables to sample population parameters using the variance-covariance matrix of the estimates computed by Monolix if the Standard Error task (Estimation of the Fisher Information matrix) was performed by stochastic approximation (resp. by linearization). To sample several population parameter sets, this element needs to be used with replicates. In the interface, the element is displayed with a reminder of the estimated values and RSEs next to the variance-covariance matrix which is used to generate new samples. The displayed variance-covariance matrix and the sampling is done in the gaussian space (i.e we sample $\{\log(V_{pop}), \log(CI_{pop}), \omega_V, \omega_{CI}, b\}$ from a multivariate normal distribution, if V and CI have a lognormal distribution). The sampled values are then converted to the non-gaussian space. For omega and error parameters, negative samples values are rejected, they are thus sampled from truncated normal distributions. This element cannot be modified nor duplicated.

mlx_PopUncertainSA [read-only]

	Estimated value	R.S.E. (%)	Uncertainty variance-covariance matrix in Gaussian space							
ka_pop	1.53264	20.3	0.0412507							
V_pop	0.455504	4.48	0.00103617	0.00201065						
Cl_pop	0.0401724	8.40	-0.000608504	-0.000385393	0.00705529					
omega_Cl	0.270623	24.3	-0.000139782	-0.0000583648	-0.00001328	0.00431548				
omega_V	0.126281	27.8	0.000301576	0.000107252	-0.0000817639	-0.000245008	0.00123293			
omega_ka	0.671055	24.0	0.00151641	-0.000149856	0.00018779	0.0000541658	0.0000148019	0.0259383		
a	0.43328	34.8	0.00165727	-0.000268677	0.000255753	0.000276002	0.000407877	0.000369118	0.0227485	
b	0.0542595	55.1	-0.000384453	0.0000472563	-0.0000278134	-0.0000572644	-0.000101725	-0.000136792	-0.00422552	0.000892541

CLOSE

3.4 Individual parameters

In the mlxtran model, the following parameters are recognized as individual parameters:

- Only the [LONGITUDINAL] block is present: all parameters of the input list, except those defined as regressors.
- Both the [LONGITUDINAL] and [INDIVIDUAL] blocks are present: parameters defined in the DEFINITION section of the [INDIVIDUAL] block.

Individual parameters can be used in the tab “Exploration” and “Simulation”. An individual parameter definition is either a vector, which has one value per parameter, or a table, where each line correspond to a value of a different individual.

Demo projects: 3.4. individual parameters

3.4.1 Overview

In the “Individual parameters” tab, elements created automatically after a “new project” or an “import from Monolix/PKanalix” and elements created by the user are shown.

The buttons on the right allow to do the following actions:

- **VIEW:** display the content of the element (the value of the individual parameters)
- **EDIT:** modify the content of the element.
- **DUPLICATE:** open a pop-up window for a new element with the same content as the previous element. *Note:* elements based on external files cannot be duplicated.
- **DELETE:** delete the element. When the deleted element is based on an external file located in <result folder>/ExternalFiles, the file itself is also deleted upon save.
- **CREATE NEW POP:** creates a new element “population parameters” from the individual parameters (e.g $V_{pop} = V$). The betas (covariate effects), omegas (standard deviation of the random effects), correlation and error parameters are set to zero. This option is available for individual elements of type “manual” only, which contain a single set of individual parameters.

3.4.2 New individual parameters elements

After loading a model, Simulx generates automatically a default individual parameter element called "IndivParameters" with all values set to 1. This element can be modified (button EDIT). New elements can be created with the button "+". Two different types of individual parameter elements are available:

- **Manual:** One value per parameter to type in. The required parameters are automatically listed.

New manual individual parameters

MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name
indivManual1

Parameter	Value
ka	1.4
V	3.6
Cl	0.25

CANCEL OK

- **External:** An external text file with either:
 - A single row and one column per parameter. The headers must correspond to the parameter names.

ka	V	Cl
1.62	7.67	0.11
 - Several rows, a first column with header "id", occasion columns (optional) and one column per parameter. The headers must correspond to the parameter names, and to the occasion names if applicable.

id	ka	V	Cl
1	1.62	7.67	0.11
2	0.87	8.34	0.13
3	0.96	8.47	0.11
4	1.51	5.09	0.072
5	1.83	11.52	0.18

The external file can be tab, comma or semicolon separated. Available file extension are: .csv or .txt.

New individual parameters from external file

MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name

indivExternal1

File

...s/ /external_indivparam.csv SELECT

CANCEL OK

3.4.3 Individual parameters elements imported from Monolix

Upon import of a Monolix run, several individual parameters elements are created automatically:

- **mlx_IndivInit:** *[when POP.PARAM task has not run]*a vector of individual parameters corresponding to the initial values of the population parameters in Monolix, i.e with covariate betas and random effects set to zero. For instance, $V=V_{pop,ini}$
- **mlx_PopIndiv:** *[when POP.PARAM task has run]*a vector of individual parameters corresponding to the population parameters estimated by Monolix, i.e with covariate betas and random effects set to zero. For instance, $V=V_{pop,est}$
- **mlx_PopIndivCov:** *[when POP.PARAM task has run and covariates are defined in the Monolix data set]*a table of individual parameters corresponding to the population parameters and the impact of the covariates, but random effects set to zero. For instance, $V=V_{pop} \times (WT70)\beta V, WT$
- **mlx_EBEs:** *[when EBEs task has run]* a table of individual parameters corresponding to the EBEs (conditional mode) estimated by Monolix (as displayed in Monolix Results > Indiv. param > Cond. mode.)
- **mlx_CondMean:** *[when COND. DISTRIB. task has run]* a table of individual parameters corresponding to the conditional mean estimated by Monolix (as displayed in Monolix Results > Indiv. param > Cond. mean.)
- **mlx_CondDistSample:** *[when COND. DISTRIB. task has run]* a table of individual parameters corresponding to one sample of the conditional distribution (first replicate of the Monolix result file IndividualParameters/simulatedIndividualParameters.txt).

3.5 Covariates

Values to use for simulation should be defined for covariates used in the statistical model, if the simulation is based on population parameters. In this case, new individual parameters are simulated from the population distributions and the covariate values. Several covariate elements can be defined in Definition, but only one covariate element should be used per simulation group in Simulation. No covariate element can be used in Exploration, since only individual parameters are used in Exploration.

Demo projects: 3.2. covariates

3.5.1 New covariate element

Several types of covariate elements can be defined:

- **Manual:** It is a vector that has one or several dosing times with identical or different amounts. The + and - buttons allow to add and remove doses.

New manual covariates

MANUAL
DISTRIBUTION
EXTERNAL

Name
covTypical

Covariate	Value
AGE	35
RACE	Asian ▾
SEX	F ▾

CANCEL OK

- **Distribution:** The covariates are described with distribution laws. When this type of element is used for simulation, new covariate values are simulated from the distributions. For continuous covariates, the distribution can be normal, lognormal or logitnormal with a mean and sd, or uniform with two interval limits. If the distribution is lognormal or logitnormal, sd is the standard deviation of the distribution in the Gaussian space. The typical value is the median of the covariate distribution.

New covariates from distribution

MANUAL
DISTRIBUTION
EXTERNAL

Name
covDistributionsAsian

Continuous covariates

Covariate	Distribution	Typical	sd
AGE	NORMAL -	45	10

Categorical covariates

Covariate	Category	Probability	Auto fill
RACE	Asian	1.0	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Black	0	<input type="checkbox"/>
	White	0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SEX	F	0.5	<input type="checkbox"/>
	M	0.5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

CANCEL OK

In the case of a lognormal distribution, in order to get the sd s_G of the distribution in the Gaussian space given a typical value of the lognormally distributed covariate μ , or given its mean m , and given its sd s , you can use the following formulae:

$$s_G = \sqrt{\ln\left(1 + \left(\frac{s}{m}\right)^2\right)} = \sqrt{\ln\left(1 + \sqrt{1 + 4\left(\frac{s}{\mu}\right)^2}\right) - \ln(2)}$$

Both formulae are equivalent if $\frac{s}{\mu} \ll 1$ (in that case $\mu \approx m$).

For categorical covariates, the probability for each category can be defined in $[0,1]$. The sum of probabilities over all categories must be 1, and an "auto fill" option allows to automatically fill one or several of the categories to satisfy this rule.

- **External:** An external text file with columns id (optional), occasions (optional), and one column per covariate (mandatory). The occasions headers must correspond to the occasion names defined in the occasion element. When id and occasion columns are present, then they must be the first columns. When the id column is not present, the covariate is considered 'common', i.e the same for all individuals. Categorical covariate values must correspond to the categories defined in the model (block [COVARIATE]). The external file can be tab, comma or semicolon separated. The possible file extensions are .csv or .txt.

3.5.2 Covariate elements imported from Monolix

Importing a Monolix project generates automatically a covariate element based on the Monolix data set.

- **mlx_Cov**: contains covariate information for each individual. The table is saved as external table in the result folder of the project. This table contains a column id, and one column per covariate. If there are occasions in the Monolix project, it also contains one or several columns for the occasion levels.
- **mlx_CovDist**: element of type “distribution” with typical values, standard deviations and probabilities calculated on the individuals of the Monolix project. No correlation between the covariates is assumed. In the 2020 version, all continuous covariates are assumed to follow a normal distribution. In the 2021 version, continuous covariates having only strictly positive values in the Monolix data set are assumed to follow a log-normal distribution, and the others are set with a normal distribution.

3.6 Treatments

Treatments definition includes times and amounts of the doses applied to the model. Treatments are applied to the model via the macros depot(), iv() or oral() used in the model. Moreover, treatments definition has an administration id, which allows to choose to which macros used in the model the doses are applied.

When used in “Exploration” or “Simulation”, several treatment elements can be combined together. For instance, a loading dose of type manual followed by maintenance doses of type regular, or a oral dose with adm=2 and an iv dose with adm=1.

The units of time and amounts must be consistent with the units of the Monolix data set or with the model definition when starting from scratch.

Demo projects: 3.1. treatments

3.6.1 New treatments element

Several types of elements can be defined:

- **Regular**: It is used for regularly spaced dosing times with a unique amount and a unique infusion duration or rate (optional). It requires the start time, inter-dose interval, number of doses, and amount.

New treatment with regular schedule

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name Adm

trtRegular1 1

Values

Start time	Interdose interval	Nb doses	Amount
0	0.1	1	100

Repeat

Non-compliance probability

CANCEL OK

- **Manual:** It is a vector that has one or several dosing times with identical or different amounts. The + and – buttons allow to add and remove doses.

New treatment with manual schedule

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name Adm

trtManual1 1

Values

Time	Amount
0	10
24	5

Repeat

Non-compliance probability

CANCEL OK

- **External:** An external text file with columns id (optional), occasions (optional), time (mandatory), amount (mandatory), tinf or rate (optional), washout (optional). The occasions headers must

correspond to the occasion names defined in the occasion element. When id and occasion columns are present, then they must be the first columns. When the id column is not present, the treatment is considered 'common', i.e the same for all individuals. The washout column can contain zeros (no washout) or ones (washout).

id	time	amount	tinf
1	0	85.3	0.5
1	12	85.3	0.5
1	24	85.3	0.5
2	0	79	0.5
2	12	79	0.5
2	24	79	0.5

The external file can be tab, comma or semicolon separated. The possible file extensions are .csv, .txt., .xls, .xlsx, .sas2bdat and .xpt.

New treatment from external file

REGULAR | MANUAL | **EXTERNAL**

Name: trtExternal1 Adm: 1

File: ... /ExternalFiles/external_treatment_byAge.csv SELECT

Non-compliance probability

CANCEL OK

3.6.1.1 Additional options:

- **adm**: [all] the administration id of the treatment element (integer). The doses of a treatment element with adm=2 apply to all model macros defined with adm=2, for instance oral(adm=2, ka). Macros used in the model without adm are implicitly defined with adm=1.

New treatment with manual schedule

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name: trtManual1 Adm: 2

Values

Time	Amount
0	1

Repeat

Non-compliance probability

CANCEL OK

- **infusion duration or rate:** [regular/manual] the list button on the right allows to display the infusion column. The value is understood as either a duration or a rate, depending on the chosen option.

New treatment with regular schedule

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name: trtRegular1 Adm: 1

Values

Start time	Interdose interval	Nb doses	Amount	Infusion
0	0.1	1	100	1

Repeat

Non-compliance probability

CANCEL OK

- **washout:** [manual] the list button on the right allows to display the washout column. When the washout tick-box is selected, a washout is applied just before the dose. A washout means that all model variables are reset to their initial values.

New treatment with manual schedule

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name: trtManual1 Adm: 2

Values

Time	Amount	Washout	
0	10	<input type="checkbox"/>	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px;"> Infusion <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Washout </div>
48	10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	- +

Repeat

Non-compliance probability

CANCEL OK

- **repeat:** [regular/manual] This option allows to repeat a base pattern of doses several times (number of repetitions), with a given periodicity (cycle duration). In the example below, the dose is given on the three first days of the week, for 4 weeks. The doses on the first week are defined using the type 'regular' with three doses and an inter-dose interval of 1 day. This base pattern is then repeated every 7 days (cycle duration), 3 times (number of repetitions) in addition to the first week.

trtRegular1*

regular ▾

Name: trtRegular1 Adm: 1 ▾

Values

Start time	Interdose interval	Nb doses	Amount
0	1	3	100

Repeat

Cycle duration: 7 ▾
Number of repetitions: 3 ▾

Non-compliance probability

CANCEL OK

- **scale amount by a covariate:** *[regular/manual]* This option allows to personalize the dose given to different individuals by scaling the dose amount with the selected covariate and with a specific intercept for the linear relationship:

$$\text{Scaled amount} = \text{Amount} \times \text{Selected covariate} + \text{Intercept}.$$

New treatment with regular schedule

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name: trtRegular1 Adm: 1

Values

Start time	Interdose interval	Nb doses	Amount
0	0.1	1	100

Repeat

Scale amount by a covariate

Covariate: AGE Intercept: 0

Non-compliance probability

CANCEL OK

- non-compliance probability:** [all] The doses defined are applied to the model with a given probability $(1-p)$, where p is the probability to miss a dose. This allows to simulate non-adherence to a treatment. Which doses are applied and which are not rely on the random number seed defined in the project settings to ensure reproducibility.

New treatment with regular schedule

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name: trtRegular1 Adm: 1

Values

Start time	Interdose interval	Nb doses	Amount
0	1	28	100

Repeat

Non-compliance probability

Probability to miss each dose

0.15

CANCEL OK

3.6.2 Treatment elements imported from Monolix

Importing a Monolix project generates automatically a treatment element for each administration id defined in the Monolix data set.

- **mlx_Admx**: contains treatment information for admID=X for each individual including: dosing times, amount, infusion duration or rates (optional) and washouts (optional, from EVID=3 or EVID=4 in Monolix). The Monolix data set column SS is replaced by additional dose lines as defined by the Monolix setting “number of steady-state doses”. The ADDL column is also replaced by additional dose lines.

3.7 Outputs

Outputs of simulations are variables from the longitudinal model of continuous, discrete or event type. There are two outputs groups:

- **Main outputs**
 - Model predictions defined in the structural model as the “output” (eg. Cc).
 - Observations (model predictions with an error model) defined in the observation model (eg. y1).
 - All variables defined in the structural model as “tables” (eg. AUC).
- **Intermediate outputs**

- Variables computed in the structural model and not listed as an “output” or “table” in the OUTPUT block (eg. amount in the peripheral compartment, time varying clearance).
- Regressors.
- Variables defined with the “additional lines” in the model definition.

Loading a model automatically generates the “main outputs”. Model predictions and tables are on a default time grid. If a project is built from scratch, then model observations use also the default time grid. Otherwise, in case of project imported from Monolix, they are on a grid given by the measurement times from the Monolix dataset.

Demos: 3.5.outputs, 7.noncontinuous_outputs

3.7.1 New output element

Outputs correspond to **output variables**, which can be written or selected from the list (green frame).

New output

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name
outputRegular1

Output variable
y1

Main outputs ▾
Intermediate outputs ▾

Start time	Interval	Final time
0	1	100

CANCEL OK

It is possible to have different outputs of the same variable. For example, one output shows the time evolution over a treatment period and another gives a value at the end of treatment to define an endpoint. However, charts display these outputs on one plot with merged time grids.

There are three output types.

- **Regular:** It is a vector on a regular time grid (start time, step, final time, (occ)) common for all subjects.

New output

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name
outCc

Output variable
Cc

Main outputs Intermediate outputs

Start time	Interval	Final time
0	0.01	120

CANCEL OK

- **Manual:** It is a vector with manually defined list of time points (use “space” to separate them) common for all subjects.

New manual output

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name
outCc_manual

Output variable
Cc

Main outputs Intermediate outputs

Times

0 × 2 × 4 × 6 × 8 × 12 × 24 × 48 ×

CANCEL OK

- **External:** It is a file with a table that has: a mandatory column “time” for time points, an optional column “id” (in the absence of the “id” column the time grid is equal for all subjects), and an optional column “occ” for occasions.

outputExternal1 [read-only]

Output: Cc

ID	OCC	time
1	1	0
1	1	1
1	1	2
1	1	3
1	1	4
1	1	5
1	1	6
1	1	7
1	1	8
1	1	9
1	1	10
1	1	11
1	1	12
1	1	13
1	1	14
1	1	15
1	1	16

CLOSE

3.7.1.1 Occasions

By default, the regular and manual output types apply to all subject-occasions. If occasions are common among all individuals, then an option “**occasion-wise values**” is available. In this case each occasion has a separate time grid.

New output

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Name
outputRegular1

Output variable
Y

Main outputs ▾

Occasion-wise values

1

Start time	Interval	Final time
0	1	100

2

Start time	Interval	Final time
100	1	200

CANCEL OK

3.7.1.2 Time-to-event outputs

Time limits (start time and final time) define the observation period during which the survival curve is computed. The final time thus defines the censoring time. Intermediate times are ignored. The time grid must be the same for all individuals. If an external file is provided with different start and end values for each individual, the events will be simulated on the same observation period for all individuals, using the min(start time) and max(end time) over all individuals.

3.7.2 Outputs imported from Monolix

Importing a Monolix project generates automatically output elements for the “main output” variables.

- **mlx_observationName** (eg. mlx_y1, mlx_y2): For each output of the observation model it is a table with ids and observation times corresponding to the measurements read from the dataset.
- **mlx_predictionName** (eg. mlx_Cc, mlx_R): For each continuous output of the structural model it is a vector with a uniform time grid with 250 points on the same time interval as the observations.
- **mlx_TableName**: For each variable of the structural model defined as table in the OUTPUT section it is a vector with a uniform time grid with 250 points on the same time interval as the observations.

3.8 Regressors

Definition of regressors elements is available only if the mlxtran model used in a Simulx project uses it. In this case, specification of regressors is mandatory. All regressors used in a model are displayed in one element as separate columns.

Regressors names

- If a Monolix project was imported, then regressors names come from a dataset – headers of columns tagged as regressor.
- When building a project from scratch, regressor names are equal to names used in a model.

Demo projects: 3.6.regressors

3.8.1 Create new regressors element

There are three types of regressor elements:

- **Manual:** It is a vector with manually defined time points and values, which are common for all individuals.

Example: parameter – covariate relationship with the covariate as a regressor

New manual regressor

MANUAL
EXTERNAL

Name
PCA_REG

Time	PCA			
0	9	▲▼	▲▼	–
1	10	▲▼	▲▼	–
3	12	▲▼	▲▼	–
6	15	▲▼	▲▼	–
12	21	▲▼	▲▼	–
24	33	▲▼	▲▼	–
36	45	▲▼	▲▼	– +

CANCEL
OK

- **External:** Regressors definition is a table with the following mandatory columns: “time” for time points and “regressor_name” for regressor values. Optionally, it can have a column “id”. In the

absence of the “id” column, the time grid is equal for all individuals and occasions (if defined in the model).

Example: PK-PD model with PK measurements as a regressor

external_Cc [read-only]

ID	time	Cc
1	0.5	3.22
1	1	5.15
1	2	6.52
1	3	6.85
1	5	5.5
1	7	4.75
1	9	3.94
1	12	2.73
1	15	2.08
1	18	1.49
1	24	0.76
2	0.5	2.81
2	1	4.6
2	2	6.5
2	3	7.04
2	5	6.56
2	7	5.8
2	9	4.84

CLOSE

- Distribution:** The regressors are described via distribution laws which define their value across individuals. When a distribution is used, the regressor is considered as constant over time. When used in the simulation, new regressor values are sampled from the defined distributions for each individual. The distribution for each regressor can be normal, lognormal or logitnormal with a mean and sd, or uniform with a lower and an upper and bound. If the distribution is lognormal or logitnormal, sd is the standard deviation of the distribution in the Gaussian space, i.e $V_{reg} = V_{typical} \times e^{\eta}$ with $\eta \sim N(0, sd^2)$. The typical value is the median of the distribution. Defining a regressor element as a distribution is convenient for sequential PD model where individual PK parameters have been defined as regressors. After exporting the project to Simulx, new individual PK parameters can be sampled by defining the regressor element for the individual PK parameters as a distribution. Note that correlation terms are not possible.

regDistrib_PKparameters*

DISTRIBUTION

Name
regDistrib_PKparameters

Regressors defined with distributions are constant over time

Regressor	Distribution	Typical	sd	Limits
Tlag	UNIFORM ▾		0	1.6
ka	LOGNORMAL ▾	1.28	0.45	
V	LOGNORMAL ▾	7.91	0.21	
Cl	LOGNORMAL ▾	0.13	0.29	

CANCEL
OK

3.8.1.1 Interpolation between defined values

Regressors are defined over time for a finite number of time points. In between those time points, the regressor value can be interpolated in two different ways:

- **last value carried forward:** if we have defined reg_A at time t_A and reg_B at time t_B
 - for $t < t_A$, $reg(t) = reg_A$ [first defined value is used]
 - for $t_A \leq t < t_B$, $reg(t) = reg_A$ [previous value is used]
 - for $t \geq t_B$, $reg(t) = reg_B$ [previous value is used]
- **linear interpolation:**
 - for $t < t_A$, $reg(t) = reg_A$ [first defined value is used]
 - for $t_A \leq t < t_B$, $reg(t) = reg_A + (t - t_A) \frac{reg_B - reg_A}{t_B - t_A}$ [linear interpolation is used]
 - for $t \geq t_B$, $reg(t) = reg_B$ [previous value is used]

This can be chosen in the DEFINITION > REGRESSORS tab and applies to all defined regressor elements.

regressor_distribution_seqPD.smlx [demo] - Simulx - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Definition Exploration Simulation

Regressors

Regressors settings

Last carried forward Linear interpolation

Regressors [VIEW] [EDIT] [DUPLICATE] [DELETE]

regDistrib_PKparameters [VIEW] [EDIT] [DUPLICATE] [DELETE]

+

MODEL

OCCASIONS

POP.PARAMS

INDIV.PARAMS

COVARIATES

TREATMENTS

OUTPUTS

REGRESSORS

3.8.2 Regressors imported from Monolix

Importing a Monolix project generates automatically regressors element with regressors names from the dataset:

- **mlx_Reg**: contains Ids, times and regressors values read from the dataset. Occasions are included if any.
- **mlx_RegDist**: *(created only if all regressors of each subject and each occasion are constant over time)* element of type "distribution" with typical values, standard deviations and probabilities calculated on the individuals of the Monolix project. No correlation between the regressors is assumed. Regressors having only strictly positive values in the Monolix dataset are assumed to follow a log-normal distribution, and the others are set with a normal distribution.

4 Exploration

The **Exploration** tab is the second tab in the interface of Simulx. It simulates a typical individual to explore a model by interactively changing treatments and model parameters.

4.1 Predicted individual

In Exploration, the predictions are based on only:

- one set of individual parameters (mandatory),
- one or several treatments (optional) for one individual,
- one or several outputs (mandatory) with a single vector of measurement times per output,
- one set of regressor values, only if regressors are present in the model (mandatory).

These elements are selected in the left panel.

Thus an element of type "Individual parameters" must be selected, and it is not possible to select an element of type "Population parameters".

If a selected element is a table containing several sets of individual values, then the first row in the table is selected by default, and the "ID" field on top of the plot in the middle allows to select the row in the table corresponding to a particular ID.

[Demo: 1.overview/importFromMonolix_resimulateProject.smlx]

This field is highlighted on the figure below, corresponding to a project that comes from a Monolix project imported into Simulx:

- the individual parameters come from the table `mlx_EBEs` contains the EBEs estimates,
 - the treatment `mlx_Adml` contains the individual doses imported from the dataset used in Monolix,
 - the output `mlx_Cc` contains a single vector of regular measurement times for Cc, the structural model output.

Thus changing the "ID" value will change the row read from the two tables `mlx_EBEs` and `mlx_Adml`.

4.2 Exploration groups

- **3.exploration/PK_exploration.smlx**

Treatment can contain several elements in different exploration groups (explorationGroup1 and explorationGroup2 below), or combined within an exploration group (as in the explorationGroup2 below). Each exploration group produces a separate prediction. If an exploration group contains several treatments, then the prediction corresponds to the treatments given together to the same individual.

In the demo shown below, there are two exploration groups: the first corresponds to the treatment element singleDose_150, while the second corresponds to the combination of loadingDose_100 and multipleDoses_50. Two prediction curves in different colors represent these two exploration groups in the plot.

4.3 Exploration outputs

- **3.exploration/TMDD_exploration.smlx**

Only non-random element of type “Output” can be selected in Exploration, thus they should:

- correspond to continuous variables (consequently excluding time-to-event, categorical or count variables)
 - not include a residual error model in their definition.

By default, there is a separate plot for each selected output, as shown below. This can be changed in the exploration settings, where it is possible to select variables to display at each chart. If the scenario contains several output elements based on the same variable (but on a different grid), then they are plotted on the same plot with merged grids.

4.4 Interactive modification of parameter values or dosing regimen

- **3.exploration/PK_exploration.smlx**

The right panel of the Exploration tab has three sub-tabs: PARAMETERS, SETTINGS and DATA OVERLAY. The parameter values and dosing regimens can be modified there to explore in real-time their impact on the model dynamics.

The figure below shows the PARAMETERS sub-tab with the model parameters (Parameters) and treatment parameters (Treatment) sections (highlighted in blue). The parameter values can be changed via the small arrows, sliders or by entering new values with the keyboard. The “reset” button , are shown as dashed lines.

Reference curves. In the figure below, the section "Treatment" – highlighted in green – shows the elements from the treatment element: multipleDoses_50. All its parameters, such as start time, interdose interval, number of doses and dose amount can be modified. Current values can be set as a reference by clicking on the button – highlighted in purple. The reference curves are listed on the right panel – highlighter in blue – and are represented by dashed lines in the plot.

Several reference curves can be created and each successive one is displayed with a corresponding number. The icon removes the reference curve from the list and from the plot. Hovering on a reference line (#1 in the figure below) highlights in yellow the corresponding reference curve, as seen in the figure below. Stroke dash-array defines the pattern of dashes and gaps of a curve.

4.5 Defining new parameter or treatment elements

- **3.exploration/PK_exploration.smlx**

Exploration allows to create new elements from the current values by clicking on the icon . In the parameter section it creates the Individual parameters element, while in the treatment section it creates the Treatment element.

A window to define a new element opens automatically. For the parameters, the individual parameter element is of type "manual" and by default replaces the previously selected element in the Exploration scenario. Untick the corresponding checkbox (blue mark in the figure below) to only define a new element – without the replacement.

Parameters

ka
0.7

Cl
2

V1
5

Q
0.8

V2
4

New manual individual parameters

MANUAL

Name
indivManual1

Parameter	Value
ka	0.7
Cl	2
V1	5
Q	0.8
V2	4

Replace in exploration: Parameters

CANCEL OK

A new treatment element can be set as a regular or manual type – depending on the definition in the exploration. By default it replaces the treatment element used in the exploration, but it can be also added as the new treatment to a new exploration group.

Treatment

< From: multipleDoses_50

Start time	Interdose interval	Nb doses	Amount
12	12	5	50

Create new treatment element

New treatment with regular schedule

REGULAR

Name
trtRegular1

Adm
1

Values

Start time	Interdose interval	Nb doses	Amount
12	12	5	50

Repeat

Non-compliance probability

Add to exploration group

Replace in exploration: multipleDoses_50

CANCEL OK

4.6 Overlay of the observed data

Continuous data can be overlaid on the prediction plots.

4.6.1 Load

Data overlay sub-tab in the Exploration tab allows to load a data file. Click on the BROWSE button and select a file. It has to be a Monolix compatible dataset and has to contain columns that correspond to: subject identifier (tag: ID), time of observations (tag: TIME) and observation values (tag: OBSERVATION). It is possible to have multiple observations to be displayed in different charts. In this case, the loaded data file need to contain the column with observation id to distinguish different observations.

After tagging columns, click on the ACCEPT button to load the data file. Displayed observations can be filtered (green frame) using categorical covariates present and correctly tagged in the loaded file. In the figure below, ticked box next to a value "0" means that in the plot there are only observations for individuals with SEX = 0. To change the tagging, click on the VIEW/EDIT button (blue frame).

When a Simulx project is built by importing a Monolix project, then the dataset – used in the Monolix project – is set automatically in the DATA OVERLAY sub-tab.

4.6.2 Display

Observed data are displayed automatically as “dots” if there is only one output in the Exploration scenario and the data file contains only one observation type. Otherwise – in case of several different outputs or multiple observations types – data display has to be selected in the SETTINGS sub-tab.

In the data – charts grid, see the figure below, observation data are listed in rows. Numerical order is applied if the observation identifiers in the data file are integers, eg. data_1, data_2, ...; or alphabetical order if the observation identifiers are strings, eg. data_PD, data_PK, as in the figure below. Charts are in columns. To display data on a chart, click on the drop-down menu of in the appropriate grid cell and select “dots” or “lines”.

4.6.3 Link to individual selection

If any of the exploration scenario elements contains a table with several individuals, then the simulated individual can be selected in the PARAMETERS sub-tab, see [individual prediction description](#) section for details. To link the observed data to the selected individual, enable the toggle “Link to individual selection”. Only data corresponding to the selected individual will be displayed on charts. The option “Link to individual selection” only appears if the list of ids found in the data set and in the elements selected for the simulation are the same.

It is also possible to display one or several individuals selected from the dataset, which may or may not be linked to the simulated individual. This option is available in the DATA OVERLAY sub-tab, in the “Selection” section. In the example below, selection contains a range of IDs between 15 and 42 and only observed data corresponding to these individuals are overlaid on the chart.

4.7 Sending elements to simulation

The button “Send elements to simulation” sends all elements selected in the Exploration to the scenario definition in the tab Simulation. Exploration groups are turned into simulation groups with a default size of 1 individual per group.

4.8 Plots settings

The panel “Settings” can be used to control plots features, such as the scale of the curves displayed on each plot and axis limits. The x-axis is common for all charts, while the y-axis can be specified independently for each chart.

In the following figure, two variables Cc and E are displayed on separate charts. They have the same x-axis limits – blue frame. The y-axis is specified for each chart: user limits 0-60 on the chart – 1, and automatic limits on the chart – 2 – green frame.

4.9 Exporting plots

The "export" button on top of the plots can be used to save the plots as an image in the result folder. Two image formats are available: PNG and SVG (Scalable Vector Graphics).

5 Simulation

5.1 Overview

The main goal of Simulx is to perform simulations of clinical trials. In other words, it simulates a population of individuals, in one or several groups, using different scenarios. It gives the last step of the modeling and simulation workflow, after model building in Monolix for instance.

There are two tasks in the simulation tab: SIMULATION that generates outputs, and OUTCOMES & ENDPOINTS – a post-processing task – that uses the simulation outputs to calculate outcomes (one per individual) and endpoints (summary over all individuals of a group). In addition, running the tasks produces and immediate feedback thanks to the automatically generated RESULTS and PLOTS.

5.1.1 Simulations of clinical trials

- Simulation scenario – Building a simulation scenario takes place in the dedicated section “Simulation” and includes selecting simulation elements, creating groups for comparison and choosing sampling options.
- Outcomes and endpoints – Outcomes & Endpoints are below the “Simulations” section. Outcomes represent a post-processing of the simulation outputs for each individual. Endpoints summarize the outcome values over all individuals, for each simulation group and for each replicate. It is a separate task, so it does not require re-running the entire simulation after a modification.
- Results – Results are in a dedicated tab as copyable tables. They include individual and output values, outcome&endpoint analysis and statistical group comparison.
- Plots – All simulation outputs, defined outcomes and endpoints are displayed on separate plots as individual outputs and distributions. In addition, plot settings, stratification options and charts preferences are available at hand in the right panel of the interface.

The screenshot displays the Simulx software interface. At the top, there is a menu bar with 'Project', 'Settings', 'Export', and 'Help'. Below this is a navigation bar with 'Definition', 'Exploration', 'Simulation' (highlighted), 'Results', and 'Plots'. The main area is divided into several sections:

- Tasks:** Contains three buttons: 'SIMULATION' (orange), 'OUTCOMES & ENDPOINTS' (grey), and 'RUN' (dark blue).
- Simulation:**
 - Options: 'Single simulation' (selected) and 'Replicates'.
 - Checkbox: 'Same individuals among groups'.
 - Sampling method: 'li'.
 - Group size: '50'.
 - Parameters: 'mix_Pop'.
 - Treatments: 'BID_3mg' and 'OD_6mg'.
 - Outputs: 'R_14days'.
- Outcomes & endpoints:**
 - Outcomes: 'efficacy_Rbelow50'.
 - Endpoint: 'Percent true'.
 - Group comparison: Toggle switch.
 - Reference group: 'trt_BID3mg'.

5.1.2 Order of events

There are prioritization rules in place in case of various event types occurring at the same time. So, the order of row numbers in the data set is not important, and same is true for the order of administration and empty/reset macros in model files.

The sequence of events will always be the following:

1. regressors are updated,
2. reset done by EVID=3 or EVID=4 is performed,
3. dose is administered,
4. empty/reset done by macros is performed,
5. observation is made.

The behavior is consistent between Monolix and Simulx.

5.2 Building a simulation scenario

Simulx allows to **interactively build a simulation scenario** using simulation elements defined in the “Definition” tab and additional options available in the interface. It is done in the Simulations tab – Simulation section – which contains:

- List of **simulation elements**, which can be shared between groups or set as group specific.
- Flexible **group definition** with drop-down menus for selecting group specific elements and with editable group names.
- Option to run a single simulation or **replicates**.
- Different **sampling options** such as using subjects with the same individual parameters or drawing individuals from table type elements with different methods.

To run a scenario, just click on the button SIMULATION in the tasks section. When importing a Monolix project, Simulx automatically sets the scenario re-simulating the Monolix project.

5.2.1 Simulation scenario elements

List of simulation elements contains: group size, parameters, treatments, outputs and, if used in a model, covariates and regressors. To select an element from already defined elements, use a drop-down menu available after clicking on the currently selected element. To edit a selected element, click on the icon to open a “New element” pop-up window in the Definition tab.

5.2.1.1 Mandatory elements

- **Group size** corresponds to the number of individuals in a group.
- **Parameters** can be chosen from POP, PARAM, or INDIV, PARAM, elements in the Definition. When Individual parameters are selected, then the covariate element disappears and new section to set the error model parameters becomes available.

Parameter	value
a	1
b	1

- **Outputs** correspond to one or more variables to be computed and displayed in plots and results. When importing a project from Monolix, by default all observation outputs (if defined in a model) are automatically selected, otherwise only the last defined model output.
- **Covariates** are available in two situations: selected treatments use a covariate scaling or individual parameters model uses covariates and population parameters are selected as an element in the Parameters.
- **Regressor** is available only if it is used is a model.

5.2.1.2 Optional elements

- **Treatment** can be one element or a combination of several treatment elements.
- **Occasions** are optional even if defined in a model, but are mandatory if any occasion-dependent element is selected in a scenario.

Simulx automatically assigns default elements: the last one from the definition list of each category or specific default “mlx_” types after importing a Monolix, see here for details. It is not possible to remove in the Definition tab an element currently used in a simulation. However, it might not be possible to run a simulation if any of the mandatory elements was removed. For instance, deleting occasions element removes automatically all occasion-dependent elements even if used in a simulation.

5.2.2 Simulation scenario with groups

Groups allows to build a scenario with population having different characteristics, such as parameters, regressors, covariates, different treatments and/or different simulation outputs. Moreover, groups can have different number of individuals to compare clinical trial of different sizes.

To *create a new group* click on the “plus” button, use the arrows to move elements from “shared” part to group section (or vice versa) and select specific element for each group. Each simulation element can be **shared between groups** or can be a **group specific**.

To edit a group name click next to it. In the Plots tab, figures for different groups appear in the same order as they are defined in the Simulation tab, not in the alphabetical order. To remove a group click “x” under the group name.

- Each new group is by default a copy of the previous one (eg. group 3 is a copy of group 2).
- Population and individual parameters can not be used in different groups simultaneously.

5.2.2.1 Examples:

1. [Demo 5.simulation: simulationGroups_treatment]: Simulation of three groups with three different oral dose levels: low (trt_1), medium (trt_5) and high dose (trt_10). Groups sizes, parameters, covariates and outputs are shared (the same) between the groups, while treatment is group specific.

- [Demo 5.simulation: simulationGroups_ethnicGroups]: Simulation of two groups with different ethnicity, which affects the bioavailability. In this case, “covariates” simulation element is group specific with: “caucasian” modality for the first group and “asian” for the second group.

5.2.3 Simulation scenario with replicates

By default, Simulx simulates one clinical trial. When the option “replicates” is selected, then Simulx simulate the scenario several times.

- If population parameters are vectors (user-defined or imported from a Monolix project), then all replicates have the same population parameters.
- If population parameters are of a distribution type, then Simulx samples one set of population parameters for each replicate.
- If population parameters are given as an external table with several population parameters sets, for instance from the simpopmlx function, then each replicate uses one set of population parameters with the order of the appearance in the table.

Tables in the results tab display information for all replicates.

The screenshot shows the 'Results' tab in Simulx, specifically the 'ENDPOINTS [TABLE]' view for 'Efficacy'. The table is organized into three columns for endpoints: OD, BID, and TID. Each endpoint column has sub-columns for 'rep', 'percentTrue', and 'totalTrue'. The first column (rep) is highlighted with a blue selection box. The 'Display' panel on the right shows 'Efficacy' selected and '3 items selected'.

OD			BID			TID		
rep	percentTrue	totalTrue	rep	percentTrue	totalTrue	rep	percentTrue	totalTrue
1	21.43	9	1	66.67	28	1	78.57	33
2	9.52	4	2	52.38	22	2	73.81	31
3	21.43	9	3	57.14	24	3	71.43	30
4	19.05	8	4	52.38	22	4	88.1	37
5	14.29	6	5	64.29	27	5	71.43	30
6	9.52	4	6	52.38	22	6	88.1	37
7	16.67	7	7	59.52	26	7	83.33	35
8	9.52	4	8	57.14	24	8	66.67	28
9	21.43	9	9	47.62	20	9	85.71	36
10	14.29	6	10	64.29	27	10	73.81	31

In “summaries” the values are summarized over all individuals and all replicates. For instance, endpoints result summarize outcomes over all replicates with the uncertainty of the result.

The screenshot shows the 'ENDPOINTS [SUMMARY]' view for 'Efficacy'. The table is organized into three columns for endpoints: OD, BID, and TID. Each endpoint column has sub-columns for 'MIN', 'P05', 'MEDIAN', 'P95', and 'MAX'. The 'percentTrue' and 'totalTrue' rows are highlighted in grey. The 'Display' panel on the right shows 'Efficacy' selected and '3 items selected'.

OD						BID						TID					
	MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX		MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX		MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX
percentTrue	9.52	9.52	16.48	21.43	21.43	percentTrue	47.62	47.62	57.14	66.67	66.67	percentTrue	66.67	66.67	76.19	88.1	88.1
totalTrue	4	4	6.5	9	9	totalTrue	20	20	24	28	28	totalTrue	28	28	32	37	37

Similarly, plots contain information of all replicates. By default, individual outputs display only one replicate, however, stratification panel allows to select one or more replicate to plot (green frame).

Endpoint distribution in case of replicates is summarized in a box plot.

5.2.4 Sampling options

5.2.4.1 Individual sampling

Simulation elements of different types are subject to different individual sampling in a simulation. Elements defined as **vectors** provide common values for all individuals, so there is no sampling. When an element is a **distribution**, then sampling is done for each individual separately. **Tables**, from external files or from Monolix after importing a project from Monolix, can contain data for more than one individual distinguished with the column called “id”. In this case, there are three sampling methods available in the Simulation tab.

- **Keep order** (default) – individual values are taken in the same order as they appear in a table.
- **With replacement** – individual values are samples from a table with replacement.
- **Without replacement** – individual values are samples from a table without replacement. This option is available only if tables contain at least the same number of individual values as a group size.

All of the above sampling methods are general and apply to all tables in a simulation scenario.

5.2.4.2 Shared ids

If there is a group of tables with individual values, an option “shared ids” allows to create an intersections of ids present in the considered tables. After that, ids from these intersection are sampled to create the data for simulation.

Shared IDs checkboxes are automatically selected when individual parameter elements are combined with the covariate element “mlx_Cov” in the simulation setup, to link covariate information with the corresponding individual.

Example: Simulation uses a treatment with a dose amount depending on the patients weights. Treatment element and weights are external tables with columns (id, time, amount) for the treatment, and (id, weight) for the covariate. Moreover, an effect of the weight is added on the definition of the individual parameter (volume of the central compartment) in the model. In this case, it is important to match a sample from the treatment element with a sample from the covariate element. It is done by ticking two boxes in the “shared ids” column for both elements (blue frame).

5.2.4.3 Same individuals among groups

“Same individuals among groups” option allows to have **the same individual parameters in all groups** and is available if the following elements (required for the sampling) are the same for all groups: size of groups, parameters (population or individual) and covariates. The main aim is to make the comparison between groups easier. In particular, it is used to *compare different treatments on the same individuals* – subjects with the same individual parameters. Selecting same individuals among groups assures that the differences between groups are only due to the treatment itself. To obtain the same conclusion without this option enabled, simulation should be performed on a very large number of individuals to averaged out the individual differences.

Example: a simulation of two treatment groups with shared parameters, covariates and outputs. When the option “same individuals among groups” is enabled, then subjects in each group have the same individual parameters because the same Parameters (manual_popParam) and Covariates (race) are used in all groups (Demo 5.simulation: simulationGroups_sameldInGroups).

The screenshot displays the Simulx software interface. On the left, a 'manual_popParam' dialog box is open, showing a table of parameters with values: Mean (0.1), Std (0.1), Qsd (0.2), and Hq (0.4). Below it, an 'equal_dist' dialog box is also open, showing a table of covariates with categories and probabilities: hispanic (0.33), caucasian (0.33), and asian (0.33). The main interface shows a 'Simulation' tab with a 'Definition' sub-tab. A 'Same individuals among groups' checkbox is checked. Below this, there are two groups: 'low_dose' and 'high_dose'. A blue arrow points from the 'low_dose' group to a table of 'Individual parameters' and covariates. The table has columns for 'low_dose' and 'high_dose', each with sub-columns for 'id', 'ka', 'Q', 'V1', 'V2', 'Cl', 'F', and 'race'. The table contains 10 rows of data for each group, showing values for these parameters and the race (caucasian, hispanic, asian).

5.3 Outcomes and endpoints

Outcomes, endpoints group comparison are in a dedicated section “Outcomes&endpoints” of the Simulation tab.

The screenshot shows the 'Simulation' tab in the Simulx software. At the top, there are three buttons: 'SIMULATION', 'OUTCOMES & ENDPOINTS', and 'RUN'. Below these, the 'Simulation' section is expanded, showing the 'Outcomes & endpoints' configuration. This section is divided into four columns: 'Outcomes', 'Combination', 'Endpoint', and 'Group comparison'. The 'Outcomes' column has three items: 'Cmax', 'CmaxBelow800', and 'InhibitionATrough'. The 'Endpoint' column has three items: 'Median_Cmax', 'Percent_ids_in_Safety_target', and 'Median_InhibitionATrough'. The 'Group comparison' column has a toggle switch and a dropdown menu set to 'OD_200mgPerDay_'. The 'Outcomes' and 'Endpoints' sections are currently empty.

To calculate outcomes and endpoints click on the “Outcomes&Endpoints” button in the Tasks section (on top). The outcomes are a post-processing of the simulation outputs, so remember that you have to first run the “Simulation” task. You can also selected the task “Outcomes&Endpoints” in a scenario (circle radio

button on the right hand side of the task button) and click the button RUN – Simulx will run both tasks automatically one by one.

The calculated values are displayed in the Results tab and Plots tab.

5.3.1 Outcomes

Outcomes represent a post-processing of the simulation outputs done for each individual. They correspond to the measure of interest per individual. Outcomes have different types: **values** (e.g Cmax), **binary true/false** (e.g true if Cmax < threshold), or **time-to-event** (e.g time to NADIR).

To create a new outcome, click on the “plus” button next to Outcomes header or on the “+ New outcome element” within the list of outcomes for an endpoint:

Each **outcome has a name** (default or user defined), which allows to select it in an endpoint definition. To define an outcome you have to **select an output element** for post – processing. You can only use output elements selected in the Simulation scenario. The specification of the outcome includes the following options to post-process the selected output.

5.3.1.1 For continuous, count and categorical outputs

Relative to: none/ baseline/ maximal or minimal value/ maximal or minimal value up to current time/ custom value: it divides (“ratio”) or subtracts (“difference”) the output values by the specific value (i.e baseline – the first value of the output). For baseline option, because the first value of the transformed output is non-informative (ratio=1 or difference=0), it is removed.

New outcome

Name

outcome1

Output

TS_fineGrid_25weeks ▾

Relative to maximal value up to current time

 ratio
 difference

Output process

- none
- baseline (first value of output)
- maximal value
- minimum value
- maximal value up to current time
- minimal value up to current time
- custom value

Apply the

 Add to endpoint: + New endpoint task...

CANCEL

OK

Output processing:

- **average value** – takes the average over all output values for each individual
- **first or last value** – takes a value at the first or last time point for each individual
- **min or max value** – takes the minimum or maximum over all output values for each individual. You can choose “*value of min/max*” to take the value of the min or max, or choose “*time of min/max*” to take the time of the min or max – as continuous time or time-to-event.
- **at custom point** – takes a value of an output at a specified time point. Only grid time points are allowed.
- **duration below or above a value or between values** – calculates time when the output values are below, above or between a given values. Strict inequalities (< or >) apply. You input threshold values manually below the output processing menu. As duration you can choose:
 - “cumulative time” – sum of time intervals between consecutive time points where output values satisfy the condition
 - “% of total time” – cumulative time divided by the final time (in percentage)
 - “number of observations” – number of time points where output values satisfy the condition
 - “time of the first occurrence” – a time point where the condition is satisfied for the first time (can be event or continuous)

New outcome

Name
outcome1

Output
noisyCc_2weeks

Relative to
none

Output processing:
duration between two values per id

- cumulative time
- % of total time
- number of observations
- time of the first occurrence (continuous)
- time of the first occurrence (event)

min 0 max 1

Apply threshold

Add to endpoint: + New endpoint task... CANCEL OK

Apply threshold: applies a logical test (usually comparing the outcome value to a threshold) to get a binary true/false outcome. You must set a threshold value and a comparison sign (=, !=, >=, <=, >, <).

New outcome

Name

outcome1

Output

Plasma_concentration ▾

 relative to baseline (first value of output)
 ratio
 difference

 Output processing:
 max per id
 value of max
 time of max

 Apply threshold ≤ 800

 Add to endpoint: + New endpoint task... ▾

CANCEL

OK

5.3.1.2 For single time-to-event outputs

- **Has event / has no event / time of event:** “has event” and “has no event” calculates if the individual had or didn’t have an event during the observation period. This is a binary true/false outcome. “time of event” uses the TTE output as outcome directly. The outcome is then of type ‘time-to-event’.

New outcome

Name

outcome1

Output

Death ▾

 has event
 has no event
 time of event

 Add to endpoint: + New endpoint task... ▾

CANCEL

OK

5.3.1.3 For repeated time-to-event outputs

- **Has at least one event / number of events per id / time of event #:** “has at least one event” leads to a binary true/false outcome depending if the individual has at least one event during the observation period or not. “number of events per id” count the total number of events for each

individual. This is an outcome of type 'value'. "Time of event # " generates a time-to-event outcome with a single event per individual. The index of the event to be considered can be typed-in by the user.

New outcome

Name
outcome1

Output

EventUntil250 ▾

has at least one event

number of event(s) per id

Time of event # 1

Add to endpoint:

5.3.1.4 Occasions

In case of occasions, you can choose to compute the outcome for each individual, or for each occasion of each individual. Select a corresponding radio button in the outcome definition window

New outcome

Name

outcome1

- calculate for each individual
- calculate for each occasion of each individual

Output

regularCc ▾

Relative to *none* ▾

Output processing: min per id and per occasion ▾

- value of min
- time of min (continuous)
- time of min (event)

 Apply threshold Add to endpoint: + New endpoint task... ▾

CANCEL

OK

5.3.1.5 Outcomes organization

Outcomes are building blocks for endpoints. When you create a new outcome, you can **add the outcome to a new or to an existing endpoint via the option “Add to endpoint”** at the bottom of the outcome definition window. The Outcomes & endpoints section displays only the outcomes used in endpoints. All defined outcomes, whether used or not in an endpoint, appear in the **list of outcomes**:

Tasks ▾

Simulation ▾

Outcomes & endpoints ▾

Name	Type	Output	Processing	Action
NADIR	numeric	PSA_measured_after0	min value	
Survival	tte	Death	timeOfEvents	
HasNoDeathEvent	boolean	Death	hasNoEvent	
TimeToNADIR	tte	PSA_measured_after0	min time	

+

Outcomes of the same type can be **combined together using AND/OR for binary true/false outcomes** (e.g Cmax < threshold1 and Ctrough > threshold2), or **MIN/MAX for double values and time-to-event** (e.g max(CmaxParent, CmaxMetabolite)).

Tasks ▾

Simulation ▾

Outcomes & endpoints ▾

Outcomes

Median_InhibitionAtTrough

InhibitionAtTrough ▾

Efficacy

InhibitionAtTroughAbove80Percent ▾

SafetyAndEfficacy

CmaxBelow800 ▾

InhibitionAtTroughAbove80Percent ▾

Geometric mean
 Arithmetic mean
 Median
 Percent true
 and
 or
 Percent true

5.3.2 Endpoints

Endpoints summarize the outcome values over all individuals, for each simulation group and each replicate. To create a new endpoint, you can select one or several outcomes of the same type from the drop-down menu (highlighted below in blue) or click on the “+” icon next to the Endpoint

header. Endpoints are also created automatically, when at the bottom of an outcome definition you select the option “Add to endpoint: New endpoint”. Once you create an endpoint, you can change its name (highlighted below in green).

The screenshot shows the Simulx software interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: 'Definition', 'Exploration', and 'Simulation' (which is active). Below the tabs, there are three main buttons: 'SIMULATION', 'OUTCOMES & ENDPOINTS', and 'RUN'. The 'OUTCOMES & ENDPOINTS' button is highlighted. Below these buttons, there is a 'Simulation' section with a dropdown arrow. Underneath, there is an 'Outcomes & endpoints' section with a dropdown arrow. This section contains several elements: 'Outcomes' with a plus icon, 'Endpoint' with a plus icon, 'Group comparison' with a toggle switch, and 'Reference group' with a dropdown menu showing 'gr_BID_lowDose'. There are two outcome elements: 'outcome_efficacy' and 'outcome_safety'. The 'outcome_safety' element has a plus icon and a dropdown arrow. Below it, there is a button labeled '+ New outcome element...'. The 'Endpoint' section shows a list of endpoints: 'percent_ids_in_target' (highlighted in green) and 'Percent true'. The 'percent_ids_in_target' endpoint has a plus icon and a dropdown arrow.

There are several options to summarize the individual outcomes into an endpoint. It depends on the type of outcomes:

- **value outcomes:** the endpoint can be
 - **geometric mean.** Includes calculation of the coefficient of variation.
 - **arithmetic mean.** Includes calculation of the standard deviation.
 - **median.** Includes calculation of the 5th and 95th percentiles.
- **binary true/false outcomes:** the endpoint will be the **percentage of true**. Includes calculation of the “total number true”.
- **time-to-event outcomes:** the endpoint will be the **median survival** (time at which the Kaplan Meier curve is equal to 0.5). Includes calculation of the lower bound (5th) and upper bound (95th) of the confidence interval of the median survival.

The screenshot shows the 'Outcomes & endpoints' configuration panel. It is divided into several sections: 'Outcomes', 'Combination', 'Endpoint', 'Group comparison', and 'Reference group'. The 'Group comparison' toggle is turned on and highlighted with a green box. The 'Reference group' dropdown is set to 'OD_200mgPerDay_...' and is highlighted with a blue box. In the 'Endpoint' column, the 'Median' radio button is selected for the first endpoint, and the 'Percent true' radio button is selected for the second endpoint. The 'Outcomes' column shows three endpoints: 'Median_Cmax', 'Safely', and 'Median_timeToMax', each with a dropdown menu and a plus icon.

5.3.3 Group comparison

You can **compare endpoints across simulation groups** by activating the toggle “Group comparison” (green highlight). One of the simulation groups must be defined as the reference group (blue highlight) and **all other groups will be compared to this reference group**. For each endpoint, the group comparison can rely on a *direct comparison* of the endpoint values, or on a *statistical test* (purple highlight). The exact comparison or test applied depends on the type of the endpoint.

This screenshot provides a more detailed view of the 'Group comparison' settings. The 'Group comparison' toggle is highlighted in green. The 'Reference group' dropdown is highlighted in blue. The 'Group comparison' section is highlighted in purple, showing three rows of settings:

- For the first endpoint (Median_Cmax), 'Statistical test' is selected, with a ratio of 1 and a p-value of 0.05.
- For the second endpoint (Safely), 'Direct comparison' is selected, with an oddRatio of 2.
- For the third endpoint (Median_timeToMax), 'Direct comparison' is selected, with a difference of 20.

 The 'Endpoint' column shows 'Geometric mean' selected for the first endpoint, 'Percent true' for the second, and 'Median survival' for the third. The 'Outcomes' column shows the same three endpoints as in the previous screenshot.

5.3.3.1 Statistical tests

This table gives an overview of the statistical tests performed in Group comparison depending on the type of outcome and endpoint. Next sections contain detailed information of each option.

Outcome	Endpoint	Metric	Statistical test	
			Same indiv = True	Same indiv = False
Continuous	Geometric mean	Ratio of means	Paired t-test on log-transformed	Unpaired t-test on log-transformed
	Arithmetic mean	Difference of means	Paired t-test	Unpaired t-test
	Median	Difference of medians	Wilcoxon signed rank test	Wilcoxon rank sum test

Binary true/false	Percent true	O d d s r a t i o	McNemar's exact test	Fisher's exact test
Time-to-event	Median survival	D i f f e r e n c e i n m e d i a n s u r v i v a l	Logrank test with variance correction	Logrank test

5.3.3.2 Endpoint "median" for value outcome

This test calculates the **difference between the median of the test group and of the reference group**: $median_{test} - median_{ref}$ with $median_{test}$ and $median_{ref}$ the median in the test and reference group respectively.

In case of a **direct comparison**, this difference is compared using operators =, !=, >, >=, <, <= to a user-defined value (default: 0). When this logical comparison is true, the trial simulation is considered as 'success'.

Example: When the direct comparison "difference > 25" is true, it means that the median in the test group is larger than in the reference group by at least 25 units (e.g ng/mL if the outcome is a peak concentration).

In case of a **statistical test**, a **Wilcoxon rank sum test** (equivalent to the Mann-Whitney test) ("Same individuals among groups" not selected) or a **Wilcoxon signed rank test** ("Same individuals among groups" selected) is done to compare the median of the test and reference group. **"difference ≠ 0" represents the alternative hypothesis H1**. By default, it performs a two-sided test (sign ≠) and checks if the medians significantly differ from each other. You can define single-sided tests by choosing ">" or "<". The minimal or maximal (depending of the direction of the test) difference can also be specified (default: 0). The statistical test results into a p-value, which is compared to a user-defined threshold (default: 0.05). If the p-value is below the threshold, the trial simulation is considered as 'success'.

Example: When the statistical test testing the alternative H1 hypothesis “difference > 25” results into a small p-value, it means that the medians of the test and reference groups differ by more than 25 units significantly (e.g ng/mL if the outcome is a peak concentration) with a larger value for test.

5.3.3.3 Endpoint “arithmetic mean” for value outcome

This test calculates the **difference between the mean of the test group and of the reference group:** $mean_{test} - mean_{ref}$ with $mean_{test}$ and $mean_{ref}$ the median in the test and reference group respectively.

In case of a **direct comparison**, this difference is compared using operators =, !=, >, >=, <, <= to a user-defined value (default: 0). When this logical comparison is true, the trial simulation is considered as ‘success’.

Example: When the direct comparison “difference > 14 ” is true, it means that the mean in the test group is larger than in the reference group by at least 14 units (e.g ng/mL if the outcome is a peak concentration).

In case of a **statistical test**, it performs an **unpaired t-test** (“Same individuals among groups” not selected) or a **paired t-test** (“Same individuals among groups” selected) to compare the test and reference group. **“difference ≠ 0” represents the alternative hypothesis H1.** By default, it performs a two-sided test (sign ≠) and checks if the two means significantly differ from each other. You can define single-sided tests by choosing “>” or “<”. The minimal or maximal (depending of the direction of the test) difference can also be specified (default: 0). The statistical test results into a p-value, and compares it to a user-defined threshold (default: 0.05). If the p-value is below the threshold, the trial simulation is considered as ‘success’.

Example: When the statistical test testing the alternative H1 hypothesis “difference > 14” results into a small p-value, it means that the means of the test and reference groups differ significantly by more than 14 units (e.g ng/mL if the outcome is a peak concentration) with a larger value for test.

5.3.3.4 Endpoint “geometric mean” for value outcome

This test calculates the **ratio of the test geometric mean divided by the reference geometric mean:** $geoMean_{test} - geoMean_{ref}$ with $geoMean_{test}$ and $geoMean_{ref}$ the median in the test and reference group respectively.

In case of a **direct comparison**, this ratio is compared using operators =, !=, >, >=, <, <= to a user-defined value (default: 1). When this logical comparison is true, the trial simulation is considered as ‘success’.

Example: When the direct comparison “ratio > 2” is true, it means that the geometric mean in the test group is at least twice larger than in the reference group.

In case of a **statistical test**, it performs an **unpaired t-test** (“Same individuals among groups” not selected) or a **paired t-test** (“Same individuals among groups” selected) on the **log-transformed values** (which are assumed to follow a normal distribution) to compare the means of the test and reference group. **“ratio ≠ 1” represents the alternative hypothesis H1.** By default, it performs a two-

sided test (sign \neq) and checks if the geometric means significantly differ from each other. You can define single-sided tests by choosing ">" or "<". The minimal or maximal (depending of the direction of the test) ratio can also be specified (default: 1). The statistical test results into a p-value, which is compared to a user-defined threshold (default: 0.05). If the p-value is below the threshold, the trial simulation is considered as 'success'.

Example: When the statistical test testing the alternative H1 hypothesis "ratio > 2" results into a small p-value, it means that the geometric mean of the test group is significantly larger than twice the geometric mean of the reference group.

5.3.3.5 Endpoint "percent true" for binary true/false outcome

This test calculates the **odds ratio between the test group and the reference group**. The odds ratio definition is different depending if you use paired samples case or not.

5.3.3.5.1 "Same individuals among groups" not selected (unpaired samples)

The odd ratio is $\frac{p_{Test}}{1-p_{Test}} / \frac{p_{Ref}}{1-p_{Ref}}$ with p_{Test} and p_{Ref} the fraction of true outcomes in the test and reference group respectively. $1 - p_{Test}$ represents the fraction of false outcomes.

Equivalently, you can use the following contingency table to define the odd ratio.

UNPAIRED			
	Number of individuals		
	TRUE	FALSE	total
Treatment test	n11=95	n10=5	100
Treatment ref	n01=87	n00=13	100
$oddRatio=(n11/n10) / (n01/n00) = (95/5) / (87/13) = 2.83$			

5.3.3.5.2 "Same individuals among groups" selected (paired samples)

In case of identical individuals among groups, the individuals which have the same outcome value in both groups (so Ref=True and Test=True, or Ref=False and Test=False) are not counted. The odd ratio is defined as $\frac{n_{Test_T Ref_F}}{n_{Test_F Ref_T}}$, with $n_{Test_T Ref_F}$ the number of individuals with true in the test group and false in the reference group. It corresponds to the contingency table below. The odds ratio can frequently be zero or infinity – in particular in the absence of measurement noise – an individual true in the reference group is also necessarily true in the test group (corresponding for instance to a higher dose).

PAIRED				
		Treatment Ref		
		TRUE	FALSE	total
Treatment test	TRUE	m11=85	m10=10	95
	FALSE	m01=2	m00=3	5
total		87	13	100

oddRatio=m10/m01 = 10 / 2 = 5

In case of a **direct comparison**, this odds ratio is compared using operators =, !=, >, >=, <, <= to a user-defined value (default: 1). When this logical comparison is true, the trial simulation is considered as 'success'.

Example: When the direct comparison "odds ratio > 2" is true, it means that the odds in the test group are at least twice larger than in the reference group.

In case of a **statistical test**, it performs a **Fisher's exact test** ("Same individuals among groups" not selected) or a **McNemar's exact test** ("Same individuals among groups" selected) to compare the results of the test and reference group via the construction of a 2x2 contingency table (which contain more information than the endpoints p_{Test} and p_{Ref}). "**odds ratio \neq 1**" represents the **alternative hypothesis H1**. By default, it performs a two-sided test (sign \neq) and checks if the odds ratio significantly differs from 1. You can define a single-sided tests by choosing ">" or "<". The minimal or maximal (depending of the direction of the test) odds ratio can also be specified (default: 1). The statistical test results into a p-value, and compare it to a user-defined threshold (default: 0.05). If the p-value is below the threshold, the trial simulation is considered as 'success'.

Example: When the statistical test testing the alternative H1 hypothesis "odds ratio > 2" results into a small p-value, it means that the odds of the test group are significantly larger than twice the odds of the reference group.

5.3.3.6 Endpoint "median survival" for time-to-event outcome

This test calculates the **difference between the median survival of the test group and of the reference group**: $medSurv_{test} - medSurv_{ref}$ with $medSurv_{test}$ and $medSurv_{ref}$ the median survival (time at which the Kaplan-Meier estimates equals 0.5) in the test and reference group respectively.

In case of a **direct comparison**, this difference is compared using operators =, !=, >, >=, <, <= to a user-defined value (default: 1). When this logical comparison is true, the trial simulation is considered as 'success'.

Example: Direct comparison "difference > 60" corresponds to median survival in the test group larger than in the reference group by 60 time units (e.g days).

In case of a **statistical test**, it performs a **logrank test** to compare the survival Kaplan-Meier curves. Selecting "Same individuals among groups", applies a variance correction (see Jung 1999). "**difference \neq 0**" represents the **alternative hypothesis H1**. By default, it performs a two-sided test (sign \neq) and checks if the survival curves significantly differ. You can define single-sided tests by choosing ">" or "<". For the log rank test, it is not possible to define a "minimal difference". The statistical test gives a p-

value, and compare it to a user-defined threshold (default: 0.05). If the p-value is below the threshold, the trial simulation is considered as 'success'.

Example: When the statistical test testing the alternative H1 hypothesis "difference $\neq 0$ " results into a small p-value, it means that the survival curves from the two groups differ significantly.

5.4 Results

The results tab displays the simulated values and the outcomes and endpoints as tables.

Result tables are organized into three sections: Simulation, Endpoints and Group comparison.

5.4.1 Simulation

The simulation tab displays the simulated output values and the sampled individual parameters.

5.4.1.1 Outputs

Because the simulated output values are usually a very large table, the results are presented as percentiles for continuous simulations (minimum, 5th percentile, median, 95th percentile and maximum) and as percentage of survival and average number of events for time-to-event simulations. These statistics are calculated over time bins calculated automatically. When replicates are used, the statistics are calculated over all replicates merged together. Each simulation group is displayed as a separate table.

The screenshot shows the 'Results' tab in the Simulx interface. It displays simulation output for two groups: 'Cc' and 'Effect'. Each group has three tables corresponding to different dosing regimens: OD_200mgPerDay_, BID_200mgPerDay_, and OD_300mgPerDay_ for the 'Cc' group, and BID_300mgPerDay_ for the 'Effect' group. Each table shows statistics for various time points (0.5, 2, 3.75, 5.5, 7.25, 9, 10.5, 12.25, 14, 15.5) across five percentiles: MIN, P05, MEDIAN, P95, and MAX. The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options (Definition, Exploration, Simulation, Results, Plots) and a 'Display' panel on the right with controls for pagination and group selection.

TIME	MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX
0.5	0	0	163.26	364.26	524.67
2	101.45	183.2	286.46	395.85	519.32
3.75	111.67	168.6	247.91	332.9	438.33
5.5	80.84	134.85	205.54	285.6	377.6
7.25	56.72	106.64	174.95	255.89	349.61
9	45.23	87.47	153.14	230.33	321.07
10.5	36.84	75.15	137.98	214.19	303.75
12.25	28.59	62.71	123.91	197.92	288.67
14	23.85	53.92	111.93	183.86	270.9
15.5	19.97	46.7	103.04	172.84	258.82

5.4.1.2 Individual parameters [Summary]

This tab displays the percentiles summarizing the distribution of individual parameters used for simulation for each of the groups. These parameters have been either directly defined by the user or sampled from the population parameters defined by the user. As for the simulated outputs, the statistics are calculated over all replicates merged together.

OD_200mgPerDay_						BID_200mgPerDay_						OD_300mgPerDay_					
	MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX		MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX		MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX
ka	0.2	0.34	0.38	0.44	0.68	ka	0.21	0.34	0.38	0.43	0.71	ka	0.23	0.34	0.38	0.44	0.73
Cl	5.26	13.97	18.11	23.79	54.31	Cl	5.72	13.66	17.82	22.82	55.9	Cl	5.7	13.33	18.24	24.12	57.74
V1	9.08	43.42	63.5	88.28	271.41	V1	14.43	43.29	62.61	90.76	277.52	V1	15.38	47.06	65.13	95.59	333.69
Q	48.1	48.1	48.1	48.1	48.1	Q	48.1	48.1	48.1	48.1	48.1	Q	48.1	48.1	48.1	48.1	48.1
V2	111.49	180.2	204.23	236.73	369.04	V2	109.12	177.01	205.74	238.46	370.55	V2	110.23	179.15	206.4	239.03	401.8
IC50	32	32	32	32	32	IC50	32	32	32	32	32	IC50	32	32	32	32	32
D50	95.79	137.18	150.64	164.13	209.4	D50	102.3	137.28	150.24	164.59	221.5	D50	101.37	136.65	149.44	164.24	230.85

BID_300mgPerDay_					
	MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX
ka	0.2	0.33	0.37	0.43	0.65
Cl	5.13	13.9	17.68	23.46	63.67
V1	12.39	43.41	63.83	92.1	470.83
Q	48.1	48.1	48.1	48.1	48.1
V2	105.9	175.4	202.26	230.52	466.47
IC50	32	32	32	32	32
D50	92.37	138.62	151.65	164.55	219.27

5.4.1.3 Individual parameters [Table]

This tab displays the full tables of individual parameters for all replicates and for all groups. The content of these tables can also be found in a table gathering all groups in the result folder>Simulation>individualParameters.txt .

Individual parameters

Sampled individual parameters and covariates

OD_200mgPerDay_										BID_200mgPerDay_									
rep	id	ka	Cl	V1	Q	V2	IC50	D50		rep	id	ka	Cl	V1	Q	V2	IC50	D50	
1	1	0.44	19.56	30.84	48.1	211.59	32	147.88		1	301	0.45	13.91	49.98	48.1	166.53	32	148.14	
1	2	0.44	24.22	53.44	48.1	222.2	32	121.95		1	302	0.4	13.01	94.64	48.1	195.51	32	140.96	
1	3	0.29	16.11	29.33	48.1	218.85	32	155.26		1	303	0.41	9.75	56.37	48.1	270.19	32	110.94	
1	4	0.4	33.59	59.84	48.1	161.43	32	125.34		1	304	0.35	18.28	63.16	48.1	183.14	32	132.65	
1	5	0.42	14.79	63.21	48.1	168.34	32	158.57		1	305	0.37	17.65	54.6	48.1	205.83	32	148.16	
1	6	0.29	18.27	9.08	48.1	200.12	32	139.28		1	306	0.45	9.9	31.78	48.1	163.04	32	135.36	
1	7	0.48	19.77	80.04	48.1	230.94	32	169.85		1	307	0.38	19.48	73.31	48.1	178.39	32	123.44	
1	8	0.29	19.88	61.31	48.1	282.1	32	127.91		1	308	0.57	26.68	144.14	48.1	249.84	32	168.09	
1	9	0.41	6.76	32.17	48.1	290.4	32	149.64		1	309	0.42	15.63	41.43	48.1	273.8	32	134.69	
1	10	0.31	12.53	84.06	48.1	308.2	32	163.63		1	310	0.4	18.56	76.73	48.1	195.28	32	152.32	

OD_300mgPerDay_										BID_300mgPerDay_									
rep	id	ka	Cl	V1	Q	V2	IC50	D50		rep	id	ka	Cl	V1	Q	V2	IC50	D50	
1	601	0.38	10.17	51.25	48.1	233.9	32	176.06		1	901	0.33	27.1	26.63	48.1	245.15	32	116.68	
1	602	0.47	11.97	76.71	48.1	329.06	32	185.64		1	902	0.42	24.29	71.22	48.1	191.87	32	134.47	
1	603	0.52	20.1	24.65	48.1	165.94	32	143.78		1	903	0.38	7.64	45.27	48.1	235.49	32	150.06	

The id column in these tables is the simulated id, meaning that id i is the i-st parameter set sampled for simulation.

Since the version 2023R1, if elements using original id lists have been used for simulation, for example a table of individual treatments, or a table of individual parameters, the original ids in these tables is reported in the individual parameter tables in the “original_id” column. For example in the demo project “importFromMonolix_useEBEs_originalID.smlx”, we use the element mlx_EBEs which is a table of individual parameters. The original IDs used in this table are reported in the sampled individual parameters table, together with the simulated id. The original id is also reported in the output files.

The image shows two screenshots from the Simulx interface. The left screenshot shows the 'Simulation' tab with a table named 'mlx_EBEs [read-only]' containing columns for ID, ka, Cl, V1, Q, and V2. A red box highlights the 'mlx_EBEs' element in the 'Parameters' section, with an arrow pointing to the right screenshot. The right screenshot shows the 'Results' tab with the 'Individual parameters' table, which includes an 'original_id' column corresponding to the 'ID' column in the 'mlx_EBEs' table. The 'original_id' column is highlighted with a red box.

If a simulated id uses information coming from several original ids (e.g when a table a individual parameters and a table of treatment is used by the “shared ids” option is not selected), then the original id is not displayed in the GUI but it can be found in the result folder in the file *ID_mapping.txt*.

5.4.2 Endpoints

The endpoints section appears if an outcome has been defined in the simulation tab, to post-process the simulation results.

5.4.2.1 Outcomes [Summary]

The summary shows one table per outcome, displaying the percentiles over individuals and replicates for each group if the outcome is continuous, and the number of true and false individuals if the outcome is a boolean.

The screenshot shows the Simulx GUI with the 'Results' tab active. The 'Endpoints (Summary)' view is displayed, showing two tables for the outcome 'InhibitionATrough'.

InhibitionATrough						InhibitionATroughAbove80Percent	
	MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX	TRUE	FALSE
OD_200mgPerDay_	0.068	0.44	0.74	0.89	0.95	930	2070
BID_200mgPerDay_	0.37	0.69	0.86	0.93	0.97	2313	687
OD_300mgPerDay_	0.16	0.49	0.77	0.9	0.96	1205	1795
BID_300mgPerDay_	0.42	0.73	0.88	0.94	0.97	2561	439

5.4.2.2 Outcomes [Table]

The outcomes table shows the outcome values for all individuals. A table of all values for each outcome also appears the result folder/Endpoints.

The screenshot shows the 'Results' tab in Simulx, displaying endpoint summaries for two groups: OD_200mgPerDay_ and BID_200mgPerDay_. Each group has two tables: 'InhibitionAtTroughAbove80Percent' and 'InhibitionAtTrough'.

rep	ID	InhibitionAtTroughAbove80Percent
1	1	false
1	2	false
1	3	false
1	4	false
1	5	false
1	6	false
1	7	false
1	8	false
1	9	true
1	10	true

rep	ID	InhibitionAtTrough
1	1	0.68
1	2	0.59
1	3	0.77
1	4	0.37
1	5	0.79
1	6	0.7
1	7	0.73
1	8	0.72
1	9	0.92
1	10	0.86

rep	ID	InhibitionAtTroughAbove80Percent
1	31	true
1	32	true
1	33	true

rep	ID	InhibitionAtTrough
1	31	0.9
1	32	0.89
1	33	0.81

5.4.2.3 Endpoints [Summary]

Endpoints summarize the outcome values over all individuals for a specific group and replicate. The endpoints summary shows percentiles for the calculated endpoint over replicates. These percentiles give the uncertainty of the endpoint value over several clinical trial simulations.

The screenshot shows the 'Results' tab in Simulx, displaying endpoint summaries for three groups: OD_200mgPerDay_, BID_200mgPerDay_, and OD_300mgPerDay_. Each group has two tables: 'Efficacy' and 'median_inhibitionATrough'.

	MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX
percentTrue	13.33	20	30	46.67	56.67
totalTrue	4	6	9	14	17

	MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX
median	0.64	0.68	0.74	0.79	0.82
lowerInterquartile	0.1	0.3	0.46	0.56	0.61
upperInterquartile	0.83	0.85	0.89	0.91	0.92

	MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX
percentTrue	60	66.67	76.67	88.33	96.67
totalTrue	18	20	23	26.5	29

	MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX
median	0.82	0.84	0.86	0.87	0.88
lowerInterquartile	0.59	0.59	0.69	0.77	0.81
upperInterquartile	0.9	0.91	0.93	0.95	0.95

	MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX
percentTrue	20	23.33	40	56.67	63.33
totalTrue	6	7	12	17	19

	MIN	P05	MEDIAN	P95	MAX
median	0.72	0.73	0.77	0.81	0.84
lowerInterquartile	0.3	0.36	0.51	0.61	0.66
upperInterquartile	0.84	0.87	0.9	0.92	0.94

5.4.2.4 Endpoints [Table]

The endpoints table shows the value of the endpoint defined in the simulation tab for each group and each replicate. A table for each endpoint is also saved in the result folder/Endpoints.

The screenshot displays the 'Results' tab in Simulx, showing two tables under the 'Endpoints [Table]' section. The first table is titled 'Efficacy' and the second is 'median_inhibitionAtTrough'. Both tables are paginated and show data for four different dosing regimens: OD_200mgPerDay, BID_200mgPerDay, OD_300mgPerDay, and BID_300mgPerDay. The 'Efficacy' table shows 'rep', 'percentTrue', and 'totalTrue' for 10 replicates. The 'median_inhibitionAtTrough' table shows 'rep', 'median', '5thPercentile', and '95thPercentile' for 3 replicates.

rep	percentTrue	totalTrue									
1	33.33	10	1	76.67	23	1	56.67	17	1	76.67	23
2	36.67	11	2	80	24	2	40	12	2	90	27
3	43.33	13	3	76.67	23	3	43.33	13	3	83.33	25
4	26.67	8	4	83.33	25	4	50	15	4	76.67	23
5	26.67	8	5	73.33	22	5	36.67	11	5	86.67	26
6	23.33	7	6	86.67	26	6	40	12	6	73.33	22
7	30	9	7	76.67	23	7	53.33	16	7	80	24
8	36.67	11	8	70	21	8	43.33	13	8	93.33	28
9	40	12	9	76.67	23	9	40	12	9	76.67	23
10	26.67	8	10	83.33	25	10	36.67	11	10	80	24

rep	median	5thPercentile	95thPercentile	rep	median	5thPercentile	95thPercentile	rep	median	5thPercentile	95thPercentile
1	0.74	0.5	0.9	1	0.85	0.7	0.93	1	0.81	0.5	0.89
2	0.75	0.45	0.89	2	0.84	0.65	0.91	2	0.77	0.57	0.91
3	0.72	0.37	0.92	3	0.66	0.74	0.93	3	0.78	0.46	0.87

5.4.3 Group Comparison

If several simulation groups are used, and if group comparison is checked in the simulation tab, the group comparison section appears in the results.

5.4.3.1 Group comparison Table

For each replicate study, a test comparing the groups is performed as defined in the group comparison section of the simulation tab. The statistics of the test, p-value and the resulting decision (success or failure) according to the defined criteria are reported for each group (compared to the reference group) and for each replicate. A table is also saved for each statistical test and for each decision criterion in the result folder/Endpoints.

Definition Exploration Simulation **Results** Plots

SIMULATION
ENDPOINTS
GROUP COMPARISON

Group comparison

Display
 Pagination
 COLLAPSE ALL EXPAND ALL

Efficacy										median_inhibitionAtTrough						
REP	BID_200MGPERDAY_			OD_300MGPERDAY_			BID_300MGPERDAY_			REP	BID_200MGPERDAY_		OD_300MGPERDAY_		BID_300MGPERDAY_	
	ODDSRATIO	P-VALUE	SUCCESS	ODDSRATIO	P-VALUE	SUCCESS	ODDSRATIO	P-VALUE	SUCCESS		DIFFERENCE	SUCCESS	DIFFERENCE	SUCCESS	DIFFERENCE	SUCCESS
1	6.57	3.42e-2	✓	2.62	4.18e-1	✗	6.57	3.42e-2	✓	1	0.12	✓	0.07	✗	0.12	✓
2	6.91	3.07e-2	✓	1.15	9.08e-1	✗	15.55	1.94e-3	✓	2	0.086	✗	0.016	✗	0.13	✓
3	4.3	1.43e-1	✗	1	9.47e-1	✗	6.54	4.43e-2	✓	3	0.14	✓	0.059	✗	0.13	✓
4	13.75	1.59e-3	✓	2.75	3.91e-1	✗	9.04	9.36e-3	✓	4	0.18	✓	0.1	✓	0.18	✓
5	7.56	1.92e-2	✓	1.59	7.63e-1	✗	17.88	5.33e-4	✓	5	0.11	✓	0.046	✗	0.15	✓
6	21.36	2.03e-4	✓	2.19	5.62e-1	✗	9.04	9.36e-3	✓	6	0.16	✓	0.043	✗	0.15	✓
7	7.67	1.86e-2	✓	2.67	4.07e-1	✗	9.33	8.68e-3	✓	7	0.11	✓	0.066	✗	0.14	✓
8	4.03	1.6e-1	✗	1.32	8.59e-1	✗	24.18	5.07e-4	✓	8	0.13	✓	0.068	✗	0.17	✓
9	4.93	9.4e-2	✗	1	9.46e-1	✗	4.93	9.4e-2	✗	9	0.083	✗	0.026	✗	0.13	✓
10	13.75	1.59e-3	✓	1.59	7.63e-1	✗	11	4.11e-3	✓	10	0.14	✓	0.046	✗	0.15	✓

Records per page: 10 25 50 100
 << Page 1 of 10 >>
 Showing 1 to 10 of 100 entries

5.4.3.2 Group comparison Summary

The summary of group comparison shows for each group the percentage of replicates that led to a successful test.

Definition Exploration Simulation **Results** Plots

SIMULATION
ENDPOINTS
GROUP COMPARISON

Summary

Percentage of success over replicates

ENDPOINT	BID_200MGPERDAY_			OD_300MGPERDAY_			BID_300MGPERDAY_		
	SUCCESS%	CI 95% LOWER	CI 95% UPPER	SUCCESS%	CI 95% LOWER	CI 95% UPPER	SUCCESS%	CI 95% LOWER	CI 95% UPPER
Efficacy	65	55.25	73.64	0	0	3.7	92	85	95.89
median_inhibitionAtTrough	65	55.25	73.64	4	1.57	9.84	85	76.72	90.69

Starting from version 2024R1, the success rate across the replicates is now complemented by the corresponding confidence interval. The formula is based on the Wilson interval formula given by:

$$CI_W = \frac{X + \kappa^2/2}{n + \kappa^2} \pm \frac{\kappa\sqrt{n}}{n + \kappa^2} \sqrt{\hat{p}\hat{q} + \kappa^2/(4n)}$$

where n is the number of replicates, X the number of successful trials over the replicates, $\hat{p} = \frac{X}{n}$ corresponds to the rate of successful trials, $\hat{q} = 1 - \hat{p}$ to the rate of unsuccessful trials. κ corresponds to the α level's z-score, where $\alpha = 0.05$ for a 95% confidence interval.

5.4.4 Export Simulations

5.4.4.1 Export simulations as output files at each run

The full table of simulated values can be generated at each run if the preference setting “Export simulation files” is true. It will then appear in the result folder > Simulation > simulation_xxx.txt with xxx the output variable name.

5.4.4.2 Export simulations as a Monolix or PKanalix project

Note that this option not available in Simulx versions prior to 2023.

After running simulations, it is possible to generate a new Monolix or PKanalix project using the simulated values as dataset. This can be done from the menu Export > Export project to:

In the pop-up window, you can choose:

- to which application you want to export the simulated dataset: PKanalix or Monolix.
- names to the generated dataset (based on simulations) and generated model file (if the model is not part of the library).

Project export

Export configuration

General

Target software

Monolix

PKanalix

Generated files will be saved next to the exported project.

Data

File name

data_generated.csv

Model

File name

model_generated.txt

CLOSE EXPORT

Click the “EXPORT” button at the bottom to confirm. The target application (Monolix or PKanalix) will open automatically with a predefined project called “untitled”. The simulated dataset and model files (if not from the library) will be copied next to the new new project – first in the temporary folder, when the project is “untitled”, then to the final destination, where you save the project.

The dataset in the new project will be set in the following way:

- A column ID contains the identifiers for the individuals simulated in the Simulx project. It is tagged as ID if no replicates have been used in Simulx.
- If replicates have been simulated, a UID column containing a unique identifier combining replicate and ids (eg 1_rep1) is tagged as ID, and a rep column indicates the replicate (it is possible to use filters to select a single replicate if necessary).
- If external elements have been used in Simulx, original IDs coming from these elements are indicated in a column original_id which is ignored by default, but can be tagged by the user as categorical covariate or ID, depending on the situation.
- Simulation groups are given in a column group tagged as stratification categorical covariate.
- If several model outputs are simulated, the output names are indicated in an obsid column tagged as observation ID.
- Pre-defined tagging is used for time, observation, amount, and simulated covariates.

LINE NUMBER	rep	ID	UID	original_id	TIME	obs	obsid	AMOUNT	age	wt	sex	group
1	1		1_rep1	2					31	66.7	1	gr_BID_N30
2	1	1	1_rep1	2	0			4	31	66.7	1	gr_BID_N30
30	1	1	1_rep1	2	0	-0.157348	y1		31	66.7	1	gr_BID_N30
33	1	1	1_rep1	2	0	108.048	y2		31	66.7	1	gr_BID_N30
3	1	1	1_rep1	2	12			4	31	66.7	1	gr_BID_N30
4	1	1	1_rep1	2	24			2	31	66.7	1	gr_BID_N30
5	1	1	1_rep1	2	36			2	31	66.7	1	gr_BID_N30
6	1	1	1_rep1	2	48			2	31	66.7	1	gr_BID_N30
7	1	1	1_rep1	2	60			2	31	66.7	1	gr_BID_N30

For an export to PKanalix, the new project will be set in the following way:

- the data is set as described above.
- NCA settings: default PKanalix settings for administration type, integral method, treatment of BLQ values, parameters
- NCA settings: “observation ID to use” set to the first one alphabetically (if obsid are strings) or numerically (if obsid are integers).
- Acceptance criteria: not selected.
- Bioequivalence: default PKanalix settings
- the structural model is set to the generated model file attached to the new project, or a model from the library if the Simulx project used a library model.
 - The generated structural model only includes the [LONGITUDINAL] block of the Simulx model, without the error model.
 - If a statistical model was used in simulx (observation or individual model), it is not included in the generated model file for PKanalix.
 - The mapping automatically links the simulated observations to the model outputs.
 - If additional lines were used in the Simulx project, they are added at the end of the generated structural model file.
 - If output elements are defined based on intermediate variables of the model in the Simulx project, they are added to the output section of the model.
- The mapping automatically links the simulated observations to the model outputs. If a statistical model was used in simulx (observation or individual model), it is not included in the generated model file for PKanalix. The generated model only includes the [LONGITUDINAL] block without DEFINITION section.
- CA initial parameter values: set to default

- CA parameters constraints: none for normally distributed parameters, positive for log-normally distributed parameters; bounded with limits imported from the Monolix project for logit-normally and probit-normally distributed parameters.
- CA calculations settings: default PKanalix settings

For an export to Monolix, the project will be set in the following way:

- the data is set as described above.
- the structural model is set to the generated model file attached to the new project, or a model from the library if the Simulx project used a library model.
 - The generated structural model only includes the [LONGITUDINAL] block of the Simulx model, without the error model.
 - The mapping automatically links the simulated observations to the model outputs.
 - If additional lines were used in the Simulx project, they are added at the end of the generated structural model file.
 - If output elements are defined based on intermediate variables of the model in the Simulx project, they are added to the output section of the model.
- Initial values are set to default.
- the observation model and individual model in Monolix statistical model tab is set based on the Simulx project, if a statistical model was defined in the model of the Simulx project (INDIVIDUAL, COVARIATE blocks or error model in the LONGITUDINAL block). Note that the statistical model is not included in the generated model file for Monolix, but it is taken into account in the statistical model tab. Only the Monolix style syntax for the INDIVIDUAL block can be imported to the Monolix project, not the flexible style. When modifications are done to the model for compatibility reasons, Simulx warns you at export to double check the model interpretation in the Monolix project.
- if some part of the statistical model is not defined in the Simulx project, it is set to default in the statistical model tab.

5.4.4.2.1 Export simulations as a formatted dataset

 Note that this option not available in Simulx versions prior to 2021.

To export simulations as a formatted dataset for further investigations outside the Monolixsuite, it is possible to use the menu Export > Export simulated data. This data set contains the dose, occasions, covariate, simulation groups, observation id informations in addition to the id, time and simulated values. The exported simulated data file is located in the result folder > Simulation > simulatedData.txt.

5.4.4.2.2 Share a Simulx project

The 2024 version of MonolixSuite introduces a highly convenient method for sharing projects. Simply click on “Share Project” in the export menu, and a zip folder is generated containing all the required files to re-open the project (dataset if applicable, model if applicable, external files if applicable, smlx file, result folder). By default, the suggested location for the zipped shared project matches that of the original, but this can be easily modified to any other location on the computer.

5.4.5 General display options

The tables generally contain many rows and are by default paginated. The page displayed and the number of records per page can be changed at the bottom (green highlight). The **Display** panel on the right (blue highlight) allows to switch the pagination off in order to show the entire table. The tables can also be all expanded and collapsed. When several groups and several output variables/outcomes/endpoints have been defined, the tables can be grouped by either simulation group or output/output/endpoint to easily compare the tables of interest. Finally it is possible to hide some of the simulation groups using the drop-down selection menu. The display panel can be hidden with the button at the top left. Only the displayed page is copied. To copy the entire table, expand it first.

The screenshot shows the Simulx interface with the 'Results' tab selected. The main content area displays a table of simulation results for the outcome 'Ctrough_aboveTh'. The table is organized into three columns: OD, BID, and TID. Each column has a 'rep ID' and a 'Ctrough_aboveTh' value. The table is paginated, showing 10 entries per page. The right sidebar contains a 'Display' panel with options for 'Pagination', 'COLLAPSE ALL', 'EXPAND ALL', and 'Group by' (Outcome, Group). The 'Outcome' group is selected, and 'Ctrough_aboveTh' is the selected item. The bottom of the table shows pagination controls for each column, including 'Records per page' and 'Page 1 of 42'.

OD			BID			TID		
rep	ID	Ctrough_aboveTh	rep	ID	Ctrough_aboveTh	rep	ID	Ctrough_aboveTh
1	1	false	1	43	true	1	85	false
1	2	false	1	44	false	1	86	false
1	3	false	1	45	false	1	87	true
1	4	false	1	46	true	1	88	true
1	5	true	1	47	true	1	89	false
1	6	false	1	48	false	1	90	true
1	7	false	1	49	true	1	91	true
1	8	true	1	50	true	1	92	true
1	9	false	1	51	false	1	93	true
1	10	false	1	52	true	1	94	true

5.5 Plots

Running the tasks in Simulx **automatically generates interactive plots** for simulation outputs, outcomes and endpoints. Interface provides many plots features such as:

- Different chart types depending on simulation outputs and post-processing methods: individual outputs or distributions.
- Plots settings: display, binning criteria, axes, visual cues.
- Stratification and customization options.
- Export: plots as images, charts data and charts settings.

To learn more about plots in the exploration tab, click [here](#) – it is a special documentation page for the model Exploration feature.

5.5.1 The Plots tab

Plots tab structure and settings in Simulx is the same as in Monolix and Pkanalix. The left panel (green frame) contains the list of available plots grouped by outcome type or by chart type. Central region displays one selected plot, for instance output distribution of Cc. Each simulation group has its own subplot. On top of the plotting area, there are layout options and a button to export current plot as an image (blue frame). The right panel is for plots settings, such as display or axis options, definition of

bins or visual cues. In addition, separate sub-tabs at the bottom of this panel (red frame) allow to stratify plots data and change preferences of the plotting area.

- **Simulation outputs.** Only output elements used in a simulation scenario generate plots. If more than one simulation output element uses the same model output, then all these simulation outputs are merged on one same plot. For instance, concentration during the whole treatment period on a fine grid and C_{trough} on the last treatment day – both using model prediction C_c . Title name of the plot corresponds to the model output name.
- **Outcomes.** Outcomes of different endpoints have separate plots, for instance “ C_{max} ” and “ $C_{maxBelow800}$ ”. If there is more than one outcome in an endpoint, then a plot displays the combination of them. Moreover, it appears in the plots list as “<endpointName>_outcome”, for instance “SafetyAndEfficacy_outcome”.
- **Endpoints** distribution is generated only for simulations with replicates.

5.5.2 Plots for continuous data

There are two types of plots for continuous outputs. Firstly, the individual output subplot, which contains individual curves. Secondly, the output distribution with the percentiles. Title of each outcome section in the plot list corresponds to the name of a model variable, for instance C_c for model predictions or y_1 for model observations. It is not the name of the output element selected in the simulation tab.

5.5.2.1 Individual output

Individual output plots represent individual curves computed for each id and each occasion (if present in the model). It is possible to DISPLAY lines, dots and median with standard deviations (green frame), or a combination of them. The statistics (median and standard deviations) use the binning options available in the BINS section of the settings (blue frame). If simulation uses replicates, then by default a plot shows only one replicate. However, you can select other replicates – one or several – in the DISPLAY sub-tab.

The ID used in plots stratification is the simulated ID, which is the id column in the result tables. ID i is the i -st parameter set sampled for simulation.

Since the version 2023R1, if a simulation uses elements with custom id lists, for example a table of individual treatments, or a table of individual parameters, the original ids in these tables are available to stratify the plots. For example in the demo project “importFromMonolix_useEBEs_originalID.smlx”, we use the element `mlx_EBEs` which is a table of individual parameters. The original IDs used in this table can be used to color or split the individual output trajectories.

5.5.2.2 Output distribution

Output distribution plots show percentiles of the simulated data for all ids and all replicates computed. The BINS section of the settings contains the binning options. DISPLAY settings allow to change plot features, such as median, number of percentiles bands and levels.

When the “Output distribution” plot is split (by simulation group or by a covariate), it is possible to overlay the prediction intervals on a single plot with different colors using the “merged splits” toggle. You can choose the colors in the “stratification groups”. This feature is available starting from the Simulx 2023 version.

5.5.3 Plots for non-continuous data

5.5.3.1 Time-to-event

Individual output of time-to-event data is a single Kaplan-Meier curve – estimator of the survival function. In addition, for simulations with replicates, the Kaplan-Meier curves for each replicate are interpolated on one grid and displayed as a prediction interval at a specific level (blue frame). Mean number of subjects plot is available in the SUBPLOTS section (green frame). Click here for more information about time-to-event data plots.

5.5.3.2 Discrete data (categorical and count)

Individual outputs are functions of time for each individual and occasion.

- Count data: plots show the number of observed events in a specific period, for instance “number of good answers” (on the left).
- Categorical data: plots show nominal categories, for instance “respiratory status level” (on the right).

Output distribution shows the time evolution of probabilities of different categories. In case of count data, each number of “counts” constitutes a separate category.

5.5.4 Plots for outcomes and endpoints

- Outcomes represent a post-processing of the simulation outputs done for each individual, so plots display their distribution within a population. Simulx displays only outcomes used in endpoints (Outcome&endpoint section in the simulation tab). If there are several outcomes in

one endpoint, then the outcome distribution corresponds to of a combination of these outcomes, and not to separate outcomes.

- Depending on a type of an outcome, plots are histograms or box plots for numeric outcomes, and stacked histograms for binary outcomes.
- Endpoints summarize the outcome values over all individuals. In simulation with replicates, Simulx displays them as box plots.
- In all boxplots, the dashed line represents the median, the blue box represents the 25th and 75th percentiles (Q1 and Q3), and the whiskers extend to the most extreme data points, outliers excluded. Outliers are the points larger than $Q1 + w*(Q3 - Q1)$ or smaller than $Q1 - w*(Q3 - Q1)$ with $w=1.5$. Outliers are shown with red crosses.

[Demo: 6.1.outcome_endpoint/OutcomeEndpoint_PKPD_Cmax_targetinhibition]

5.5.4.1 Numeric outcome distribution

“Cmax” outcome gives for each individual the maximum of the output element “Plasma concentration”. In this case, the outcome distribution can be a box-plot or as a histogram (selection in the DISPLAY settings). Each group is on a separate subplot. This outcome is the only outcome in the endpoint, so the title name of the plot in the list coincides with the outcome name.

5.5.4.2 Binary outcome distribution

“CmaxBelow800” outcome is a of boolean type (true/false) and compares the maximal value of the “Plasma concentration” with a threshold of 800. If Cmax is below this value, then the outcome is true, otherwise it is false. Similarly, “inhibitionAtTroughAbove80Percent” outcome compares the average of the values in the output element “TargetInhibition_at168h” with a threshold of 0.8 (i.e 80%). These two outcomes belong to one endpoint “SafetyAndEfficacy”, so the plot shows the distribution of true/false values corresponding to the combination of the two conditions. In this case, the title name of the outcome plot is the name of the endpoint “_outcome” (red frame). Binary outcomes use stacked or

grouped histograms (green frame). Hovering on a any part of the histogram highlights it, shows the outcome value and the corresponding number of individuals.

5.5.4.3 Endpoint distribution

If this simulation scenario is run several times – option “replicates” available in the Simulation section – then the endpoint distribution plots are added to the plots list. Endpoint median_Cmax is a a box-plot with median value and standard errors for groups listed on the x-axis. For endpoints using numerical outcomes, uncertainty of the 5th and 95th percentiles can be added from the settings – SUBPLOTS section (green frame).

Endpoints using binary outcomes, in this example the SafetyAndEfficacy endpoint, calculate the percentage of individuals with “true” outcomes values. As previously, the endpoint distribution is a box-plots with different groups on the x-axis. A subplot with the number of individuals is available from the settings.

5.5.5 Plots features

The right panel of the Plots tab has several sub-tabs – at the bottom of the interface window – to interact and customize the charts:

- “Settings” modify plots elements, such as: hide or display additional data, adjust binning criteria, change axis or add visual cues
- “Stratify” splits, filters or colors data points using covariates.
- “Preferences” customize graphical aspects of plots such as colors, font sizes, line width or margins.

Icons at the left-top angle of the plotting area – – allow to select sub-plots for visualization, change the sub-plots layout and export the plots as a png or svg file (saved in the Chart folder in the Results). In addition, using the “Export” in the top menu saves all generated plots (Export plots), saves all data used to generate plots as txt files to re-plot them outside Simulx (Export charts data, see here for more information) and save charts settings so that the selected customization is applied to all Simulx projects (Export charts settings as default).

Simulx has the same architecture of plots features, preferences and export options as Monolix. **Here** is an **extensive documentation** about it, with links to **Features of the week videos** that explain how to use customization in MonolixSuite applications.

5.5.5.1 Settings

Settings sub tab has several sections, which may differ between plot.

- **General** settings include toggle buttons add legend, data information, dosing etc. Zoom is interactive by selecting with a cursor a region directly on a plot.
- **Display** section for “individual output” plots has toggle buttons to add lines, data dots and Mean and SD (at least one option needs to be selected). For “output distribution” it customizes the level of percentiles and the number of bands shown.
- **Bins** serve to specify the criteria for computing the mean&SD for the “individual outputs” and percentiles for the “output distribution”. There are several strategies to segment the data: equal width, equal size and the least squares criterion. In addition, number of bins, range and number of data per bin are changeable.
- **Axes** is for general X and Y axis settings, such as log scale, same limits across plots and main axis titles.
- **Visual cues** freehand guides option allow to place additional lines or points on plots directly with a cursor. Definition of a specific location is via (X,Y) coordinates – one entry filled gives a line, two filled entries specify a point.

5.5.5.2 Stratify

Stratification panel contains a list of covariates that can split, color or filter the data. Simulx automatically allocates covariates in groups – according to modalities for categorical covariates and in

two “equal count” groups for continuous covariates. As a result stratification is immediately applied after ticking appropriate boxes.

Example:

- Color data according to two weight groups (blue frame)
- Split data between HV (healthy volunteers) and RA (rheumatoid arthritis) patients (green frame)

When the “Output distribution” plot is split (by simulation group or by a covariate), it is possible to overlay the prediction intervals on a single plot with different colors using the “merged splits” toggle. The colors can be chosen in the “stratification groups”. This feature is available starting from the 2023 version.

6 FAQ

6.1 Frequently asked questions

We list here the questions regarding the use of Simulx when everything runs fine. If you have an issue with download, installation, run and display, please check Frequent installation issues.

If you think there is a bug in one of the MonolixSuite apps, please check if it is already in our List of known bugs, and otherwise write us at support@lixoft.com.

6.1.1 General

- **How can I reuse my previous mlxR scripts (which were using the simulx() R function)?** Simulx has evolved a lot between the 2019 and 2020 versions, and its API also. mlxR (and its simulx() function) is not compatible with Simulx versions starting from 2020. However, Simulx 2020 is available via a very convenient and intuitive GUI, and via a complete R API, which allows to do from R any step that exists in the GUI. To make the transition smoother, we also provide an additional R package RsSimulx with a simulx() wrapper function using the R API, very similar to the simulx() function of mlxR. All deprecated arguments coming from the mlxR syntax will generate a warning with RsSimulx versions starting from 2.0.0.
- **It is possible to automatically convert a Nonmem model to a Simulx model?** No, but the conversion is relatively easy. For the structural model, you can replace the Nonmem ADVAN routines 1-3 by the pkmodel macro, and the syntax for ODEs is easy to adapt. Parameter distributions and covariate effects are defined in the [\[INDIVIDUAL\] section](#). You can also check our case studies (video and slides) "[Setting up a simulation from scratch](#)" will give examples of translations from Nonmem to Simulx.
- **How can I share a Simulx project?** A Simulx project is composed of a .smlx file, possibly external files you have used to define elements (model file, covariate table, etc) and a result folder. All these must be shared, keeping the relative path between them. In the Simulx project settings (**Settings > Project settings > "Save the user files in the results folder"**), you can request to save the external files (model and other input files) in the result folder. This way, you only need to share the .smlx file and the result folder.
- **How fast is Simulx?** Simulx is very fast because it performs the calculations using a C++ engine (the same as Monolix).
- **Is it possible to script my simulations?** Yes. All actions done in the GUI can also be done via R functions. Have a look at the lixoftConnectors.

6.1.2 Model

- **Do I have to define correlations between all parameters (i.e full omega matrix)?** No. The omega matrix need to be block diagonal only. [See the correlation definition here.](#)

6.1.3 Definition tab

- **Is it possible to include uncertainty of the population parameters?** Yes. If you have obtained sets of population parameters via bootstrap, you can define the [population parameter element via an external file](#) with several lines, each line corresponding to a different set of population parameters. You can also define the population parameters using the type “distribution” which will allow to sample the population distribution from an uncertainty distribution. You can for instance choose normal distributions and give the estimated standard errors in the “sd” column. However this does not include correlations between estimates. To include those, you need to sample to population parameters from their uncertainty distribution outside Simulx and provide them as external file. We will provide soon a R package Rssimulx to help for this. Note that the a different of population parameters will be used for each replicate.
- **Is it possible to sample covariates from a truncated normal distribution?** Not yet. For the moment you can use a logit distribution if you need bounds, or sample the covariate elsewhere and provide an external file.
- **Can I flexibly define a treatment depending on covariates (such as WT or BSA)?** Yes, this is possible if you have the covariate appearing in your model. Select “[scale amount by a covariate](#)” in the treatment definition.

6.1.4 Simulation tab

- **Can we perform trial simulations accounting for drop-outs?** You can define a joint model with PD and a time-to-event model representing the drop-outs. Simulx will simulate the time of drop-out, but not remove observations happening after the drop-out. This will request to post-process the results outside Simulx.
- **Can I calculate the time of Cmax?** This can be done in the [outcome definition](#). Select the output corresponding to the concentration, then “max per id” and “time of max”.

6.1.5 Results and outputs

- **How can I get the simulated values?** The population parameters, individual parameters, doses, covariates and regressors are saved as .txt files in the Simulation folder of the result folder. By default the simulated values are not exported because they can be very large in size. However it is possible to choose this option in **Settings > Preferences > Export simulation files**. Outcomes and endpoints are saved in the Endpoints folder of the results. You can also get the results using the lixoftConnectors R package.
- **What is the best way to post-process the Simulx results in R?** You can use the R package lixoftConnectors to interact with your Simulx run. In particular, the function

`getSimulationResults()` allows you to recover all results. These results can then be post-processed using typical R code.

6.1.6 Plots

- **Is it possible to display a 90% prediction interval?** Yes, by default the different shades of blue in the “Output distribution” plot represent different percentiles. If in the “Display” settings in the right panel you choose `band=2` and `level=90`, then you will see a 90% prediction interval.

6.1.7 lixoftConnectors

- **setGroupElement() worked in 2021R1 but gives an error in the 2021R2 version.** The error message has been added in the R2 version when potentially incompatible elements are set together, eg. parameters as EBEs and covariates. In this case you need to set each element separately, as the error message suggests.
- **getSimulationResults() does not return results** It can happen if the results are too large (too many data points). In the 2021R2 version there are additional two arguments, `ID` and `REP`, to request a subset of results.

6.2 Submission of Simulx runs to regulatory agencies

Simulx is used a part of **regulatory submissions (including the FDA and the EMA)** of simulations with population PK and PK/PD models. The FDA and the EMA do have access to Simulx and the modelling and simulation experts to understand, review and run Simulx. In addition, regulators are also taking part in publishing research articles with Monolix and Simulx.

6.2.1 Files to include for submissions

Regulatory guidelines provide only little information on the required electronic files for submission. Based on exchanges with regulatory agencies and confirmed through past regulatory submissions using Simulx, the following listed files in Table 1 and 2 are required as part of a submission package.

Table 1 lists all files needed to run Simulx and reproduce the results and diagnostic plots. A Simulx project can depend on several external files. In order to bring required file into the same folder, we strongly suggest to set **Settings > Project Settings > Save the user files in the results folder**, and re-save the project.

Table 2 lists the files containing the simulation results. The simulated values are by default not exported as txt file. In order to be able to include this file in your submission, set **Settings > Preferences > Export simulation files** and run the simulation again. If you prefer to generate a single file as formatted dataset containing both the design (covariates, doses, etc) and the simulated values, use **Export > Export simulated dataset**.

It is also possible to create a .zip containing all requires input files, as well as all results with **Export > Share project**.

Note that all files are in a human readable format. Thus, the information contained in these files can also be included into the appendices of the report creating one single document that contains everything to reproduce the results.

All MonolixSuite file types are accepted by the FDA and are listed in the "Specifications for File Format Types Using eCTD Specifications".

Table 1 Simulx files required for reproducibility of results

File	When to include	Content	File extension
Simulx project file (.smlx)	Always	Path to external files (dataset, model, parameters, etc), defined simulation element, settings	.smlx
All files in "DataFile" folder	If a project has been imported from Monolix	Input dataset used in imported Monolix project (and additional columns files if applicable)	.txt, .csv, .xls, .xlsx, .sas2 bdat or .xpt
All files in "External files" folder	If external files have been used and this folder exists	External files used in the definition of the simulation elements	.txt
Model file in "ModelFile" folder	If not using a model from the libraries	Structural (and possibly statistical) model in mlxtran syntax	.txt
Plot properties (.smlxproperties)	Always (except if file not present because only default settings)	Plot stratify, settings and preferences	.smlxproperties

Table 2 Simulx files containing the key results

File	When to include	Content	File extension
Simulation/ simulation_XXX.txt	Always	Simulated values	.txt
simulatedData.csv	As alternative to simulation_XXX.txt	Simulated values as formatted dataset containing also the design (doses, covariates, etc)	.csv

All files in "Endpoints" folder	If outcome/endpoints have been run	Individual outcomes and endpoints over simulation groups	.txt
---------------------------------	------------------------------------	--	------

6.2.2 Examples of submissions

This section lists examples of Clinical pharmacology reviews (FDA) and Assessment reports (EMA) explicitly mentioning the use of MonolixSuite.

6.2.2.1 Submissions to the FDA using MonolixSuite

- ZALTRAP (Aflibercept) - Sanofi - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- CORLANOR (Ivabradine) - Amgen - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- JEVTANA (Cabazitaxel) - Sanofi - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- PONVORY (Ponesimod) - Janssen - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- RYZNEUTA (Efbemalenograstim) - Evive Biotechnology Singapore - Integrated review ([link](#))
- EXBLIFEP (Cefepime and enmetazobactam) - Allecra Therapeutics - Integrated review ([link](#))

6.2.2.2 Submission to the EMA using MonolixSuite

- OSELTAMIVIR (Tamiflu) - Roche - Assesment report ([link](#))
(Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/000402/II/0110/G – EMA/CHMP/186699/2015)
- BOSENTAN (Tracleer) - Actelion - Assessment report ([link](#))
(Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/000401/II/0066 – EMA/168487/2015)
- ISATUXIMAB (Sarclisa) - Sanofi - Assesment report ([link](#)) and Statistical analysis plan ([link](#))
(Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004977/II/0003 – EMA/CHMP/186236/2021)

6.2.3 Publications by the FDA using MonolixSuite

This section lists a few (non-exhaustive) publications by the FDA using MonolixSuite.

- "Plasma pharmacokinetics of ceftiofur metabolite desfuroylceftiofur cysteine disulfide in holstein steers: application of nonlinear mixed-effects modeling.", *J Vet Pharmacol Ther* 2016 Apr;39(2):149-56, DOI: 10.1111/jvp.12245. *O. A. Chiesa, S. Feng, P. Kijak, E. A. Smith, H. Li and J. Qiu.*
- "Quantification of disease progression and dropout for Alzheimer's disease.", *Int. Journal of Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, Volume 51 – February (120 – 131),(Doi: 10.5414/CP201787). *D. William-Faltaos, Y. Chen, Y. Wang, J. Gobburu,, and H. Zhu.*
- "Estimation of Population Pharmacokinetic Parameters Using MLXTRAN Interpreter in MONOLIX 2.4", *D. William Faltaos, Acop* 2009.

6.2.4 Regulatory guidelines

- EMA “Guideline on reporting the results of population pharmacokinetic analyses” (CHMP/EWP/185990/06): details what should be contained in a PK or PK/PD analysis report.
- FDA “Population pharmacokinetics – Guidance for industry” (2022): guidance on how to present the results of a population pharmacokinetic analysis and the information to be included. It also addresses “Electronic Files”.
- FDA “Exposure-Response Relationships – Study Design, Data Analysis, and Regulatory Applications – Guidance for Industry”. (2003)

7 Advanced topics

7.1 Creating forest plots

The process of creating forest plots based on a Monolix project is explained in this video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BgGhaAFTpcs>

Below you can find an example R function that creates forest plots for visualization of covariate effects on a typical individual based on a Simulx project, as described in the video above. The function `plotCovariateEffects` takes two arguments:

- `project` – path to the Simulx project,
- `outcome` – name of the outcome that calculates the exposure parameter.

Certain elements of created forest plots will be based on the names of simulation groups and outcomes in the used Simulx project. Here is an image describing the origin of those elements:


```
library(ggplot2)
library(dplyr)
library(LixoftConnectors)

plotCovariateEffects <- function(project, outcome) {

  # Load a project
  initializeLixoftConnectors("simulx", force = TRUE)
  loadProject(project)
```

```

# Get and format results
results <- getEndpointsResults()$outcomes
summary <- results[[outcome]] %>% group_by(group) %>%
  summarise(
    mid = quantile(.data[[outcome]], 0.5),
    lower = quantile(.data[[outcome]], 0.05),
    upper = quantile(.data[[outcome]], 0.95)
  )

reference_value <- summary[summary$group == "Reference", ]$mid
summary <- summary %>%
  mutate(across(mid:upper, .fns = ~.x/reference_value)) %>%
  mutate(
    LABEL = paste0(
      format(round(mid, 2), nsmall = 2),
      " [",
      format(round(lower, 2), nsmall = 2),
      "-",
      format(round(upper, 2), nsmall = 2),
      "]"
    )
  )
)

summary$covname <- gsub("_.*", "", summary$group)
summary$label <- gsub("^(.*?)_", "", summary$group)
summary$label <- gsub("_", " ", summary$label) %>% paste("\n", summary$LABEL)

# Plot the results
print(
  ggplot(data = summary[summary$covname != "Reference",], aes_string(
    y = "label",
    x = "mid",
    xmin = "lower",
    xmax = "upper"
  )) +
  geom_pointrange(
    aes(color = "90% CI\nCovariate Effects"),
    size = 1,
    alpha = 1
  ) +
  annotate("rect", xmin = min(0.8), xmax = max(1.25),
    ymin = -Inf, ymax = Inf, fill = "gray", alpha=0.1) +
  geom_vline(aes(xintercept = 1, linetype = "Reference"), linetype = "dashed") +
  facet_grid(covname ~ ., scales = "free_y", switch = "y") +
  labs(y = "", x = paste(outcome, "Relative to Reference Value"),
    colour = "", linetype = "") +
  theme_bw() +
  scale_color_manual(values = c("blue"))
)
}

```

It is possible to automate the process of creating the Simulx project using *lixoftConnectors*. Here you can download two examples that start from a Monolix project and create a Simulx project and forest plots completely in R using *lixoftConnectors*: forest_plots.zip. Example 1 creates forest plots that visualize effect of covariates on a typical individual, while example 2 creates forest plots that illustrate individual exposure.

The explanation of the process is described in this video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hFQB3fAlcmA>

7.2 Calculating exposure metrics

Exposure-response analysis is an important tool for guiding clinical trial decisions, in particular dose selection and justification. It allows us to determine the relationship between the drug exposure and the drug effect, whether the effect is therapeutic or toxic. The first step of this process: calculating exposure metrics. These metrics help us describe the drug's presence in the body - how much, how long and how it changes - and are essential for exposure-response analysis.

<https://youtu.be/sib3mbBWO1c>

Link to download materials from the Feature of the Week Video: download

Some of the **most common exposure metrics** include:

- C_{max}, that is the peak concentration of the drug in the body, and
- AUC, or area under the concentration curve, which reflects overall drug exposure.

For **multi-dose regimens**, we also calculate:

- partial AUC, which is the AUC over a specific time interval, like between two doses or daily; and
- C trough which is the minimum concentration before the next dose.

Metrics at steady state, such as C_{max} and average steady-state concentrations, are also frequently used. These metrics represent the drug's equilibrium, where the amount entering and leaving the body is balanced. This makes them especially useful for assessing long-term drug effects.

Exposure-response workflow:

First we built a PK model in Monolix. Then, we export this model to Simulx to calculate exposures. We can calculate exposures directly in Simulx, or simulate time-concentration curves and calculate exposures outside of Simulx using tools like R. Finally, we merge the exposure metrics with PD data and use them to build the exposure-response model in Monolix.

Example Case Study:

Dataset for a rug targeting PCSK9 to lower the cholesterol levels in the blood. PK data is the drug concentration over time and response data is the change from baseline in LDLc levels. There are 50 individuals who received 12 doses - one dose every 2 weeks over a six months period. Sampling is dense after the first dose, but for the rest of the study, we mostly have trough samples. At 6 months the drug concentration is at steady state.

The response data in this study was also collected up to 6 months. In the following examples only subsets of this dataset will be used to explain the workflows of exposure calculation.

7.2.1 Exposure metrics in a single time interval

Consider that there is only one response value per individual at time 168 days and the goal is to link it with the exposures at steady state. To be sure that steady-state has been reached for all individuals, the steady state will correspond to the inter-dose interval after the last dose. C_{max} , C_{trough} and C_{avg} at steady state can be easily calculated using post-processing in Simulx's outcomes and endpoints module.

Steps Cmax, Ctrough, Cavg:

- Export the Monolix project with a PK model and results to Simulx. The model, parameters and treatment information will be imported.
- In the simulation tab: switch the parameter from `mlx_pop` to `mlx_EBEs` to simulate the individuals from the original study, not a new population. Note that `mlx_Adm` is selected by default, which allows to re-simulate the original treatment regimen.
- Define a new output element using model prediction of the drug concentration on a regular time grid covering the interval from 154 to 168, which corresponds to two weeks (it's one inter-dose interval after the last dose). Rename this output element, e.g. `ConcSs`
- Add new output to the simulation scenario.
- Create outcomes based on this new output element. For Cmax, select "max value per id" as the post-processing option; for Ctrough choose "last value per id"; for average concentration use the "average value per id" option.

Steps AUC:

For AUC, the calculation requires a few additional steps, as it's not directly available in the post-processing menu. To compute AUC in Simulx, add its definition to the model via the "additional lines" option. For cumulative AUC:

```
AUC_0 = 0
ddt_AUC = concentration_variable
```

This integrates the concentration profile from the start to a defined time point.

- To compute AUC between two specific time points `t1` and `t2`, use an "if/else" statement that calculates AUC from 0 to `t1` and from 0 to `t2`. The partial AUC for the interval from `t1` to `t2` is simply the difference between these two values. In this example, `t1=154` and `t2=168`.
Reminder Mlxtran syntax: If/else statement cannot contain ODEs equations. Define an intermediate variable, e.g. `dAUCt1`, and use it as the "right hand side" of an ODE.

```
t1 = 154
t2 = 168
AUCt1_0 = 0
if(t < t1)
  dAUCt1 = concentration_variable
else
  dAUCt1 = 0
end
ddt_AUCt1 = dAUCt1

AUCt2_0 = 0
if(t < t2)
  dAUCt2 = concentration_variable
else
  dAUCt2 = 0
end
```

```
ddt_AUCt2 = dAUCt2
```

```
AUC168 = AUCt2 - AUCt1
```

- Create an output element for AUC using variables in the “intermediate outputs” menu. Instead of using a full time grid, use the manual method and extract the value only at t=168 to reduce computational cost.
- Add the new output to the simulation.
- Create an outcome for AUC - no post-processing is required but with an outcome equal to the output all the metrics are in the same result file.

Once the setup is complete, run simulation and outcomes and endpoints tasks. The results include dedicated plots for each outcome and are also presented in outcome tables. They are also saved in the output files in the result folder and can be used to merge them with the response data.

Note: You can add several partial AUC in this way, for example AUC on day 1 and day 3. It requires writing the code for each partial AUC, so if you need more than a few values, it is easier to simulate the concentration profiles on a dense time grid and calculate AUCs as a post-processing outside Simulx – see the section for inter-dose/daily AUC calculations.

7.2.1.1 Merge exposure metrics with response data via data formatting module.

Data formatting module in Monolix allows to add information from external files to a dataset for analysis without modifying the original dataset. There are two important rules:

1. The file you want to add can have only one value per individual, e.g. constant in time exposure metrics at steady state.
2. The response dataset and files with exposure metrics must have
 - a. the same number of individuals
 - b. the same subject identifiers in the column ID,

Response Dataset

ID	TIME	RESPONSE
1	168	-91.45
2	168	-56.68
3	168	-59.84
4	168	-55.94
5	168	-83.02
6	168	-26.63
7	168	-104.42
8	168	-94.22
9	168	-66.04
10	168	-96.95
11	168	-58.32
12	168	-61.37
13	168	-82.82

Outcome File from Simulx

id	original_id	AucSS	group
1	1	1578.87	simulationGroup1
2	2	1415.06	simulationGroup1
3	3	905.095	simulationGroup1
4	4	1707.71	simulationGroup1
5	5	1837.86	simulationGroup1
6	6	976.89	simulationGroup1
7	7	1958.44	simulationGroup1
8	8	2418.81	simulationGroup1
9	9	1808.89	simulationGroup1
10	10	1855.9	simulationGroup1
11	11	1373.97	simulationGroup1
12	12	1948.42	simulationGroup1
13	13	3707.51	simulationGroup1

When it's not the case - ID in a response dataset is not an integer from 1 to N, but is a custom number or a string - Simulx outcomes files cannot be merged directly in data formatting (column ID in the response dataset will be different from the column id in the outcome file).

ID	TIME	RESPONSE
SUB1001	168	-91.45
SUB1002	168	-56.68
SUB1003	168	-59.84
SUB1004	168	-55.94
SUB1005	168	-83.02
SUB1006	168	-26.63
SUB1007	168	-104.42
SUB1008	168	-94.22
SUB1009	168	-66.04
SUB1010	168	-96.95
SUB1011	168	-58.32
SUB1012	168	-61.37
SUB1013	168	-82.82

id	original_id	AucSS	group
1	SUB1001	1578.87	simulationGroup1
2	SUB1002	1415.06	simulationGroup1
3	SUB1003	905.095	simulationGroup1
4	SUB1004	1707.71	simulationGroup1
5	SUB1005	1837.86	simulationGroup1
6	SUB1006	976.89	simulationGroup1
7	SUB1007	1958.44	simulationGroup1
8	SUB1008	2418.81	simulationGroup1
9	SUB1009	1808.89	simulationGroup1
10	SUB1010	1855.9	simulationGroup1
11	SUB1011	1373.97	simulationGroup1
12	SUB1012	1948.42	simulationGroup1
13	SUB1013	3707.51	simulationGroup1

But Simulx output files have two columns with id. Simple **"id"** header is for simulated ids - automatic sequential integer numbers for simulated subjects. Column with **"original_id"** includes specific identifiers used in simulation elements, for example in a table of individual treatments, or a table of individual parameters. The original ids are reported in the outcome result files or as a separate file.

To use data formatting in this case, modify the outcome files outside Monolix: remove the column with simulated ids and rename the column header from original-id to id.

7.2.2 Exposure metrics in two (or more but small number) time intervals

In this case the response dataset has two measurements per individual at the end of the first dose interval,

and at steady state.

When calculating exposure metrics over more than one time interval, but not too many intervals, the process is straightforward. Simply add a new output element in Simulx with the corresponding time limits.

In this case, if the output as the steady state is already present (from the previous example) add new output from 0 to 14 and create new outcomes as in the previous example. The same is for AUC calculation. Add the computation of AUC for additional time intervals, define output elements and add new outcomes.

When there are several exposure metric values over time, as in this example, merge the results with the response dataset cannot be done with the data formatting module in Monolix. To handle this, use an R script (example to download on top of the page) that merges data from multiple files in the Simulx "Endpoints" results folder into a single file that includes response data.

Note that exposure metrics may be available at time points where no response measurements are present. In this case, you can leave "dot" in the observation column. Conversely, if there are response measurements without corresponding exposure values. Monolix can handle this automatically by applying either a last carried forward or linear interpolation method for the missing exposure values.

7.2.3 Exposure metrics over several intervals (e.g. inter-dose, daily)

To calculate exposures for many intervals, such as each inter-dose intervals over a long period, daily exposures, or weekly exposures using a script in R is more efficient and flexible than doing it manually in Simulx, as in the previous example.

Steps:

- Use a PK model built in Monolix to simulate in Simulx a concentration profiles and AUC on a fine grid covering the observation period of interest (note: previously we used Simulx to calculate directly exposure metrics)
- Read the results in R, and calculate exposure metrics and merge them with the response data.

This method is highly flexible. It allows to define the interval lengths, the number of intervals and use individual specific intervals if needed.

After running the simulation in Simulx, use an R-script (example to download on top of the page) to calculate metrics for custom time intervals and merge then with PD data.

Note: You can calculate AUC directly in Simulx using the same approach as in previous examples. While it's possible to calculate AUC in R, Simulx uses an ode solver and efficient C++ code. It can provide greater accuracy and efficiency than for example the trapezoidal rule in R.

Using `lixoftConnectors` you can automatize the whole process of building and running a simulation, exporting simulated data and using it for the post-processing.

7.2.4 Exposure - response analysis for a new scenario

In these three examples exposure metrics are calculated based on the original design and individuals from the original study. However, this workflow can be extended to simulate new scenarios. This procedure must be done at two stages:

1. Create a Simulx project with the PK model and simulate PK time-concentration profiles of the new scenario and calculate exposures.
2. Use the exposure-response model in a second Simulx project. Here exposures are treated as regressors, defined using external files generated during the first simulation.